

Efficient Edge-to-Cloud Workload Management

Title	D2.4 - State of the Art Analysis, Vision & ENACT Specifications - Final
Document Owners	ICCS
Contributors	All consortium partners
Dissemination	Public (PU)
Date	30/06/2025
Version	V1.0

Version History

Nr.	Date	Author (Organisation)	Description
0.1	22/03/2025	Efstathios Karanastasis (ICCS)	Deliverable structure / ToC
0.2 - 0.7	31/03/2025 – 20/06/2025	Vesna Kobal and Jan Harej (ARC); Alexandros Nizamis, Thanasis Kotsiopoulos and Ioanna Angeliki Kapetanidou (CERTH); Dejan Drajić and Srdjan Krco (DNET); Nadia Khan (DS4), André Gomes and Philippe Krief (ECL); Manolis Kelaidis and Haya Al Kassir (FDI); Tomasz Jaroszewski, Szymon Byczek and Marek Buchta (FUJ); Efstathios Karanastasis Efthymios Chondrogiannis Vassiliki Andronikou, Stylianos Tsanakas and Vagelis Apostolakis (ICCS); Usman Wajid, Oscar Garcia Perales and Ross Campbell (ICE); Óscar Lázaro, Katia Lavin, Cristina Domínguez and Diego Ospina (INNO); Eva Mata and Murilo Couceiro (MOG); Septimiu Nechifor, Gabriel Danciu and Cosmin Grigoras (SIE); Tiago Teixeira and Diogo Logrado (UNP); Athanasios Liatifis, Anna Triantafyllou, Dimitrios Pliatsios, Panagiotis Sarigiannidis and Thomas Lagkas (UOWM); Clara I. Valero, Juan, Gascón and Jaime Flor (UPV); Eneko Aguirre, Leonardo Hakim, Carla Sánchez and Ainhoa Gómez (OSOblue); Larraitz Eguren, Artzai Eiguren and Amaya Remon (EITB).	Content updates in all (technical and pilot) Sections. Revisions to structure and content. Several iterations.
0.6	24/06/2025	Efstathios Karanastasis (ICCS)	Prepared version for internal review.
0.7	25/06/2025 – 27/06/2025	ALL partners	Updates and final improvements.
1.0	30/06/2025	Efstathios Karanastasis (ICCS)	Final version for submission.

Disclaimer

The content of this deliverable has been prepared in compliance with the requirements of the European Commission for the management, organisation, documentation, and sharing of research data generated or collected during the course of the ENACT project. The nature of this deliverable is public (PU), hence its content can be shared with consortium partners and general public.

Acknowledgement

The ENACT project is funded by the Horizon Europe Program of the European Commission under **Grant Agreement 101135423**.

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List of Abbreviations

- AAA Authorisation, Authentication and Access
- AAC Advanced_Audio Coding
- ABAC Attribute-Based Access Control
- aerOS Autonomous, scalable, tRustworthy, intelligent European meta Operating System for the
- AES Advanced Encryption Standard
- AI Artificial Intelligence
- AI4EU Artificial Intelligence for Europe
- AlaaS AI as a Service
- AIoT Artificial Intelligence of Things
- AMQP Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
- ANN Artificial Neural Network

API	Application Programming Interface
APK	Android Application Package
APM	Application Programming Model
AR	Augmented Reality
ARCTUR	ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO
ARDIA	A resource Reference model for Data-Intensive Applications
AutoML	Automated Machine Learning
AWS	Amazon Web Services
Bi-LSTM	Bidirectional LSTM
BioPAX	Biological Pathway Exchange
BOOST	Big Data Value Spaces for COmpetitiveness of European COnnected Smart FacTories
BSD	Berkeley Software Distribution
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
CCC	Cognitive Computing Continuum
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CEP	Complex Event Processing
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS
CHOP	Configuring, Healing, Optimising, and Protecting
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CIA	Confidentiality, Integrity and Availability
CLI	Command-Line Interface
CNI	Container Network Interface
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	CREATE, READ, UPDATE and DELETE
CSF	Cyber Security Framework
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
cuDNN	CUDA Deep Neural Network
D	Deliverable
D3HUB	Tourism of Tomorrow Data-Driven Destinations Hub
DASH	Dynamic Adaptive Streaming over HTTP
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DB	Database
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DDoS	Distributed Denial of Service
DFD	Data Flow Diagram
DGL	Deep Graph Library
DGM	Dynamic Graph Modeller
DHCP	Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol
DID	Decentralised IDentifiers
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technologies
DMO	Destination Management Organisation
DNET	DUNAVNET LIMITED
DNN	Deep Neural Network
DoA	Description of Action
DPH	Deployment Plan Handler

Dracena	Dynamically Reconfigurable Asynchronous Consistent Event Processing Architecture
DREAD	Damage potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected users, and Discoverability
DRL	Deep Reinforced Learning
DS4	DIGITAL SYSTEMS 4.0
eBPF	extended Berkley Packet Filters
ECL	ECLIPSE FOUNDATION EUROPE GMBH
ECR	Amazon Elastic Container Registry
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Components
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EITB	Euskal Irrati Telebista
ELK	Elasticsearch, Logstash, and Kibana
eSIM	embedded Subscriber Identity Module
ETB	Euskal Telebista
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
EuroCC	National Competence Centres in the framework of EuroHPC
EuroHPC	European High-Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
FDI	FOUR DOT INFINITY INFORMATION AND TELECOMMUNICATIONS SOLUTIONS PRIVATE COMPANY
FL	Federated Learning
FOAF	Friend-Of-A-Friend
FPGA	Field Programmable Gate Arrays
fps	frames per second
FUJ	FUJITSU TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS SPZOO
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GAT	Graph Attention Network
GB	Gigabyte
GCN	Graph Convolutional Network
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEXF	Graph Exchange XML Format
GIN	Graph Isomorphism Network
GNN	Graph Neural Network
GPL	General Public License
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics processing unit
GraphSAGE	Graph Sample and Aggregation
GSM	Global System for Mobile Communications
GSMA	GSM Association
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDD	Hard Disk Drive
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HIPAA	Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act
HLS	HTTP Live Streaming
HPA	Horizontal Pod Autoscaler
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTML	Hypertext Mark-up Language

HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
Hz	Hertz
IaC	Infrastructure as Code
ICCS	EREVNITIKO PANEPISTIMIAKO INSTITOUTO SYSTIMATON EPIKOINONION KAI YPOLOGISTON
ICE	INFORMATION CATALYST SL
ID	Identifier
IDE	integrated development environment
IDS	International Data Spaces
IDSA	IDS Association
IE	Infrastructure Element
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
INNO	ASOCIACION DE EMPRESAS TECNOLOGICAS INNOVALIA
IoT	Internet of Things
IoT-SAFE	IoT SIM Applet For Secure End-2-End Communication
IP	Internet Protocol
ISMS	Information Security Management System
ISO	International Standard Organisation
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
JAR	Java ARchive
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
K8S	Kubernetes
KB	Kilobyte
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LD	Linked Data
LGPL	GNU Lesser General Public License
LLM	Large Language Model
LSTM	long Short-Term Memory
MAAS	Metal as a Service
MB	Megabyte
Mbps	Megabits per second
MEC	Multiple Access Edge Computing
min	minute
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
MOG	MOG TECHNOLOGIES SA
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
ms	milisecond
MTAD	Multivariate Time-series Anomaly Detection
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NGSI	Next Generation Service Interface
NIC	Network Interface Card
nq	N-Quads
OCI	Oracle Cloud Infrastructure

ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OpenWDL	Workflow Description Language
ORG	Organisation
OS	Operating System
OSGI	Open Services Gateway Initiative
OSM	Open Service Mesh
OTA	Over-The-Air
OTel	Open Telemetry Data Format
OWASP	Open Web Application Security Project
OWASP	The Open Web Application Security Project
OWL	Web Ontology Language
OVH	On Vous Héberge
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
PDF	Portable Document Format
PLATOON	Digital PLATform and analytical TOOlS for eNergy
PUE	Power Usage Effectiveness
QoE	Quality of Experience
QoS	Quality of Service
RAG	Retrieval-Augmented Generation
RAM	Random Access Memory
RAM	Reference Architecture Model
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFS	Resource Description Framework Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RNN	Recurrent Neural Network
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
RT	Real Time
RTM	Risk Treatment Plan
RTP	Risk Treatment Plan
s	second
SaaS	Software as a Service
SBML	Systems Biology Markup Language
SDF	Service Description Framework
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SIE	SIEMENS SRL
SLA	Service-Level Agreement
SM	System Model
SMART4ALL	SELF-SUSTAINED CROSS BORDER CUSTOMIZED CYBERPHYSICAL SYSTEM EXPERIMENTS FOR CAPACITY BUILDING AMONG EUROPEAN STAKEHOLDERS
SME	Small Medium Enterprise
SOA	Service-Oriented Architectures
Soft-AP	Software-enabled Access Points
SotA	State of the Art
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language

SQL	Structured Query Language
SRM	Security Risk Modeller
SRT	Secure Reliable Transport
SSD	Solid State Drive
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
SSM	Systems Security Modeller
STORE	Security Threat Oriented Requirements Engineering
STRIDE	Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege
SVM	Support Vector Machine
SVR	Support Vector Regression
T	Task
TBD	To be discussed
TDCME	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
TEMS	Trusted European Media Data Space
TFTP	Trivial File Transfer Protocol
TMT	Microsoft Threat Modelling Tool
TOSCA	Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TTP	Time-To-Provision
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UI	User Interface
UML	Unified Modelling Language
UNP	UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA
UOWM	PANEPISTIMIO DYTIKIS MAKEDONIAS
UPV	UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA
VM	Virtual Machine
VR	Virtual Reality
VTE	Virtual Training Environment
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WP	Work Package
WS	Web Service
WSDL	Web Service Description Language
xD	x-dimensional
XGML	eXtensible Graph Markup and Modelling Language
XLS	Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet
XLSX	Microsoft Excel Spreadsheet
XML	Extensible Markup Language
XREG	eXternal REGressors
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language
YOLO	You Only Look Once
ZTP	Zero-Touch Provisioning

1. Executive Summary

This ENACT deliverable **D2.4 (State of the Art Analysis, Vision, & ENACT Specifications - Final)** combines and presents the final iteration of work undertaken in T2.1 (State of Art Analysis and Requirements for Efficient Data Processing in Compute Continuum), T2.2 (Specifications of Innovative Solutions for Efficient Data Processing in the Compute Continuum) and T2.4 (ENACT Use-Case Definitions and Specifications of Use-Case Solutions) of the ENACT project, and includes a thorough analysis of the SotA in research fields relevant to ENACT areas of focus and objectives; the specification of the ENACT platform and its components; the definitions and specifications of the ENACT Use Cases (UCs); and the Impact and Vision for the ENACT platform as well as the ENACT Pilots.

The deliverable takes into consideration the activities and purposes detailed in the Description of Action (DoA) and presents the outcome of iterative and highly collaborative work performed among technical and UC partners in the framework of ENACT WP2 activities, including the aforementioned Tasks as well as T2.3 (Architecture of the ENACT Cognitive Continuum). Activities were organised by the respective Task leaders and overseen by the WP2 lead and project coordination, ensuring close collaboration among Tasks and partners, and compliance with the ENACT project areas of focus and objectives as well as with the ENACT platform architecture being prepared in parallel.

In this deliverable, following concrete methodologies, all partners contributed to the SotA analysis, pilot partners provided the definitions and specifications of the UCs and technical partners defined the final version of ENACT platform and components specifications. The results of this work serve mainly as input to the next round of components development, integration and testing, enabling a continuous research, improvement, integration and deployment phase leading to successful implementation of the project. The supplementary outcomes of WP2 work will be presented in deliverables **D2.5 (ENACT User and System Requirements - Final)** and **D2.6 (ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Reference Architecture - Final)**.

2. Introduction

2.1 Purpose and scope of the deliverable

This deliverable is the updated and final version of **D2.1 (State of the Art Analysis, Vision, & ENACT Specifications)**. As its predecessor, it focuses on three main topics that comprise a crucial foundation for the design and implementation of the ENACT platform: the SotA analysis, the specification of the ENACT platform and its components, and the definitions and specifications of the UCs.

State of the Art analysis is a crucial initial step in any research project. It involves a thorough review and evaluation of the latest research, technologies, methodologies, practices, standards, and solutions within relevant scientific fields. This analysis establishes a benchmark for identifying existing knowledge, innovations, and gaps that the project aims to address. By understanding the current landscape, researchers can consolidate foundational concepts, theories, and methodologies essential to the project, and define a precise research focus. SotA analysis prevents redundancy by ensuring researchers are aware of existing work, thus avoiding duplication and promoting innovation

by building upon previous research. It also guides the selection of appropriate methodologies and tools, enhancing the rigor of the research. Additionally, SotA analysis identifies potential collaborators and establishes benchmarks for evaluating progress and outcomes, ensuring the research remains relevant and current. Overall, it grounds the research in current knowledge, addresses genuine gaps, and contributes meaningful advancements to the field.

The specifications of a software system and its components encompass detailed descriptions of the functional and non-functional requirements, architecture, interfaces, and behaviours that the software must exhibit. These specifications provide a comprehensive blueprint for guiding the development, deployment, and maintenance of the software. They outline how different components interact with each other and with external systems, ensuring interoperability and scalability. Clear and detailed specifications are crucial for aligning stakeholders, including developers, project managers and end-users, by providing a common understanding of the system's goals and requirements.

This alignment sets realistic expectations and ensures all parties are on the same page regarding the project's scope and deliverables. Specifications act as a roadmap for developers, offering precise guidelines for implementation, reducing ambiguity, and minimising the risk of misinterpretation. They facilitate the identification of potential issues early in the development cycle, allowing for proactive problem-solving and reducing costly rework. Detailed specifications are vital for quality assurance and testing, providing criteria against which the software is validated and verified, ensuring it meets defined requirements and performs as expected. They also support maintenance and scalability, offering a clear reference for future enhancements and modifications. In summary, software specifications ensure stakeholder alignment, guide development, facilitate quality assurance, and support maintenance and scalability, forming the cornerstone of successful software engineering.

Out of these aspects, this deliverable focuses on the ENACT component specifications, while the functional and non-functional requirements and platform architecture are addressed in ENACT deliverables D2.5 (ENACT User and System Requirements - Final) and D2.6 (ENACT Cognitive Compute Continuum Reference Architecture - Final) respectively.

The definitions and specifications of Use Cases in a pilot project refer to detailed descriptions of scenarios in which the software system will be utilised. These UCs outline the interactions between users (or other systems) and the software to achieve specific goals, including the identification of actors, the sequence of actions, expected outcomes, and any variations or exceptions. They also usually detail preconditions that must be met before the UC begins and postconditions that define the system's state after the UC is completed. Defining and specifying UCs is essential for capturing the functional requirements of the system from the user's perspective, ensuring it meets actual needs and expectations. This enhances user satisfaction and system usability. UC specifications facilitate communication among stakeholders, serving as a common language that bridges the gap between technical and non-technical parties. This alignment helps set accurate expectations and avoids misunderstandings that could lead to delays. UCs provide a foundation for testing and validation by offering specific scenarios for developing test cases, ensuring the system is thoroughly tested against real-world conditions. They guide the development process by helping developers understand the context and flow of user interactions, enabling them to design and implement the system more effectively. In summary, UC definitions and specifications are critical for capturing user requirements, facilitating stakeholder communication, guiding development, and ensuring thorough

testing and validation. They are essential for successful project execution, ensuring the system meets user needs and operates effectively in real-world scenarios.

The deliverable further presents **the Vision for the ENACT platform as well as the ENACT Pilots**.

This deliverable includes the final UC specifications and Vision for all three ENACT Pilots. This also includes a new Pilot regarding the production and distribution of media content for the cultural heritage and tourism sectors, which was introduced to replace the original Pilot 3 from the ENACT proposal, following an early withdrawal of the associated partners. In the meantime, the new Pilot was successfully integrated into ENACT project, and the relevant activities progressed as planned. As a result, all three Pilots are now at a similar level of maturity.

Finally, it was decided that this deliverable would take the form of a full revision of its previous version, rather than merely presenting sporadic updates to specific Sections. This approach was chosen to offer a comprehensive and coherent overview of the topics under discussion, and to serve as a complete reference for the upcoming developments within the project. To help the reader keep track of the updates, a dedicated Section 2.4 has been included detailing the changes made since the previous version.

2.2 Relation to other WPs and tasks

This deliverable is produced within WP2 (Requirements and Specifications for Cognitive Compute Continuum), and the work presented was completed within T2.1 (State of Art Analysis and Requirements for Efficient Data Processing in Compute Continuums), T2.2 (Specifications of Innovative Solutions for Efficient Data Processing in the Compute Continuum), and T2.4 (Use-case definitions and Specifications of Use-Case Solutions). During the completion of this work, there was also close collaboration with T2.3 (Architecture of the ENACT Cognitive Continuum).

This work is also closely connected to other ENACT WPs. Specifically, the State of the Art review and platform specifications have served as the foundation for the technical developments carried out in WP4 (Cloud-Edge Abstraction, Distributed Storage, Interoperability, and Modelling), WP5 (Edge-Cloud Orchestration, Scheduling, and Adaptation), and WP6 (Application Programming Model and Support for Hyper-Distributed Applications).

Meanwhile, the use cases described in this deliverable, along with the evaluation of the ENACT platform and its components, are being implemented under WP3 (ENACT Use-Case Implementations and Evaluations). The first and, in particular, the second iterations of this deliverable have been characterised by extensive interaction, close communication, and active collaboration among these involved WPs.

Finally, the updated platform specifications presented in Deliverable D2.4 will play a key role in guiding the integration and enhancement work to be carried out in WP7 (Continuous Research, Improvements, Integrations, and Deployments) during the next phase of the project.

2.3 Structure of the deliverable

This deliverable is broken down into the following Sections:

- **Section 1 (Executive Summary):** Provides a summary of the most relevant parts of the project in relation to this deliverable.

- **Section 2 (Introduction):** Provides an introduction to this deliverable, which includes the purpose and scope, Relation to other WP's and Tasks, and the Structure of the deliverable.
- **Section 3 (Methodology):** Describes the processes and methods used to distribute and organise work, to collect and analyse the SotA, the UC definitions and specifications, and the ENACT platform specifications.
- **Section 4 (State of the Art and Beyond):** Provides an analysis of the SotA in different key fields of interest to ENACT, including research directions and related work, market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards, and information regarding the ENACT advancements beyond the SotA.
- **Section 5 (ENACT Platform Specifications):** Provides the specifications of the ENACT platform, including an overview of each component followed by detailed information regarding (as applicable) the component modules, workflow, interactions with other components, prototypical mock-ups of GUIs, pre- and post-ENACT Technology Readiness Level (TRL), applicability in the ENACT Pilots, relevance with layers of the ENACT architecture, and implementation details, such as technologies, frameworks, libraries and tools envisioned to be used, high-level description of the interfaces, deployment type, authorisation details and licensing information. Furthermore, the functional specifications of the component modules and functions are defined, including description, implementation priority, interactions and success criteria.
- **Section 6 (ENACT Use Cases Analysis and Specifications):** Provides a general description of each ENACT Pilot, including the opportunities and barriers, motivation, target objectives and key research areas, followed by the UC scenario, including its description, the high-level architecture, involved components, information flows, datasets and models, ENACT impact and benefits, the current status, and testing and validation details.
- **Section 7 (ENACT Vision):** Provides the goals and aspirations for the ENACT platform as well as the vision for each of the aforementioned Pilots and associated UCs.
- **Section 8 (Conclusions):** Provides concluding remarks and closes the deliverable.

2.4 Changes from previous version

This second and final version of the deliverable incorporates several significant updates from the initial release. In particular, the methodologies outlined in Section 3 have been revised to reflect how the various tasks were approached during the second iteration. Notably, the approach to collecting, monitoring, and tracking platform specifications has been refined to support both the elicitation of new component features, modules, and capabilities, as well as the updating of existing ones in a structured and transparent manner. With regard to the UC specifications, the methodology has been adapted to capture the necessary revisions stemming from an evolving understanding of the project's technical and operational context, along with a clearer definition of integration planning. While the methodology for the State of the Art (SotA) analysis remains largely unchanged, the Section has seen substantial content updates.

In the SotA analysis presented in Section 4, several topics were updated to varying degrees. These include Computing Continuum Modelling (T01), Distributed Storage and Data Spaces (T02), AI Algorithms and Training Environments (T06), Application Programming Models (T07), Application

Control (T08), and Quality and Security for Distributed Applications (T10). Additionally, the tables detailing external components, technologies, and projects relevant to ENACT have been populated with the most recent findings.

Additionally, extensive updates were made to the platform specifications in Section 5, where several components, as well as their internal modules and functionalities, were revised based on newly elicited or updated requirements and the revised ENACT architecture. Enhancements were implemented across a range of components, including the Virtual Training Environment (VTE), Application Controller, Graph Neural Network (GNN), CCC Data Models, Data Access and Sharing Interfaces, Data Manager, AI Forecaster, Orchestrator, Application Programming Model (APM), Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME), and Security Risk Modeller (SRM).

With regard to the UC specifications in Section 6, aside from several updates to existing entries, the most significant addition was the full specification of the new pilot and its associated use case, focused on the production and distribution of media content for the cultural heritage and tourism sectors. The vision for this pilot is also outlined in Section 7.

Finally, the introductory, concluding, and references Sections were updated accordingly.

Table 1 below details all changes from the previous version of the document.

Section(s)	Description of updates
1, 2.1, 2.4	The executive summary, List of abbreviations and Introductory Sections were updated to reflect the revised version of the deliverable. Section 2.4 was introduced, and this table was added to capture the changes from the previous version.
3.1	Additions in Section 3.1 explaining the topics definition and work distribution methodology. Division into two Subsections, one for the first and one for the second iteration.
3.2	Updates the State of the Art collection methodology for the second iteration, in Section 3.2.
3.3	Added the modification of the Methodology in collecting, monitoring and tracking of component specifications after the first iteration using ECLIPSE Gitlab.
3.4	In Subsection 3.4, the changes mainly addressed the new Pilot’s involvement and the workflow regarding the 3 UCs in the latest period.
4.1.1.1, 4.1.3.1	The current research directions and related work in the Computing Continuum Modelling topic (T01.1) were updated with the inclusion of newly found work that is of interest for ENACT purposes.
4.2.1, 4.2.2	The research directions and related work and the market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards on Distributed storage and data spaces topic (T02) have been updated to reflect accurately the current state-of-the-art.
4.6.1.2, 4.6.2.2, 4.6.3.2	Since the identification of a new requirement regarding anomaly detection in the ENACT continuum, a new Subtopic was identified regarding AI Algorithms for Anomaly Detection (T06.2). Subsequently, three new Subsections were introduced and populated with the relevant Research directions and related work, Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards, and Beyond State of the Art, under the AI algorithms and training environments topic (T06).
4.7.1, 4.7.2, 4.7.3	The Application Programming Models Topic (T07) SotA was revised. All three Sections were updated, including the research directions and related work, commercial solutions and standards, and beyond SotA aspects.
4.8.3	Update of technical detail in Beyond SotA of the Application Control Topic (T08).
4.10.1, 4.10.2	All three SotA Sections of the Quality and Security for Distributed Applications Topic (T10) were revised.

4.11.1, 4.11.2	Updated the table about Relevant external components and technologies to reflect the updates made in the State of the Art Sections. Also, the Relevant projects table was considerably updated with newly identified projects.
5.1	The VTE specifications were updated considerably, including its modules and functions to reflect the final usage of the component and interactions with other ENACT platform components. One new function was added.
5.2	Updates to component specification for Application Controller to reflect changes in internal component architecture. Revisions in all modules and functions of the component.
5.3	Updates to the GNN component specification, including external component interaction, interfaces and success criteria. Also updated one function.
5.4	Mildly revised DGM component specifications, to reflect the updated architecture and interactions with other ENACT components.
5.5	Updates to the CCC Data Models specifications that reflect the updated usage of the Models by the various ENACT platform components.
5.6	Updates to the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces component specifications including all of the component's modules.
5.7	Several updates to the Data Manager component specifications, including all of its modules and functions.
5.8	The AI Forecaster component specifications were updated to reflect the final component design that also includes the newly introduced anomaly detection functionality. Two new functions were introduced.
5.9	Light updates to the DRL component to reflect the updated platform architecture.
5.10	Updates to the Orchestrator component specifications and two of its modules that reflect the latest platform architecture and components interactions.
5.12	Updates to Application Programming Model (APM) component specifications.
5.13	Minor update to the specification of Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) component.
5.14	Major updates to the ZTP component, including a revision of all of its modules and functions.
5.15	Updates to Security Risk Modeller (SRM) component specifications, including several of its functions, and addition of the new Network Security Policies module along with two new functions.
5.16	Light updates to the Software Development Kit (SDK) component specifications.
5.17	Light updates to the Application Policy Model component specifications.
6, 6.1.2.1, 6.1.2.2, 6.1.2.3, 6.1.2.4, 6.1.2.5, 6.1.2.7, 6.1.2.9, 6.1.2.10	Changes in Section 6 have been made to reflect the updated architecture and incorporate a revised vision for the integration plan, specifically in relation to Pilot 1. These updates aim to align the Section more closely with the latest developments and ensure a clearer path forward for the implementation and demonstration of the pilot.
6.2	Newly introduced Pilot 2, regarding the production and distribution of media content for cultural heritage and tourism sectors. Includes details about the opportunities and barriers, the motivation, target objectives and key research areas (6.2.1), the use case scenario description, participants info, high-level architecture, flow description, datasets and models, current status, ENACT impact, benefits, technologies, testing and validation and the expected CC resources needed (6.2.2).
7.3	New content in the Vision section for the newly introduced Pilot 2.
8	The conclusion and references sections were revised to reflect the updated content of the document and the scope of work carried out.

Table 1: Changes from the previous document version

3. Methodology

3.1 Key topics definition and work distribution

3.1.1 Methodology of first iteration

The ENACT project brings together UC providers and technical partners to deliver innovative solutions that can radicalise the utilisation and management of a cognitive edge-cloud continuum. At the beginning of WP2 activities, and specifically as part of T2.1, the ENACT consortium, as a whole, undertook a process to identify the key technology areas pertinent to the Project's scope and objectives. The identification of these areas was informed by the project's goals and vision, as well as the individual partners' expertise. This activity resulted in the establishment of ten Key Topics that represent the key innovations in the project. Some of these Topics were further split into Subtopics to facilitate work distribution and mapping with the actual ENACT CCC Layers, as defined in deliverable D2.3. For a complete list of these Topics and Subtopics please refer to Section 3.1.2.

These Topics form the foundation for a) SotA analysis (initial version in deliverable D2.1 and final version in the current deliverable D2.4), and b) requirements collection and analysis (initial version in deliverable D2.2 and final version in D2.5). To ensure high quality contributions across all ten innovation Topics and fifteen Subtopics within the designated timeframe and work plan, a dedicated working group was established for each Key Topic, comprising both technical and UC partners. These groups were tasked with focusing on the SotA and requirements collection and analysis pertinent to their specific Topic. Based on the partner expertise and effort distribution in T2.1 and the relevant Project Tasks (in WP2 and other technical WPs), each Key Topic was assigned a Lead technical partner and a number of Main (technical) participants, while all technical and UC partners were invited to contribute to the activities related to each Topic. Lead partners were responsible for overseeing work within their Topic, communicating with participants and consolidating the relevant Sections of the corresponding deliverables, while the T2.1 leader guided and organised the overall work.

It is worth noting that the activities in ENACT T2.1 (State of the Art and requirements collection and analysis), T2.2 (ENACT solutions and components specification), T2.3 (Architecture specification) and T2.4 (ENACT Use Cases definition and specification) were conducted concurrently within WP2. These activities evolved progressively through close collaboration and information sharing among the participants of these Tasks. Additional collaboration between technical and UC partners ensured that the outcomes were highly relevant to the ENACT UC scopes and requirements.

The work was undertaken in several iterations and biweekly calls were held at T2.1, T2.2, T2.3 and T2.4 levels, involving all participating partners. Monthly WP2 and project-level meetings further supported a comprehensive, multi-level work approach. Various tools and techniques were utilised to enhance efficiency and coordination. Online collaboration platforms were employed to facilitate information exchange and track progress. These platforms supported document sharing, version control, and collaborative editing.

3.1.2 Methodology of second iteration

In the second iteration of T2.1 activities, a similar methodology was followed. The SotA for each Subtopic was revised as needed based on the most recent developments. Existing requirements were updated and detailed, and new ones were elicited (as explained in more detail in Deliverable

D2.5) through close collaboration among the technical and UC partners. The UC specifications were also updated (Sections 3.4 and 6). In parallel, the ENACT components evolved and their development progressed as part of the technical WPs, including revisions and addition of new features.

These activities also reflected on the Topics. A new Subtopic T06.2 was introduced in the second iteration of WP2 activities to address a need identified in the new platform requirements concerning anomaly detection in the CCC infrastructure. In this instance the process was reversed; it was the definition of requirements that led to the creation of a new Subtopic. The final Topics and Subtopics are outlined in Table 2.

ID	Key Topic	Lead partner	Main Participants	Relevant Tech WP
T01	Computing continuum modelling and visualisation <i>T01.1 Computing continuum modelling</i> <i>T01.2 Visualisation tools</i>	UPV	ICCS	WP4
T02	Distributed storage and data spaces	CERTH	ARCTUR, INNO	WP4
T03	Risk and compliance <i>T03.1 Security risk modelling</i> <i>T03.2 Regulatory compliance</i>	DS4	UOWM	WP4
T04	Zero-touch provisioning services	SIE	-	WP4
T05	Edge-cloud orchestration	UNP	CERTH, ICCS, FDI	WP5
T06	AI Algorithms and training environments <i>T06.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling</i> <i>T06.2 AI algorithms for anomaly detection</i> <i>T06.3 Graph Neural Networks</i> <i>T06.4 Virtual Training Environments</i>	CERTH	UPV, ICCS, FDI	WP5
T07	Application programming models	SIE	ICE	WP6
T08	Application control	ICE	SIE	WP6
T09	Software development kits	SIE	-	WP6
T10	Quality and security for distributed applications	UOMM	DS4	WP6

Table 2: Key Topics

Figure 1 below presents the Topics and Subtopics in relation to the ENACT Layers.

Figure 1: Topics and Subtopics in relation to ENACT Layers

3.2 State of the Art collection and analysis methodology

3.2.1 Methodology of first iteration

One of the primary activities in T2.1, as presented in this deliverable, was the collection and analysis of the SotA for each Key Topic. The work was distributed among the most relevant partners according to their expertise. For each Topic/Subtopic, participants agreed to focus on the following three areas, which correspond to specific Sections of this deliverable:

- **Research directions and related work:** This area focuses on the most recent and relevant research in each Topic. It includes a review of international scientific literature, including the latest contributions from ENACT partners. It also introduces and analyses the experiences of past and ongoing related projects where information is available.
- **Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards:** This area aims to highlight the most significant and widely used mature solutions and standards of relevance, which are commonly utilised by the industry and in commercial settings. It involves analysing official reports, documents and specifications, presenting the main characteristics and capabilities of these solutions, and assessing their relevance to the ENACT project’s scope and objectives.

- **Beyond State of the Art:** This focus area provides detailed information on the technological advancements in each Key Topic within the ENACT project and the specific ENACT components involved. Partner contributions in this area were completed in the final phase, incorporating the latest work on ENACT specifications (T2.2) and Architecture (T2.3) to ensure that the information reflects the actual ENACT platform components to be developed.

In the first phase of T2.1, the work was conducted and completed in three main rounds of contributions, with improvements made progressively based on discussions at the T2.1 level and the evolution of work in other related Tasks of the Project.

3.2.2 Methodology of second iteration

In the second and final iteration, the State of the Art analysis was updated following the same main approach as before. The relevant content was revised and extended to reflect the most recent platform requirements updates and ENACT component specifications and technological developments,

3.3 ENACT platform specifications methodology

3.3.1 Methodology of first iteration

The main activity for Task 2.2 was to define the functional and technical specifications for the ENACT CCC platform covering all its components. This was done in close collaboration with other WP2 Tasks such as:

- **T2.1** in order to take into account the findings of state-of-the-art analysis of similar technologies and concepts as well as system requirements as identified and described in this Deliverable.
- **T2.3** in order for each component's specifications to be in-line with the ENACT architecture and achieve the desired overall ENACT functionality and goals.
- **T2.4** in order to satisfy end-user requirements and the specific needs of the pilot projects.

Once the system and end-user requirements were elicited a high-level architecture was designed with the main components identified. This process was highly iterative since outputs from T2.2 and T2.3 were interlinked, i.e. the functionality and specifications of each component was to a large extent dependent on its neighbouring ones.

Once the required components of the ENACT platform were finalised their specifications were assigned to partners based on two parameters: (i) who was leading a relevant project Task, and (ii) relevant expertise and prior experience.

The next step was to collect the functional specifications of each of the ENACT components using a template and approach based on previous experience from other EU projects where it proved effective for collecting them in a standardised manner. There are three levels of templates used in the same document:

- **ENACT Component** – The overall ENACT Solution as described in the DoA (Table 3).
- **Module** – A specific area in the ENACT Solution that may contain many functions (if applicable) (Table 4).

- **Function** – A specific function or component in the app, dedicated to one, or one type of task (Table 5).

After one iteration, where component (i) Interfaces and (ii) Technologies fields were added, the templates used were finalised as presented in Table 3, Table 4, and Table 5.

Component Name	<The name of the ENACT component>
Intro / Overview	<Provide a short summary of the main modules and functionalities to be implemented in the ENACT Component.>
Extracted Modules	<Provide a bulleted list of all Modules available in the ENACT Component. For each Module listed, the Module Specification Template should be duplicated and completed.>
Component Workflow	<Identify and describe the overall flow of control via activity diagrams to be implemented by the ENACT Component. In the activity diagram of a component, graphical representations of a limited number of shapes, connected with arrows are provided to show component activities (also data exchanged).>
External Component Interaction	<Describes component interactions with other connected components of the ENACT platform. It is described which input data is demanded and which output data is provided.>
Prototypical Mock-ups	<Mock-ups to visualise a first draft of possible implementations of User Interfaces. These Mock-ups are in a prototypical state and do not represent the final User Interface at the end of the project. They only serve as guidelines for further implementations.>
TRL	<Provide the Technology Readiness Level of the proposed component>
Potential Use-cases	<Describe the Use Case where this component could be applied>
Layer	<The Layer in the proposed architecture where this component belongs to>
Technologies	<Technologies, frameworks, libraries, tools that you envision of using>
Interfaces	<High-level description of interfaces including: Overview: a description of the interface Type: e.g., REST State: Synchronous or asynchronous Data Format: e.g., JSON >
Deployment Type	<e.g., Hardware vs Software>
Authorisation Definition	<Licensing and Permissions that are needed to use Modules, Functions, and UI elements of the ENACT component for the respective user.>
Licence	<State the licence of the overall ENACT component. E.g., GPL, LGPL, Apache License 2.0, BSD, MIT>

Table 3: ENACT Component Functional Specification Template

Module Name	<The name of the module should be defined wisely, to indicate the meaning based on the name>	Priority	<Must / Should / Nice to have>
Description	<Describes the meaning of the Module – i.e., what the module does and which result(s) can be achieved.>		
Interacts with	<Provide a bulleted list of all modules that interact directly with this module>		
Extracted Functions	<Provide a bulleted list of all Functions available in the ENACT Module. For each function listed, the Function Specification Template should be duplicated and completed.>		
Success Criteria	<Describes the minimal criteria, which the implementation should fulfil, related to the requirements of D2.1.>		

Table 4: Module Functional Specification Template (if applicable)

Function Name	<The name of the function should be defined wisely, to indicate the meaning based on the name>	Priority	<Must / Should / Nice to have>
Description	<Describes the meaning of the Function – i.e., what the function does and which result(s) can be achieved.>		
Interacts with	< Provide a bulleted list of all functions that interact directly with this function>		
Success Criteria	<Describes the minimal criteria, which the implementation should fulfil, related to the requirements of D2.1.>		

Table 5: Function Specification Template

Since the result of T2.1 (Specifications) was to a large extent the output of T2.3 (Architecture) and vice-versa, several revisions of the component specifications were required with improvements made progressively based on scheduled WP2-wide bi-weekly calls, dedicated Slack¹ channel and one-to-one discussions. T2.2 and T2.3 leaders were tasked with coordinating these activities and making sure there were no discrepancies with the overall architecture as well as between neighbouring components.

3.3.2 Methodology of second iteration

After the first phase of the Specifications definition, as they were registered in D2.1, and in order to ensure proper monitoring of their changes as the technical WP were progressing, a new method for recording and tracking component specifications was devised.

In order to facilitate easier tracking of Specifications, this new method made use of the existing ECLIPSE Gitlab infrastructure initially set-up for monitoring the technical development of the components. It treated component specifications as 'Issues' and 'Child Issues', which could be continuously amended or updated in a way that would be visible to all partners. Thereby, through this tracking/monitoring of specification changes method, ENACT partners are able to avoid conflicts between nearby components during their technical development until the project's completion. Figure 2 (see "WP2" column) and Figure 3 showcase how this method is implemented for the Application Controller specifications.

¹ <https://slack.com/>

Figure 2: Application Controller Specifications as Issues in Eclipse Gitlab (WP2 column)

[S.C02.03] Component Workflow

Open Task created 5 days ago by Manolis Kelaidis

No description

👍 0 🗳️ 0 😊

Linked items 0 Add ⋮ ^

Link items together to show that they're related or that one is blocking others. [Learn more.](#)

Activity All activity Oldest first

- Manolis Kelaidis added #21 as parent issue 5 days ago

Manolis Kelaidis @manolisfdi Author Developer 5 days ago

To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.

Preview | **B** *I* U | **≡** `</>` 🔗 📌 🔍 📄 📁 📎 🔖

Write a comment or drag your files here...

Figure 3: Application Controller 'Component Workflow' Specification as Child Issue in Eclipse Gitlab

3.4 Use Cases definition and specifications methodology

3.4.1 Methodology of first iteration

The methodology for use-case definition and specification involved several key phases. Initially, the focus was on **Requirements Gathering**. This involved engaging other consortium partners, end-users, and other relevant parties. A detailed analysis was also performed during this phase to identify specific needs and scenarios, which helped in pinpointing what needed to be specified for each UC.

Once requirements were gathered, the **Specification Development** phase commenced. A standardised template was prepared and shared to facilitate information collection. This template ensured consistency in capturing details across different UCs.

The work organisation for the project was structured around **rounds and iterations of contributions**. The information collection and specification processes were iterative, with multiple rounds allowing for incremental improvements and refinements. Feedback loops were integral to this process, as initial drafts were reviewed, and feedback was provided to contributors for necessary **revisions**.

There was also significant **collaboration with other tasks** within the project to ensure that the specifications were aligned with the overall project goals and integrated seamlessly with other work packages. **Task meetings** facilitated the exchange of information and alignment of efforts.

By applying this structured methodology, the ENACT project was able to develop detailed, accurate, and comprehensive specifications for platform components and UCs. The iterative approach, combined with effective stakeholder engagement and collaboration across tasks, ensured the success of the requirements and specification process.

3.4.2 Methodology of second iteration

Over the course of the following months, during the second and final iteration of T2.4, the requirements and specifications were revisited and refined to reflect the evolving understanding of the project's technical and operational landscape. These updates were driven by continuous discussions and clarifications among the partners, which revealed more accurate communication needs between platform components. This process also helped correct initial assumptions and led to a clearer alignment between the technical specifications and the practical needs of the pilots.

In parallel, efforts were made to define the integration planning more precisely. As the interaction points between components became better understood, so too did their relevance and positioning across the three pilot scenarios. This deeper comprehension enabled the consortium to optimise integration strategies, ensuring that the technical solutions not only meet the functional requirements but also effectively support the specific use cases of each pilot. This iterative validation and clarification contributed to the coherence and readiness of the implementation phase.

4. State of the Art analysis and beyond

This Section presents the SotA analysis performed by the ENACT consortium, grouped per Key Topic and focusing in three areas (as already explained in section 3.2): Research directions and related work; Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards; Beyond State of the Art. Following the completion of the second phase of work, the content underwent significant revisions.

4.1 Computing continuum modelling and visualisation

4.1.1 Research directions and related work

4.1.1.1 Computing continuum modelling

Modelling the various entities and data types of a computing continuum ecosystem in a detailed and usable manner constitutes a crucial foundation for enabling the realisation of a computing continuum that supports real-time visibility, automatic discovery, dynamic deployment, predictive management and real-time self-adaptation of federated resources. Data modelling and representation aspects involve how information is structured, encoded, and manipulated to successfully facilitate the exchange of needed data as well as its usage for demanding cognitive tasks, such as learning, reasoning and decision-making. The advance specification of data elements' format, structure, and meaning not only streamlines the development of pertinent systems by ensuring inclusion of all crucial parameters but also shields against potential errors, such as data misinterpretation.

The computing continuum infrastructure encompasses various types of resources, usually including edge and cloud computing infrastructures and fog computing nodes. Edge infrastructure includes the hardware and software resources deployed at the edge of the network to facilitate local processing, storage, and analysis of data. It typically features edge servers, gateways, and devices like sensors, smartphones, and IoT devices. Additionally, various resources such as NICs and accelerators (e.g., GPU, FPGA) with diverse capabilities may be connected to these entities. Cloud computing infrastructure, made available by cloud service providers, offers on-demand access to computing resources over the internet, including virtual machines, storage, and networking. Fog computing extends the cloud computing paradigm to the network edge, delivering computing, storage, and networking services closer to end-users or data sources through fog nodes, which communicate with both edge devices and cloud infrastructure.

Optimal deployment of applications or services in the available computing continuum resources requires comprehensive consideration of several key parameters. Latency requirements guide decisions on processing location at the edge or the cloud, balancing real-time responsiveness with available computational resources. Bandwidth needs for data transmission between edge devices, fog nodes, and cloud infrastructure must be evaluated to ensure efficient data transfer and minimise network congestion. Scalability demands dynamic resource allocation across the continuum to accommodate fluctuating workloads. Security measures, including data encryption and access control, are essential for protecting sensitive information and privacy. Cost and energy considerations, covering infrastructure provisioning, maintenance, and operational expenses, guide the development of cost-effective and energy-efficient deployment strategies optimising resource utilisation and/or minimise energy consumption while meeting application requirements.

Enabling real-time visibility and automatic resource discovery in the cloud continuum depends on effective monitoring, metadata management, and standardised communication protocols. Robust monitoring mechanisms continuously collect telemetry data, providing insights into resource status and performance metrics such as CPU utilisation, network latency, and storage availability. Effective metadata management indexes and categorises resources based on their attributes and relationships, facilitating rapid and accurate discovery. These parameters are crucial for establishing

a dynamic and responsive cloud continuum ecosystem supporting diverse applications and workloads with agility and scalability.

Telemetry data play a vital role in facilitating optimal orchestration in the computing continuum, providing real-time insights into resources performance and state. Continuous monitoring of metrics like CPU utilisation, memory usage, network latency and storage capacity across edge devices, fog nodes, and cloud infrastructure allows orchestration systems to dynamically adjust resource allocation and workload distribution to optimise performance and resource utilisation. Historical telemetry data offer valuable insights for predictive orchestration, enabling anticipation of future resource demands and proactive adjustments to accommodate expected workloads. By combining historical telemetry data with real-time monitoring, organisations can enhance system efficiency, reliability and agility, and mitigate performance degradation risks. Intelligent application orchestration is further enhanced by combining historical telemetry data on particular applications' deployment outcomes with the characteristics of the involved resources. This approach harnesses data from various sources in a combinatory manner, enabling optimal predictive dynamic orchestration.

To accomplish the objectives of the ENACT continuum, data from all the previously mentioned sources and categories, including applications and services, resources and devices, as well as telemetry, must undergo appropriate modelling and be made accessible for utilisation by the platform and its diverse components. The models developed should exhibit a level of representability and expressibility adequate to encompass the mentioned scopes comprehensively.

A recent work on A resource Reference model for Data-Intensive Applications (ARDIA) Framework [1] introduces a collection of models that provide a rich semantic representation of the concepts for the overall description of application / service, resource / device and telemetry data in the context of data-intensive security-critical applications, and enables the specification of relations among these entities. The ARDIA Framework, developed in the EU-funded SERRANO project², has been used as the foundation of a robust architecture aimed at enhancing cloud continuum application deployment and execution through intent-based AI-enhanced orchestration.

It contains three fundamental models. The Application Model, describes applications and services in terms of their high-level requirements, which include design, intent, implementation details, and deployment constraints. It serves as a framework for specifying what the application needs to function optimally in a computing continuum environment, also capturing the overall goal and requirements of the application provider in an abstract, infrastructure-independent manner. It can further capture the internal application components and workflow on the basis of OpenWDL (for more information please refer to Section 4.1.2.1). The Resource Model details the physical and software resources available in the infrastructure. It outlines the performance aspects, security capabilities, utilisation, and deployment specifics of each resource as well as connected entities and accelerators, providing a comprehensive view of the infrastructure capabilities. The Telemetry Data Model is used for capturing and managing the telemetry data from the applications deployed in the continuum resources, further enabling evaluation of application execution and quality of experience. It focuses on runtime measurements, storing data in a time-series database, which aids in monitoring and decision-making processes related to predictive orchestration. The models are in line with the

² SERRANO - Transparent Application Deployment in a Secure, Accelerated and Cognitive Cloud Continuum. Grant agreement ID: 101017168. <https://ict-serrano.eu/>

TOSCA specification (for more information please refer to Section 4.1.2.1), allowing for easily extending the TOSCA base types to provide added functionality. These models interact through a series of AI-driven processes and mapping rules, facilitating dynamic and efficient application deployment. The architecture leverages Machine Learning (ML) to enhance the decision-making process, ensuring that the deployments are optimally aligned with the application and user requirements, and the available resources. This system showcases the potential of integrating AI with cloud resource management to adapt swiftly to changing application needs and environments.

The aerOS Continuum Ontology³ is an ongoing work being developed in the EU funded aerOS project⁴ inspired by existing ontologies such as Organisation (ORG)⁵ and (Friend-of-a-Friend) FOAF⁶, and standardisation initiatives such as TOSCA (see 4.1.2.1). It is being built to describe an IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum managed by the aerOS Meta-OS, which represents a distributed computing architecture where data flows seamlessly from IoT devices at the edge of the network to a centralised cloud infrastructure. The inherent complexity of this computing continuum was modelled into a data ontology intended to encapsulate the essential concepts, relationships, and properties relevant to data management, processing, and orchestration within this architecture.

The entities of this ontology can be divided into three blocks: (i) aerOS Authorisation, Authentication and Access (AAA) aiming to represent relationships between human actors and the services and resources in the continuum through the definition of users, roles, and organisations; (ii) resource orchestration, which covers the physical computing resources (infrastructure elements) and their states, and additionally includes conceptual layers on top of them to depict domains and Low-Level Orchestrators; (iii) service orchestration, which represents the deployed services in the Infrastructure Elements (IEs) of the continuum. These entities represent both the current status of the deployed services and all the stages of the services orchestration process, from service requirements specifications (SLAs, minimum computing resources, etc.) to execution parameters (network ports, container images, environment variables, etc.).

Since the aerOS project is still ongoing, some parts of the continuum may not be covered yet in the aerOS Continuum Ontology or may still be expanded in future iterations. Additionally, the ontology has not been yet fully tested, which will be finalised in the next months as the development of the aerOS project services evolves.

4.1.1.2 Visualisation tools

Graph visualisation, also known as network visualisation or link analysis, is a method for visually depicting the relationships between different data entities. A node-link model is the most effective method for graph visualisation, with nodes representing entities and links depicting their connections.

These nodes and links (Figure 4) can represent any kind of information, such as transactions between accounts, devices connected in a network, or communications between friends. Their size or content of data does not matter, as long as there are connections between the data that can be visualised/drawn in a graph way. This visualisation is not static. It can be characterised by filtering data.

³ <https://w3id.org/aerOS/continuum>

⁴ <https://aeros-project.eu/>

⁵ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-org/>

⁶ <http://xmlns.com/foaf/spec/>

Graphs are mainly used in very complex data structures with huge amounts of data that could be difficult to process and relate directly with the raw data, but it could be easy to digest and understand if the data is shown as a graph.

Figure 4: Node and edge in a graph

Graph visualisation tools are software programs designed to transform complex network data into clear and understandable visual representations. These tools help researchers, analysts, and anyone working with interconnected information to explore relationships, identify patterns, and gain insights from their data.

These kinds of tools were developed mainly as desktop applications that must be installed in a computer and used to analyse local data. Actually, with the advances of microservices technology these tools have evolved from desktop app to code libraries to be used directly by almost any programming language. These libraries, open the possibility to adapt almost any frontend technology to be able to represent graphs. It is true that libraries are not as powerful as original desktop applications, especially in the use of resources being less capable compared to desktop applications, but for some applications that will process little size data sets is more than enough.

4.1.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

4.1.2.1 Computing continuum modelling

Starting from more generic and legacy approaches in the domain of application/service description, the Web Service Description Language (WSDL)⁷, commonly used in Service-Oriented Architectures (SOA) and web services, provides a standardised way to describe applications and services, including their capabilities, interfaces, and requirements, facilitating service discovery, composition, and interoperability in distributed systems. For modelling resources and devices, the Resource Description Framework (RDF)⁸ can be used, which is a flexible data model for representing resources and their relationships in graph format. It provides a standard syntax for expressing metadata about resources on the Web and is widely used in the context of the Semantic Web for describing resources and enabling interoperability. On the other hand, Time Series Data Models [2] [3], which are specialised for representing temporal data usually collected from sensors or devices over time, can be used for storing telemetry data. These models often include W3C Recommendation features for timestamping^{9,10}, interpolation [4], and aggregation of time-series data. The Open Telemetry Data

⁷ <https://www.w3.org/TR/wsd.html>

⁸ <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>

⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/performance-timeline/>

¹⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/user-timing/>

Format (OTel)¹¹ is an open-source standard for representing telemetry data collected from distributed systems and applications. It provides a vendor-neutral format for exporting metrics, traces, and logs, enabling interoperability and observability across different platforms. Finally, for representing data models of various kinds, including their structure, data types and attributes, the Unified Modelling Language (UML)¹² can be used, as it provides a standardised notation for designing and visualising data models.

Applications usually consist of services or microservices executed in a specific order. The Workflow Description Language (OpenWDL)¹³ standard provides a robust framework for describing and executing computational workflows in a scalable and reproducible manner. Developed by the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), OpenWDL offers a structured syntax for defining workflows comprising multiple tasks and dependencies, facilitating interoperability across different workflow execution engines and environments. Its declarative nature allows users to specify computational tasks, inputs, outputs, and dependencies concisely, enabling automated execution and portability across various computational platforms. OpenWDL's flexibility and extensibility make it suitable for a wide range of scientific applications, empowering researchers to design, share, and execute complex computational workflows efficiently. This standardisation greatly enhances collaboration, reproducibility, and scalability.

Particularly in the realm of cloud applications, the OASIS Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications (TOSCA) v2.0¹⁴ is a standard for modelling and managing cloud-native and traditional applications across their lifecycle. TOSCA defines a language to describe application topologies, components, relationships, and deployment workflows, with v2.0 enhancing support for modularity, reusability, and portability across heterogeneous cloud and edge environments, enabling automated orchestration and policy-driven management. TOSCA-based orchestration relies on YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML)¹⁵, a human-readable data serialisation language commonly used for configuration files. YAML is also extensively used by Kubernetes (K8s)¹⁶ for defining and configuring resources such as pods, deployments, services, and more. In Kubernetes, YAML files serve as the primary means of declaring the desired state of the system, specifying attributes, configurations, and relationships between various components. YAML's human-readable syntax and structure make it easy for developers and administrators to write and understand configuration files, allowing them to define complex deployments and manage Kubernetes resources effectively. By leveraging YAML, Kubernetes provides a standardised and intuitive way to define, manage, and orchestrate containerised applications and microservices within a cluster environment, facilitating efficient deployment, scaling, and management of distributed systems.

¹¹ [telemetry/opentelemetry-specification](https://opentelemetry.io/specifications/)

¹² <https://www.omg.org/spec/UML/>

¹³ <https://github.com/ga4gh/workflow-execution-service-schemas>

¹⁴ <https://docs.oasis-open.org/tosca/TOSCA/v2.0/TOSCA-v2.0.html>

¹⁵ <https://yaml.org/>

¹⁶ <https://kubernetes.io/>

Semantic Web [5] technologies, including the aforementioned RDF¹⁷, RDFS¹⁸, and OWL¹⁹, facilitate the representation of knowledge in a machine-processable format, typically in the form of ontologies [6]. Ontologies offer a formal and explicit specification of a shared conceptualisation within a specific domain. They delineate concepts, relationships, and constraints, thereby fostering interoperability and knowledge sharing among diverse cognitive systems. Semantic and Knowledge Graphs [7], on the other hand, comprise specific instances of ontological relationships and are created by applying an ontology to a set of individual data points. They can serve as data representations, capturing complicated relationships and semantics between entities. Widely utilised in cognitive computing systems, they facilitate the representation of structured knowledge, enabling advanced reasoning and inference capabilities. SPARQL (SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language)²⁰ is commonly employed for querying and manipulating semantic data.

4.1.2.2 Visualisation tools

Here's a comparison among the most popular open-source tools for graph visualisation:

- **Gephi**²¹ [8] [9]: Gephi is a free and open-source software program that's specifically designed for network analysis and visualisation. Developed by a diverse community of researchers and developers, Gephi provides a user-friendly platform for exploring and understanding the relationships within networks of various kinds, including social networks, biological networks, transportation networks among others.
 - Usability: Intuitive graphical interface that is easy to use, suitable for users without programming experience.
 - Features: Real-time visualisation, support for large networks, dynamic layout algorithms, and interactive manipulation capabilities.
 - Customisation: Allows customisation of the visualisation with various layout algorithms and has extensible plugins like MultiViz²² for multilayer visualisation.
 - Data Handling Capabilities: Excellent for dynamically changing data and visualising complex structures.
 - Graph input format:
 - Desktop application: GEXF, GDF, GML, GraphML, Pajek NET, GraphViz DOT, CSV, UCINET DL, Tulip TPL, Netdraw VNA, Spreadsheet.
 - Web Based: GEXF, GraphML.

¹⁷ Resource Description Framework (RDF). World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2004). RDF 1.1 Concepts and Abstract Syntax. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/>

¹⁸ Resource Description Framework Schema (RDFS). World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2014). RDF Schema 1.1. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-schema/>

¹⁹ Web Ontology Language (OWL). World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2012). OWL 2 Web Ontology Language Document Overview (Second Edition). <https://www.w3.org/TR/owl2-overview/>

²⁰ SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language. World Wide Web Consortium (W3C). (2008). SPARQL Query Language for RDF. <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/>

²¹ Jacomy M. Gephi Lite. Gephi blog. 2022. <https://gephi.wordpress.com/2022/11/15/gephi-lite/>

²² <https://manlius.github.io/muxViz/>

- Type: Desktop application and Web Based (lite) version.
- **Graphviz**²³: Graphviz is a software toolkit primarily designed for the creation and visualisation of diagrams specified in the DOT language. Originally developed by AT&T Labs, Graphviz was later released as open-source software under the Eclipse Public License.
 - Usability: More oriented towards users with programming skills; used via scripts.
 - Features: Strong in creating structured diagrams; uses DOT language to describe graphs.
 - Customisation: Less interactive in real-time but very flexible in generating complex static graphics.
 - Data Handling Capabilities: Ideal for static visualisations and complex flowcharts.
 - Graph input format: DOT.
 - Type: Desktop application and library.
- **Cytoscape**²⁴: Cytoscape is an open-source bioinformatics software platform designed to visualise intricate molecular interaction networks and seamlessly integrate with gene expression profiles and other pertinent data. Beyond its core functionalities, Cytoscape boasts a wealth of additional features accessible through plugins. These plugins expand the platform's capabilities to encompass network and molecular profiling analyses, introduce novel layouts, broaden support for various file formats, and establish connections with databases, facilitating efficient searches within expansive networks.
 - Usability: Graphical interface focused on computational biology and molecular networks.
 - Features: Excellent for the analysis of biological networks, integration of biomedical data, and interactive visualisation.
 - Customisation: Wide range of plugins for specific analysis in the biological domain.
 - Data Handling Capabilities: Specially designed to handle specific attributes of biological data.
 - Graph input format: SIF, GML, XGMML, SBML, BioPAX, GraphML, Delimited text, XLS, XLSX, Cytoscape.js JSON, Cytoscape CX.
 - Type: Desktop application.
- **NetworkX**²⁵: NetworkX is a Python library designed for exploring graphs and conducting network analysis. It's freely available under the BSD-new license. NetworkX excels at handling extensive real-world graphs, including those with more than 10 million nodes and 100 million edges. Leveraging a pure Python data structure known as a "dictionary of dictionary," NetworkX proves to be a reasonably efficient and highly adaptable framework, making it an excellent choice for analysing both social and general networks

²³ Graphviz. <https://graphviz.org/>

²⁴ What is Cytoscape? https://cytoscape.org/what_is_cytoscape.html

²⁵ NetworkX. <https://networkx.org/>

- Usability: Python library; it requires programming skills for effective use.
- Features: Strong in modelling, transforming, and analysing complex graphs; not focused on visualisation.
- Customisation: Highly customizable through code; integrates well with other Python libraries for visualisation like Matplotlib.
- Data Handling Capabilities: Excellent for algorithmic network analysis but does not provide advanced visualisation tools directly.
- Graph input format: DOT, GEXF, GraphML, JSON, LEDA, SpareGraph6, Pajek, Matrix Market, Network text.
- Type: Library.

The choice of tool depends on the type of data, the analysis goals, the need for visualisation interactivity, user's skills and type of application. Gephi excels in interactive and dynamic visualisations with an easy-to-use interface, making it popular in fields outside of computational biology, unlike Cytoscape, which is preferred in that field for its specific capabilities. Graphviz and NetworkX offer strong programming capabilities for technical users, preferred in scenarios where extensive automation and customisation in graph generation are required.

Another thing to take into consideration is the type of software in which each tool is packed. Nowadays with the containerisation and microservices as the standard for the architecture of any project/IT solution it is difficult to include/adapt a desktop application to be used in this kind of environment. Apart that it is possible that the performance of the desktop version won't be the same than the original one, so a library or web-based solutions are more suitable for this kind of actual standards. For this reason, Gephi in their Web Based version is the only tool that could be easily adapted to be used as a microservice and hence with actual standards.

4.1.3 Beyond State of the Art

4.1.3.1 *Computing continuum modelling*

Conceptual modelling often stems from the specific purposes it aims to fulfil. Consequently, the parameters defined for a particular domain heavily rely on decisions made during system design, such as the chosen design paradigm and classification axes. Adopting models developed for alternative purposes presents significant challenges, necessitating a complex transformation process with potentially ambiguous outcomes. This process assumes precise mapping of elements from existing specifications to those explicitly or implicitly dictated by the specific needs of ENACT. Independent design of applications and corresponding models exacerbates this mapping process, particularly when dealing with partially overlapping knowledge domains, leading to potential oversights or mismatches in element mapping. Anticipating the goals and necessary parameters for system functionality is critical during model design, enabling the identification of potential issues. Accordingly, investigating the formal expression of various concepts, their potential relationships, and their impact on service execution is essential. Enabling interoperable representation of critical model elements and their relationships facilitates the application of these models to address ENACT's needs and objectives, particularly concerning optimal orchestration and interaction among platform components.

In light of this, certain works outlined in the preceding Section demonstrate notable relevance to the objectives and requirements of ENACT. As a result, we intend to conduct a thorough examination of these works, with the possibility of leveraging them as foundational resources. If deemed pertinent, we aim to build upon, integrate, and extend these works, utilising them as a basis for designing and implementing the ENACT CCC Models, a data modelling framework tailored to the needs of ENACT. These models will facilitate the representation of essential concepts and data required for ENACT's objectives. Specifically, they will support the seamless integration of relevant ENACT platform components, such as the Dynamic Graph Modeller, the Orchestrator, the AI Forecaster, the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine, the Data Manager, the APM, the Application Controller and the Application Policy Model, and enable the realisation of a fully integrated computing continuum. This continuum will prioritise trustworthy and secure communication and service execution across various levels, while embracing features such as discoverability, dynamic deployments, data management, and intelligent predictive and real-time orchestration.

The development of the data modelling framework will entail close collaboration with all ENACT Tasks impacted by relevant decisions, ensuring comprehensive consideration of all requirements. The models will undergo iterative improvement and evolution in alignment with the specifications as well as emerging needs and requirements of the ENACT platform and its components as design and implementation proceed.

Moreover, we will assess and strive for compatibility with established and widely recognised standards in the pertinent domains, aiming to implement models and components that seamlessly integrate with other systems. If relevant, ENACT will actively collaborate with existing or emerging standardisation initiatives in the field, with the intention of contributing where feasible.

ENACT will leverage the tree models of the ARDIA Framework (application / service, resource / device and telemetry), which was developed in the EU-funded SERRANO project, as the basis for developing the CCC Models. Given the commonalities of SERRANO and ARDIA with ENACT and the envisioned CCC Models respectively, ARDIA can serve well as the starting point for further developments. The main similarities among the two projects and associated platforms are their wider scope and the direction followed in the data modelling approach. However, there are also key differences, such as the connected continuum infrastructure types, the architectural approach and layers, the components and the mechanisms / technologies involved, which also are also reflected on the data modelling part. Hence, the ARDIA models will be reworked and customised as required, after investigation of the exact data needs at component and platform level, and improved for optimal coverage of the ENACT requirements and facilitation of the project objectives and key innovations.

4.1.3.2 Visualisation tools

The proposed ENACT modelling environment is the main outcome of T4.2. It will advance the state-of-the-art in cloud-edge continuum visualisation and optimisation by leveraging the power of graph theory and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs). The visualisation tool will represent the continuum information collected through the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine and the Zero-Touch Provisioning services.

At the core of the modelling environment will be a graph-based representation of the cloud-edge continuum. Each node in the graph will represent a computing resource, whether it be a cloud data centre, an edge server, or an IoT device. The edges between nodes will represent the network connections, with attributes such as bandwidth, latency, and reliability associated with each edge.

This graph-based representation will allow for a rich and intuitive visualisation of the complex cloud-edge ecosystem. Users will be able to easily navigate the topology, inspect the properties of individual nodes and edges, and understand the interconnections between different components. This level of visibility is crucial for effectively managing and optimising the cloud-edge continuum.

DGM will provide graph information to DRL, AI forecaster and GNN components to predict optimal configurations for the cloud-edge continuum. This will allow the modelling environment to show changes in the network topology, resource allocation, or application deployment.

The key innovations of the proposed modelling environment are:

- **Comprehensive visualisation:** The graph-based representation of the cloud-edge continuum will provide a level of visibility and understanding that is not possible with traditional visualisation tools.
- **Predictive capabilities:** The integration of AI components will enable the modelling environment to go beyond simple visualisation and provide actionable insights for optimising the cloud-edge continuum.
- **Scalability and flexibility:** The graph-based approach and the use of GNNs will allow the modelling environment to scale to large, complex cloud-edge systems and adapt to a wide range of UCs and requirements.

The ENACT visualisation tool will leverage Gephi, an open-source, general-purpose software application for network analysis and visualisation, to represent the ENACT cloud-edge continuum using graph theory. The tool will be customised to integrate seamlessly with Kubernetes, enabling the display of pods, nodes, services, and their relationships, along with associated metrics. A data acquisition module will be incorporated to ensure continuous updates to the ENACT representation of the continuum. Furthermore, the tool will be designed to support integration across a wide range of use cases and scenarios.

4.2 Distributed storage and data spaces

4.2.1 Research directions and related work

The Commission is determined to make this Europe's "Digital Decade"²⁶. Europe must now strengthen its digital sovereignty and set standards, rather than following those of others – with a clear focus on data, technology, and infrastructure.

Federated cloud environments such as GAIA-X²⁷ and initiatives like IDSA²⁸ and FIWARE²⁹ deliver infrastructure, reference architectures and formal standards to enable secure and trustworthy data-sharing [10] [11]. These initiatives provide complete frameworks for data sharing including:

- Business level that describes the roles of participants in a data space such as data owner, data provider/consumer, service provider, etc.

²⁶ https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age_en

²⁷ <https://www.data-infrastructure.eu/GAIA-X/Navigation/EN/Home/home.html>

²⁸ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/>

²⁹ <https://www.fiware.org/>

- Functional level that describes all the necessary components should be included in a data sharing ecosystem such data connectors, metadata registry service, etc.
- Process level that includes all the interactions and connections between the various components in a data sharing ecosystem.
- Information level that is just the modelling of both components and stakeholders.
- System level that instantiates the previous levels, so components, their connectors and the actual actors to setup an operational system to enable the shafting of data.

Based on popular standards^{30 31}, secure and trustworthy data sharing can be supported by data connectors and APIs (Open API standards), with security delegated in third-party components. Current approaches^{32 33 34} are based on containers and virtualisation concepts, and they are mainly focused on data sharing. This container-based approach enables data connectors and other related components to be packed over an OS, to include an application container manager that enables the execution of a specific application alongside with containers for the configuration of a data connector during runtime.

Figure 5: Data Space Architecture based on IDSA RAM

³⁰ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/ids-officially-a-standard-din-spec-27070-is-published/>

³¹ <https://internationaldataspaces.org/dataspace-protocol-ensuring-data-space-interoperability/>

³² <https://fiware-tutorials.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

³³ <https://international-data-spaces-association.github.io/DataspaceConnector/>

³⁴ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/technology.edc>

In particular, the various approaches related to data spaces are built over the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (IDSA RAM³⁵). It defines all the roles in a data sharing ecosystem, the sharing policies and the major software components:

- Connector: It is a dedicated software component that allows participants to attach usage policies to their data in a data space and enforce the usage policies. This component acts as a gateway for data and services.
- Metadata Broker/Registry: It offers information about data sources in terms of content, structure quality, etc.
- Clearing House: It is the service for logging and keeping track of all data exchange and financial transactions within a data space.
- Vocabularies: They are mainly data models and ontologies that are related to specific domains/UCs and aim to describe the structure of the data that are transferred.
- Identity Provider: This software component creates, maintains, manages and validates identity information of and for participants in a data space.
- App Store: It provides applications that can be deployed in Connectors to execute various tasks like data analytics, etc.

As the core component is the Data Connector, the different relevant initiatives and foundations has developed relevant components. FIWARE has introduced its connector³⁶, that is based in FIWARE's core component, the ORION Context Broker. It uses Keycloak to issue certificates, Keyrock for authorisation and both SQL and no-SQL databases for storing data. Eclipse Foundation has also introduced a series of Data Space components based on IDSA principles. However, the only operational component there is the EDC connector. It is based on Dataspace Connector Java implementation, and it is expected to provide extra functionalities such as federated cache for metadata, etc. EDC connectors were combined with GAIA-X infrastructure (that it is focuses on sovereign cloud services and cloud infrastructure) to enable the setup of Catena-X³⁷ and Eona-X³⁸ data spaces.

Given the wide adoption of Data Spaces, a more recent research challenge in this field is to enable seamless interconnection between them. A notable solution in this regard is Simpl³⁹, an open-source, smart and secure middleware platform that supports data access and interoperability among European Data Spaces.

However, in the distributed applications the need for sharing of data (as chunks and streams) is often complemented by the need for sharing data objects [12]. Regarding the objects sharing and distributed management, there are some distributed storages coming from academia. BSC dataClay [13], i.e., a distributed data store that enables applications to store and access objects in the same format they have in memory. However, BSC dataClay is bounded by proprietary software and platforms.

³⁵ <https://docs.internationaldataspaces.org/knowledge-base/ids-ram-4.0>

³⁶ <https://github.com/FIWARE/data-space-connector>

³⁷ <https://catena-x.net/en/>

³⁸ <https://eona-x.eu/>

³⁹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/simpl>

Capybara [14] is an edge-friendly, scalable, and programmable distributed object store. It enables storing and sharing serverless function objects on edge infrastructures, aiming to allow edge nodes to be seamlessly integrated as a unified serverless storage infrastructure.

Nevertheless, the aforementioned object stores are not designed to support the notion of trusted shared Data Spaces. To address Data Space compatibility, the IoT-Connector [15] has been proposed to enable the sharing of IoT-generated data with IDS Data Spaces. It employs the OGC SensorThings API as the intermediary to ensure its interoperability with IoT devices, irrespective of their provider, thus facilitating seamless data exchange in IoT environments. Still, this Connector is primarily focused on IoT networks.

4.2.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

Various market-ready solutions have been developed so far related to data sharing and data space technologies. Two prominent Dataspace Connectors are the IDS Dataspace Connector⁴⁰ and the Eclipse EDC Connector⁴¹ which have established the guidelines for compliance with IDS and Gaia-X standards, using the Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) for expressing and enforcing usage control rules, and providing the Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service (DAPS) for identity management via bespoke centralised IDS identity authorities. The EDC Connector supports also decentralised identity management through decentralised identifiers (DIDs) and verifiable credentials (VCs). Apart from these two connectors, other notable implementations include the:

- **Sovity EDC Connector**⁴²: Sovity extends the EDC Connector's capabilities by providing enterprise-ready managed services. "Connector-as-a-Service" is a key Sovity-provided service that facilitates access to dataspace.
- **FIWARE Connector**⁴³: Compliant with the Data Spaces Business Alliance (DBSA) Technical Convergence recommendations and the ETSI NGSI-LD compliant API for data exchange. Data usage is governed by attribute-based access control (ABAC) policies defined using ODRL.
- **Telekom DIH Connector**⁴⁴: T-Systems has developed IDS certified, Gaia-X compliant, cloud agnostic, plug-and-play connectors. It supports HTTPs communication protocol and Identity Management both Centralised (X.509) and Decentralised (did:web). Available for both cloud and edge deployment.
- **Tritom Enterprise Connector**⁴⁵: It enables data source and target systems technical connectivity to the Tritom service to produce services based on data sovereignty principles. Tritom also brings together ecosystem parties and provides the capabilities to create data and service catalogues. It supports REST communication protocol. Available for both cloud and edge deployment.

⁴⁰ <https://international-data-spaces-association.github.io/DataspaceConnector/>

⁴¹ <https://github.com/eclipse-edc/Connector>

⁴² <https://github.com/sovity/edc-ce>

⁴³ <https://github.com/FIWARE/data-space-connector>

⁴⁴ <https://dih.telekom.com/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.dataspace.fi/en/data-intermediation-service>

- **Trusted Supplier Connector**⁴⁶: German Edge Cloud GmbH & Co offers its connector that supports IDS Multipart, HTTP, Cloud Events and IDS Header for communication. Available for both cloud and edge deployment.
- **TRUE Connector**⁴⁷ : Engineering Ingegneria Informatica has developed this connector that enables the trusted data exchange in order to be an active part of an IDS Ecosystem, a virtual data space leveraging existing standards and technologies, as well as governance models well accepted in the data economy, to facilitate secure and standardised data exchange and data linkage in a trusted business ecosystem. The TRUE connector is also part of the Fiware Catalogue. It supports IDS Multipart and IDS protocol (IDSCP) for communication. Available for both cloud and edge deployment.

Besides Data Spaces, market-ready solutions are available related to distributed data storage with a key representative to be Amazon S3⁴⁸. It is an object storage service offering industry-leading scalability, data availability, security, and performance. It is created to enable the storage and retrieval of any size of data and provides services for data protection and security, access control and management. OpenStack Swift⁴⁹ is another prominent solution positioning itself as a highly available, distributed, and eventually consistent object store.

There are also several platform-specific solutions, including Google Cloud Storage⁵⁰, IBM Cloud Object Storage⁵¹ or Azure Blob Storage⁵², LinkedIn's Ambry [16] and f4 used by Facebook [17].

4.2.3 Beyond State of the Art

ENACT will create its own data space to be used for data exchange across the Cognitive Computing Continuum and its pilot cases by aiming to combine these two core concepts of European research, the compute continuums and data spaces. More specifically, ENACT aims to provide a Secure and Sovereign Distributed Data Storage comprising of (i) Data Stores distributed across the cloud and edge nodes of the ENACT continuum, (ii) a Data Manager that is responsible for identity and access management, handles metadata and monitors the Distributed Data Storage's health, and (iii) Sharing Interfaces for data exchange with external ENACT components. The latter will employ Data Space Connectors to ensure that data is shared among different parties in a secure and sovereign manner.

Moreover, ENACT will try move a step further from data sharing to an innovative sharing of (data) objects between the applications that will be associated with the concept of data space. The faster implementation of distributed and dynamic ENACT applications will be enabled as the dataspace will act as a kind of a distributed data store that can manage the localisation and dynamism requirements of the application. The shared object space can be used by different components or services ranging from those running at edge devices to HPC clusters.

⁴⁶ <https://gec.io/solutions/gaia-x-dienste/>

⁴⁷ <https://github.com/Engineering-Research-and-Development/true-connector>

⁴⁸ <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

⁴⁹ <https://docs.openstack.org/swift/latest/>

⁵⁰ <https://cloud.google.com/storage?hl=en>

⁵¹ <https://www.ibm.com/products/cloud-object-storage>

⁵² <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/storage/blobs>

ENACT is envisioning a different approach for distributed data storages regarding CCC. ENACT will build a Data Space to support its CCC based on IDSA principles and Reference Architecture Model. The development will be based on EDC Connectors available implementations. ENACT will try to move beyond data sharing to objects sharing as well in its Data Space to support ENACT applications' development.

4.3 Risk and compliance

Risk and compliance are achieved in ENACT's CCC by addressing both technical and regulatory aspects of the system as a whole to make it secure and in accordance with legal requirements such as GDPR and AI Act. Large amount of sensitive data processed in the edge-to-cloud continuum makes it vulnerable to security breaches and unauthorised access. ENACT performs security risk modelling based on ISO 27005 for risk management which provides framework for information security management systems. Also, the data used by the ENACT's solutions will be assessed to check their adherence to the principles of AI Act addressing transparency, trustworthiness and accountability of high-risk applications. The process of checking compliance of data with AI Act will be automated in the ENACT.

4.3.1 Research directions and related work

4.3.1.1 Security Risk Modelling

With a rapid increase in demand for data intensive applications, the need for distributed data processing through extended edge services and reduced latency is ever increasing. Introduction of cognitive capabilities into computing environment such as edge, fog and cloud computing ensure that processing capabilities are distributed and operational across different layers of the network. The combination of cognitive computing with cloud computing results in real-time decision making, enhanced big data analytics, cost and resource efficiency.

To take full advantage of the Cognitive Computing Continuum (CCC) in a secure and trustworthy approach, multiple (layers of) cloud, edge and IoT platforms need to be continually analysed for cybersecurity threats. Cybersecurity means protecting digital information in the cyber environment which is a collection of networking devices, infrastructure, applications, communications protocols, and services. Proactive and automated mechanisms should be applied for risk analysis and mitigation to ensure the security and privacy of data and applications in such an interconnected distributed environment. To handle cybersecurity utilising International Standard Organisation (ISO) standards, security elements such as integrity, identification, privacy, durability, physical security must be considered for distributed applications in the CCC. Following is a list of security threats faced by applications in the CCC:

1. Data security and privacy: Any unauthorised access to sensitive data stored on the cloud can cause data breaches. Inadequate protection of data can lead to data leakage.
2. Compliance and legal risks: Applications stored/process using cloud infrastructure must comply with regulations such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA). Data stored within the cloud environment must follow the laws of the country where the data centres are located.

3. Adversarial attacks: Cognitive systems based on ML can face adversarial attacks due to model manipulation through feeding manipulated data into the system to affect its outcome. It is also vulnerable to data poisoning where the malicious data is injected into the training data.
4. Operational risk: Service downtime and integrity of data must be considered to avoid impacting applications outcome and reliability.
5. Security threats: Applications in the CCC are vulnerable to various cyber threats such as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) [18] attacks, malware, and ransomware.
 - DDoS attack tries to disturb the normal traffic of a server by flooding it with traffic from multiple sources. These types of attacks exhaust the resources i.e. bandwidth, CPU and memory decreasing the availability to the legitimate users in the cloud computing environment.
 - Malware [19] imposes threats due to misconfiguration, unpatched software, phishing and infected data.
 - Ransomware [20] is a type of software that tries to block access to system/data by encrypting the data making it inaccessible for the user.

The aforementioned security threats should be considered in the deployment and management of distributed applications. These types of security threats can be reduced by considering certain mitigation strategies such as:

- Using data encryption algorithms to protect sensitive data from unauthorised access. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES)⁵³ and End-to-End encryption [21] is widely used to encrypt data from sender to receiver.
- Implementation of access control and identity management to ensure only authorised users can access sensitive information. Standardised approaches to support the user identification and authorisation include OpenID Connect [22], and OAuth 2.0 [23], which are realised to verify clients access to the resources.

Data protection [24] is one of the key objectives for the security of cloud technology, it focuses on confidentiality, integrity, and availability (CIA) triad. For addressing the security and privacy related concerns, Cyber Security Framework (CSF) is a collection of security principles, standards, regulations, directives, and risk management process that can be used to protect the users and their assets⁵⁴. Moreover, innovative threat modelling techniques are needed to identify and mitigate security vulnerabilities. There are solutions available that are able to perform threat modelling and analysis. Many of the advanced ones are also able to estimate and analyse the likelihood and impact of each threat to help determine the possible solution or mitigation action based on the specific risk level. There are various risk treatment techniques to identify potential security threats to the distributed applications in the CCC environment. Following is a list of well-known solutions in the literature:

1. Threat modelling: Threat modelling tools identify vulnerabilities in the system. Below is a list of common methodologies:

⁵³ Dworkin, Morris J., et al. "Advanced encryption standard (AES)." (2001).
<https://nvlpubs.nist.gov/nistpubs/FIPS/NIST.FIPS.197-upd1.pdf>

⁵⁴ ITU-T, "Series X: Data Networks, Open System Communications and Security, X.1205," ITU-T, 2008.
<https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X>

- a. Security Threat Oriented Requirements Engineering (STORE) [25] methodology which embeds security requirements in the software development process based on a threat catalogue which contains previously identified threats.
 - b. Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege (STRIDE) [26] for identification of threats.
 - c. Damage potential, Reproducibility, Exploitability, Affected users, and Discoverability (DREAD) [27] Threat Model which evaluates the security threats.
2. Risk Assessment Frameworks: There are various organisations that define Cyber Security Framework (CSF).
- a. The non-governmental International Organisation of Standardisation (ISO)⁵⁵ created in 1947 promoted by International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC). The most important ISO standard for Information Security Management System (ISMS) is ISO/IEC 27005 [28]. Based on ISO/IEC 27000, different security requirements are identified at the planning stage of a software, cybersecurity threats are assessed and then control strategies are developed to lower the risks. In order to ensure trustworthiness, ISMS performance should be analysed frequently on an ongoing basis to address foreseen risks and make improvements for any future risks.
 - b. NIST SP 800-37⁵⁶: National Institute of Standards and Technology provides guidelines for managing and assessing security and privacy risks in cloud computing.

4.3.1.2 Regulatory compliance

The AI Act⁵⁷ is a proposed regulatory framework by the European Union aimed at managing the use and development of AI within its member states. The primary goal of the AI Act is to ensure that AI technologies are safe, trustworthy, and aligned with EU values and fundamental rights.

The key aspects of the AI Act are:

1. **Risk-Based Approach:** The AI Act categorises AI systems based on the level of risk they pose to users. These categories include:
 - a. **Unacceptable Risk:** AI systems that are considered a clear threat to safety, livelihoods, and rights are banned. Examples include social scoring by governments.
 - b. **High Risk:** These systems require strict regulations and oversight. They are subject to rigorous testing, documentation, and monitoring. Examples include AI in critical infrastructure, education, employment, and law enforcement.
 - c. **Limited Risk:** These systems have specific transparency obligations. Users must be informed that they are interacting with an AI system.

⁵⁵ <https://www.iso.org/about>

⁵⁶ <https://csrc.nist.gov/pubs/sp/800/37/r2/final>

⁵⁷ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/>

- d. **Minimal Risk:** These AI systems are considered low-risk and can operate without additional requirements. This category includes applications like AI-enabled video games or spam filters.
2. **Compliance and Enforcement:** The AI Act establishes requirements for AI providers and users, including risk management systems, data governance, documentation and logging, transparency, human oversight, and robustness. It also proposes the creation of national supervisory authorities and a European AI Board to ensure compliance and enforcement.
3. **Innovation and Flexibility:** The Act aims to balance regulation with fostering innovation. It includes provisions to support regulatory sandboxes, where AI systems can be tested under controlled conditions before being deployed.
4. **Alignment with EU Values:** The AI Act emphasises the importance of protecting fundamental rights, including privacy, non-discrimination, and data protection. It seeks to ensure that AI systems respect human dignity and democratic values.

With the introduction of the AI Act, it is important for solution developers to ensure compliance with these acts to avoid potential legal problems and financial repercussions. The ambition of proposed component to automatically check the data planned to be used by the solutions to assess their adherence to the principles of the AI Act. The research focus is on developing an approach for automated regulatory compliance verification, designed for seamless integration into diverse technology stacks.

4.3.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

4.3.2.1 Security Risk Modelling

Various market ready solutions have been developed to address cybersecurity threats. Following is a list of commercial solution for security threat modelling and analysis:

- **Microsoft Threat Modelling Tool (TMT)** [29] is a software developed by Microsoft for identifying security vulnerabilities in software applications. It is based on Spoofing, Tampering, Repudiation, Information Disclosure, Denial of Service, and Elevation of privilege (STRIDE) [30] method to systematically identify threats. Data flow diagrams (DFDs) are used to model the system and its behaviour based on STRIDE categories. Users can create a threat model, visualise attack patterns and control strategies are generated as reports for the implementation of security measures.
- **Threat Modeller** [31] Software, Inc. has developed a threat modelling platform which help organisations assess and mitigate cyber intrusion using a process flow diagram. It offers automated threat intelligence and attack path analysis and integration with security workflows.
- **Open Web Application Security Project (OWASP) threat dragon** [32] is an open-source software for threat modelling that is used to create threat models for the software applications.
- **IriusRisk** [33] is a commercial threat modelling tool developed by IriusRisk Ltd. which requires a paid subscription to use. It uses a variation of data flow diagrams.

- **Eclipse Papyrus for Real Time (Papyrus-RT)** [34] is an open-source software for creating architectural models for real time and embedded systems. It is not designed specifically for threat modelling but can be used to identify potential security vulnerabilities.
- **Lucidchart** [35] is a commercial cloud-based diagram tool used to create various diagrams to visualise system architecture and security vulnerabilities.
- **Systems Security Modeller (SSM)** [36] processes system models to perform risk analysis. A system model represents the structural and functional aspects of the applications and hardware involved for risk analysis. It includes various processing components and their interconnections. Physical objects (such as data, database, process, servers, etc.) are represented as nodes in the system model which are termed as assets. The interaction between these assets is known as connections.

SSM developed by University of Southampton is based on asset-approach to system security enabling automatic identification of potential security risks to all assets and also consider inter-connectivity between assets. Assets include both humans and technology. It also checks for GDPR⁵⁸ compliance and follows ISO 27005⁵⁹ risk assessment procedure hence also supports ISO 27001⁶⁰. It also checks for threat patterns from OWASP Top 10 vulnerabilities [37].

Risk assessment methods in literature primarily focus on the specific assets of the system (such as database or data storage) and do not consider the interconnectivity between these assets in a system known as context establishment. However, risk modelling solutions should also be able to analyse the risks arising from interconnectivity of the assets so that risk analysis of the overall system can be performed. SSM described above is one such solution in the literature which performs risk analysis for assets and their interactions.

4.3.2.2 Regulatory compliance

As of now, specific tools designed exclusively for AI Act compliance are not widely available, given that the AI Act is still in the proposal stage and has not been fully enacted. However, several existing AI compliance and governance tools can help organisations align with the anticipated requirements of the AI Act. These tools generally focus on transparency, fairness, bias detection, and robust documentation, which are key elements of the AI Act. Here are some tools that can be leveraged for this purpose.

EU AI Act Compliance Checker⁶¹ is developed by the team at the Future of Life Institute. The EU AI Act Compliance Checker is a tool or service designed to help organisations ensure that their AI systems comply with the European Union's AI Act. The tool consists of the set of questions related to AI Act, related to the organisation, like: "*Which kind of entity is your organisation?*"; "*Is your system a General Purpose AI model?*"; "*Does your AI system (or the product for which your AI system is a 'safety component') fall within any of the following high-risk categories?*"; etc.

⁵⁸ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

⁵⁹ ISO/IEC 27005 (2018). Information technology - Security techniques - Information security risk management. <https://www.iso.org/obp/ui/#iso:std:iso-iec:27005:ed-3:v1:en>

⁶⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/82875.html>

⁶¹ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/assessment/eu-ai-act-compliance-checker/>

Based on the answers the tool provides guidance through different aspects of compliance with AI Act (Risk Classification, Compliance Assessment, Documentation and Reporting, Monitoring and Auditing, Best practices, Mitigation strategies).

However the tool does not provide possibility to the search by the specific questions and topics and on the other hand, tool is built in a way that makes it difficult to support implementation on other sites, since there are no APIs available.

The **AI Compliance tool**⁶² will guide technical, business and risk, and compliance teams through the requirements of the AI Act and provide them with a single platform to cooperate and document the compliance of separate AI projects within an organisation.

Key features of the tool are:

- Organisation of many AI projects in one place and quick assessment of their risks.
- Following of straightforward step-by-step tasks to tackle complex legal requirements.
- Documentation of an organisation's compliance journey.
- Collection of supporting evidence in one place.
- Access to guidance for AI governance best practices to understand the ways to achieve the highest level of compliance.
- Utilisation of a tool which will be updated regularly.

AI Act self-assessment tool⁶³ for business owners who use AI technology in their product and plan to distribute their product or already distribute their product in the EU. The scope of the tool is to answer is the technology used falls under the definition of the AI system. There is a definition inside the self-assessment tool that will help better understand if the AI Act applies in each case.

The self-assessment tool is split into four parts:

1. The first few questions focus on understanding whether the AI Act will *apply* to the organisation's AI system.
2. The second set of questions evaluates if the organisation's system can be considered *prohibited* under the AI Act.
3. If it's not likely to be prohibited, one can proceed to the questions evaluating if the system can be considered *high-risk*, and if not, what other obligations might apply under the AI Act.
4. Finally, if the AI system is not deemed high risk or prohibited, the tool will assist in evaluating whether it poses *limited risk* under the AI Act and the corresponding obligations associated with it.

European AI Scanner⁶⁴ (RegTech tool for EU AI Act compliance) is EU AI Act compliance platform that identifies and assesses AI systems to assign a risk categorisation. It leverages tools, software, and data analytics to automate assessment processes, monitor regulatory changes, and manage risk. The

⁶² <https://www.pwc.com/cz/en/sluzby/technologie-a-data/ai-act/ai-compliance-tool.html>

⁶³ <https://legalnodes.com/article/eu-ai-act-self-assessment>

⁶⁴ <https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/best-practices/european-ai-scanner-regtech-tool-eu-ai-act-compliance>

tool focuses on streamlining and automating the assessment process to assign risk categories under the EU AI Act. It assists businesses in managing compliance requirements for both high-risk and non-high-risk AI systems. Key features of the European AI Scanner include a configurable Rules Engine and an Impact Assessment module, providing various options to ensure compliance with the EU AI Act. The tool supports alignment with internal policies and generates necessary documentation and reports for functions such as CSR, ethical charters, and boards.

In-depth EU AI Toolkit: AI Act Toolkit⁶⁵ project is developing a step-by-step pro-justice compliance tool for developers of high-risk AI.

Complying with the AI Act can be challenging for providers of high-risk AI, as it demands extensive documentation, including a risk management system, data governance, and a declaration of conformity.

The Tool simplifies this critical task, streamlining the process of conducting mandatory internal controls and documentation while offering essential guidance on ethical and social considerations related to AI products. It reorganises the AI Act requirements into step-by-step instructions, guiding users through the workflow to ensure all necessary documentation is complete and compliant with regulatory guidelines. Users can download the completed documents for compliance or public disclosure and upload them to a dedicated Section for citizens and prospective clients to view. This demonstrates their commitment to exceeding the legal minimum required by the Act.

This tool goes beyond legal compliance. It encourages product managers to critically consider how AI relates to structural inequality and engage with the ethos of the Act. It prompts AI practitioners to consider both technical and sociotechnical responses to risk, recognising that systems can be harmful even without errors or biases. The tool advises consulting ethics experts from the product ideation stage and includes educational resources like short videos illustrating potential risks.

Privacy Pact⁶⁶ is a tool designed for companies to demonstrate their commitment to adhering to the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) rules and principles, regardless of their location. It includes the contractual obligations outlined in Article 28, which are required for all Data Processors. This tool is contractually binding and authenticated using Blockchain technology, making it a secure way to communicate the organisation's commitment on its website. While it is not a certification, it can be used to prepare for certification processes like Europrivacy⁶⁷.

Europrivacy, approved by the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) as the European Data Protection Seal, assesses and certifies compliance with GDPR and complementary national data protection regulations. It helps applicants identify and mitigate risks, demonstrate and validate their compliance, and enhance their reputation and market access. Europrivacy is the only GDPR certification officially recognised in all EU Member States.

⁶⁵ <http://lcfi.ac.uk/projects/ai-innovation-praxis/eu-ai-act-toolkit/>

⁶⁶ <https://www.europrivacy.org/en/resource/privacy-pact>

⁶⁷ <https://www.europrivacy.com/>

4.3.3 Beyond State of the Art

4.3.3.1 Security Risk Modelling

Despite the recent advancements in risk analysis methods, these approaches do not consider the challenges faced by edge-cloud continuum in terms of auto-generation of system models to perform a thorough risk analysis. ENACT aims to provide beyond state-of-art by performing auto-discovery of assets that are spread over edge-to-cloud continuum and embedding this information in the Dynamic Federated Graph-based Modeller of Resources, Devices and Services (DGM). Security Risk Modelling will be performed which is based on the open-source solution called System Security Modeller (SSM). SSM functionalities will be extended in the SRM to automatically generate system models using graph data and perform risk analysis. This choice of the baseline solution is depended on the functionality expected from the threat modelling solution in the ENACT conceptual architecture, where assessment of cybersecurity risks associated with distributed systems is an important aspect.

SRM allows to develop a system model by connecting different assets and perform design-time risk analysis. SRM allows implementation of ISO 27005, Open Worldwide Application Security Project⁶⁸ (OWASP), and GDPR⁶⁹ principles at the backend to analyse risks. As ENACT UCs are processing personal data, there is also a need to consider GDPR compliance throughout the data processing pipeline in the edge-cloud continuum. Figure 6 depicts the internal workflow for SRM.

Figure 6: Internal workflow of the Security Risk Modeller

The risk mitigation strategies generated by the SRM will enhance the overall security of ENACT platform and the distributed systems/application running in the cloud-edge continuum.

⁶⁸ <https://owasp.org/>

⁶⁹ <https://gdpr-info.eu/>

ISO 27001 encompasses people, processes, and technology, and is particularly well-suited for risk assessment in distributed environments that involve interconnected components, such as servers, cloud services, and databases, where securing these interactions is critical. ENACT will integrate the security-by-design principles outlined in ISO 27001 and ensure their application throughout the deployment decision-making process. ENACT automates the risk modelling process by auto-generating system models from graph data and providing a risk analysis report for the ENACT deployment configuration. This will involve evaluating control measures such as access control, encryption, and third-party service assessments, ensuring that security controls are embedded during the design phase before implementation. Alerts will be generated if any required controls are missing or not implemented.

4.3.3.2 Regulatory compliance

In order to develop an **AI Act Compliance Checker** component that will automatically check the data planned to be used by the solutions to assess their adherence to the principles of the AI Act, we plan to use LLM (Large Language Models) like: GPT-4, Gemini Pro, or Llama 3.1. We will follow developments in the field of LLM and regularly update the LLM used to avail of the latest capabilities. Integrating of any LLM with the AI Act's regulatory framework involves ensuring that the use of the chosen LLM complies with the requirements and guidelines outlined in the AI Act, particularly around high-risk applications, transparency, trustworthiness, fairness, and accountability. We will analyse LLMs performances (architecture, parameters, training data, key features, UCs) and choose the most suitable model for the component functionalities.

We want to automate checking compliance with the AI Act as much as possible, from assessing the type of the solution and to which risk group it belongs, to evaluating the documentation and whether it is sufficient as well as assessing the datasets used for training.

To comply with the AI Act, solution providers must prepare comprehensive documentation covering technical details, data usage, testing, transparency, regulatory compliance, and ethical considerations. Required technical documentation could be found in Annex IV⁷⁰ :

- A general description of the AI system,
- A detailed description of the elements of the AI system and of the process for its development, Detailed information about the monitoring, functioning and control of the AI system,
- A description of the appropriateness of the performance metrics for the specific AI system;
- A detailed description of the risk management system,
- A description of relevant changes made by the provider to the system through its lifecycle;
- A list of the harmonised standards applied in full or in part the references of which have been published in the Official Journal of the European Union,
- A copy of the EU declaration of conformity,
- A detailed description of the system in place to evaluate the AI system performance in the post-market phase

⁷⁰ <https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/annex/4/>

Our goal is to automatically process as many of those documents as possible in terms of used data (to explain what kind of data he used for training, how he/she did testing, accuracy, etc.).

ENACT will integrate advanced automation capabilities to assess AI systems' adherence to the AI Act, utilizing meta-information, user manuals and supplementary documentation to enhance precision in risk categorisation and compliance evaluation. Unlike current tools, ENACT solution will incorporate an adaptive API-compatible framework for seamless integration into diverse technology stacks, ensuring scalability and interoperability. Furthermore, ENACT will introduce dynamic updates to align with evolving regulatory requirements and embed mechanisms for real-time documentation quality checks and actionable compliance recommendations, advancing state-of-the-art regulatory verification.

4.4 Zero-touch provisioning services

In the contemporary landscape of network management, the escalation of business expansion and the diversification of geographic presence necessitate an advanced approach to network deployment. Traditional methods, which involve manual configuration and extensive human involvement, are not only labour-intensive but also prone to errors and security vulnerabilities. These challenges underscore the need for an innovative solution that can streamline the deployment process while enhancing operational efficiency and security.

Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) emerges as a pivotal technology in this context. ZTP revolutionises network deployment by automating the entire provisioning process, thereby minimising manual intervention and significantly reducing the potential for human errors. This state-of-the-art approach enables businesses to deploy networks rapidly across multiple locations without the traditional burdens of manual setups. It not only expedites the deployment process but also ensures increased security by eliminating the need to ship pre-configured devices that could potentially be compromised.

The operational benefits of ZTP include a substantial reduction in deployment time and costs, heightened security protocols, and enhanced scalability. This makes ZTP an indispensable tool for businesses looking to efficiently scale their network infrastructure in alignment with their growth and the dynamic demands of the market.

4.4.1 Research directions and related work

This research paper: "Time-to-Provision Evaluation of IoT Devices Using Automated Zero-Touch Provisioning" [38] by Ivan Boškov and colleagues, presents a state-of-the-art evaluation of ZTP for IoT devices, highlighting its necessity for efficient network management in large-scale deployments. The paper details two innovative ZTP approaches: one utilising software-enabled access points (Soft-AP) and another based on Bluetooth technology, both designed to automate and streamline the provisioning process without human intervention. These methods aim to tackle the challenges associated with the manual setup of heterogeneous IoT devices by significantly reducing provisioning time and potential human errors.

The study extensively tests these solutions on a specific testbed, demonstrating that automated ZTP not only outperforms manual provisioning methods in terms of time-to-provision (TTP) but also enhances the overall reliability of network setup processes. This work contributes to the IoT deployment field by providing scalable, efficient, and vendor-independent provisioning solutions that

can adapt to the evolving requirements of modern networks, underscoring the potential of ZTP to facilitate the broader adoption and expansion of IoT technologies.

The article "Intent-based zero-touch service chaining layer for software-defined edge cloud networks" [39] explores the innovative integration of Edge Computing, Software Defined Networking (SDN), and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV). This integration facilitates the dynamic and elastic deployment of services as virtualised functions across distributed clouds extended to the network edge, a concept referred to as dynamic service chains.

The paper introduces an intent-based zero-touch service chaining layer that enhances the programmability of service chain paths in edge cloud networks. This layer autonomously adapts service chain paths in response to network conditions like sudden congestion, utilising intent-based directives that simplify network management and reduce the necessity for manual configuration. The experiments conducted in an emulated network environment validate the feasibility of this approach and measure its impact on network resource usage and adaptation overhead.

The backdrop of this study is the rapid evolution of mobile networks, the Internet of Things (IoT), and various smart devices that are creating new application demands in sectors such as telemedicine and industrial automation. These applications benefit from Edge Computing, which provides necessary computing resources closer to the data source, enhancing responsiveness and interactive behaviour.

Traditional provisioning methods for IoT devices, reliant on manual configurations and updates, pose significant security risks and inefficiencies. The integration of embedded SIMs (eSIMs) presented in paper [40] emerges as a robust solution, enhancing secure and flexible identity management in IoT devices. This study introduces a low-cost, zero-touch provisioning system utilising the GSMA Over-The-Air (OTA) IoT-SAFE protocol, facilitating eSIM-based remote provisioning. The system leverages blockchain technology for immutable data storage and verification through Ethereum smart contracts, ensuring enhanced security and integrity across IoT deployments. Through comprehensive simulations and security analysis, the proposed system -dubbed SleSIM- demonstrates superior efficiency and resilience compared to traditional provisioning methods, significantly reducing Time-To-Provision (TTP) and enhancing scalability and security against diverse attack vectors in AIoT environments. This research underscores the potential of eSIM and blockchain in revolutionising IoT device management, paving the way for more secure, efficient, and autonomous IoT ecosystems.

4.4.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

ZTP solutions are prevalent in industries where quick and reliable network deployment is essential, such as telecommunications, data centres, and enterprise networks.

- Cisco's DNA Center⁷¹ offers a centralised network control and management dashboard that facilitates ZTP for switches, routers, and wireless controllers. It automates the process of device configuration and management, making network deployments faster and reducing manual errors.

⁷¹ <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/products/collateral/cloud-systems-management/dna-center/nb-06-dna-center-data-sheet-cte-en.html>

- Ubiquiti's UniFi platform supports ZTP for scalable network device deployment, particularly useful in managing and expanding enterprise networks with minimal IT assistance.
- Dell's OpenManage Network Manager⁷² facilitates easy deployment of network configurations and firmware updates, offering ZTP features that help automate and streamline network setup and management.
- Cumulus Linux, an open network operating system, provides ZTP functionalities that help automate the deployment of network devices from a bare metal state.

4.4.3 Beyond State of the Art

ZTP is highly applicable in dynamic and scalable environments like cloud data centres, large corporate networks, and rapidly expanding IoT ecosystems. It facilitates quick and reliable network expansion and upgrades, supports consistent policy enforcement across the network, and enhances security by reducing the attack vectors associated with manual configurations.

As ZTP evolves, it is likely to tackle the increasing complexity and security needs of modern networks with several key developments:

- ZTP will increasingly incorporate AI to optimise configurations and predict network needs, allowing for real-time adjustments and proactive issue management. ZTP will read these optimised configurations from the Orchestrator who at its turn will be notified by other CCC components.
- The configurations lists will be managed by the ZTP who will actively communicate any update appeared in the network to the Orchestrator
- As edge computing expands, ZTP will adapt to manage a wide array of edge devices, ensuring seamless integration and security across distributed architectures.
- ZTP will also handle the K8 clusters configurations using Ansible playbooks. This can be done with MAAS and Juju⁷³ open-source component.

While ZTP provides substantial benefits, it also poses challenges such as the need for comprehensive pre-deployment planning and the risk of security vulnerabilities in the automation scripts themselves. Future advancements in ZTP are likely to focus on integrating artificial intelligence to predict and adapt to network changes dynamically and enhancing security measures to safeguard against automated attacks.

ENACT's Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) will utilise Ubuntu MAAS (Metal as a Service) as a foundational tool to automate the deployment and onboarding of new edge devices as they join the network. MAAS will streamline the provisioning process by enabling the automatic detection, configuration, and management of hardware resources, ensuring a seamless integration of edge devices into the ENACT ecosystem.

⁷² <https://www.dell.com/support/home/de-at/product-support/product/dell-openmanage-network-manager/overview>

⁷³ <https://juju.is/>

To tailor the ZTP process to ENACT's specific requirements, the system will incorporate Ansible playbooks and Cloud-Init scripts. These tools will allow for the automated installation and configuration of ENACT's suite of tools and components that are needed to be deployed on a device.

By leveraging these technologies, ENACT's ZTP process will minimise manual intervention, reducing setup times and potential errors, and enabling a scalable and efficient onboarding of edge devices across diverse environments. The process will ensure that each device is fully operational and integrated with ENACT CCC architecture.

The ZTP solution will be developed as an open-source framework, promoting transparency and adaptability. It will aim to support a wide variety of deployment scenarios and environments, balancing flexibility with practicality to align with ENACT's overarching goals. By accommodating diverse infrastructure needs, ENACT ZTP will extend its usability beyond typical edge deployments, enhancing its robustness and applicability in real-world scenarios. Thus, providing a more general approach compared to existing solutions.

4.5 Edge-cloud orchestration

4.5.1 Research directions and related work

The major research challenges regarding orchestration in cloud-to-edge continuums are resource visibility [41] dynamic resource allocation [42] (e.g. due to resource uncertainty, energy constraints and dynamic dependencies), dynamic management of application elasticity, and dynamic workload scheduling and resource heterogeneity at the edge [43].

Typically, orchestration was rather focused on cloud settings, while a more recent trend involves edge-oriented solutions. However, the latter, more often than not, employ communication middlewares to facilitate cloud-to-edge interconnection and control using master-worker nodes. One such prevalent solution is FLEDGE [44], a low-resource container orchestrator that is capable of directly connecting to Kubernetes clusters via virtual communication channels and has been proven to be a viable alternative to lightweight K8S approaches such as K3S (further discussed in the next Section).

Nonetheless, with the advent of distributed, micro-service based applications that span across the computing continuum, new challenges have been introduced for orchestration. To cope with such challenges specialised orchestration solutions that fully leverage the capabilities of both the cloud and edge resources, while meeting the respective requirements, are necessitated. In this context, several research efforts have been made to investigate orchestration approaches tailored to the Cloud-to-Edge characteristics. For instance, the work in [45] introduces the concept of end-to-end slices. This concept supports the unified management of compute, storage and network resources by creating on-demand, software-enabled and per-tenant resource partitions across the cloud-to-edge continuum. Each slice is built as a fully-isolated set of such resources, allocated on-demand and exposed to a tenant as a single manageable object through proper abstractions, with the guarantee that the service performance will be independent of the status of the services running on other slices. Nevertheless, this approach pertains to resource orchestration to satisfy tenants' needs in multi-tenant environments but does not consider the dynamic scheduling of applications and their components to meet their requirements.

On the contrary, works such as ENORM [46], [47], [48] focus on the application orchestration and dynamic placement within the continuum spectrum, each one with its distinct pros and cons. Indicatively, ENORM enables offloading of computation tasks from cloud to edge and dynamic autoscaling of edge resources but does not support application migration among resources, while the second work presents a modular architecture wherein applications are treated as containerised micro-services, offloaded to edge resources and running in an isolated and scalable manner. Finally, the third solution extends the ETSI NFV MANO standard to achieve improved bandwidth utilisation and delivery time in smart city applications. However, none of them not consider dynamic application demands or infrastructure changes, lacking real-time re-configurations. Many research projects have also addressed the problem of orchestration in the cloud-to-edge continuum, resulting in relevant systems. A lot of them, including DECENTER [49], Capillary [50], SODALITE@RT [51] and PrEstoCloud [52], rely on the TOSCA (Topology and Orchestration Specification for Cloud Applications) specification to ensure deployment portability. However, their dependence on TOSCA renders them inevitably centralised, while since TOSCA does not provide support for edge deployments, such solutions rely on custom extensions to cater for edge requirements, thus their portability is at stake. Recently some blockchain-based solutions, such as mF2C [53], RAINBOW⁷⁴ [54] that depart from the traditional centralised management model have emerged. Still, they either do not consider important aspects such as scalability, dynamic application management [57] or infrastructure changes [59], or are focused particularly on the Edge rather than the entire continuum [58]. A thorough overview of the existing Cloud-to-Edge orchestration systems can be found in [55].

However, the current solutions struggle to manage the dynamism (at application and infrastructure) at edge and fog computing environments, as they are primarily inspired by the reliability inherent in the cloud environments. In this direction, MiCADO [56] recently introduced an orchestrator towards cloud-to-edge continuum however it is focused more on the delivery of an operational solution and not on the improvement of the orchestrator's intelligence in dealing with complex and dynamic orchestration needs of applications.

Distributed orchestration approaches to guarantee QoS across Cloud-Edge continuum based on Kubernetes have been introduced [57]. SmartORC [58] also uses a kind of optimisation algorithms and matchmaking related to QoS to support orchestration. Recently, knowledge [59] introduces a cloud-edge continuum that orchestrates AI models execution but it is completely focused on this. Oakestra proposes a hierarchical orchestration framework specifically designed to support service operation over edge infrastructures that incorporates novel features such as federated cluster management, delegated task scheduling, and semantic overlay networking, but the framework is designed to operate under the assumption that network conditions are relatively stable and reliable, while it also inherently sacrifices global optimality for local decision-making efficiency [60].

To deal with resource heterogeneity at the edge, EVE-OS, a universal, open Linux-based operating system for distributed edge computing that provides a flexible foundation for distributed edge deployments with choice of any hardware, application and cloud has been proposed. However, deploying an OS on some edge devices is still challenging due to hardware computing limitations [61]. In this regard, BalenaOS, a host operating system based on Yocto Linux which provides a small

⁷⁴ RAINBOW_D1,2-RAINBOW-Reference-Architecture, https://rainbow-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/RAINBOW_D1.2-RAINBOW-Reference-Architecture.pdf

memory footprint, with the purpose of running Docker containers on embedded devices has been proposed, yet it currently supports only up to 20 different device types [62].

In terms of scheduling, Kubernetes offers its standard scheduler, capable of managing multiple applications, however, as we will see in the papers mentioned next, it comes with its limitations.

In this work [63], the author attempts to improve the Horizontal Pod Autoscaler (HPA) that comes with Kubernetes, creating an HPA+ based on prediction models. He mentions that the default scaler is static and doesn't offer much choice for cases where the applications require a more dynamic approach.

Due to the lack of specific features, this author [64] creates an alternative method to the standard scheduler. He says that the default scheduler of Kubernetes, only has as queue-based scheduler, can only dispatch one at a time, and the pod scheduling time is globally optimal. The author then addresses the increasing need of a better scheduling automation solution, due to increased complexity levels and real-time requirements of large-scale cloud computing systems. The proposed solution is a deep learning and reinforcement learning algorithm, each one charged with a different task. Deep learning for monitoring and prediction, and then combined with the reinforcement learning, the task scheduling is altered based on the real-time system state and task characteristics, achieving optimal resource utilisation and maximum efficiency for the task at hand.

The author in [65] wanted to create a custom scheduler due to the Kubernetes limitations regarding the default scheduler. Newer applications required different needs, and so he decided to make a solution that was able to fulfil the requirements of these applications, respecting factors like storage metrics, CPU and RAM metrics, or other resources. In order to do this, he looked at components like etcd⁷⁵, that is utilised to record the current status of the system making state observation available for all, the Scheduler itself, which will be responsible for allocating a time slot for every pod residing in a certain node, the API server in charge of accepting instructions and altering the information for the Kubernetes components, Kubelet⁷⁶ manages the communication between nodes, namespaces allows for same pods with same namespace to interact with each other, and as a monitoring module he uses Prometheus and Kubernetes dashboard to check on pod and node data.

Some pods might require a different approach due to security concerns. Delicate data needs to be handled differently, and that is when network policies come in. Kubernetes already has a plugin⁷⁷ dedicated to this matter, so it is possible to manage the pod affected by these policies, like controlling who communicates with it. The two known states of isolation for these kinds of pods will be "isolation for egress" or "isolation for ingress", meaning that the only connections available from the pod come from a egress list, in case of "isolation for egress", while "isolation for ingress" allows connections into the pod from the pod's node and ingress list, and the default pod configuration is "non-isolated for egress" and "non-isolated for ingress", allowing all types of connections. A pod with the policy "isolated for egress" has a list with the allowed traffic routes from the pod, while the "isolated for ingress" allows traffic for the pod.

⁷⁵ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/administer-cluster/configure-upgrade-etcd/>

⁷⁶ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/reference/command-line-tools-reference/kubelet/>

⁷⁷ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/concepts/services-networking/network-policies/>

4.5.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

In recent years, several cloud orchestration solutions have become available, such as Kubernetes, Cloudify⁷⁸ and Docker Swarm⁷⁹. Major cloud providers also offer tools for orchestration, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) CloudFormation⁸⁰ and Google's Deployment Manager⁸¹. Overall, orchestration solutions are rather focused on cloud-based deployments and, cover only to a lesser extent, emerging Edge-to-Cloud scenarios.

Kubernetes is one of the most recommended tools for container orchestration and broadly used by the industry. Its API is responsible for listening to the other parts of the system and communicating with the orchestration process, so they could manage the applications considering factors like resource allocation, priority orders, container availability and health, and other criteria.

Several lightweight Kubernetes derivatives have been developed (e.g., K3s⁸², K0s⁸³, MicroK8s⁸⁴) to handle the particular requirements of the Edge. There are also platforms designed for the Edge, such as KubeOne⁸⁵, EdgeX Foundry⁸⁶, and Open Horizon⁸⁷ that extend the orchestration logic to the Edge aiming to provide unified management. One notable open-source initiative to handle the connections and orchestration of edge resources is KubeEdge [66]. KubeEdge consists of a cloud part and an edge part, with the cloud part interfacing with the cloud Kubernetes API for edge node management. The edge part is deployed on each device to manage pods. KubeEdge supports bidirectional communication between the edge and the cloud parts to ensure metadata synchronisation, syncing cloud-side resource updates to the edge, and reporting edge-side host and device status changes to the cloud. It also supports MQTT which enables edge devices to access through edge nodes.

Kubernetes supports the customisation of schedulers to better adapt the assignment of application pods to the intended objectives and requirements. Multiple custom schedulers⁸⁸ are currently available, but they all have specific objectives, and they do not offer an option to be fed custom AI model decisions. There are also some Scheduler Plugins⁸⁹ that can be looked further, but a custom scheduler would allow us to create a more appropriate approach to the problem.

This custom scheduler, tailored to specific needs, could receive details about the application requirements, like the type of node demands, either be a high availability node or a standard one, useful for high-availability applications. Following these instructions, the scheduler would search among the available nodes for the best candidate.

⁷⁸ <https://docs.cloudify.co/>

⁷⁹ <https://docs.docker.com/engine/swarm/>

⁸⁰ <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudformation/>

⁸¹ <https://cloud.google.com/deployment-manager/docs>

⁸² <https://k3s.io/>

⁸³ <https://k0sproject.io/>

⁸⁴ <https://microk8s.io/>

⁸⁵ <https://www.kubermatic.com/products/kubermatic-kubeone/edge/>

⁸⁶ <https://www.edgexfoundry.org/>

⁸⁷ <https://www.lfedge.org/projects/openhorizon/>

⁸⁸ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/extend-kubernetes/configure-multiple-schedulers/>

⁸⁹ DavidW. (2024, March 8). 11 Kubernetes Custom Schedulers You Should Use. <https://overcast.blog/11-awesome-kubernetes-custom-schedulers-you-should-use-a29e86c82838>

For monitoring purposes, Kubernetes⁹⁰ already establishes that it works with OpenMetrics⁹¹, also part of the CNCF⁹², that extends the Prometheus exposition format. This guarantees a reliable service since we can check how the applications behave when deployed, delivering performance data, resource utilisation metrics, and other useful information to pass on.

4.5.3 Beyond State of the Art

Despite recent advancements in orchestration systems, most approaches do not adequately address the challenges posed by the Edge-Cloud continuum paradigm in terms of dynamic resource discovery and scheduling, scalability, elasticity, heterogeneity, etc. ENACT aims to advance beyond state-of-the-art by providing an AI-powered orchestration engine to explicitly cover novel Edge-Cloud applications and UCs. ENACT is expected to add value to existing solutions (e.g. KubeEdge) by extending them to achieve enhanced, AI-based orchestration decisions across the entire Edge-Cloud spectrum. Task allocation will be performed dynamically aiming to distribute workload across computing nodes considering computational capacity, data properties, available infrastructure and network status.

The communication between Kubernetes API and the other parts of the ENACT architecture is an important step in the orchestration process. The required solution needs to be able to bridge these components to allow the handling of information in real-time, leading to better orchestration decisions.

The customisation of Kubernetes schedulers is extended, to consider the decisions made by the AI Models and execute the deployment solution, that was requested by the DRL+GNN component in the AI layer (based on the input received from the AI Forecaster), and results to the optimisation of resource utilisation and achieving the targeted runtime efficiency. It may also be important to use/develop technology capable of interpreting the decisions made by this layer, to be able to translate it to formats that the technology, used for the orchestration tool, can understand.

The implementation of ENACT orchestrator requires the development of a custom scheduler, capable of receiving deployment instructions that were generated by AI algorithms, providing information about where applications need to be deployed. Instead of looking individually at each application's requirements and finding the best node, the custom scheduler will get instructions that have in consideration requirements and continuous performance of all applications, providing the optimal deployment for the entire range of applications.

To support heterogeneous nodes, ENACT orchestrator will use Kubernetes node description capabilities to add information that could be useful for the AI algorithm to calculate the best possible nodes for the application. Base resource descriptions will be extended as needed to properly describe the hardware resources.

Edge nodes can have lower resource availability, making them less viable to run containers and full applications, and it's through technologies like KubeEdge, EdgeX Foundry, KubeOne, OpenHorizon that will give these devices adaptation methods. Deeper study on those technologies on complex applications setups will be needed to understand the appropriate technologies to be used in ENACT to support the deployment and execution of applications on these devices.

⁹⁰ <https://kubernetes.io/docs/tasks/debug/debug-cluster/resource-usage-monitoring/>

⁹¹ <https://openmetrics.io/>

⁹² <https://www.cncf.io/>

4.6 AI Algorithms and training environments

Based on recent research outcomes, the orchestration intelligence can be based on approaches such as search-based algorithms, mathematical programming algorithms and game-theoretical or deep learning algorithms. E.g., AI4DL [67] shows how to manage resources by analysing deep learning workloads. Similarly, Theta-Scan leverages behaviour analysis to auto-scale containers in the cloud. RL has also been introduced [68] as a method for cloud-edge-fog orchestration and scheduling.

4.6.1 Research directions and related work

4.6.1.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling

Forecasting the resource demand and provide the optimal allocations are open problems in which multi-factors should be considered. For the resource demand forecasting, factors such as low resource utilisation, unbalanced load and security issues play an important role. Such forecasting is typically based on time series analysis or regression methods to predict request arrival rates and resource usage patterns [69]. Most existing AI-based or ML-based forecasting mechanisms use algorithms including long short-term memory (LSTM) [70] [71] or bidirectional LSTM (Bi-LSTM) [72] to achieve improved accuracy in resource demand predictions, while other approaches such as artificial neural networks (ANNs) [73] or regression algorithms (e.g., support vector regression (SVR)) have been widely used [74] for predicting the application performance. However, such forecasting models have been explored mainly in the context of cloud environments and are usually focused on optimising either workload distribution or application performance [70].

In addition, the provision of the optimal allocation should be also considered as multi-factor problem, trying to optimise the allocation between the network delay, energy consumption, deadline of the application, the processing cost and the number of tasks that have to be executed [75].

A considerable amount of works are using heuristic approaches to schedule the resource demand and allocation. Pasiadis et al. in [76] used a genetic algorithm along with a Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) algorithm to optimally schedule the resource allocation in an SDN environment. In their solution they are optimising the scheduling based in the network QoS, jitter, delay and bandwidth. Another heuristic solution is presented in [77] where they are trying to provide the optimal scheduling based on minimising the transmission time. However, the resource needs in delay are not taken into consideration along with the deadlines of the applications.

In recent years, the literature suggests that instead of using heuristic algorithms (genetic algorithms, MILP) one should target for Deep Learning techniques and especially Deep Reinforcement Learning, due to its ability to recognise complex patterns, handle high-dimensional data, continuously improve in new domain data, and enable dynamic allocation of resources based on the current system state, offering personalised and optimised solutions to complex scheduling problems in CCC environments [78]. Deep Reinforcement Learning is found to be applied in several academic papers [79] [80]. However, in their solution they do not take into consideration the duration demand of the applications which request resources and they do not consider any security issues.

4.6.1.2 AI algorithms for anomaly detection

Empirical studies⁹³ have shown that server failure rates increase significantly with equipment age. As individual servers exhibit a measurable annual probability of failure, the cumulative risk across a large infrastructure becomes substantial over time. This growing likelihood of component failures poses a tangible threat to resource allocation and system reliability within a cloud continuum environment. This risk is further exacerbated when server failures have cascading effects on neighbouring nodes, potentially disrupting service continuity. Consequently, the development of robust anomaly detection mechanisms becomes essential for identifying and mitigating potential failures, ensuring resilience and efficient resource management across the continuum. Infrastructure anomaly detection techniques aim to identify these issues early on, allowing providers to take corrective action before they escalate into more significant problems.

Anomaly detection, also known as outlier detection, refers to the process of identifying rare or unusual patterns in data, referred to as anomalies, which deviate significantly from expected behaviour. Anomalies can indicate important information such as system failure, malicious activity or any kind of special presence that would be useful to analyse. Anomaly detection techniques have been developed in various application fields, from cybersecurity for detecting malicious behaviour, to medicine diagnosis for disease detection and treatment optimisation [104] and industrial monitoring.

Anomaly detection systems are designed to identify deviations from expected patterns within datasets by employing a range of statistical and machine learning (ML) techniques. These deviations can be broadly categorised into point anomalies and contextual anomalies. Point anomalies represent individual data instances that diverge significantly from the rest of the dataset, often manifesting as outliers. In contrast, contextual anomalies arise in structured data where contextual information is essential for interpretation. To effectively detect such irregularities, anomaly detection systems are typically trained on large volumes of historical data. The training phase enables the model to learn the underlying patterns of normal system behaviour, thereby establishing a baseline. Once trained, the system can monitor incoming data in real time and issue alerts when significant deviations from the learned norm are observed [105].

Two primary approaches exist for training anomaly detection models: supervised learning and unsupervised learning. In supervised learning, the training dataset includes explicitly labelled examples of both normal and anomalous instances. This facilitates the validation and calibration of the model by providing a clear ground truth. Conversely, unsupervised learning does not rely on labelled data; instead, it operates under the assumption that normal instances are dominant in the dataset. Anomalies are then inferred as observations that exhibit significant divergence from the inferred distribution of normal behaviour [105].

Both supervised and unsupervised ML models have been explored for anomaly detection. Supervised approaches typically use techniques like decision trees, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Isolation Forest. These methods classify services based on known patterns of normal and abnormal behaviour, making them effective at detecting deviations in system performance [105].

⁹³ Frequency of server failure based on the age of the server (per year) 2014:
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/430769/annual-failure-rates-of-servers/>

One promising unsupervised method is the use of Autoencoders, a type of Deep Neural Network (DNN). Autoencoders are first trained to recognise the normal state of a system and are then used to detect anomalies by identifying discrepancies between normal and observed data. This approach is particularly effective when dealing with large volumes of data and unknown anomalies [106].

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs), particularly Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks, are another popular method for anomaly detection. These models are well-suited for time-series data, such as resource utilisation patterns, which are common in cloud systems. LSTM networks are capable of learning from past anomalies and can predict future behaviour based on historical data, making them effective at detecting deviations that manifest over time [107].

Finally, in more recent bibliographic works, many anomaly detection techniques have leveraged Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to identify anomalies and capture the dependency patterns among features [108].

4.6.1.3 Graph Neural Networks

The computing continuum refers to the bridge that connects the vast expanse of Internet of Things (IoT) devices, also known as the edge, to the robust infrastructure of high-performance cloud services. With all the amount of data that it is being gathered, transmitted and processed nowadays, arises a pressing need for innovative solutions to keep this data flow viable.

Due to this increase in the amount of data being worked with, new approaches to this problem have had to be considered, such as increasing the data processing capacity in IoT devices to reduce the huge amount of computational work on the high-performance cloud part, so a much lower latency can be achieved, or to avoid an overload in the network that prevents the correct processing of this same data in the cloud.

Using Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) to optimise the functionality of the computing continuum represents a cutting-edge application of AI in enhancing distributed computing environments. GNNs are employed to optimise resource allocation and task offloading across the computing continuum by modelling the heterogeneous computing resources and their interconnections as a graph. Also, they assist in dynamically balancing the load across edge, fog, and cloud computing nodes based on real-time workload and resource availability. By continuously analysing the graph representing the computing continuum, GNNs adaptively adjust resource allocations to prevent bottlenecks and ensure efficient utilisation of computational resources.

As the GNNs are working with real-time data from edge devices, sensors and cloud servers, they can adopt a predictive behaviour by learning complex patterns and correlations in the data graph so they can predict future resource demands and system behaviour, optimising the performance and stability of the computing continuum. Also, the use of GNNs enables intelligent decision-making and inference at the edge devices by deploying lightweight models for real-time data analysis and processing. With this practice, GNNs can decide to leave this computational task to the edge devices achieving reduced latency and bandwidth usage, leading to faster response times and improved privacy.

In terms of how GNNs work, the core of many of their architectures is message passing. Nodes in the graph exchange information with their neighbours iteratively, updating their own representations based on the aggregated information. This mechanism allows GNNs to capture complex relational dependencies in these graph-structured datasets.

The acronym GNN encompasses a range of algorithms rather than a singular design. Over time, numerous architectures have emerged within this domain. Figure 7 stemming from [81] shows a visual representation showcasing crucial works in the field.

Figure 7: Graph Neural Networks: A Review of Methods and Applications

Below, some of the most notable architectures are reviewed:

- **Graph Convolutional Networks (GCNs):** GCNs are one of the earliest and most popular types of GNNs. They extend the concept of convolutional layers from regular grids (e.g., images) to irregular structures like graphs. GCNs have been successfully applied in various domains, but they have limitations in capturing long-range dependencies and handling graphs with different sizes.
- **Graph Attention Networks (GATs):** GATs improve upon GCNs by introducing attention mechanisms, allowing nodes to selectively aggregate information from their neighbours based on learned attention coefficients. This enables them to capture more fine-grained relationships in the graph, leading to improved performance in tasks such as node classification and link prediction.
- **Graph Sample and Aggregation (GraphSAGE):** GraphSAGE is another popular GNN architecture that samples and aggregates information from a node's local neighbourhood. It addresses scalability issues by operating on large graphs through sampling techniques while maintaining expressive power by aggregating information from different neighbourhood layers.
- **Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN):** GINs are powerful GNN models that can learn permutation-invariant node representations. Unlike GCNs, GINs use MLPs (Multi-Layer

Perceptrons) to aggregate information from neighbouring nodes, making them more expressive and capable of capturing global graph structures.

Overall, GNNs have been integrated into reinforcement learning frameworks for tasks involving graph-structured data, such as social network analysis, recommendation systems, and traffic prediction. GNNs can effectively model the interactions between entities in the graph, enabling more effective decision-making in these domains. Despite their success, scalability remains a challenge for GNNs, especially when dealing with large-scale graphs. Research efforts are ongoing to develop scalable architectures and training algorithms that can handle massive graphs efficiently.

4.6.1.4 Virtual Training Environments

In the field of distributed and federated deployment systems, AI, is playing an ever-increasing role in supporting more accurate and reliable predictions of optimal deployment configurations for dynamic and distributed applications. However, the reliability, accuracy and efficacy of AI models is heavily dependent on both the quality of the training data, and the algorithms robustness. In order to ensure the accuracy and reliability of AI models are continually improved, regular training, retraining and recalibration are often required. The use of a Virtual Training Environment (VTE) provides a solution to address the needs of AI models through the provision of a simulated environment that facilitates the training, retraining, and recalibration of AI models through an efficient and controlled approach.

Through the use of virtualisation technologies for the creation of simulated environments, AI models are enabled to interact with synthetic and real-world data. The utilisation of a Virtual Training Environment can allow AI model developers to conduct training, retraining, and recalibration processes on their model, and without the need for extensive infrastructure.

Within the field of VTE's for AI training, there are many recent advancements which further boost the advantages of the VTE in comparison to other typical approaches for AI model training, which may rely on the purchase of additional hardware and software resources to provision required computing capacity. Innovations in the area of VTE have focused on strengthening various aspects related to AI models training such as scalability, cost effectiveness, iterative improvements and accessibility.

In regard to scalability, there are a number of new development areas, for example:

- **Parallel and Distributed Processing** – the VTE can enable the partitioning of an AI or GNN model across multiple nodes or clusters by enabling accelerated parallel training (Model Parallelism), and can also enable the distribution of model training data across multiple nodes (Data Parallelism).
- **Container and Orchestration Technologies** – Through the use of technologies in this field such as Docker or Kubernetes, streamlined deployment, replication, and management of components across distributed environment can be enabled.
- **Autoscaling and Resource Management** – Through the use of ZTP, the VTE can dynamically adjust dynamically the allocated resources of different components of AI models such to help with workload distribution, performance, demand, and cost.

Increased capabilities in terms of scalability allow a greater level of iterative improvement within AI model training with optimisation of this process over distributed and dynamic resources.

In addition, VTE's provide an advantage over previous approaches due their effect on considerations such as cost effectiveness, accessibility, and safety and control. Removing the need for high powered,

or extensive physical infrastructure at the development level provides a number of other advantages with the first of which being increased accessibility.

Removing the need for extensive local infrastructure also plays a role in increasing accessibility to AI and AI training, to developers and the wider public with the tool being accessible regardless of local resources or physical location. This effect is also seen in terms of cost effectiveness, with AI developers now able to use the virtual training environments, in which access may be provided under various pricing models, however the large upfront costs associated with AI capable hardware is negated. The final advantage found under this approach is the increase safety and control that can be provided. Through the provision of the virtual training environments, AI developers are afforded a safe and controlled environment for testing and training their AI models, and without the risk of errors or accidents associated with real-world experimentation.

4.6.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

4.6.2.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling

To the best of our knowledge, there are not any technologies able to achieve a TRL (8-9) and be ready for Market that adopt AI for prediction and scheduling in CCC.

4.6.2.2 AI algorithms for anomaly detection

Anomaly detection mechanisms are usually custom-built to address a particular problem in a particular domain, and need to be trained on data that are representative of each use case. Hence, to the best of our knowledge, there are no market-ready solutions that could be referred to in this context. Below is a list of well-known vendors offering products and services related to anomaly detection. These vendors either provide tools that enable organisations to develop their own solutions, or offer services to build tailored solutions on their behalf. The latter typically involves substantial preparatory work, including training and integration phases, before the solutions can be effectively deployed for a specific purpose and aligned with concrete operational requirements. The main technologies employed by each vendor are also listed.

- **Anodot**⁹⁴: A technology company specialising in ML-based anomaly detection for real-time monitoring of business and application-level metrics. Its platform automatically learns normal patterns in high-volume data streams and identifies statistically significant deviations without relying on predefined thresholds. This allows detecting irregularities as they happen, minimising risks and enabling faster response times. Anodot's services are especially valuable in data-intensive industries such as fintech, and telecommunications, where operational efficiency and real-time insights are crucial. The platform supports proactive decision-making by delivering actionable insights that can improve performance, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction. To access Anodot's services, companies begin with a consultation to define their monitoring needs and business objectives. A personalised demo is then scheduled to showcase how the platform applies to their specific use case. Once confirmed, clients receive access to the cloud-based platform without the need for on-premises installation. The integration process involves connecting data sources to Anodot's system, supported by the company's technical team. After setup, clients undergo training to ensure

⁹⁴ <https://www.anodot.com/>

effective platform use, with continued support available as needs evolve. This end-to-end process is required to ensure smooth deployment and ongoing value through continuous optimisation and monitoring.

- **ITRex⁹⁵**: A technology company that specialises in building custom anomaly detection solutions by leveraging its expertise in cloud computing, artificial intelligence, data science, and the Internet of Things (IoT). The company develops intelligent systems tailored to client-specific needs, capable of identifying abnormal patterns across complex data environments. ITRex provides both cloud-based and edge-based anomaly detection options. In cloud settings, data is aggregated from internal systems, connected devices, and third-party services, then processed in the cloud using custom-trained machine learning models that detect deviations from expected behaviour and trigger alerts. For mission-critical applications, such as production line control, autonomous vehicles, and medical IoT, the company offers edge-based detection, where analysis occurs locally on devices, minimising latency and reducing cloud infrastructure costs, while non-urgent data is uploaded to the cloud for storage and further examination. Clients engaging with ITRex begin by collaborating on a fully customised solution aiming to meet the specific operational challenges of their industry, whether healthcare, banking, or commerce. ITRex draws on a wide array of technologies, including platforms like Amazon Web Services (AWS)⁹⁶, Microsoft Azure⁹⁷, and Google Cloud⁹⁸, and frameworks such as TensorFlow⁹⁹, PyTorch¹⁰⁰, and Apache Spark¹⁰¹. Their approach eliminates the need for manual data review, making it convenient to client's use, and enhances system reliability.
- **Microsoft Azure - AI Anomaly Detector¹⁰²**: Azure offers a wide range of AI-powered solutions across various application domains, including AI-based anomaly detection. Through Cognitive Services, developers can seamlessly integrate these AI capabilities into their applications via API requests, abstracting away the complexities of implementation. This standardised approach, designed by Microsoft, enables developers to focus on business logic automation rather than the intricacies of AI model deployment. Anomaly detection is a key AI service that supports decision-making processes. To enhance multivariate anomaly detection, Microsoft introduced MTAD-GAT (Multivariate Time-series Anomaly Detection via Graph Attention Network), leveraging Graph Attention Networks (GATs) to model complex dependencies across multiple time-series variables. For univariate time-series anomaly detection, Microsoft AI solutions employ conventional statistical and machine learning techniques, including Fourier Transformation, Z-score detection, and other established methods.[6]

⁹⁵ <https://itrexgroup.com/services/anomaly-detection/>

⁹⁶ <https://aws.amazon.com/>

⁹⁷ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/>

⁹⁸ <https://cloud.google.com/>

⁹⁹ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

¹⁰⁰ <https://pytorch.org/>

¹⁰¹ <https://spark.apache.org/>

¹⁰² <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/ai-services/ai-anomaly-detector>

- **Google BigQuery**¹⁰³: A fully managed, serverless data warehouse that enables efficient analysis of large datasets using SQL. It integrates machine learning (ML) capabilities, allowing users to build and deploy models directly within the platform. One key application of BigQuery ML is anomaly detection, which helps identify irregularities in data that may indicate fraud, system failures, or unexpected trends. BigQuery supports both supervised and unsupervised approaches for anomaly detection. When labelled data is available, supervised models, such as linear and logistic regression, boosted trees, random forests, DNNs, and AutoML models can be used via the ML.PREDICT function to classify anomalies. These models analyse past data to recognise patterns and identify deviations. For cases without labelled data, unsupervised learning methods are used with the ML.DETECT_ANOMALIES function. Time-series anomalies can be detected using ARIMA_PLUS and ARIMA_PLUS_XREG models, which identify unusual spikes or drops over time. K-Means clustering detects anomalies based on how far a data point deviates from cluster centroids. Autoencoders identify anomalies by measuring reconstruction loss, while Principal Component Analysis (PCA) flags data points that deviate significantly from expected variance patterns. BigQuery's serverless architecture, scalability, and SQL-based approach make it a powerful tool for anomaly detection. It simplifies applying ML to large-scale data without requiring infrastructure management, making it accessible for fraud detection, predictive maintenance, and real-time monitoring. By leveraging machine learning models, BigQuery helps organisations proactively identify issues and optimise decision-making processes.

4.6.2.3 Graph Neural Networks

In the rapidly evolving landscape of AI, Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) have emerged as powerful tools for modelling and analysing complex relational data. As the demand for GNN-based applications continues to grow, the need for robust and accessible tools has become increasingly crucial. The tools presented in this Section offer a unique set of functionalities tailored to support the development and deployment of GNN-based models, providing a diverse ecosystem for exploring graph-based ML techniques.

- **PyTorch Geometric**¹⁰⁴ offers a comprehensive suite of pre-built GNN layers and utilities tailored specifically for graph-based deep learning tasks. Its seamless integration with PyTorch facilitates flexible model definition and easy debugging. Additionally, it supports efficient batching and parallelisation for training large-scale GNN models and includes datasets and data loaders for common graph-based tasks, simplifying the data preprocessing pipeline. However, due to its rich feature set and flexibility, PyTorch Geometric presents a steeper learning curve compared to simpler frameworks. Furthermore, it provides limited support for the Windows operating system compared to other platforms.
- **Deep Graph Library (DGL)**¹⁰⁵ provides a high-level API for constructing and training GNN models, making it suitable for both beginners and advanced users. It offers support for

¹⁰³ <https://cloud.google.com/bigquery/docs/anomaly-detection-overview>

¹⁰⁴ <https://pytorch-geometric.readthedocs.io/>

¹⁰⁵ <https://www.dgl.ai/>

multiple frameworks, including TensorFlow¹⁰⁶, PyTorch¹⁰⁷, and MXNet¹⁰⁸, and enables dynamic graph construction and manipulation for dynamic graph learning scenarios. Extensive documentation and tutorials for various GNN tasks are available. However, DGL has limited support for advanced features compared to more specialised libraries like PyTorch Geometric and slightly lower performance for certain operations.

- **StellarGraph**¹⁰⁹ is a specialised library designed for scalable graph ML tasks, particularly suited for large-scale graphs. It provides implementations of state-of-the-art GNN models optimised for efficiency and scalability, supporting heterogeneous graphs and various graph-based learning tasks such as node classification, link prediction, and graph classification. While seamlessly integrating with popular deep learning frameworks like TensorFlow and Keras, StellarGraph offers limited support for PyTorch compared to other libraries. Some advanced features may require familiarity with the underlying graph processing engines for optimal performance.
- **Graph Nets**¹¹⁰, developed by DeepMind, offers a flexible framework for building graph-based neural networks supporting both static and dynamic graph scenarios. It provides implementations of various GNN components in the form of demos, illustrating how to create, manipulate, and train graph networks. Despite its flexibility, beginners may encounter a steep learning curve. Graph Nets requires TensorFlow 1¹¹¹, which might make it feel outdated for some users.
- **NetworkX**¹¹² is a Python library that offers a wide range of algorithms and utilities for graph analysis and visualisation. Primarily focused on the creation and manipulation of small to medium-sized graphs, NetworkX is suitable for prototyping graph-based algorithms and exploring graph structures. However, it has limited support for deep learning-based approaches compared to specialised GNN libraries.

4.6.2.4 Virtual Training Environments

- **Dataiku**¹¹³ is an AI and Analytics platform that allows users to extract insights from their data. It is provided in the form of a unified environment designed for use by a range of user levels from data scientists to business users, and allows for collaborative development. The platform provides features such as ML, model deployment, visual workflows and MLOps. In addition, the platform provides visualisation capabilities that enable users to capture key insights in charts and interactive dashboards. The Dataiku solution is available through free and Paid editions with different feature sets available, and it can be used in the desktop, cloud or on-premise environments.

¹⁰⁶ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

¹⁰⁷ <https://pytorch.org/>

¹⁰⁸ <https://mxnet.apache.org>

¹⁰⁹ <https://stellargraph.readthedocs.io/>

¹¹⁰ https://github.com/google-deeplearning/graph_nets

¹¹¹ https://www.tensorflow.org/versions#tensorflow_1

¹¹² <https://networkx.org/>

¹¹³ <https://www.dataiku.com/>

- **DataRobot AI Platform**¹¹⁴ provides an environment for both generative and predictive AI where users can create, deploy and manage AI models. The platform provides a range of features that are designed to cater to different user level. Key feature provided include visual workflows, training and tuning of models, model deployment and monitoring, and access control. In addition, the DataRobot provides capabilities design to ensure accurate documentation and regulatory compliance. The DataRobot AI Platform is only available as a paid on-premise or cloud-based service.
- **Alteryx Designer**¹¹⁵ is a tool that enables users to access and manipulate data sources through both visual work flows and code-based SDK, and extract insights through embedded AI capabilities. The tool provides an ecosystem of data connectors to access data from a wide range of sources and provides reporting and visualisation features. Features are also provided that cater to both technical and non-technical users. Like the previous one, the Alteryx Designer is available only as a paid solution.
- **H2O.ai**¹¹⁶ is an open-source ML platform that is designed for scalability and efficiency. The platform is more focused towards the technical user with the ability to provide custom ai applications for business users. The platform supports a range of ML algorithms, model creation, deployment and monitoring, and support increased transparency through model interpretability. H2O.ai resources are available as open-source solutions.

When selecting a tool or platform to provide capabilities in AI training, retraining, and recalibration, there are several core considerations that need to be taken into account depending on the intended usage. One such consideration is the usability of the platform, in terms of the intended user base of the. Some platforms such as the Alteryx Designer or the DataRobot platform provider a greater focus on addressing the needs of business users and ensure all operations can be performed through more intuitive visual workflows, whereas tools such as H2o.ai provide a greater focus on supporting tech users such as data scientists or programmers. Another key consideration is the licensing and pricing options available for each solution. A key advantage of H2O.ai in relation to the ENACT project is that it is open-source in nature and, as such, is available for reuse or extension. Although in the other alternatives mentioned that are proprietary, there are free versions available as is the case with Dataiku, these often come with a limited set of features or usage restrictions. It is also important to consider both the scalability and flexibility of each AI training platform, with reflection on support for a range of algorithms and specifically in the case of ENACT, support for GNN based data. For this reason, it is considered that there is no suitable tool on the market, that provides both an open-sources tool and the flexibility required for GNN based data and algorithms.

4.6.3 Beyond State of the Art

4.6.3.1 AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling

As analysed in Section 4.6.1.1, the AI scheduling and orchestration outcomes from the ENACT Project will advance current Deep Reinforcement Learning techniques by incorporating application duration and security policies into their objective function. Additionally, established Deep Learning algorithms

¹¹⁴ <https://www.datarobot.com/platform/>

¹¹⁵ <https://www.alteryx.com/products/alteryx-designer>

¹¹⁶ <https://h2o.ai/platform/ai-cloud/make/h2o/>

will be employed to predict telemetry data (available resources) for future time steps. This approach will enable the generation of multiple simulated network states and propose resource allocation not only for the current time step (t) but also for the future time step (t').

ENACT will go beyond the state-of-the-art approaches of applying various machine learning models to find the one that can provide the most accurate forecasting results. This will be conducted through the integration of hyperparameter tuning approaches to the model implementations using sophisticated optimisation algorithms like the Differential Evolution Algorithm [82], and more advanced online-parameter tuning methodologies that will provide the most optimal settings within the given execution timeframe in order to alleviate the time-consuming phase of manually tuning the models to the corresponding data. The optimal settings will be used to train state-of-the-art forecasting algorithms like the Long Short-Term Memory [83].

4.6.3.2 AI algorithms for anomaly detection

Innovative anomaly detection mechanisms that focus on the CCC resources will be developed as part of the AI Forecaster component, tasked with analysing real time data stemming from the ENACT continuum devices and identifying potential anomalous behaviour through computational monitoring. This information along with the calculated anomaly score can then be utilised by the DRL+GNN components for resource allocation purposes. To achieve this, the Anomaly Detector module will process telemetry data from ENACT continuum devices collected via the Telemetry Data Collection and Monitoring Engine component and fed from the AI Forecaster Data Analysis module. The data will incorporate key metrics such as CPU utilisation, energy consumption, latency, device/pod status, and other relevant variables to assess potential anomalies.

ENACT will introduce AI-driven anomaly detection mechanisms that go beyond the current state-of-the-art by focusing on the computing resources dimension, to enable the identification of potential issues of devices, such as faults or instabilities. These technologies will enhance the overall robustness and efficiency of the ENACT platform by employing machine learning techniques for obtaining optimal results. These methods will be rigorously tested to determine the most effective approach for the given use case.

4.6.3.3 Graph Neural Networks

The application of GNN models in the continuum represents a significant advancement in edge-to-cloud resource management. By harnessing the power of GNNs to support predictive maintenance, automatic scheduling, and efficient decision-making, T5.2 will contribute to enhance the efficiency, resilience of the ENACT continuum.

The GNN models will be designed to capture the complex interdependencies and interactions within the entire cloud-edge continuum. By modelling the system as a dynamic graph, the models will be able to account for factors such as resource heterogeneity, network topology, application dependencies, and environmental conditions. This holistic approach will enable more comprehensive and informed decision-making for orchestration and deployment strategies.

The key innovations are:

- **Real-time optimisation:** By operating on dynamic graph models and processing data in real-time, GNN models will enable continuous optimisation of the edge-to-cloud continuum. This

capability to adapt to changing conditions and requirements will set a new standard for efficiency and responsiveness in resource management.

- **Efficiency and resilience:** GNN models will enhance efficiency and resilience in the continuum by providing insights into optimal resource allocation, predicting maintenance needs, and enabling dynamic scheduling based on real-time conditions. This proactive approach will minimise downtime, improve performance, and optimise resource utilisation.
- **Complex decision-making:** GNN models will enable complex decision-making processes by considering a wide range of factors, such as performance metrics, energy efficiency, and network connectivity. This holistic approach will lead to more informed and effective decisions in managing the continuum.
- **Energy-efficient execution optimisation:** The GNN models will prioritise energy efficiency in application execution by identifying the most suitable nodes for executing tasks at any given time. By considering factors like power consumption, workload distribution, and environmental conditions, these models will optimise resource allocation to minimise energy consumption while meeting performance requirements.

ENACT is envisioning to combine a DRL Agent with GNNs to optimise the use of ENACT resources to minimise performance metrics, energy efficiency and network connectivity. This will be conducted through the deployment of a DRL agent that interacts with the dynamic environment of the ENACT continuum and adjusts actions based on real-time network conditions and resource utilisation. GNNs will play a critical role in modelling the relationships and dependencies between different nodes, providing to the DRL agent with structured and contextual information about the state of the network, which includes real-time data on resource usage and network topology. In addition, moving forward the developments identified in [79], ENACT will implement GCN and GAT layers in the GNN instead of simple layers, will explore the addition of meta learning approaches with the aim to self-tune the DRL Agent and will explore the addition of different exploration techniques compared to the well-known epsilon greedy algorithm.

4.6.3.4 Virtual Training Environments

The VTE developed in ENACT will be able to make use of a range of compute resources such as VM's, GPU's, and TPU' in a distributed computing framework to enable parallelised processing of data and model training across multiple nodes. In line with current trends, the ENACT VTE will be able to make use of containerisation technologies to encapsulate AI model training workflows and provide data management capabilities for ingesting, preprocessing and storing different types of training data. To support the iterative training and deployment scenarios, the VTE will provide model versioning and control mechanisms for managing different AI model versions, artifacts and metadata. User-centricity will be ensured through capabilities to track manage and monitor AI model training experiments, hyperparameters, performance metrics and artifacts across different model configurations. In order to optimise the AI model training workflows, the VTE will provide automated ML (AutoML) capabilities to the model development process such as feature engineering, hyperparameter optimisation, and model selection. The users of the VTE will also be supported by the real-time monitoring and alerting mechanisms for the detection of anomalies, errors or performance reduction during AI model training. Security and privacy of the models will be ensured through robust security measures for the protection of sensitive data, model assets and compliance with industry regulations. The VTE will also provide secure API's, authentication mechanisms and

audit trails to maintain data integrity and confidentiality. User centricity will also be supported by an intuitive user interface that includes the availability of visualisation tools for the generation of interactive, charts, graphs and dashboards. To support wider utilisation and exploitation of the VTE, the developed solution will be offered as an open-source resource.

The VTE will primarily be based on the ICE Analytics Product, developed and enhanced within EU projects such as iHelp, Themis, and EXTRA-BRAIN. At present, the VTE integrates libraries and toolsets such as H2O.ai, Tensorflow, and Sklearn to provide an innovative AI training platform. In addition, the tool makes use of technologies such as ApexCharts and SHAP for visualisation and explainability respectively.

ENACT intends to leverage proven technologies and methodologies to create a robust, scalable and cost-effective AI training platform. Through the integration of advancements in parallel and distributed processing, container and Orchestration technologies like Docker and Kubernetes, and autoscaling and resource management, ENACT will enhance the scalability and efficiency of AI model training. In addition, ENACT will contribute to going beyond state of the art through the provision of support for GNN-based data.

4.7 Application programming models

4.7.1 Research directions and related work

The development of hyper-distributed applications involves enabling functionality across a wide spectrum of nodes and devices, including edge environments. This requires modular and portable software components that simplify integration across diverse platforms. Moving away from the traditional model of deploying standalone web applications and REST APIs, our current approach packages core capabilities into reusable Java libraries (JARs) distributed through a public repository. This shift provides developers with direct access to essential functions without the overhead of networked services or application deployment.

Frameworks like OSGi (Open Services Gateway Initiative), notably Eclipse Equinox¹¹⁷, and Apache Felix¹¹⁸, still offer valuable context for modular Java application design. However, by delivering core logic as lightweight, embeddable libraries, we reduce the operational complexity and infrastructure requirements associated with service-based architectures. Developers are now empowered to embed capabilities directly into their applications, accelerating development while maintaining flexibility.

Challenges in this space—such as managing device heterogeneity, handling intermittent connectivity, and maintaining data consistency—remain, but this library-based approach opens new possibilities. Future directions include embedding distributed AI models locally, improving edge processing autonomy, and integrating lightweight security mechanisms such as blockchain-based attestations—all without relying on centralised APIs or external orchestration.

In today's distributed enterprise environment, where users and applications span cloud, edge, and hybrid contexts, the demand for tools that abstract complexity is stronger than ever. By offering well-

¹¹⁷ <https://projects.eclipse.org/projects/eclipse.equinox>

¹¹⁸ <https://felix.apache.org/documentation/index.html>

defined SDKs instead of REST services, we enable faster prototyping and more adaptable deployments. This aligns with trends in infrastructure design, where minimizing dependencies on centralised services helps improve resilience, scalability, and performance.

The continuum-aware programming model described in [84] is still highly relevant. By translating workflows into portable service compositions with explicit Quality-of-Service contracts, it aligns well with our shift to embeddable components—now enabling these flows to be constructed with self-contained logic rather than remote service dependencies. Similarly, the advancements in [85] reinforce the value of intelligent, distributed computing models that can operate seamlessly from cloud to far-edge environments. Though IoT devices primarily collect data, most processing remains centralised in cloud infrastructures—introducing latency and energy inefficiencies. By empowering developers to integrate decision-making and processing logic directly within edge devices through local libraries, we aim to promote architectures that maximise responsiveness and reduce network reliance.

Historically, IoT and Edge devices have functioned as mere extensions of the Cloud, with control and intelligence residing centrally. Our current model flips this paradigm: by decentralizing logic into portable SDKs, developers can focus on their domain problems without worrying about distributed system orchestration, ultimately fostering more autonomous, context-aware, and scalable applications.

4.7.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

In the context of hyper-distributed applications, a number of commercial and industrial solutions illustrate the market's shift toward low-latency, secure, and modular architectures. These solutions—while often built around managed services and edge-cloud integration—highlight important trends that also inform the approach of the ENACT project. However, rather than relying on full-fledged cloud platforms or REST-based services, our updated direction emphasises a lightweight, embeddable model: delivering modular Java libraries (JARs) through public repositories. This enables seamless integration into host applications and systems across a wide range of environments, from edge devices to enterprise backends, without requiring additional service orchestration.

Solutions like Azure IoT Edge¹¹⁹, AWS IoT Greengrass¹²⁰, and Google Cloud IoT Edge¹²¹, have traditionally offered managed runtimes to deploy analytics, AI models, and business logic onto edge devices. These platforms bring computation closer to the data source to reduce latency, improve resilience, and optimise bandwidth. While they operate under managed service paradigms with central orchestration, our JAR-based approach provides a comparable advantage by enabling developers to embed similar logic directly within their own applications—without depending on external platforms or connectivity.

For instance, Azure IoT Edge supports containerised workloads and close integration with Azure cloud services. In our paradigm, developers would instead integrate JARs offering edge-optimised processing or domain-specific logic directly within Java applications running on constrained devices.

¹¹⁹ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/iot-edge>

¹²⁰ <https://aws.amazon.com/greengrass/>

¹²¹ <https://cloud.google.com/architecture/connected-devices/iot-platform-product-architecture>

This removes the need for Docker or Kubernetes environments, simplifying deployments where containerisation is impractical.

Similarly, AWS IoT Greengrass provides localised Lambda execution and ML inference at the edge. In our model, such processing can be delivered via pluggable Java modules, making it easier to deploy ML inference, device data aggregation, or rule-based automation without provisioning a cloud stack or maintaining persistent runtime services. These cloud-centric solutions are increasingly used in domains such as smart manufacturing, smart cities, and healthcare. In each case, our modular JAR-based approach offers an alternative that preserves the benefits of edge processing and AI enablement while significantly lowering the operational barrier.

Developers can compose applications with domain-specific JARs tailored for tasks like predictive maintenance, real-time diagnostics, or sensor data filtering, all executed locally without service dependencies. By emphasising embeddable software components over remotely managed services, our approach better supports disconnected or security-sensitive environments, promotes reuse, and minimises latency. Furthermore, this model aligns with modern software engineering trends such as dependency management, CI/CD integration, and reproducible builds—offering compatibility with public repositories like Maven Central¹²², or JitPack¹²³. Ultimately, by leveraging modular libraries instead of REST endpoints, the ENACT project can deliver flexible, domain-specific capabilities directly to developers. This supports the creation of highly responsive, scalable, and portable hyper-distributed systems—without binding them to any single cloud provider or infrastructure model.

An alternative to distributing reusable logic via JARs in public repositories is providing functionality through containerised microservices accessed via REST or gRPC APIs. This model decouples implementation from the client and allows for language-agnostic consumption, centralised updates, and dynamic scaling. It's particularly useful in cloud-native environments where infrastructure orchestration (e.g., Kubernetes) is already in place. However, it introduces network latency, operational overhead, and dependency on runtime availability, which can be limiting in edge or disconnected environments.

Another approach involves native code generation or code scaffolding tools, where developers generate source code or configurations tailored to their applications using CLI tools or build-time plugins. This allows for deep customisation and integration, often in a language- or framework-specific manner, without the need for shared binaries. While powerful, this method can increase complexity and reduce maintainability over time, especially when upstream logic changes require regeneration or manual updates.

4.7.3 Beyond State of the Art

Novel data management and processing frameworks oppose this resource-greedy, centralised management mechanisms and establish new control planes distributed across the Continuum integrating the -- compute, store, connectivity and cyber-physical -- capabilities of the devices with seamless management across providers, connectivity types and network zone. These next-generation computing and data technologies pave the way for the raise of new programming

¹²² <https://central.sonatype.com/>

¹²³ <https://jitpack.io/>

environments that ease the programming, deployment, and maintenance of hyper-distributed applications on the Continuum.

APM will be designed as a framework of JAR files and simulators for building applications and services that offer characteristics such as dynamism, adaptation, elasticity, load balancing, replication, portability, identification, secure communication, etc. The APM will provide high-level abstractions and APIs that will simplify the interactions between all ENACT components in order to create flows according to predefined scenarios. For example, it can help at integrating the results of the AI Forecaster that optimises configurations and predicts network needs with the Orchestrator, which deploys these configurations to the destination. Another example is to provide functions that export the implementation of secured data access and sharing mechanisms along with risk assessment tools that ensure data integrity.

The ENACT APM leverages existing research findings and market-ready solutions in multiple ways to enhance its integration with the ENACT CCC components. By adopting and extending the modularity of OSGi implementations, the APM could provide a dynamic query layer that abstracts complexities like lifecycle management and security configurations. Furthermore, the APM incorporates cutting-edge authentication and authorisation mechanisms to seamlessly secure communication without requiring additional tools or user intervention. Existing market solutions often lack this level of integration with SDKs or language flexibility; the ENACT APM improves upon this by offering not just Java-based support but plans for multi-language compatibility, including Python 3. By incorporating research findings on secure, modular, and extensible software systems, as well as sandboxing methodologies, the APM ensures a robust, scalable, and user-friendly interface.

APM fosters a novel programming paradigm by harmonising distributed device capabilities across the Continuum. It abstracts the complexities of multi-provider environments, providing an adaptive and secure layer for programming, deploying, and maintaining hyper-distributed applications. These innovations position the ENACT APM as a cornerstone for advancing data processing and management frameworks while enabling a transformative approach to building resilient and adaptable systems in the Continuum.

4.8 Application control

4.8.1 Research directions and related work

The increasing availability and capabilities of edge devices raise the opportunity to share the application workloads between edge and cloud resources. Lately a lot of emphasis has been put on the sustainability and energy efficiency of edge and cloud infrastructures through better virtual and physical resource management. In this context, ENACT brings forward an additional opportunity for optimising the performance and environmental aspects of applications running on the edge and cloud infrastructure. This opportunity is realised by developing an application programming model and application-level adaptation strategies that guide the design and execution phases of distributed applications.

Application-level adaptation has been investigated in existing literature with two main objectives, that is a) the objective to optimise the performance and energy efficiency of the applications, and b) the objective to optimise the utilisation of underlying (compute and storage) edge and cloud resources. In the first category, several context-aware dynamic adaptation solutions for mobile applications

have been proposed based on different mechanisms such as polymorphic methods [86] and reflection. In the edge computing domain, self-adaptive frameworks have been studied [87] that enable the applications to monitor their execution and adapt system behaviour.

Similarly, in the cloud computing domain, In [88], the authors focus on CPU usage as a way for determining where to redirect the workload of a task, based on the existing correlation between CPU usage and power consumption. Considering the application level, [89] proposes an approach based on the workload prediction to have a faster rearrangement of the system with the aim of reducing energy consumption.

In the second category, resource allocation algorithms are used to decide the best location of application components. The decision of such algorithms depends on the policies focusing on the optimal utilisation of the resources, also taking into account the energy efficiency perspective. An example can be found in [90], where resources are allocated using a bin packing algorithm based on an energy-aware heuristic. Moreover, algorithms considering eco-metrics for the deployment of distributed applications have been considered by eco4clouds [91], where a two-layer algorithm has been proposed for optimal resource utilisation in the multi-cloud environment. Similarly, in the edge computing, an adaptive resource allocation mechanism is developed for effective resource utilisation in dynamic settings [92]. The proposed mechanism is adaptable to a maximum number of incoming requests application deployment along with optimising the utilisation of limited resources at the edge node. In the edge-cloud infrastructures, a Software Defined Network (SDN) based approach is proposed [93] that provides a flexible load-balancing mechanism to allocate the required edge and cloud resources according to traffic load. Additionally, a dynamic resource allocation algorithm for cloud-edge environment is proposed in [94], which consists of a resource scheduling algorithm and a resource matching algorithm. The results achieved through experimentation of this algorithm indicate that proposed algorithms can effectively reduce network delay and enhance QoS of distributed edge and cloud applications.

In ENACT, the focus is on interlinking the compute and storage resources across the edge-cloud continuum and therefore the information coming from the monitoring the connected (edge-cloud) infrastructure is used to take decisions about the best deployment configurations in terms of energy efficiency, resource utilisation and quality of service (QoS) aspects among other relevant ones. Moreover, ENACT also considers application-level elasticity and scalability needs to extend the scope of adaptation actions that can help with the energy efficiency and QoS of applications. ENACT aims to realise such adaptivity through the design of an Application Controller that, enacting the right adaptation strategy for a given context, allows the improvement of the trade-off between QoS, resource utilisation, energy efficiency and other application-level constraints and optimisation parameters.

4.8.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

Application-level adaptation has been deeply investigated in the mobile application domain, where constraints on energy consumption and limited resource availability necessitates dynamic adjustments in application behaviours based on user needs and interactions. In this respect, for Android-based mobile applications, the Xposed framework allows to modify the application aspects and behaviour at runtime without modifying any Android application package (APK).

Other solutions to support application-level adaptation include: **OpenTelemetry**¹²⁴, which is an observability framework and toolkit that provides a neutral approach for the collection and exportation of telemetry data such as metrics, traces, logs, events, and profiles. As a framework OpenTelemetry addresses the limitations of existing tools, through the facilitation of a range of systems monitoring tools such as Prometheus, Jaeger and Zipkin. Through this approach, OpenTelemetry provides a standardised framework for the collection of metrics and observability signals. Alongside this, OpenTelemetry provides a range of inbuilt tools such as the Collector, designed to support common procedures with performance monitoring operations. Open Telemetry is available as an Open-Source solution.

Similarly, **Prometheus**¹²⁵ is an open-source systems monitoring and alerting toolkit. The tool has widespread adoption across the industry with a vast range of companies and organisations using it. Prometheus provides the capability to collect and store metrics as time-series data while also logging additional key value pairs in labels. The tool provides a multi-dimensional data model, flexible query language, and operates in a pull-based fashion to collect time series data over HTTP. Alongside this, there is no reliance on distributed storage and inbuilt autonomy for individual server nodes. Prometheus is also available as an Open-source framework.

Jaeger¹²⁶ is another open-source, end to end distributed tracing solution that is design for the monitoring, analysis, and troubleshooting of microservice based applications. The tool provides monitoring and analysis of dependencies, latencies, and performance bottlenecks, to support the identification and resolution of issues. Jaeger supports the tracing of path request between microservice to visualise a chain of events and provide insights on system behaviour. Through this approach Jaeger can monitor data movement, identify performance bottlenecks, and identify the root cause of issues to support distributed tracing. Jaeger is available as an Open-Source solution and can be used in the microservice architecture.

Lastly, **Zipkin**¹²⁷ is a distributed tracing system that is designed to gather real time, time series metrics in order to trouble shoot issues in microservice based architectures. The tool provides a focus on supporting integration, scalability, and problem resolution. Zipkin also provides the capability to trace requests as it travels through the system to enable the identification of bottlenecks, errors, and issues. Through the collection of data at different points in the system, Zipkin also provides through a web-based UI, detailed view of the system and data flows. Like other solutions described in this Section, Zipkin is also available as an Open-source resource.

4.8.3 Beyond State of the Art

In the field of dynamic and distributed deployment, application adaptation strategies have emerged as vital means for ensuring the optimal performance and user experience of applications across a diverse range of platforms and environments. These strategies or mechanisms can encompass a wide range of techniques that aim to tailor software application behaviour to suit different device capabilities, network conditions, and user preferences.

¹²⁴ <https://opentelemetry.io/>

¹²⁵ <https://prometheus.io/>

¹²⁶ <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

¹²⁷ <https://zipkin.io/>

Figure 8: Application Control in ENACT

For the development of application adaptation strategies, it is first essential to understand the deployment requirements and the metrics that needs to be monitored and taken into consideration by the application in order to perform the relevant adaptation actions. The work in (T6.2 of) ENACT will therefore focus on developing the set of metrics that can be used for effective monitoring of application behaviour and infrastructure utilisation at various layers in the edge-cloud ecosystem. Two key layers will be considered in ENACT, an Infrastructure layer from where resource related metrics (such as resource utilisation, energy consumption, environmental impact, etc.) from Sites, Hosts, devices and VM's will be gathered. Additionally, the metrics at Application layer will consider the metrics related to performance, energy and resources consumption of (various components of) distributed applications. The analysis of metrics from both layers, will enable the adaptation strategies to optimise the performance, resource utilisation and energy aspects of applications during runtime.

In ENACT, the application-level adaptation strategies will be implemented within a component called Application Controller, which will be part of the distributed application architecture, following the guidelines prescribed in the ENACT Application Programming Model. The Application Controller, will be responsible for performing 2 key operations, as shown in the above figure: a) monitoring of application (all relevant components) in terms of performance and resource consumption, and b) making intelligent decisions to perform runtime adaptations in the application execution behaviour or its deployment configuration. The adaptation decisions may correspond to the following:

- Turn On/Off application components/containers (to help with energy efficiency).
- Request (ENACT Orchestrator) changes in application deployment, e.g., move containers (to help with load-balancing).

- Request (ENACT Orchestrator) Increase/Decrease allocated resource (to help with elasticity and cost aspects).

The above decisions will be made based on the analysis of (different types of metrics) and the application specific optimisation function (e.g., energy efficiency, load balancing, cost reduction, etc.). The application-specific optimisation function can be configured at design/deployment time or at runtime, e.g., through an API of the Application Controller.

The envisioned functionalities of the Application Controller provide new opportunities for developing more intelligent applications that can not only react to the dynamic changes and new opportunities in the compute continuum but also take proactive actions to optimise their execution through behavioural adjustments or deployment reconfigurations.

Within the ENACT Application Development Layer, while there are similarities in across technologies referenced by each component, it is important to also understand the distinction between components. In particular, the Application Controller and Application Policy Model will be discussed. The SDK is a component in which users can define their application deployment configuration and enable defined functions and services available in the APM within the ENACT architecture. One such service may be the definition of an Application Policy Model that contains a particular runtime constraint on the application. When an application is deployed within the ENACT ecosystem, it is deployed alongside an instance of the Application Controller which holds and enforces all policies. When particular constraints are met, the Application Controller will take action directly, for example by enabling or disabling individual containers, or request redeployment through the DRL Agent and ENACT Orchestrator.

ENACT will build on existing research to integrate advanced monitoring and adaptation techniques to optimise application performance and energy efficiency across edge and cloud infrastructures. Well established frameworks for observability, systems monitoring and distributed tracing will be also incorporated from market ready solutions such as OpenTelemetry, Prometheus, and Jaeger respectively. The Application controller will advance on these tools through the development of intelligent decision-making algorithms that dynamically adjust deployment configurations based on comprehensive metrics analysis.

4.9 Software development kits

4.9.1 Research directions and related work

The development of SDKs for hyper-distributed applications requires addressing several key research challenges. Research on abstracting the heterogeneity of devices and networks to simplify application development. Techniques such as model-driven engineering and middleware solutions can provide unified interfaces and protocols. Projects like FogFlow¹²⁸ focus on dynamic workflows across IoT, fog, and cloud environments, addressing the heterogeneity challenge.

¹²⁸ <https://github.com/smartfog/fogflow>

Tools like GitHub Copilot¹²⁹ and DeepCode¹³⁰ use ML to provide intelligent code suggestions and identify potential issues early in the development process.

Using Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) like Hyperledger¹³¹ and Ethereum¹³² to develop decentralised applications, promoting trust and transparency in transactions, which is crucial for edge-cloud orchestration and zero-touch provisioning services. Research has been performed on blockchain-based decentralised IoT frameworks, such as "Blockchain for IoT Security and Privacy: The Case Study of a Smart Home" by Dorri et al. [95].

4.9.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

To develop the ENACT Software Development Kit (SDK) effectively, it's essential to understand the existing tools to create SDKs. A list of such tools is comprised from developer tools that are either frameworks or IDEs as described in what follows.

- **Apache Mesos**¹³³ is a platform that enhances the scalability and efficiency of distributed systems by abstracting resources such as CPU, memory, and storage, facilitating deployment across diverse infrastructures.
- **Kubernetes**¹³⁴ stands as a leading tool in managing containerised applications, Kubernetes automates the deployment, scaling, and management of distributed applications. It supports a wide range of programming languages and platforms, highlighting its versatility for development needs.
- **Eclipse Che**¹³⁵ is a cloud-based IDE tailored for developing distributed applications, supporting multiple languages and frameworks. It allows for the extension with plugins and supports collaborative development environments.
- **Visual Studio Code**¹³⁶, known for its extensive support through plugins for languages like Python and Java, Visual Studio Code integrates well with Docker, Kubernetes, and Azure, facilitates the development of cloud-native and distributed applications.
- **Spring Boot**¹³⁷ is a primarily for the Java ecosystem, Spring Boot simplifies the development of microservice architectures with comprehensive libraries and supports resilience and fault tolerance. It also accommodates Kotlin, offering flexibility to developers.
- **Django**¹³⁸ and **Flask**¹³⁹ for Python are important frameworks for developers looking to build microservices efficiently. Django offers a high-level framework designed for rapid

¹²⁹ <https://github.com/features/copilot>

¹³⁰ <https://snyk.io/platform/deepcode-ai/>

¹³¹ <https://www.hyperledger.org/>

¹³² <https://ethereum.org/en/>

¹³³ <https://mesos.apache.org/>

¹³⁴ <https://kubernetes.io/>

¹³⁵ <https://eclipse.dev/che/>

¹³⁶ <https://code.visualstudio.com/>

¹³⁷ <https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

¹³⁸ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>

¹³⁹ <https://flask.palletsprojects.com/en/3.0.x/>

development and clean, pragmatic design, while Flask provides a more lightweight and flexible approach.

In the context of the ENACT Software Development Kit (SDK) for realising hyper-distributed applications, there are several market-ready, commercial, and industrial solutions that provide a foundation to start from.

- **Eclipse Che** is a cloud-based IDE that supports the development of distributed applications across multiple languages and frameworks. As the ENACT SDK is to be designed as a plugin for the Eclipse SDK, Eclipse Che provides a familiar environment for developers to leverage the power of microservices and edge computing.
- **Cisco Edge Intelligence**¹⁴⁰ simplifies data extraction, transformation, and delivery from connected assets at the edge to multiple destinations, supporting real-time data processing.
- **Red Hat OpenShift**¹⁴¹ is a Kubernetes-based platform that provides a comprehensive environment for deploying and managing containerised applications. It supports a wide range of programming languages and offers tools for continuous integration and delivery.
- **Oracle Cloud Infrastructure (OCI)**¹⁴² provides a robust platform for deploying and managing applications in the cloud. It offers extensive support for containerised applications, serverless functions, and machine learning.

These solutions are widely adopted in finance, retail, manufacturing, industrial IoT, healthcare, and government sectors.

4.9.3 Beyond State of the Art

To go beyond the current state of the art in SDK development, we need to explore emerging technologies and innovative approaches that extend beyond the capabilities of the existing tools.

Using DLT enablers like Hyperledger Ethereum can facilitate the development of decentralised applications promoting trust and transparency in transactions like the edge-cloud orchestrations or zero provisioning services.

Including modules that support quantum computing development could prepare the platform for the next era of computing power and problem-solving capabilities.

As the SDK will provide a concrete implementation of the APM, the SDK will be an Eclipse plugin that offers the developers the possibility to implement the scenarios like the ones mentioned in Section 4.7.

The SDK will allow the developers to create and manage the interaction with all ENACT components via the APM specifications.

The SDK will be implemented as an Eclipse plugin with UI that allows the developer to easily load ENACT components exposed interfaces. This will further allow the user to see the connections between components and update specific configurations. One potential use case for the SDK is to

¹⁴⁰ <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/solutions/internet-of-things/edge-intelligence.html>

¹⁴¹ <https://www.redhat.com/en/technologies/cloud-computing/openshift>

¹⁴² <https://www.oracle.com/cloud/>

create scenarios without even writing Python or Java code, but instead using the UI or the markup language interpreted by the SDK to create Python or Java scripts.

One of the strong points of the SDK is that it can interconnect the ENACT components and provide a “birds-eye-view” of the platform. Another potential strong point is that it could ease the Continuous Delivery of the platform in a scalable and elastic manner.

The SDK will be developed in two complementary versions, both under active development. The Maven library version will be deployed via Maven Central to ensure easy integration into Java projects. It will provide direct access to the APM functionalities and will be designed to handle secure and efficient interactions with almost all ENACT components. The Eclipse plugin version will leverage JavaFX for its UI and integrate with Eclipse's Plugin Development Environment (PDE) to provide a graphical interface for configuring APM scenarios and generating Python or Java code.

The SDK will support configuration through XML files, serving as a markup language for specifying scenarios. These files allow users to define APM calls and parameters, which the SDK interprets to execute the specified functionality dynamically. This mechanism supports automation and reusable configurations without manual intervention.

The SDK aims to provide a holistic platform view, visualizing the interactions between ENACT components. This visualisation is built using JavaFX and integrates directly with the APM's APIs for real-time feedback on component states and interactions.

The SDK will also support elastic and scalable configurations for continuous delivery pipelines, utilizing Java-based frameworks for thread management and concurrency (e.g., ExecutorService) to ensure efficient scaling during runtime.

As of right now, there aren't many available tools that can achieve an easy and secure development of cross-cloud applications similar to our effort. Apart from achieving this with the ENACT SDK, there is also the aspect of the dual-deployment approach which will make the SDK easy to use for developers of various expertise levels, highlighting its inclusiveness.

4.10 Quality and security for distributed applications

4.10.1 Research directions and related work

Distributed Applications offer several benefits in comparison to traditional centralised applications such as flexible placement of services near geographic areas of high demand and rapid scaling depending on user requests. Despite their benefits, distributed applications often introduce complexity due to their nature. Moreover, modern containerisation and service orchestration frameworks, such as Kubernetes (K8s), introduce several layers of abstraction and introduce additional complexity to application development and infrastructure management [96]. Proper configuration and fine-tuning of such tools is a necessary step to ensure that applications can scale properly with little effort in an automated and secure manner. Moreover, there is limited work in expressing the desired runtime behaviour of distributed applications. Solutions such as IaCMF offer compliance of Infrastructure as Code (IaC) configuration, however it is not capable of describing the desired state of applications that run on top [97]. Walther et al. [98] designed a policy enforcement and validation solution that aims to securely deploy containerised applications. The proposed solution supports Kubernetes and Docker compose targets; however it is not tightly coupled to the Kubernetes ecosystem. Other methods are based on infrastructure events, to generate monitoring

rules to efficiently manage computational workloads and detect failures without affecting distributed application behaviour [99]. However, these approaches are not capable of describing the desired state of applications in terms of geographic placement, computational nodes capacity and network characteristics.

Ensuring the quality, security and privacy of distributed applications in modern hyper-converged cloud environments is a challenging task though [100]. It involves many monitoring techniques and methods accompanied by complex policies to ensure that services operate in their optimal condition securely and privately where unauthorised communication is not permitted. Moreover, securing and ensuring the privacy of distributed applications in large geographical and diverse infrastructure environments is crucial in maintaining user trust, protecting sensitive data, and aligning with regulatory bodies.

The increased communication between microservices containers renders the process of tracing difficult while also introducing additional network policies the administrator has to take into account when configuring the underlying networking infrastructure [101]. Kubernetes relies on Container Network Interface (CNI) plugin technologies such as Calico and Cilium, to manage all networking aspects of container communication and security, thus making the CNI an important element of each cloud environment. Most modern CNIs offer additional capabilities in terms of tracing and monitoring network traffic, exposing APIs, metrics and events to third-party tools and also provide SDKs to simplify the development of Control Plane applications that manage the underlying infrastructure. Additionally, CNIs provide extensive APIs to enforce network policies on a pod or cluster-wide scale.

Given that many distributed applications may span across multiple clusters, Service Meshes have emerged lately as a solution to multi-cluster interconnection. A Service Mesh will inject a sidecar container on each K8s pod responsible for handling all inbound and outbound traffic. Sidecar containers can easily be integrated with existing distributed applications without the need for altering the application logic at the cost of higher resource usage.

In light of the aforementioned challenges, it is evident that flexible, adaptive, and fine-grained monitoring methods are necessary to ensure distributed applications function as expected. Moreover, the underlying infrastructure should offer mechanisms and interfaces to enforce, design and implement complex policies related to placement of services and data.

4.10.2 Market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards

There is a large number of tools available to the community capable of monitoring distributed applications in many levels. Many tools offer tracing capabilities, providing enriched insights to administrators about to events and how information flows between containers. Tools such as Jaeger and Istio Service Mesh offer such capabilities. Other tools focus on log collection analysis and reporting through visual front-end interfaces. Tools like ELK Stack and Splunk collect logs and process them efficiently to provide interactive visualisations. Finally, many security features and policies cannot be realised without a scalable and flexible network fabric. Calico, Cilium and Flannel are three of the most widely used CNI plugins in Kubernetes deployments. A description of the main feature each tool offer is listed below:

Monitoring Tools:

- **Prometheus**¹⁴³ is an open-source monitoring and alerting tool used for the collection and recording of real-time events and metrics while also supporting some basic pre-processing of data before storing. It is a highly scalable application suitable for cloud native and highly distributed environments without introducing much overhead in terms of processing needs. Thanks to its flexible querying language administrators can easily express complex queries and obtain insights, generate alerts, or even push data to visualisation tools like Grafana¹⁴⁴. Prometheus can easily scale across multi-node clusters by deploying agents on each node, whereas a server is responsible for collecting and storing data, producing alerts and exporting data to Grafana.
- **ELK Stack**¹⁴⁵ is a set of three tools that when combined together provide a dynamic logging and monitoring platform capable of processing large volumes of events and logs in structured and unstructured formats. At its core the Elastic Stack uses Elasticsearch¹⁴⁶, a distributed search and analytics engine optimised for text based analytics that is accompanied by a REST-based querying language. The ELK Stack also focuses on the preprocessing of data by exploiting Logstash, a data processing pipeline capable of ingesting large volumes of data, transforming them and even enriching them with additional information before appending them to Elasticsearch. Log and metrics collections on nodes is achieved using the Beats tool, a lightweight agent deployed on each node capable of collecting logs and metrics. There are several UC specific Beats such as FileBeat¹⁴⁷ (focusing on log files monitoring) or MetricBeat¹⁴⁸ (focusing on system metric collection). Finally, Kibana is the main graphical user interface that visualises complex entries of Elasticsearch offering insights and interactive dashboards.
- **Splunk**¹⁴⁹ is a software platform like ELK Stack that can process, index and analyse text, numeric in structured and unstructured formats. Splunk can easily make correlations between events Splunk proprietary indexing database offers unparalleled querying speeds while its unified service model ensures smooth interoperability between its components.
- **Zabbix**¹⁵⁰ is another server-client infrastructure monitoring solution that is popular in the IT sector. Zabbix deploys agents on nodes capable of operating system processes, network status and unlike other solutions it is capable of monitoring services like databases, websites and virtual machines. The Zabbix server is responsible for aggregating logs and metrics of agents, storing them and producing reports that can be delivered through various methods. Administrators can interact through a dashboard that offers interactive visualisations and notifications in a user-friendly environment.

¹⁴³ <https://prometheus.io/>

¹⁴⁴ <https://grafana.com/>

¹⁴⁵ <https://www.elastic.co/elastic-stack>

¹⁴⁶ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>

¹⁴⁷ <https://www.elastic.co/beats/filebeat>

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.elastic.co/beats/metricbeat>

¹⁴⁹ <https://www.splunk.com/>

¹⁵⁰ <https://www.zabbix.com/>

- **Jaeger**¹⁵¹ is a distributed tracing observability platform designed specifically for distributed applications. Using Jaeger administrator can efficiently monitor all interactions between microservices in a distributed applications and identify bottlenecks, analyse request flows and identify root causes between microservices. Jaeger can export these metrics to popular tools like Grafana.
- **Zipkin**¹⁵² is an open-source distributed tracing tool designed for monitoring microservices. Developers can trace interactions between containers. Zipkin traces interactions between containers by monitoring calls and sending traces to a centralised server using Tracers, software applets that reside inside the distributed application.
- **Apache SkyWalking**¹⁵³ is an open-source application performance monitoring software designed for distributed cloud environments and cloud architectures. It provides cluster-wide observability and behaviour monitoring of distributed applications by collecting and analysing infrastructure logs, applications traces and telemetry data. SkyWalking offers support for multiple programming languages and can easily be integrated to existing distributed applications without much effort.
- **Thanos**¹⁵⁴ is an open-source solution which provides Prometheus deployments with scalable highly available long-term storage capabilities. Thanos components work with Prometheus servers to provide global cluster querying and extended metric retention through Amazon S3 and Google Cloud Storage and Microsoft Azure object storage solutions. The Sidecar component of Thanos functions as a module that sends Prometheus data to storage while providing gRPC API access to the data. The Store Gateway component allows users to retrieve historical metrics for efficient querying. The Query layer component provides unified PromQL access while the Compactor component optimises storage through deduplication and downsampling and retention policy enforcement. Thanos solves Prometheus storage scalability and high availability issues to support monitoring of large-scale distributed cloud native systems.
- **Logz.io**¹⁵⁵ serves as a cloud native observability platform which unifies logs, metrics, and traces through a single interface to enable complete monitoring and troubleshooting of modern applications. Logz.io uses OpenSearch together with Prometheus and OpenTelemetry to provide pre-built dashboards and automated insights which help users detect and resolve performance issues more efficiently. The Open 360™ platform from Logz.io delivers full-stack observability through Kubernetes 360 for cluster monitoring and App 360 for application performance management to reduce operational costs and minimise mean time to resolution (MTTR). Logz.io provides scalable cost-effective observability solutions for distributed systems by using open-source technologies through its managed service platform.
- **Weave Scope**¹⁵⁶ is an open-source visualisation and monitoring tool for Docker and Kubernetes. Users can monitor containerised applications through its graphical interface which shows container relationships, processes and hosts in real-time for troubleshooting purposes.

¹⁵¹ <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

¹⁵² <https://zipkin.io/>

¹⁵³ <https://skywalking.apache.org/>

¹⁵⁴ <https://thanos.io/>

¹⁵⁵ <https://logz.io/>

¹⁵⁶ <https://github.com/weaveworks/scope>

- **OpenSearch**¹⁵⁷ functions as an open-source search and analytics suite that originated from Elasticsearch. It enables users to monitor applications in real time and provides robust observability features. OpenSearch Dashboards offers an intuitive interface for viewing and analysing data stored within OpenSearch.
- **Cortex**¹⁵⁸ is an open-source project that provides horizontally scalable, highly available, multi-tenant, long term storage for Prometheus metrics. It allows users to query metrics from multiple Prometheus instances in a single place, facilitating centralised monitoring and alerting.

CNIs and Service Mesh Tools:

- **Cilium**¹⁵⁹ is a popular open-source project that provides networking, service monitoring and security capabilities for containerised environments. Cilium Container Network Interface (CNI) relies upon the extended Berkley Packet Filters (eBPF)¹⁶⁰ Linux kernel feature to insert security, policies, and network control in the Linux kernel. This enables Cilium to handle packets as early as possible, before being processed by the Linux network stack, thus offering higher overall performance, finer-grained monitoring of communication between distributed application containers and superior security features compared to traditional solutions. Using Cilium Policies, administrators can express complex communication policies between microservices, monitor inter-container communication and effectively and efficiently identify bottlenecks across the cluster. Cilium provides additional tools to express policies, monitor the cluster and APIs to communication with various Cilium Stack components.
- **Calico**¹⁶¹ is an open-source networking and security solution designed for cloud native containerised environments. Calico CNI offers an OSI Layer 3 data plane fabric capable of interconnecting containers, virtual machines, and native host environments. Calico project also provides a network policy suite offering administrators tools to express complex communication policies between containers.
- **Flannel**¹⁶² is another popular CNI framework that is used in many Kubernetes deployments and is popular for its simplicity and low overall resource utilisation. Flannel relies on Kubernetes etcd¹⁶³ distributed data store to store all its information.
- **Istio Service Mesh**¹⁶⁴ is an open-source service mesh platform that provides enhanced security, observability and control of distributed services. Istio operates on orchestration platforms such as Kubernetes to provide transparent, policy driven communication between distributed applications using sidecar proxies while also focusing on privacy and security establishment between communicating entities.
- **Project Antrea**¹⁶⁵ is an open-source Kubernetes CNI plugin built to integrate natively with Kubernetes. It uses Open vSwitch (OVS) as its data plane to implement pod networking and

¹⁵⁷ <https://opensearch.org/>

¹⁵⁸ <https://cortexmetrics.io/>

¹⁵⁹ <https://cilium.io/>

¹⁶⁰ <https://ebpf.io/>

¹⁶¹ <https://www.tigera.io/project-calico/>

¹⁶² <https://github.com/flannel-io/flannel>

¹⁶³ <https://etcd.io/>

¹⁶⁴ <https://istio.io>

¹⁶⁵ <https://antrea.io/>

security features. Antrea runs an agent on each node and a centralised controller, leveraging OVS pipelines to enforce Kubernetes network policies efficiently (OVS flows are used for high-performance policy enforcement). The design enables Antrea to deliver scalable networking capabilities and advanced security features, such as Network Policy and overlay networking encapsulation, while maintaining standard Kubernetes API compatibility. Antrea provides a Kubernetes native solution that uses OVS as its virtual switch to deliver robust functionality for clusters that need seamless integration with existing SDN technology and efficient policy enforcement.

- **Kube-Route**¹⁶⁶ is an open-source networking solution that serves as a CNI plugin as well as a distributed load balancer, firewall, and router for Kubernetes. It implements pod connectivity using pure L3 routing. Each node learns routes for pods on other nodes via Border Gateway Protocol (BGP). Specifically, Kube-Route uses the GoBGP library to enable direct routing of traffic without needing overlay tunnelling. Kube-router integrates tightly with Kubernetes API resources. Also, it can enforce network policies (acting as a firewall) and even replace Kube-proxy by leveraging IPVS for service load-balancing. By consolidating pod networking, network policy and service routing into a single component, kube-router minimises overhead and can improve performance and scalability through efficient kernel level forwarding and route distribution.
- **Multus**¹⁶⁷ is an open-source CNI plugin that enables Kubernetes pods to attach to multiple networks. Also, it allows each pod to have more than one network interface. Rather than providing a standalone network implementation, Multus acts as a “meta-plugin” when a pod is created. In addition, Multus invokes other CNI plugins to create additional network attachments alongside the pod’s primary network. This means you can use Multus in conjunction with other CNIs. Multus is particularly useful in scenarios like NFV (Network Function Virtualisation) or any application that requires segregated networks. It brings flexibility to Kubernetes networking by coordinating multiple network interfaces per pod while still adhering to CNI standards.
- **OVN-Kubernetes**¹⁶⁸ is an open-source CNI plugin built on Open Virtual Networking (OVN) and Open vSwitch (OVS) to provide advanced networking for Kubernetes clusters. It deploys a set of OVN/OVS daemons (controllers and agents) that translate Kubernetes network and policy abstractions into OpenFlow rules on each node’s OVS instance. OVN’s centralised control plane enables OVN-Kubernetes to establish an overlay network through Geneve or VXLAN tunnels or to handle underlay routing for pod connectivity across the cluster while supporting Kubernetes Services and Network Policies. The plugin benefits from OVN’s mature software-defined networking capabilities through its distributed logical routing and built-in load balancing and security groups features. The plugin provides a robust and scalable architecture which makes it suitable for large or complex deployments that need a proven policy-driven networking solution.

¹⁶⁶ <https://www.kube-router.io/>

¹⁶⁷ <https://github.com/k8snetworkplumbingwg/multus-cni>

¹⁶⁸ <https://ovn-kubernetes.io/>

- **Amazon VPC CNI**¹⁶⁹ is an open-source CNI plugin which AWS developed to give Kubernetes pods native connectivity to Amazon Virtual Private Cloud (VPC). The plugin assigns VPC IP addresses to pods directly so they can connect easily with AWS services and resources. The plugin handles ENIs and IP address allocations to deliver high performance and scalability to Amazon EKS clusters. The method reduces network complexity while using existing VPC configurations to boost security.
- **Azure CNI**¹⁷⁰ is an open-source CNI plugin that enables Kubernetes networking integration with Azure Virtual Network (VNet) by directly assigning Vnet IP addresses to pods. This configuration enables pods to obtain routable IP addresses from the VNet which allows them to communicate directly with Azure resources and on-premises networks. Azure CNI provides advanced networking capabilities through network security groups and user-defined routes which enable users to control traffic flow and security in Azure Kubernetes Service (AKS).
- **Open Service Mesh (OSM)**¹⁷¹ is an open-source service mesh platform that aims to provide a lightweight, easy-to-use and flexible means of traffic management, observability tracing and security of distributed applications. OSM adopts a simple and customizable architectural design focusing on ease of use while also adopting best practices with respect to security and integration with existing orchestrating platforms.

Runtime Policy Definition and Enforcement:

- **Tetragon**¹⁷² is an open-source security observability and runtime enforcement tool which uses eBPF-based technology to operate within Kubernetes environments. The tool functions inside the Linux kernel to monitor system events in real time while enforcing policies for process executions and file accesses and network activities. Tetragon uses Kubernetes metadata to deliver context-aware insights which enables the creation of precise security policies that detect and prevent unauthorised behaviours during runtime. The system design provides both high performance and detailed monitoring of workload operations.
- **Open Policy Agent (OPA)**¹⁷³ is an open-source general purpose policy engine which separates policy decision making from application logic. Open Policy Agent functions as an admission controller in Kubernetes to enforce detailed context specific policies on resource configurations. The Rego declarative language enables administrators to create rules for access control and resource usage and compliance requirements. The flexible nature of OPA allows consistent policy enforcement throughout all components of the cloud native stack.
- **Kyverno**¹⁷⁴ is an open-source policy engine designed specifically for Kubernetes. Through Kyverno users can define configurations and validate them and mutate them and generate them using native Kubernetes YAML syntax. It operates as a dynamic admission controller, allowing for seamless policy enforcement without requiring a separate policy language. Kyverno supports background scanning and can automatically remediate non-compliant

¹⁶⁹ <https://github.com/aws/amazon-vpc-cni-k8s>

¹⁷⁰ <https://github.com/Azure/azure-container-networking>

¹⁷¹ <https://openservicemesh.io/>

¹⁷² <https://github.com/cilium/tetragon>

¹⁷³ <https://www.openpolicyagent.org/>

¹⁷⁴ <https://kyverno.io/>

resources, making it a powerful tool for maintaining consistent configurations and security standards within Kubernetes clusters.

- **Falco**¹⁷⁵ is an open-source runtime security tool that monitors system calls and Kubernetes audit logs to detect anomalous behaviour in containers, hosts, and cloud environments. Through custom rules, Falco can identify unexpected application activities, configuration changes, and potential security threats in real-time, providing alerts to help maintain the integrity and security of Kubernetes workloads.
- **KubeArmor**¹⁷⁶ functions as a Kubernetes runtime security system which implements eBPF and Linux Security Modules (LSM) to enforce detailed security policies for containerised workloads. Through policy definitions administrators can limit process execution, file access and network operations to improve Kubernetes cluster application security.
- **Tracee**¹⁷⁷ is an open-source runtime security and forensics tool developed by Aqua Security, designed to detect and analyse suspicious activities in cloud-native environments using eBPF technology. It provides deep visibility into system behaviour, enabling the detection of anomalous processes, file access patterns, and network activities, which aids in threat detection and incident response within Kubernetes clusters.
- **StackRox Kubernetes Security Platform**¹⁷⁸ is an open-source Kubernetes security platform that provides a complete security solution across the container lifecycle. The platform includes risk analysis of container environments, visibility into runtime threats, and policy enforcement to stop attacks in real-time. The platform integrates with Kubernetes via a central controller and per cluster sensors, monitoring runtime behaviour and generating alerts or blocking actions that violate security policies. StackRox delivers recommendations to harden cluster configurations and can enforce rules to proactively improve the security posture of cloud native applications.
- **NeuVector**¹⁷⁹ is an open-source container security platform that focuses on live container runtime protection and network security enforcement. It offers “full-lifecycle” container security from vulnerability scanning in CI/CD to real-time, automated enforcement at runtime. NeuVector deploys as agents (enforcers) on Kubernetes nodes, acting as a container firewall that can inspect network traffic, detect anomalies, and restrict connections or processes based on predefined security policies. The tools integrate seamlessly with Kubernetes (and platforms like OpenShift or Rancher) to provide intrusion detection and prevention, monitoring container behaviour and blocking suspicious activity in line with security rules. Originally a commercial product, NeuVector was open-sourced by SUSE and remains actively maintained with extensive documentation for cloud-native deployment and policy configuration.
- **jsPolicy**¹⁸⁰ is an open-source Kubernetes policy engine that allows administrators to define and enforce cluster policies using JavaScript or TypeScript. It functions as an admission

¹⁷⁵ <https://falco.org/>

¹⁷⁶ <https://kubearmor.io/>

¹⁷⁷ <https://github.com/aquasecurity/tracee>

¹⁷⁸ <https://github.com/stackrox/stackrox>

¹⁷⁹ <https://github.com/neuvector/neuvector>

¹⁸⁰ <https://github.com/loft-sh/jspolicy>

controller, where policy logic is executed by the V8 JavaScript engine in a sandboxed environment for speed and safety. With jsPolicy, users can create validating policies to accept/deny requests, mutating policies to modify resource manifests, or even controller policies that react to Kubernetes events. The jsPolicy controller takes care of the heavy lifting (webhook server, high availability, certificate management, auditing), so developers can focus on policy logic, making it a flexible and well-documented alternative to traditional policy engines in cloud native environments.

- **Kubewarden**¹⁸¹ is an open-source policy engine for Kubernetes that uses WebAssembly (WASM) to run security policies. Instead of a domain specific language, Kubewarden lets you write policies in various programming languages (Rust, Go, Swift) or simple DSLs, then compile them to WASM modules for efficient, sandboxed execution. The Kubewarden controller and policy server operate as an admission controller to evaluate WASM based policies for every API request thus enforcing custom validation or mutation rules. Kubewarden enables cluster operators to create detailed security controls through WASM performance benefits while avoiding the need to develop complete Kubernetes webhooks. The project, which was initially developed by SUSE, remains active and well documented with tooling and a catalogue of ready to use policies to provide flexible security for cloud native workloads.

4.10.3 Beyond State of the Art

As applications shift towards a distributed deployment model, novel monitoring solutions that operate on diverse cloud environments can easily integrate into existing cloud setups. Moreover, managing the state of these applications requires new mechanisms for expressing the relations and runtime behaviour of these applications. Altering the core logic of containerised applications can easily become a challenging process for developers. To this end, sophisticated monitoring solutions that track the performance of applications should be employed accompanied by means of expressing the desired state of the application as developers envision it. Given the multiple layers of abstraction present in modern virtualised environments, these solutions should be able to operate in containerised applications without the need to alter the distributed application. Moreover, monitoring across multiple layers (i.e., application, networking, cluster) ensures the best possible acquisition of metrics and logs.

Any monitoring process should not consume significant resources compared to the distributed application. In past years, enhanced programmability has emerged as a means of offering the developer more freedom in developing custom solutions that are not bound to hardware-specific implementations. Infrastructure programmability has resulted in more efficient use of hardware. Acceleration of computing and networking tasks using hardware-specific devices can reduce overall energy consumption without impacting total system performance [102] [103].

Based on the aforementioned points, T6.3 undertakes the development of an infrastructure monitoring tool capable of collecting metrics of multi-cluster environments across the edge-to-cloud continuum focusing on minimizing unnecessary data transfers and employing efficient monitoring methods to provide alerts and metrics to other ENACT components. The Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine is a tool based on open-source technologies and frameworks combined with custom solutions following the microservices approach. The tool collects low-level infrastructure

¹⁸¹ <https://www.kubewarden.io/>

metrics, stores them efficiently and forwards them to other components. Moreover, the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine will produce alerts when certain performance indicators are met and notify other components by producing events. Additionally, the Application Policy Model offers developers cloud-native methods of expressing the runtime behaviour of distributed applications in terms of computing, storage, locality, networking and security without impacting existing cloud deployment pipelines.

ENACT will build upon industry-grade solutions, such as Prometheus, a cloud-continuum monitoring fabric capable of efficiently collecting and storing infrastructure metrics from multiple layers and endpoints. Traditional monitoring solutions are designed for single cluster deployments. ENACT will extend these concepts to multi-cluster scenarios, by providing guidelines, new software functionalities and methods to collect, store, and analyse multi-cluster infrastructure metrics. The TDCME will integrate open source and custom software to realise the aforementioned functionalities, offering adaptive monitoring of the underlying infrastructure, store them efficiently and generate alerts and forward them to other components. Additionally, the ENACT project introduces the concept of runtime behaviour, offering mechanisms for developers and administrator to specify the desired state of distributed applications through a cloud native approach and by using standardised methods. The Application Policy Model component realises this concept by adopting the ENACT CCC model.

4.11 Overview of technologies and projects

These Sections provide an overview of technologies and projects that are relevant to the ENACT project.

4.11.1 Relevant external components and technologies

This table serves as a recap of the information presented in the previous Sections.

Key Topic related to CCC	Existing solutions, tools, method etc. to be used and TRL (pre/post)	Gaps based on SotA Analysis	ENACT improvements	Relevance with ENACT Architecture (Layers / Components)
(T01) Computing continuum modelling and visualisation				
(T01.1) Computing continuum modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A Resource reference model for Data-Intensive Applications (ARDIA) (3/5) aerOS continuum ontology (4/4) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The three ARDIA models and the aerOS continuum ontology were defined around the SERRANO and aerOS project details and requirements respectively. They cover specific parameters for applications definition and deployment optimisation, connected infrastructure types and capabilities, and (live / historical) telemetry data. They do not fully correspond to the ENACT requirements and need to be updated for use in accordance with the project's objectives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENACT will update each of the three ARDIA models to fully cover the project's specific data needs and scopes, and facilitate key innovations. Models updates will be considered as far as their semantics, structure (especially concerning the resource and telemetry models) and parameters (data definitions) are concerned, as needed. For improving the models, focus will be given on the data requirements of the individual ENACT components and overall interoperability of the ENACT platform. aerOS continuum ontology will be studied to further enhance the ARDIA models' aspects, as appropriate. 	<p>The CCC Models are being utilised by several ENACT components in various architecture layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the Modelling Layer, the DGM and SRM components. In the Orchestration Layer, the TDCME and the Orchestrator. In the AI Layer, the AI Forecaster. In the Application Development Layer, the Application Controller, APM and Application Policy Model. In the Data Layer, the Data Manager.
(T01.2) Visualisation tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gephi (8-9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graph visualisation tools are general-purpose tools and should be customised to be able to show data generated by Kubernetes deployments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The ENACT visualisation tool will be tailored specifically to represent data from Kubernetes deployments, displaying pods, nodes, services, and their relationships. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENACT Modelling Layer and Dynamic Graph Modeller component.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Graph visualisation tools lack real-time data integration. • Graph visualisation tools are not designed to scale across different environments and use cases. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A data acquisition module will be added to ensure continuous updates and real-time integration of metrics from the ENACT cloud-edge continuum. • Scalability Across Environments: The tool will be designed to scale effectively across different use cases and namespaces.
(T02) Distributed storage and data spaces		
(T02.1) Distributed storage and data spaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclipse Data Space Connectors implementations (7/8) • Keycloak Identity and Access Management Framework (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current distributed data stores for CCC are not based on Data Spaces concept. • Data Spaces Approaches are focused on data sharing and do not consider other aspects related to distributed apps development. • Secure and Sovereign Data Space across the CCC to act as a distributed data store. • ENACT Data Space to be used as an Object Space to support the development of applications based on APM and SDK.
(T03) Risk and compliance		
(T03.1) Security Risk Modelling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security Risk Modeller (3/6) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of automated risk analysis. • Need of human intervention. • Lack of real-time risk reporting. • Automated security risk analysis. • Risk reporting to other components. • API support. • Security-by-design approach.
(T03.2) Regulatory compliance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAG implementation (TRL7) based on OpenAI LLMs as the starting point for technical implementation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited Automation. • Lack of API Support. • Static Guidance. • Insufficient Support for Evidence Collection. • Fully automated compliance check. • API support. • Dynamic adaptation to evolving AI Act requirements. • Systematic collection and evidence organisation.

(T04) Zero-touch provisioning services				
(T04.1) Zero-touch provisioning services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ubuntu MAAS Zero Touch Provisioning Tool (9/9) • Kubernetes (9/9) • FastAPI Python Rest API implementation (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many tools are locked on single-environment. • Few open-source solutions for ZTP. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZTP functionality across different environments. • Develop an Open-Source ZTP solution. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT Orchestration Layer, mainly the Orchestrator.
(T05) Edge-cloud orchestration				
(T05.1) Edge-cloud orchestration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kubernetes (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lacks performance awareness. • Non-intelligent scheduling. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ready for AI-based instructions. • Dynamic scheduling and rescheduling. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT Orchestration Layer. • ENACT Modelling Layer. • ENACT Application Development Layer. • ENACT AI Layer.
(T06) AI Algorithms and training environments				
(T06.1) AI algorithms for prediction and scheduling	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing online parameter tuning methodologies for metaheuristic optimisation algorithms. • Agent presented in [79]. • Agents presented in [78], [80]. (3/5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited automated machine learning systems. • Limited exploration of GNN architectures, limited investigation of exploration strategies and no investigation of self-tuning capabilities. • Limited consideration of task dependencies. • Limited exploration of infrastructure-based anomaly detection. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide an automated solution with autotune capabilities. • Provide a DRL agent which will explore GCN and GAT layers instead of simple parsing layers, will investigate the utilisation of different exploration techniques (Upper Bound Confidence, Thompson Sampling) and investigate meta learning functionalities to self-tune the DRL agent. • Will use GNNs to learn the topology and capture the task dependencies. • Provide anomaly detection mechanisms for CCC resources by investigating and combining various techniques. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT AI Layer / AI forecaster, GNN, DRL agent.
(T06.2) Graph Neural Networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several GNN architectures have been 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existing DRL-based solutions fail to generalise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is expected that the DRL+GNN agent is able to outperform state- 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT AI Layer, GNN component.

	proposed, each implementing distinct approaches to message passing (3/5)	when applied to different network scenarios not seen during training.	of-the-art solutions in topologies never seen during training.	
(T06.3) Virtual Training Environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICE Analytics (2/5) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of support for GNN based data. • high barriers to entry for AI model training. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for GNN data, enhanced scalability. • Increased efficiency in AI model training. • Improved usability. • AI explainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The VTE is outside of all layers and interacts with the ENACT Data Layer and ENACT AI Layer.
(T07) Application programming models				
(T07.1) Application programming models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OSGi (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Java only. • Requires tool/service lifecycle management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM will be available for Python 3 in the future. • Seamless integration/function. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT Application Development Layer / Application Programming Model component.
(T08) Application control				
(T08.1) Application control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Springboot (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application-level Adaptation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Intelligent decision making algorithms for dynamic configuration adjustment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT Application Development Layer / Application Controller component.
(T09) Software development kits				
(T09.1) Software development kits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eclipse IDE (9/9) • JavaFX (9/9) • Eclipse PDE (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As of right now, not many development kits are available that can achieve easy and secure cross-cloud deployment. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SDK will offer an integrated approach to cross-cloud deployment, tailored to different user expertise levels 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT App Development Layer, SDK component interacting with the APM module.
(T10) Quality and security for distributed applications				
(T10.1) Quality and security for distributed applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prometheus (9/9) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Current solutions are designed to operate on single cluster scenarios. However, multi cluster scenarios are an emerging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine will collect metrics across the Edge-to-Cloud continuum from multiple infrastructure layers. The adaptive collection mechanisms will ensure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TDCME will provide metrics and alerts to other ENACT components. TDCME acts as a central monitoring entity where low level metrics are

	topic in highly distributed applications.	metrics are collected optimally without impacting performance.	translated to alerts and information through an API.
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Table 6: Relevant components and technologies

4.11.2 Relevant projects

The ENACT project contributes to the realisation of Cognitive Computing Continuum as part of a European collaborative research effort led by the European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum (EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu) initiative, which aims to lay out the guidelines for the design, development and establishment of the CCC. This effort is further supported by Coordination and Support Actions (CSAs), with the NexusForum.EU project being highly related to ENACT. This project works towards consolidating the development and innovation activities on the CCC, and ensuring their alignment with relevant key strategic areas identified by the EU. Therefore, ENACT's solutions are being developed considering the pathways set by both EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu and NexusForum.eu initiatives.

Table 7 below presents additional projects that are highly relevant to ENACT, along with a brief description of each, their similarities, and potential or anticipated points of collaboration.

Project title	Brief description	Potential strategies / Related objective(s)
SERRANO	It aims to create a seamless and secure cloud computing ecosystem. It introduces an abstraction layer to integrate distributed edge, cloud, and high-performance computing (HPC) resources into a unified infrastructure.	The ARDIA Framework will be closely examined for the development of the ENACT CCC models. Other technologies of this project can be also examined, given its close relevance to ENACT.
TERMINET	The project aims to design and develop the next generation IoT architecture based on cutting-edge technologies such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Multiple Access Edge Computing (MEC) and Federated Learning.	TERMINET outputs and results and lessons learnt related to infrastructure and networking technologies will be examined and evaluated and taken into consideration.
DECICE	DECICE aims to develop an open and portable management framework for AI-based adaptive execution and optimisation of applications in computing continuum.	Sharing common objectives such as AI-based scheduling for orchestration of the application workload on the cloud-edge infrastructure, virtual training capabilities, security-compliant service deployment.
CODECO	CODECO aims to contribute to a smoother and more flexible support of services across the Edge-Cloud continuum via a unique, smart, and cross-layer orchestration between the decentralised data flow, computation, and networking services, to address Edge-Cloud challenges derived from the rising Internet and IoT service decentralisation.	Sharing common objectives, such as automated deployment, dynamic workload scheduling, decentralised learning and metadata management.
AC3	AC3 offers a common and secure federated platform that manages data source, CECC resources, and application behaviour in a unified and harmonised manner to ensure the desired SLA and save energy consumption. Moreover, the AC3 platform can adapt to a different context and events happening in the network, such as lack of resources, data deluge, or mobility of data source, by managing (i.e. deploying or migrating) micro-services across CECC infrastructures.	Sharing common objectives such as zero-touch management and configuration, AI-based resource forecasting and scheduling, focus on data management and integration with Data Spaces
DataCloud	Aiming to create a novel paradigm for Big Data pipeline processing over heterogeneous resources encompassing the Computing	Although focused on Big Data Pipelines management, there are shared objectives such as intelligent resource management

Continuum, covering the complete lifecycle of managing Big Data pipelines. across the computing continuum with an infrastructure drift adaptability and decentralised data storage.

RE4DY	RE4DY mission is to demonstrate how European industry can jointly build unique data-driven manufacturing and supply network active resilience strategies and yet sustain competitive advantages through digital continuity and sovereign data spaces across all phases of product and process lifecycle	Sharing common objectives such as sovereign data spaces and AI-enabled cognition
knowlEdge	The knowlEdge project developed a framework that provides means for the secure management of distributed data and the computational infrastructure to execute the needed analytic algorithms and redistribute the knowledge towards a knowledge exchange society.	Sharing common objectives such as distributed AI training and deployment, data modelling, distributed data storage, metadata management and data governance
Zero-SWARM	The project establishes a unique forum where separately maturing technologies of 5G and cloud-edge continuum, data technologies and analysis (including data spaces and GAIA-X) and operational technology (automation and agility) break their siloes to co-design and co-create	Sharing common objectives such as zero-touch management, distributed intelligence for managing distributed applications, adaptability to changing conditions, distributed automation over the decentralised data and intelligence infrastructures
SCENE	SCENE develops a scalable and flexible framework, streamlining the entire film production process from pre-production to distribution. Through a network of interconnected and autonomous cognitive systems	Sharing common objectives such as cognitive AI, distributed data sharing, and monitoring of alignment with privacy and security regulations
MobiSpaces	MobiSpaces provides end-to-end mobility-aware and optimised data governance platform. It aims to achieve a common data space for the mobility data through in-situ processing with all the security and privacy related functionalities.	Within MobiSpaces, security risk analysis is manual based on direct access to pilot data which will be automated in ENACT.
aerOS	aerOS aims to transparently utilise resources on the edge-to-cloud computing continuum to enable applications in an effective manner while incorporating multiple services. Its goal is to design and build a virtualised, platform-agnostic meta operating system for the IoT edge-cloud continuum.	The aerOS continuum ontology will be closely examined for potentially improving the ENACT CCC models under development.
INTEND	INTEND aims to leverage the latest AI breakthroughs to bring next-level human-like intelligence into the cognitive continuum, allowing the continuum to adapt, think and talk like human.	Sharing common objectives such as distributed data storage and management across the computing continuum, graph visualisation for CCC visibility, and adaptive orchestration functions.
MYRTUS	MYRTUS places a particular focus on the infrastructure part, considering even	Pursuing common goals such as runtime adaptivity across computing layers, semantic

hardware-level acceleration. It integrates three main pillars: heterogeneous CCC infrastructure, a dynamic 360-degree orchestration engine, and application programming support to facilitate resource interoperability across the CCC. continuum modelling and resource and data interoperability in line with well-established standards.

HYPER-AI	HYPER-AI builds on swarm intelligence, enhancing it with CHOP (Configuring, Healing, Optimizing, Protecting) capabilities to enable self-management.	Shared focus on data-intensive applications management and commonalities in terms of automated dynamic CCC management and interoperability based on open standards
EMPYREAN	EMPYREAN introduces the concept of "Associations", i.e., collaborative federations of heterogeneous IoT devices and resources, that dynamically and autonomously cooperate in a secure and trusted manner. This notion enables a flexible abstraction for cognitive resource orchestration.	Sharing common objectives such as AI-driven adaptability, efficient data processing of hyper-distributed applications and automated application programming.
CoGNETS	CoGNETS has designed an orchestration middleware for configuring dynamic mesh networks of heterogeneous resources. It leverages Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL), incorporating splitting and pruning mechanisms to support distributed training and inference. CoGNETS also adopts FIWARE Data Space Connectors as a registry interface for establishing a trusted CCC participation framework.	Commonalities in terms of distributed AI techniques, decentralised data processing and Data Space-enabled interoperability.
Swarmchestrator	Swarmchestrator introduces a novel, decentralised orchestration framework using dynamic Swarms. It emphasises trusted orchestration, necessitating that orchestration decisions must be trusted and explainable, as well as end-to-end security through cutting-edge technologies like blockchain, self-sovereign identities, and cryptographic algorithms.	Pursuing common goals such as application-aware orchestration, semantic resource and application representation and prediction-based decision-making.

Table 7: Relevant projects

5. ENACT platform specifications

The functional and technical specifications of the ENACT platform components were elicited based on the methodology described in Section 3.3 of this Deliverable. The templates used for each component include the component, its modules and functions (if applicable) and the filled-in tables are provided in the next Sections for each individual component.

5.1 Virtual Training Environment (VTE) component

Component Name
Intro / Overview

Virtual Training Environment

The Virtual Training Environment (VTE) for training, retraining, and recalibration of AI models is a workbench that helps users without skills in Data Analytics, Data Science, and AI techniques to train their own AI/ML algorithms. The component is composed of three main modules:

- The **Model Manager** is the entry point to the workbench where any of the algorithms present in the platform can be trained with their respective training/validation datasets. The Model Manager is also the place where all trained models are listed and can be finally configured prior to their execution in the target system through the AI Forecaster. Within this module, the user can connect to data pipelines for packaging the trained models prior to being sent for inference.
- **Federated Learning (FL) Module** implemented on infrastructures or clusters within the CCC. Each cluster performs local training on its data, and the FL module aggregates these local models into a comprehensive global model, ensuring data privacy and efficient training.
- In addition, a **General module** is provided which contains all remaining components that may span across several modules such as the user interface, visualisation and security features.

Extracted Modules

- Model Manager
- Federated Learning
- General

Component Workflow

To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the ENACT Virtual Training Environment, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.

External Component Interaction

Interaction with the ENACT Virtual Training Environment is realised through the ENACT Data Layer. Users upload their input in the form of models and datasets, from which the ENACT virtual training environment can gain access. Within the UI of the component, models are trained with the dataset provided, configured and once complete, the trained

model is saved within the Model Manager and sent to the AI Forecaster for inference. In the case where exchanging models and datasets through the ENACT Data Layer is not possible, Federated Learning Mechanisms will be explored and deployed. AI models will be exchanged only where edge node models will be used to train and update a common 'master' model in the cloud.

Prototypical Mock-ups
TRL

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Potential Use-cases
Layer

- Applicable in all pilot scenarios
- ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer
 - ENACT AI Layer
 - ENACT Modelling Layer

Technologies

The Virtual Training Environment is powered by the following technologies:

Programming Languages:

- Python¹⁸²
- Typescript¹⁸³
- Java¹⁸⁴

Frameworks:

- Angular¹⁸⁵: a TypeScript-based free and open-source single-page web application framework run on Node.js.

¹⁸² <https://www.python.org/>

¹⁸³ <https://www.typescriptlang.org/>

¹⁸⁴ <https://www.java.com/en/>

¹⁸⁵ <https://angular.dev/>

Interfaces

- Node.js¹⁸⁶: a cross-platform, open-source JavaScript runtime environment
- TensorFlow¹⁸⁷: an open-source framework for ML.
- PyTorch¹⁸⁸: A popular ML library for dynamic computation graph capabilities.
- Flower (Federated Learning Framework)¹⁸⁹: A framework for building federated learning systems, facilitating the orchestration of distributed training and model aggregation.

Libraries:

- Numpy¹⁹⁰: a library for the Python programming language, adding support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays.
- Scipy¹⁹¹: a library for scientific and technical computing
- Pandas¹⁹²: an open-source data analysis and manipulation tool.
- Scikit-learn¹⁹³: an open-source library for ML
- SHAP¹⁹⁴: an open-source library to support the explanation of ML models.

Model Manager Interface:

- **Overview:** The Model Manger Interface facilitates communication with Model Manager module and can execute requests to the Execution Engine. Through the Model Manager Interface, a user can perform CRUD operation on existing models, as well as request the execution of particular model. In addition, the interface provides endpoints for the upload of training and test data for model training operations. The Model Manager Interface also supports the configuration of models to allow data ingestion from MQTT and AMQP sources.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Initialisation Interface:

- **Overview:** This interface is responsible for initialising the federated learning process by distributing the initial model to the virtual edge nodes. It sets up the necessary environment for each node to begin local training.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Local Training Interface:

- **Overview:** Facilitates the actual training of ML models on local data available at client devices. It ensures models are trained using appropriate configurations and optimisation techniques.
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Asynchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

¹⁸⁶ https://nodejs.org/en#_blank

¹⁸⁷ <https://www.tensorflow.org/>

¹⁸⁸ <https://pytorch.org/>

¹⁸⁹ <https://flower.dev/>

¹⁹⁰ <https://numpy.org/>

¹⁹¹ <https://scipy.org/>

¹⁹² <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

¹⁹³ <https://scikit-learn.org/>

¹⁹⁴ <https://shap.readthedocs.io/>

Deployment Type	Model Aggregation and Update Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: This interface aggregates the locally trained models from different client devices into a single global model. It ensures that model updates are appropriately weighted and combined. ● Type: REST API ● State: Synchronous ● Data Format: JSON Validation and Testing Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: Validates and tests the aggregated model to ensure it meets specified performance and accuracy criteria. This interface is crucial for certifying the model before deployment. ● Type: REST API ● State: Synchronous ● Data Format: JSON Deployment and Monitoring Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Overview: Deploys the validated model to real-world edge devices and cloud servers. This interface also provides continuous monitoring of the model's performance, ensuring it remains effective and efficient in real-world applications. ● Type: REST API ● State: Asynchronous ● Data Format: JSON
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Java¹⁹⁵ ● Software as a Service ● Docker Containers The current deployment form of the virtual training environment is a series of docker containers. The component is also provided with a docker-compose script that allows for the deployment of all containers in the stack. The component requires minimum resources of 4GB RAM and 2 CPU cores.
	Given authentication is provided and validated in the ENACT Security and User Management system, all users will be able to access the ENACT Virtual Training Environment and its available AI/ML models. For the trained AI/ML models, a permissions system will be implemented allowing users to configure the access policies to their trained models. A permissions policy will be implemented to allow users to make their models either private and only visible/accessible to the model creator, or public, so that it can be discovered by other users in the ENACT Platform.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 8: Virtual Training Environment Component specification

5.1.1 Model Manager module

Module Name	Model Manager	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Manager is the entry point to the workbench through where any of the algorithms present in the platform can be trained, by using the Model Trainer sub-module with their respective training/validation datasets. The Model Manager is also the place where all trained modules are listed and can be finally configured prior to their execution in the target system through the AI Forecaster . Within this module, the user can connect to data pipelines to package the trained models prior to being sent for inference.		

¹⁹⁵ <https://www.java.com/en/>

Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General • Federated Learning
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Ingestor • Data Pipelines • ML Library • AI Explainability • Model Uploader • Model Validator • Model Registry • Model Configurator • Model Orchestrator • Model Deployer
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.

Table 9: Model Manager module specification

Data Ingestor function

Function Name	Data Ingestor	Priority	Must
Description	<p>This Data Ingestor allows for the ingestion of data. These ingested data are the ones to be used for training the different algorithms that will create the respective models. Usually, for training a model, a sample of structured datasets is needed, and this sample is composed of static data for the achievement of a good model. These data are typically represented using either a CSV or a JSON file format. Other file formats include results from queries against a database (e.g., MySQL, SQL Server, PostgreSQL, etc.).</p>		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	<p>The Data Ingestor should be able to ingest a range of datatypes and formats including MQTT, AMQP, REST and File Upload.</p>		

Table 10: Data Ingestor function specification

Data Pipelines function

Function Name	Data Pipelines	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Data Pipelines function manages the different input and output data pipelines that will serve the data for the training of a given model (e.g., from an IoT sensor) when this model is being trained with the Model Trainer or the Federated Learning modules. For the models trained outside the VTE, this module comes into play, if such models are imported into the VTE Model Registry.</p>		

Table 11: Data Pipelines function specification

ML Library function

Function Name	ML Library	Priority	Must
Description	The ML Library is a collection of ML/AI algorithms, grouped by family (covering both Supervised and Unsupervised) for the training of the data. After the training of such data, the analytical models can be assessed by the user (or Data Scientist) by exploring the Explainability of the training. If everything looks correct, the trained model can be uploaded to the central repository of the Model Manager.		

Table 12: ML Library function specification

Model Uploader function

Function Name	Model Uploader	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Uploader provides the capability to upload analytical models into the Model Manager from the VTE. This upload feature can be applied to models trained by means of the Model Trainer, by means of Federated Learning or models trained externally. External models are considered those trained outside of the VTE offer. Currently, this is performed via REST API, but will also be exposed through an additional API interface. AI/ML models trained within the VTE can be directly uploaded, without direct intervention of the user.		

Interacts with

Success Criteria

The Model Uploader should be able to upload a range of trained models for validation prior storing in the model registry.

Table 13: Model Uploader function specification

Model Configurator function

Function Name	Model Configurator	Priority	Must
Description	This Model Configurator helps to configure a model (both local and global ones in case of Federated Learning) that is going to be deployed in the AI Forecaster with regards to data pipelines for data ingestion, etc.		
Interacts with	<p>The diagram shows the Model Manager architecture. It includes Model Validator, Model Registry, Model Configurator, and Model Deployer. Model Validator sends data, XAI, and trained models to Model Registry. Model Registry then sends a trained model to Model Configurator. Model Configurator outputs a model to Model Deployer.</p>		
Success Criteria	The Model Configurator should be able to manage a range of different configuration parameters for a model including the data input and output of a given model.		

Table 14: Model Configurator function specification

Model Validator function

Function Name	Model Validator	Priority	Must
Description	This Model Validator will automatically validate the models that have been trained using technologies other than the VTE with respect to metadata and model descriptors, such as the RMSE, predictors, features and output parameters.		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD subgraph Model_Manager [Model Manager] direction TB MU[Model Uploader] -- "data, XAI & trained model" --> MV[Model Validator] MV -- "data, XAI & trained model" --> MR[Model Registry] MR -- "data, XAI & trained model" --> IDS[(Internal Data Store)] MV -- "trained model" --> MC[Model Configurator] end style MV stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>		
Success Criteria	The Model Configurator should be able to manage a range of different configuration parameters for a model including the data input and output of a given model.		

Table 15: Model Validator function specification

Model Registry function

Function Name	Model Registry	Priority	Must
Description	This Model Registry is for registering the models trained so that they can be configured, monitored or selected for execution. This component represents the actual database (currently implemented over MySQL) for the persistency and management of trained models. It is necessary to mention that the XAI information is stored also in this component so then it can be served to the Reporting module.		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	The Model Registry should be able to store a range of types of models while providing basic CRUD functionality to the registry.

Table 16: Model Registry function specification

Model Orchestrator function

Function Name	Model Orchestrator	Priority	Must
Description	The Model Orchestrator specifies the orchestration means for the execution of the different to-be-deployed-in-AI-Forecaster models while ensuring that the data is ready for its ingestion at the model entry points. It takes the pods generated by the Model Deployer and, after performing the final wiring, launches the model (included within the pod) to execution in the AI Forecaster.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The Model Orchestrator should be able to successfully send the pod for its execution to the AI Forecaster.		

Table 17: Model Orchestrator function specification

Model Deployer function

Function Name	Model Deployer	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Model Deployer is used for deploying the different trained models to a production system as this acts as part of the bridge between the Training functionality (either by means of the VTE or outside) and the Execution of these trained models within the AI Forecaster. Here the models are packaged in the form of Kubernetes pod so that they can be deployed at the target system right after orchestration of the data-in and results-out is completed.</p>		
Interacts with	<div style="border: 1px dashed black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> <p>Model Manager</p> <pre> graph LR MC[Model Configurator] -- model --> MD[Model Deployer] MD -- pod --> MO[Model Orchestrator] </pre> </div>		
Success Criteria	<p>The Model Deployer should be able to deploy all validated models. Those provided by the ENACT Virtual Training Environment and those uploaded by external sources..</p>		

Table 18: Model Deployer function specification

AI Explainability function

Function Name	AI Explainability	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The AI Explainability function is used for explaining the training of any ML model trained by means of the Model Trainer. This output is represented using Shapley values, which are a widely used approach from cooperative game theory that come with desirable properties. It is implemented using the SHAP library.</p>		

Interacts with	<pre> graph TD subgraph Model_Manager [Model Manager] DP[Data Pipelines] ML[ML Library] MU[Model Uploader] end subgraph Model_Trainer [Model Trainer] ML AE[AI Explainability] end DP --> ML ML --> MU MU -- "data, XAI & Trained Model" --> MU ML -.-> AE AE -.-> ML style AE stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>
Success Criteria	The AI Explainability function should be able to provide accurate explanations of the output of any ML model that has been trained within the Model Trainer. The explanations should be provided and represented through Shapley values.

Table 19: AI Explainability function specification

5.1.2 General module

Module Name	General	Priority	Must
Description	The General module houses remaining components that are used across the ENACT Virtual Training Environment.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Model Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web UI User Management Security Visualisation Reporting 		
Success Criteria	All module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 20: General module specification

Web UI function

Function Name	Web UI	Priority	Must
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Description	The Web UI component provides the point of interaction for the intended end users. It will be offered via web address and accessible via the internet. The Web UI will provide a means to interact with all modules and functions in the ENACT Virtual Training Environment.
Interacts with	<p>The diagram illustrates the interaction between the Web UI and the Model Manager. The Web UI is highlighted with a red circle. The Model Manager is a large dashed box containing several components: a Data Ingestor (with MQTT, AMQP, REST, and File Upload protocols), a Model Uploader, a Model Registry, and Reporting/Visualisation modules. An external trained model is shown interacting with the Model Manager. XAI data flows from the Model Registry to the Reporting module. The Web UI is connected to the Model Manager via a dashed line, indicating its role as the user interface for these functions.</p>
Success Criteria	The Web UI should be accessible over HTTPS and secured effectively. It should provide a positive user experience and be intuitive in nature. It should effectively provide access to the solution's Model Manager and Model Trainer.

Table 21: Web UI function specification

User Management function

Function Name	User Management	Priority	Must
Description	The User Management function manages user account and checks which users have access to which algorithms for training and which trained models. Currently this is based on ad-hoc login mechanisms although Keycloak is being assessed as an open-source alternative for its implementation.		

Interacts with

Success Criteria

The User Management function should effectively manage the user account of each user, while also effectively managing access to different stored models based on the permissions configured.

Table 22: User Management function specification

Security function

Function Name	Security	Priority	Must
Description	The security function manages and enforces the user and permissions-based access to models and training data. Working together with the User Management module, the security function will provide the authentication and authorisation mechanisms to enforce secure Models and Training Data.		

Interacts with

Success Criteria

The security function should provide authentication and authorisation mechanism to the User Management function, to support effective user-based access control.

Table 23: Security function specification

Visualisation function

Function Name	Visualisation	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Visualisation function is in charge of generating a range of charts, plots and visualisations. The function will create lightweight plots that can be generated from the results of the training of a model, i.e., Explainability-based plots, while being easier to generate and maintain. The visualisation function will also generate professional, heavyweight plots which can form dashboards for professional use. The heavyweight charts will be able to facilitate the use of complex-linked charts and the creation of dashboards for viewing the results of the model training.</p>		

<p>Interacts with</p>	
<p>Success Criteria</p>	<p>The Visualisation function should provide easy-to-generate and maintain lightweight visualisations. It should provide heavyweight visualisations for professional UCs. It should provide the ability to create dashboards from multiple plots or charts. It should be able to generate charts reflecting the explanation of the trained data and models.</p>

Table 24: Visualisation function specification

Reporting function

Function Name	Reporting	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Reporting function is expected to plot in a graphical way (UI) the results of the explainability data (XAI) when training a model. This component represents the actual plotting libraries together with the collection of tables and HTMLs to show the results.</p>		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	The Reporting function should be able to provide in report format visualisations and insights regarding the metrics and KPIs of a given model. The Model Reporter will be able to provide reports in both HTML and PDF formats.

Table 25: Model Reporter function specification

5.1.3 Federated Learning module

Module Name	Federated Learning	Priority	Must
Description	The Federated Learning (FL) module within the Virtual Training Environment (VTE) is designed to facilitate the training, validation, and deployment of AI models across distributed nodes such as edge devices and cloud servers. This module ensures that data remains localised, maintaining privacy while enabling collaborative model training. The VTE’s capabilities for simulation, validation, and optimisation are leveraged to support efficient federated learning.		
Interacts with Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Model Manager Initialisation Local Training Model Aggregation Validation and Testing Deployment and Monitoring 		
Success Criteria	Different for each function.		

Table 26: Federated Learning module specification

Initialisation function

Function Name	Initialisation	Priority	Must
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Description	Initialises the federated learning process by distributing the initial model to the virtual edge nodes simulated in the VTE. This function sets up the necessary environment for each node to begin local training.
Interacts with	
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The initial model is successfully distributed to all nodes. • Training parameters are correctly configured and aligned with the Model Manager. • No initialisation errors occur, ensuring a smooth start to the training process.

Table 27: Initialisation function specification

Local Training function

Function Name	Local Training	Priority	Must
Description	<p>Training involves the actual training of the ML model on the local data available on the client device. The training process may be repeated for multiple epochs to allow the model to learn from the data effectively. To improve efficiency, optimisation and model compression techniques are used.</p> <p>Model compression techniques may be applied to reduce the size of the trained model before sending updates to the central server. Model compression helps minimise communication overhead by reducing the amount of data transmitted between client devices and the central server. Techniques such as quantisation, pruning, or knowledge distillation may be used for model compression, depending on the requirements of the federated learning scenario.</p> <p>Optimisation techniques are applied to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the training process. Techniques like regularisation, dropout, or learning rate scheduling may</p>		

be employed to prevent overfitting, enhance convergence, and improve generalisation. **Early exit** may also be used to halt training when the model performance on a validation dataset starts deteriorating, thus preventing unnecessary computation.

Interacts with

Success Criteria

- Each node completes local training within the specified timeframe.
- Models are trained using the correct local data without errors.
- Training results are accurately reported back to the VTE.

Table 28: Local Training function specification

Model Aggregation and Update function

Function Name	Model Aggregation and update	Priority	Must
Description	Aggregation determines how model updates from different client devices are combined to update the global model. Common aggregation techniques include simple averaging, weighted averaging, or more sophisticated methods like Federated Averaging or Secure Aggregation. Aggregation techniques ensure that each client's contribution to the global model is appropriately weighted based on factors like data quality or model performance.		

Table 29: Model Aggregation and Update function specification

Validation and Testing function

Function Name	Validation and Testing	Priority	Must
Description	The aggregated model is validated and tested within the VTE to ensure it meets performance and accuracy criteria.		

Interacts with

Success Criteria

1. The aggregated model passes all validation tests with specified accuracy and performance metrics.
 - No critical errors are found during the testing phase.
 - The model is certified as ready for deployment based on validation results.

Table 30: Validation and Testing function specification

Deployment and Monitoring function

Function Name	Deployment and Monitoring	Priority	Must
Description	Once validated, the model is deployed to real-world edge devices and cloud servers. The VTE continues to monitor the model’s performance and provides feedback for continuous improvement. This function ensures that the model remains effective and efficient in real-world applications.		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The model is successfully deployed to all targeted edge devices and cloud servers. Continuous monitoring is established without interruptions. Performance metrics are collected and analysed to provide actionable feedback for model improvements.

Table 31: Deployment and Monitoring function specification

5.2 Application Controller component

Component Name	Application Controller
Intro / Overview	<p>The Application Controller will be deployed alongside containerised components of all ENACT applications. It will monitor and collect application metrics and dynamically realise and implement application adaptation mechanisms to enable applications to modify their behaviour or configuration based on feedback from the environment or user preferences. Adaptation actions will focus on the following strategies to help optimise the application execution behaviour:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Load balancing Elasticity Energy efficiency
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application Adaptation Strategies Application Adaptation Engine Application Data Manager Application Reconciler Engine

Component Workflow

To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the ENACT Application Controller, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.

External Component Interaction

The Application Controller will be deployed by the ENACT Orchestrator as a pod alongside each of the components (containers) of a given application.

The Application Controller will be deployed with a set of user defined or ENACT recommended adaptation strategies for the given application.

On deployment, the application will report application telemetry data back to the DRL Agent where needed. The tool will provide an interface for application components to interact with the ENACT Data Layer. The Application Controller will retrieve, read and enforce policies defined in the Application Policy Model via redeployment requests to the DRL. Finally, it will interact with the AI Act Compliance Checker component, to assess if the application is conforming to current AI Legislation. The Application Controller will receive the deployment schedules via the Application Manager function, and request deployment from the DRL Agent.

Prototypical Mock-ups

N/A

TRL

Current: TRL – 0
Expected: TRL – 3

Potential Use-cases

All pilot scenarios

Layer Technologies

Application Development Layer

The Virtual Training Environment is powered by the following technologies:

Programming Languages:

- Java

Frameworks:

Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spring Boot: an open-source Java framework used for programming standalone, production-grade Spring-based applications with a bundle of libraries that make project startup and management easier. <p>Libraries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OpenTelemetry¹⁹⁶: Observability framework and toolkit. Prometheus¹⁹⁷: Monitoring and alerting toolkit. Jaeger¹⁹⁸: Distributed tracing platform
	<p>Application Manager Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: The Application Manager Interface provides the entry point to the application controller, allowing communication with the Orchestrator to support deployment and redeployment, as well as the feedback of application telemetry data. Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON <p>Application Data Manager Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overview: The Application Data Manager Interface facilitates the communication between deployed application components and the ENACT Data Layer. Type: REST API State: Synchronous Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	The Application Controller will be deployed as a pod alongside each application.
Authorisation Definition	All user interactions with the Application Controller will be authorised and mediated exclusively through the Application Policy Model (APM). The APM serves as the designated interface for configuring and operationalising Application Controller behaviour, while direct access to the controller’s internal functions remains restricted and is not exposed to end users.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 32: Application Controller Component specification

Application Manager function

Function Name	Application Manager	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Application Manager serves as the core coordination function within the Application Controller. It is responsible for managing the internal modules, and the runtime deployment of the user application. The introduction of the Application Reconciler Engine means the Application Manager now additionally acts as a relay for high-level policy enforcement and compliance validation. It receives policy-driven and compliance-based adaptation suggestions from the Reconciler Engine, evaluates their feasibility, and coordinates the required actions by invoking the appropriate Application Adaptation Strategy via the Application Adaptation Engine. The Application Manager is also responsible for constructing and transmitting redeployment or configuration change requests to the DRL Agent, based on reconciled policy outcomes. The function also manages the flow of telemetry data between application containers and the ENACT Data Layer via the</p>		

¹⁹⁶ <https://opentelemetry.io/>

¹⁹⁷ <https://prometheus.io/>

¹⁹⁸ <https://www.jaegertracing.io/>

Interacts with	Application Data Manager, ensuring adaptation decisions are grounded in real-time metrics.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Adaptation Engine • Application Data Manager • Application Reconciler Engine • DRL Agent • Orchestrator
Success Criteria	The application manager must be able to successfully coordinate the operation of the Application Reconciliation Engine, and the Application Data Manager. It must be able to communicate with the DRL Agent for requesting changes in deployment configuration and confirm their execution status. It must coordinate successfully with the Application Reconciler Engine to receive and act on policy-based and compliance triggered adaptation suggestions.

Table 33: Application Manager function specification

5.2.1 Application Adaptation Engine module

Module Name	Application Adaptation Engine	Priority	Must
Description	A set of implementable mechanisms that can be used to execute a given application adaptation strategy when a threshold or trigger point is met.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Adaptation Strategies • Application Manager • Application Reconciler Engine 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relocation Requester • Resource Allocation Requester • Container Enabler 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 34: Application Adaptation Engine module specification

Relocation Requester function

Function Name	Relocation Requester	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request a change in the deployment of the application from the DRL Agent.		
Interacts with	Load Balancing Application Adaptation Strategy		
Success Criteria	The Relocation Requester must be able to effectively read present load balancing application adaptation strategies, and when set criteria are met, must be able to execute a request, after compliance checks and via the Application Manager to the DRL Agent, that requests for a redeployment of components to meet application demands.		

Table 35: Relocation Requester function specification

Resource Allocation Requester function

Function Name	Resource Allocation Requester	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request a change in the deployment of the application from the DRL Agent.		
Interacts with	Elasticity Application Adaptation Strategy		
Success Criteria	The Resource Allocation Requester must be able to effectively read the present elasticity-based application adaptation strategies, and when set criteria are met, must be able to		

execute a request, after compliance checks and via the Application Manager to the DRL Agent, that requests a change in the allocated resources for a specific app component.

Table 36: Resource Allocation Requester function specification

Container Enabler function

Function Name	Container Enabler	Priority	Must
Description	An executable mechanism that can be used to implement the energy efficiency application adaptation strategy. The mechanism enables the Application Controller to turn individual application components or containers off and on as and when they are needed, in order to optimise energy usage.		
Interacts with	Energy Efficiency Application Adaptation Strategy		
Success Criteria	The container enabler must be able to effectively read present energy efficiency application adaptation strategies, and when set criteria are met, must be able to turn individual application components off and on, in order to support energy efficiency requirements.		

Table 37: Container Enabler function specification

5.2.2 Application Adaptation Strategies module

Module Name	Application Adaptation Strategies	Priority	Must
Description	A set of user-defined or ENACT-recommended adaptation strategies for a given application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application Adaptation Engine Application Reconciler Engine 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Load Balancing Elasticity Energy Efficiency 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 38: Application Adaptation Strategies module specification

Load Balancing function

Function Name	Load Balancing	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request a change in the deployment of the application from the DRL Agent.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relocation Requester 		
Success Criteria	The Load Balancing application adaptation strategy must be able to hold a defined procedure for the request of a change in deployment location of application containers, including metrics and trigger points for the strategy to be implemented.		

Table 39: Load Balancing function specification

Elasticity function

Function Name	Elasticity	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request a change in the allocated resources of the application from the DRL Agent.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resource Allocation Requester 		

Success Criteria	The Elasticity application adaptation strategy must be able to hold a defined procedure for the request of a change in the allocated resources of application containers, including metrics and trigger points for the strategy to be implemented.
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Table 40: Elasticity function specification

Energy Efficiency function

Function Name	Energy Efficiency	Priority	Must
Description	An adaptation strategy or multiple strategies that can be triggered upon defined conditions to request to turn off or on individual application containers.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Container Enabler 		
Success Criteria	The Energy Efficiency application adaptation strategy must be able to hold a defined procedure including metrics and trigger points that enable the Application Controller to turn off and on individual containers as and when it is needed.		

Table 41: Energy Efficiency function specification

5.2.3 Data Manager module

Module Name	Data Manager	Priority	Must
Description	A set of mechanisms designed to support the operations of the Application Controller. Functions provided to support the monitoring of telemetry data from application components, and to enable the adaptation suggestions of the Application Manager.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Manager • Application Containers 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Telemetry Data Manager • Application Data Manager 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 42: Data Manager module specification

Telemetry Data Manager function

Function Name	Telemetry Data Manager	Priority	Must
Description	A mechanism that enables the capture, monitoring, and reporting of application telemetry data for both enabling adaptation strategies on their trigger points, and reporting back to the DRL Agent.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Manager • TDCME 		
Success Criteria	The Telemetry Data Manager must be able to capture, monitor and report application telemetry data from running application components and report data back to the DRL Agent.		

Table 43: Telemetry Data Manager function specification

Application Data Manager function

Function Name	Application Data Manager	Priority	Must
Description	A mechanism that provides access to the ENACT Data Layer for applications and allows the application to access and store user data in a central repository.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Manager • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces 		

Success Criteria	The Application Data Manager function must be able to provide effective access to the ENACT data layer for deployed applications. The function must be able to support CRUD operations for each deployed application and facilitate data access and storage.
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Table 44: Application Data Manager function specification

5.2.4 Application Reconciler Engine module

Module Name	Application Reconciler Engine	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Application Reconciler Engine acts as a bridge between the Application Controller and two external components: the Application Policy Model and the AI Act Compliance Checker. Its main job is to help the Application Controller understand high-level policies and legal requirements and turn them into practical adaptation strategies. Unlike a system that constantly checks for updates, the Reconciler Engine only consults the Application Policy Model when the Application Controller specifically requests for it; usually when there's a need for deployment or redeployment decisions due to changes in the application's requirements or conditions. At the same time, it works with the AI Act Compliance Checker to verify that the application's current or intended behaviour complies with AI regulations. When both the Policy Model and AI Act Compliance Checker are successfully passed, the Reconciler Engine generates deployment or redeployment suggestions and forwards them to the DRL Agent through the Application Manager. However, if the compliance check fails, the Reconciler Engine sends the deployment or redeployment suggestions back to the Application Controller, along with detailed feedback. The Application Controller can then initiate the adaptation process by engaging the Adaptation Engine and selecting suitable Adaptation Strategies. Once the necessary adjustments are made, the request can be regenerated and re-evaluated for compliance and policy alignment.</p>		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Policy Model • AI Act Compliance Checker • DRL Agent • Application Containers 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Policy Model • AI Act Compliance Checker 		
Success Criteria	<p>The module must be able to successfully retrieve and interpret data from the Application Policy Model. The module must invoke the AI Act Compliance Checker and correctly handle compliance evaluation results. The module must be able to select the most appropriate adaptation strategy and coordinate execution via the Application Adaptation Engine. The module must generate valid and optimised redeployment suggestions and forward them to the Application Manager. The module should ensure that all adaptation actions uphold define policies and meet legal compliance standards.</p>		

Table 45: Application Data Manager function specification

5.3 Graph Neural Network (GNN) Models component

Component Name	ENACT Graph Neural Network (GNN) models
Intro / Overview	<p>The ENACT GNN models, developed using ML-based GNN algorithms, will permit the scheduling and dynamic optimisation of ENACT hyper-distributed applications.</p> <p>By leveraging graph representation, the models enable a more efficient and effective analysis of relationships between diverse nodes. They proficiently model the connections among various services and accurately predict optimal configurations to improve service</p>

Extracted Modules
Component
Workflow
External
Component
Interaction

availability, latency, and other performance metrics. The adopted scope is based on the use of Deep Q-learning, where the DRL Agent interacts with the environment to explore and exploit different deployment configurations. The agent triggers the GNN component to obtain the Q-value, which reflects the best assignment of applications to computing nodes. This mechanism enables the intelligent scheduling and optimisation of application placement in dynamic environments.

N/A

N/A

The Dynamic Graph Modeller is responsible for constructing and updating the graph structure based on incoming telemetry data, which will feed the updated graph data into the AI Forecaster to predict trends and the continuum's behavioural patterns. With these predictions generated by the ML algorithms employed by the AI Forecaster, the GNN uses this data to perform graph-based learning tasks, such as node classification or link prediction. By doing this, the GNN refines and optimises these sub-optimal schedules and sends them to the DRL for further decision-making and deployment.

In parallel, based on the performance metrics and potential new data, models used by the GNN in order to perform these computations on the schedules are constantly being updated within the Virtual Training Environment, adjusting the GNN model's parameters to enhance its accuracy and generalisation capabilities for subsequent use.

Prototypical Mock-ups

N/A

TRL	Current: TRL-2 Expected: TRL-5
Potential Use-cases	Applicable in all pilot scenarios
Layer	ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer
Technologies	The Graph Neural Network is powered by the following technologies: Programming languages: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Python Framework: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PyTorch • TensorFlow Libraries / Tools: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PyTorch Geometric • NVIDIA CUDA Toolkit • cuDNN
Interfaces	Inference Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Interface provides the necessary communication between the AI Forecaster component and the GNN component in order to receive predicted telemetry data for scheduling based on future needs, and transfer the optimal schedules to the AI Forecaster and to the Orchestrator (via the Application Controller) for further deployment. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON Retraining Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This interface would serve to transfer the models used by the GNN + DRL Agent to the VTE, a component that would be in charge of re-training the models to make them more accurate and efficient to be used by the GNN + DRL Agent for future optimisations. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI as a Service (AlaaS) • Docker Containers <p>The AI model will be accessible to other services via a REST API, allowing seamless integration and interaction with its capabilities. Additionally, the API will be dockerised, ensuring easy deployment and scalability across different environments.</p>
Authorisation Definition	Authorisation for accessing the ENACT GNN models will be facilitated through a RESTful API, with authentication being provided and validated by the ENACT Security and User Management system. Upon successful authentication, the API will enforce authorisation rules to determine whether the authenticated user has the necessary permissions to access the GNN models.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 46: Graph Neural Network Component specification

Inference function

Function Name	Inference	Priority	Must
Description	Users can leverage this component to interact with the model, providing inputs for processing and receiving corresponding predictions or results in return.		
Interacts with	Orchestrator: To pass the optimised deployment configurations.		

Success Criteria	The component should consistently provide optimised deployment configurations or results without errors or unexpected behaviour.
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Table 47: Inference function specification

Retraining function

Function Name	Retraining	Priority	Must
Description	GNN models should possess the capability to update their parameters through local retraining techniques within the Virtual Training Environment, leveraging events to enhance the cognitive capabilities of the ENACT edge-to-cloud continuum.		
Interacts with	Virtual Training Environment: To update the improved models used for optimising the deployments.		
Success Criteria	The model can be re-trained with new data within the Virtual Training Environment.		

Table 48: Retraining function specification

Evaluate function

Function Name	Evaluate	Priority	Should
Description	GNN models should be capable of generating relevant and understandable evaluation metrics reflecting their performance across various tasks and datasets. These metrics should be quantifiable, interpretable, and provide meaningful insights into the accuracy, robustness, efficiency, and other important characteristics of the models.		
Interacts with	N/A		
Success Criteria	GNN models should enable reproducible and consistent assessment of their performance over time and across different environments.		

Table 49: Evaluate function specification

Data converter function

Function Name	Data converter	Priority	Should
Description	Before realising the inference/training of the model with the data, GNN models should be capable of converting the ENACT data type format received into a format they can work with, such as arrays, in order to execute these functions.		
Interacts with	N/A		
Success Criteria	The component should correctly generate data that is compatible with the ENACT format provided.		

Table 50: Data converter function specification

5.4 Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) component

Component Name	Dynamic Graph Modeller
Intro / Overview	<p>The Dynamic Graph Modeller obtains data from a deployment in the ENACT environment, processes and converts it into a visual graph (edges and nodes). In addition, users can also edit this graph or send it to other tools like GNN to modify it to be more suitable regarding features like better latency, power efficiency, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Data Requester is the entry point of data to feed to the component; it gathers the info of the rest of the components and prepares it to be transferred to the Graph Modeller component. • The Graph Modeller is in charge of convert the entry data into a graph structure of nodes and edges.

**Extracted Modules
Component
Workflow**

- The **Graph Visualiser** represents the graph data structures providing a graphical way to ENACT operators.

N/A

To depict the ENACT Dynamic Graph Modeller workflow, a diagram has been used to represent the interaction between internal components.

**External
Component
Interaction**

The Dynamic Graph Modeller has a series of connectors that are used to interact with other components in the ENACT environment. The component that provides data to the DGM is the Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine.

The components that receive data from the DGM are:

- AI Forecaster
- Security Risk Modeller
- DRL + GNN

Prototypical Mock-ups

Home Page: This is the first page users will see once they open the tool. There is a Navigation Bar with the different views available of the ENACTs continuum:

- Node visualisation
- Pod visualisation
- SRM Report visualisation
- AI graph visualisation

Node visualisation: The following image shows the cluster nodes running on the ENACT continuum.

Pod visualisation: The following image shows the pods running and their connections between them.

SRM report visualisation: The following image shows the visualisation of the report generated by the SRM component.

DCM Node Visualization Pod Visualization **SRM Report** AI Visualization

Label	Asset	Assertable	Proposed	Work in Progress
SLA	system#replicaset_open5gs-sgwu-6b5798bfd	Yes	No	No
SoftwareTesting	system#container_open5gs-sgwu	Yes	No	No
X509ServiceVerifier	system#pod_open5gs-scp-5cc5c9674f-9ghwk	Yes	No	No
SoftwarePatched	system#pod_open5gs-mongodb-7d98bfc976-cvg4g	Yes	No	No
SuspendInfectedProcess	system#LoginService_replicaset_open5gs-ausf-86f8588766	Yes	No	No
X509ClientVerifier	system#replicaset_open5gs-pcrf-b4b665f5	Yes	No	No
KeyManagement	system#container_open5gs-nrf-DataService	Yes	No	No
PenetrationTesting	system#pod_open5gs-mongodb-7d98bfc976-cvg4g	Yes	No	No
DisableServiceAccess	system#interface_container_open5gs-upf_InternetAsset	Yes	No	No
X509	system#LoginService_container_open5gs-amf	Yes	No	No
AccessControl	system#LoginService_container_open5gs-mme	Yes	No	No
RestrictedShell	system#LoginService_replicaset_open5gs-udr-5f7bff976	Yes	No	No
FormalVerification	system#container_open5gs-scp-DataService	Yes	No	No

AI graph visualisation: The following image shows the visualisation in which the input and output graphs generated by the AI layer are represented.

DCM Node Visualization Pod Visualization SRM Report **AI Visualization**

Original Graph **AI Graph**

TRL

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Potential Use-cases
Layer
Technologies

Applicable in all pilot scenarios

- ENACT Modelling Layer

The Dynamic Graph Modeller is powered by the following technologies:

Programming languages:

- Python
- Typescript

Frameworks:

- Node.js: a cross-platform, open-source JavaScript runtime environment

Libraries:

Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Networkx¹⁹⁹: Python package for the creation, manipulation, and study of the structure, dynamics, and functions of complex networks. • Sigma.js²⁰⁰: JavaScript library aimed at visualising graphs of thousands of nodes and edges
	<p>Data Requester Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Data Requester is in charge of gathering (requesting) all the info from the Telemetry Data Collector& Monitoring Engine and Orchestrator. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Graph Modeller Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: The Graph Modeller receives the data of the system structured as a graph and represents it in a visual way. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: GEXF, GRAPHML (graph formats)
Deployment Type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software as a Service • Docker Containers • Helm Chart <p>The deployment form of the Dynamic Graph Modeller will be a containerised solution in Docker that can be easily deployed in a Kubernetes environment with the use of Helm. The solution will be packaged as a Helm chart and will be ready to deploy by the Kubernetes orchestrator.</p>
Authorisation Definition	<p>Authorisation for accessing the ENACT Dynamic Graph Modeller will be facilitated through a RESTful API, with authentication being provided and validated by the ENACT Security and User Management system. Upon successful authentication, the API will enforce authorisation rules to determine whether the authenticated user has the necessary permissions to access the DGM.</p>
Licence	<p>Apache 2.0</p>

Table 51: Dynamic Graph Modeller Component specification

Data Requester function

Function Name	Data Requester	Priority	Should
Description	<p>This function enables requesting and interacting with the components responsible for gathering the information about the actual state of the deployment (Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine and Orchestrator) and prepare and sending it to the Graph Modeller Function.</p>		

¹⁹⁹ <https://networkx.org/>

²⁰⁰ <https://www.sigmajavascript.org/>

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	The Data Requester should be able to request and receive all the data related to a deployment in the ENACT environment.

Table 52: Data Requester function specification

Graph Modeller function

Function Name	Graph Modeller	Priority	Must
Description	This function receives the raw data of a deployment as input and converts it into a graph format as output.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	The function is able to convert raw data from a deployment in a graph format compatible with the Graph Control Panel function (.GEXF or .GRAPHML).		

Table 53: Graph Modeller function specification

Graph Visualiser function

Function Name	Graph Visualiser	Priority	Must
Description	This function represents the graph data in a graphical way.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	Represent correctly the graph data info gathered converted into a graph in as output in the Graph Modeller function.		

Table 54: Graph Visualiser function specification

5.5 CCC Data Models

The CCC Data Models are not an actual ENACT component but rather a set of data models that facilitate interoperability among other ENACT platform components. In this Section, they are presented following the templates established for the definition of components and modules.

Component Name	CCC Data Models
Intro / Overview	The models provide a rich semantic representation of the concepts for the overall description of Service/Application, Resource/Device and Telemetry data, in the context of

	<p>dynamic heterogeneous complex distributed systems. The models will be used for internal communication of the relevant ENACT components as well as for the definition of high-level service/application deployment requirements, the specification of infrastructure resource/device characteristics, capabilities and configurations, and the collection and storage of Telemetry data for various purposes. The models will be developed with clarity, modularity, and interoperability in mind. They should make a semantic distinction between concepts and observations, be easily extendable and adaptable, and applicable to different systems and configurations.</p>
Extracted Modules	<p>The term “modules” is not relevant in the case of the CCC Models. However, they include three main sub-models:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application Model • Resource Model • Telemetry Model
Component Workflow	<p>The CCC Data Models are not a tangible component, but rather a collection of data models utilised by other ENACT components for interoperability / communication and data storage purposes. As such, no specific workflows can be presented here; however, the CCC Models are utilised in the background within the workflows of other ENACT components and their interactions with each other.</p>
External Component Interaction	<p>The CCC Data Models are utilised by the following ENACT components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) • Security Risk Modeller (SRM) • Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) • Orchestrator • AI Forecaster • Application Controller • Application Programming Model (APM) • Application Policy Model • Data Manager
Prototypical Mock-ups	<p><i>Not applicable.</i></p>
TRL	<p>Current TRL: 3 Expected TRL: 5</p>
Potential Use-cases Layer	<p>Applicable in all pilot scenarios</p>
Layer	<p>The CCC Models are utilised at various ENACT layers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ENACT Modelling Layer • ENACT Orchestration Layer • ENACT AI Layer • ENACT Application Development Layer • ENACT Data Layer
Technologies	<p>The ENACT CCC Models will be powered by the following technologies and standards, as required:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unified Modelling Language (UML) • YAML Ain't Markup Language (YAML) • Extensible Markup Language (XML) • JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)
Interfaces	<p><i>Not applicable.</i></p>
Deployment Type	<p><i>Not applicable.</i></p>
Authorisation	<p><i>Not applicable.</i></p>
Definition	
Licence	<p>Apache 2.0</p>

Table 55: CCC Models specification

5.5.1 Application Model

Module Name	Application Model	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Application Model includes the parameters that can be used for the high-level or lower-level description of an application or service to be deployed to the ENACT Continuum, along with its characteristics and the user-set deployment objectives / goals. Based on these parameters, the application deployment can be optimised by the ENACT platform mechanisms. The Application model includes parameters such as the application usage demand, service level (e.g., reliability, accuracy), application performance (e.g., total execution time, response latency, hardware acceleration and its type, parallelisation), data storage and data transfer, network, security and privacy (e.g., encryption, legal framework), energy consumption, deployment cost, timeframe, in-depth technical details (e.g., programming language, execution environment), etc.</p>		
Interacts with	<p>The Application model is to be utilised by the following ENACT components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security Risk Modeller (SRM) • Orchestrator • Application Programming Model (APM) • Application Controller • Application Policy Model • Data Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<p><i>Not applicable.</i></p>		
Success Criteria	<p>The model should enable the adequate description of the parameters of interest of each particular application / service and the requirements that they should satisfy, in order to facilitate their optimal deployment and execution in the ENACT Continuum. The relevant ENACT components should utilise the developed data models for exchanging data and interacting with each other successfully.</p>		

Table 56: Application / service model specification

5.5.2 Resource Model

Module Name	Resource Model	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Resource Abstraction model can be utilised for representing the hardware and software resources that will be part of the ENACT Continuum along with their detailed characteristics and attributes. It captures both capability specifications and configuration aspects in a distinct manner, enabling a precise representation of both what a resource can achieve and how it is currently configured. A hardware resource (Node) can have various attributes (e.g., CPU, Memory, Network, Storage), execution capabilities (e.g., trusted execution enclaves, vector extensions, streaming extensions, software extensions) and one or more attached resources (e.g., GPUs, FPGAs, SmartNICs). A software resource aggregates and handles multiple hardware resources with different capabilities and offers functional facilities on top (e.g., storage service, execution service).</p>		
Interacts with	<p>The Resource model is to be utilised by the following ENACT components:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) • Security Risk Modeller (SRM) • Application Programming Model (APM) • Data Manager 		

Extracted Functions	<i>Not applicable.</i>
Success Criteria	The elements of the Resource Model should enable the efficient expression of all the resources linked to the ENACT platform, their characteristics and configurations. The resource parameters captured by the model can be utilised by the relevant ENACT components and intelligent orchestration mechanisms for optimal deployment of applications to the ENACT Continuum.

Table 57: Resource / device model specification

5.5.3 Telemetry Model

Module Name	Telemetry Model	Priority	Must
Description	The Telemetry Model captures the infrastructure runtime measurements of the various resources and components that comprise the ENACT Continuum. Its aim is to adequately describe the state of the hardware and software components available for allocation and usage. It builds on time series streams that refer to the current state of the hardware and low-level software resources available, and covers various telemetry information categories, such as compute, memory, disk, network and hardware. For each of the categories more in-depth metrics are provided that describe the current state of the infrastructure and enable the ENACT platform components to act on various resources, as required.		
Interacts with	The Telemetry Data Model is to be utilised by the following ENACT components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) Security Risk Modeller (SRM) Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine (TDCME) AI Forecaster Application Controller Application Programming Model (APM) Data Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<i>Not applicable.</i>		
Success Criteria	The elements of the Telemetry Model should facilitate the sharing and storage of telemetry data from all the resources linked with the ENACT platform in a predefined format. The historical telemetry data should be linkable to particular services characteristics and cover their whole lifecycle. The telemetry parameters captured by the model can be utilised by the relevant ENACT components and AI mechanisms enabling smart orchestration for optimal deployment of applications to the ENACT Continuum.		

Table 58: Telemetry data model specification

5.6 Data Access and Sharing Interfaces component

Component Name	Data Access and Sharing Interfaces
Intro / Overview	The Data Access and Sharing Interfaces will provide mechanisms for accessing and retrieving data stored in the distributed data sources. They include data connectors and APIs, to enable other components and applications to interact with the distributed data store and perform read and write operations.
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APIs Data Connectors

Component Workflow

There are no internal interactions; legacy APIs and Data Connectors are used for forwarding read/write requests of and transferring data to other ENACT components. Custom, independent API endpoints are used as the interface of Data Connectors.

External Component Interaction

External components interact with the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces by making API calls to either dedicated endpoints or a connector’s inter-face. These API calls serve various purposes, including:

- Requests to read historical telemetry data or write new data
- Requests to write telemetry forecasting results
- Requests to read or write code objects

Overall, these interfaces act as an intermediary between the Data Layer and the ENACT platform. All project components and applications aiming to share, store and/or consume (mainly historical) data should be able to interact with the distributed data space. We currently consider that the EN-ACT Data Space communicates with:

1. The Telemetry Data Collector to record the collected telemetry data.
2. The AI Forecaster to store past forecasting results.
3. The Application Controller to provide it with forecasted telemetry, but also for granting access.
4. The Virtual Training Environment, which retrieves datasets to be used for AI training.
5. The Application Programming Model (APM) to store or send code objects to be used by the Software Development Kit (SDK).

In the case of communicating through the connector, the latter determines the access to data based on pre-specified data usage policies. Once a request is received, it is forwarded to the Data Manager for further processing.

Prototypical Mock-ups

The AI Forecaster sends its predictions to be stored in the Data Layer. For authorised data read requests, the relevant data is sent back to the requester. If the request involves forecasted telemetry data, matching stored data, but also relevant access responses, are sent to the Application Controller. For requests coming from the VTE for data for AI training, the appropriate datasets are returned from the respective data store to VTE. In object sharing, the APM acts as an intermediary between the Data Space and the SDK, either sending code objects to be stored at the Data Layer or retrieving code objects to be used during application development. Health logs and alerts might also be shared internally in the Data Space to monitor stores' health.

The Data Layer is not expected to have a UI. The Sovity EDC connector itself offers a UI:

TRL Potential Use-cases

Expected TRL: 9
 In all three pilot cases, while general data transfer can be considered regarding historical data

Layer Technologies

ENACT Data Layer

- REST APIs
- gRPC APIs (optional)
- Sovity Community Edition EDC Connectors²⁰¹. The Data Connectors are built upon:
 - JSON-LD²⁰² for connecting Linked Data
 - DCAT²⁰³ to enable interoperability between data catalogues
 - Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)²⁰⁴ to define policies

Interfaces

API Interfaces:

- **Overview:** Used for the communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components
- **Type:** REST API
- **State:** Synchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Data Connector Interfaces:

²⁰¹ <https://github.com/soivity/edc-ce>

²⁰² <https://www.w3.org/TR/json-ld11/>

²⁰³ <https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-3/>

²⁰⁴ <https://w3c.github.io/poe/model/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components • Type: Eclipse Dataspace Protocol • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	Software
Authorisation Definition	Data Space Connectors can help set up some data access/sharing mechanisms and define the data usage policies.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 59: Data Access and Sharing Interfaces Component specification

5.6.1 APIs module

Module Name	APIs	Priority	Must
Description	API endpoints for communication between the ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • AI Forecaster • VTE • Application Controller • Application Programming Model 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read Data • Write Data 		
Success Criteria	Satisfies authorised read/write requests. Returns data expressed as indicated by the ENACT CCC models.		

Table 60: API's module specification

Read Data function

Function Name	Read Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow retrieving data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) from the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application Controller 		
Success Criteria	Other components are able to retrieve stored data.		

Table 61: Read Data function specification

Write Data function

Function Name	Write Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow recording data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) in the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector 		

Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • VTE • Application Controller
	Relevant (historical) data are stored in the ENACT data store.

Table 62: Write Data function specification

5.6.2 Data Connector module

Module Name	Data Connectors	Priority	Must
Description	Data Connectors for communication between ENACT Data layer and external ENACT components.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • AI Forecaster • VTE • Application Controller • Application Programming Model 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Read Data • Write Data 		
Success Criteria	Satisfies authorised read/write requests based on predefined data usage policies. Returns data expressed as indicated by the ENACT CCC models.		

Table 63: Data Connector module specification

Read Data function

Function Name	Read Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow retrieving data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) from the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application Controller 		
Success Criteria	Only authorised parties are able to retrieve stored data without violating the predefined data usage policies.		

Table 64: Read Data function specification

Write Data function

Function Name	Write Data	Priority	Must
Description	To allow recording data (telemetry, health logs and datasets for AI training) in the ENACT data store.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other Data Access and Sharing Interfaces • Data Manager • Telemetry Data Connector • VTE • Application Controller 		
Success Criteria	Relevant (historical) data sent by authorised parties are stored in the ENACT data store.		

Table 65: Write Data function specification

5.7 Data Manager component

Component Name	Data Manager
Intro / Overview	<p>A distributed data store/space for the whole computing continuum. ENACT will adopt data sovereignty and governance principles as they are derived by leading initiatives like IDSA, GAIA-X, etc. Therefore, the component will provide distributed storage services by being interlinked with interfaces like Data Connectors for sovereign data sharing among different parties. In particular, the ENACT Data Manager will consist of the following subcomponents:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Data Stores which will reside in nodes/devices distributed across the continuum. 2. The Metadata Manager which handles the metadata, including data location, attributes, access permissions, etc. <p>In addition, ENACT provides two auxiliary subcomponents as well, namely:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Monitoring Services to keep track of the Distributed Data Storage performance, monitor its health and provide associate alerts and diagnostics. 2. The Security and Access Control Manager for identity and access management. <p>Moreover, ENACT will try to move a step further in data sharing and storage, by supporting an innovative sharing of objects between the applications in the CCC.</p>
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Store(s) • Metadata Manager • Monitoring Services (optional) • Security and Access Control (optional)
Component Workflow	<p>The following diagram illustrates the interactions and workflow between the ENACT Data Manager modules.</p> <p>The diagram, titled 'Data Layer (Space)', shows the following workflow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Access & Sharing Interfaces send access requests to the Security & Access Control Manager. The Security & Access Control Manager (containing Identity verification and Access control) sends access responses back to the interfaces and sends access requests to the Monitoring Services and Metadata Manager. The Metadata Manager (containing Data Indexing, Data Filtering, and Data De-indexing) sends access requests to the ENACT Data Stores. The ENACT Data Stores send Telemetry data and Objects back to the Metadata Manager. The ENACT Data Stores also send Telemetry data and Objects back to the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces. The Monitoring Services send Health logs and alerts back to the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces.
Component Workflow	<p>First, the request is directed to the Security and Access Control Manager. This manager is responsible for verifying the requesting entities' credentials and determining whether they are authorised to perform actions such as reading stored data, writing new data, or obtaining monitoring logs. Authorisation tokens may be generated and sent back to the applications. Additionally, to ensure that data is securely stored, encryption techniques may also be applied.</p>

External Component Interaction

If a data read/write request is authorised, the request is forwarded to the Metadata Manager. In case of write requests, the Metadata Manager enriches the data or objects to be stored with proper indices indicating their source, attributes, etc. Subsequently, the data is securely stored in the distributed data stores.

For authorised data read requests, the relevant data is sent back to the requester. If the request involves historical telemetry data or code objects, the stored asset is filtered to retrieve the matching asset from the data store wherein it resides. For requests for AI training, the appropriate datasets involving historical telemetry data and predictions are fetched from the respective data store. Returned telemetry data and objects pass through the metadata manager.

The Monitoring Services might also be triggered to generate health logs and alerts.

The Data Manager interacts with the ENACT platform via the Data Access & Sharing Interfaces of the Data Layer.

Prototypical Mock-ups

There is not any UI expected to be developed for the Data Manager.

TRL

Expected TRL: 5

Potential Use-cases

In all three pilot cases, while general data transfer can be considered regarding historical data.

Layer Technologies

ENACT Data Layer

The technologies being considered currently for the implementation of the Distributed Data Space include:

For the Data Store:

- Elastic Search²⁰⁵ to enable distributed data storing and search

For the Metadata manager:

- Elastic Search to enable distributed metadata mapping and search

For the Security & Access Control Manager:

- The Keycloak²⁰⁶ framework for identity and access management
- OpenID Connect
- OAuth 2.0
- SAML 2.0

For the Monitoring Services:

²⁰⁵ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

²⁰⁶ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prometheus²⁰⁷ for performance monitoring <p>Moreover, technologies such as Docker²⁰⁸ and Node.js²⁰⁹ for component containerisation and the deployment of the Distributed Data Storage across the ENACT continuum nodes will be utilised.</p> <p>The aforementioned technologies and frameworks utilise various programming languages, including Javascript, SQL and ODRL.</p>
	<p>Data Store Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the execution of CRUD operations • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Metadata Manager Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the execution of data/metadata write operations • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Security & Access Control Manager Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for handling the authentication and access requests, and forwarding of CRUD requests • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Monitoring Services Interfaces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Used for the execution of health logs read requests • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	Software – Containerisation approach will be used for the packaging and deployment of various components of ENACT Data Store/Space.
Authorisation Definition	Access granted based on predefined authentication/authorisation rules.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 66: Data Manager Component specification

5.7.1 Data Store module

Module Name	Data Store	Priority	Must
Description	Individual computing devices, servers, etc. that store and manage data in the distributed system (or in CCC)		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Stores residing in other Nodes • Metadata Manager 		

²⁰⁷ <https://prometheus.io/>

²⁰⁸ <https://www.docker.com/>

²⁰⁹ <https://nodejs.org/en>

Extracted Functions	
Success Criteria	Availability (to support data storage and retrieval), connection with other components

For the sake of comprehensibility, telemetry data and objects transfers are represented by bi-directional arrows. However, the exact workflow is as follows: For writing requests, assets are indexed to include metadata and then stored in data store(s). For authorised read requests, assets are filtered to be retrieved from the relevant data store(s) and then de-indexed before being returned to Data Access & Sharing Interfaces.

Table 67: Data Store module specification

Data Storage function

Function Name	Data Storage	Priority	Must
Description	Pertains to storing historical telemetry data, code objects as well as data/models for AI training.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Retrieval 		
Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stored data must be expressed as indicated by the ENACT CC models. Data stores distributed across different nodes should be synchronised. 		

Table 68: Data Storage functional specification

Data Retrieval function

Function Name	Data Retrieval	Priority	Must
Description	Returns requested data.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Storage 		
Success Criteria	Returned data must be expressed as indicated by the ENACT CC models.		

Table 69: Data Retrieval function specification

5.7.2 Metadata Manager module

Module Name	Metadata Manager	Priority	Must
Description	It provides indexing/de-indexing of data and filters stored metadata to retrieve matching data from the corresponding data store to satisfy read requests.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Store Security and Access Control Manager Data Access and Sharing Interfaces 		

Table 70: Metadata Manager module specification

Data Indexing function

Function Name	Data Indexing	Priority	Must
Description	It provides indexing of assets prior to storage, to include metadata information such as their location, attributes, access permissions, etc.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Storage • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces 		

Table 71: Data Indexing functional specification
Data Filtering function

Table 72: Data Filtering function specification
Data De-indexing function

Table 73: Data De-indexing functional specification

5.7.3 Security & Access Control module

Table 74: Security & Access Control module specification

Identity Verification function

Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces • Monitoring Services • Data Indexing • Data Filtering
Success Criteria	<p>Authentication mechanisms are in place.</p>

Table 75: Identity Verification functional specification

Access Control function

Function Name	Access Control	Priority	Should
Description	It supports the definition and enforcement of access control policies.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Access & Sharing Interfaces • Monitoring Services • Data Indexing • Data Filtering 		
Success Criteria	<p>Access is restricted to authorised parties.</p>		

Table 76: Access Control function specification

5.7.4 Monitoring Services module

Module Name	Monitoring Services	Priority	Nice to have
Description	Monitoring services to provide visibility over the distributed storage system's performance, health, and utilisation. Services will include logging, alerting, and diagnostic functionalities.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Security and Access Control Manager • Data Access and Sharing Interfaces 		

<p>Extracted Functions</p>	
<p>Success Criteria</p>	<p>Currently none.</p> <p>Health logs, alerts and diagnostics provided to applications.</p>

Table 77: Monitoring Services module specification

5.8 AI forecaster component

<p>Component Name Intro / Overview</p>	<p>AI Forecaster</p> <p>This tool harnesses the power of AI algorithms to efficiently forecast network data and detect potential anomalies in the CCC infrastructure.</p> <p>The component is composed of 3 modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Data analysis module is responsible for analysing and preprocess network data from the network environment. • The AI forecasting & Anomaly detection module is the core engine of the component, aiming to perform anomaly detection in the infrastructure and provide a forecast of the network based on application demands, security concerns and network changes to the GNN and DRL to obtain the optimised forecasted schedule. • The Data exchange module is responsible for handling the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster component.
<p>Extracted Modules</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data analysis module • AI forecasting & Anomaly detection module • Data exchange module
<p>Component Workflow</p>	<p>The following diagram illustrates the internal workflow and the communication between the modules.</p>

External Component Interaction

The figure below describes the component interactions with its connected components of the ENACT platform.

**Prototypical Mock-ups
TRL**

This component is operating as a backend component. No UIs are going to be created.

**Potential Use-cases
Layer**

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

**Technologies
Interfaces**

Applicable in all pilot scenarios
ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer
Python Programming Language, PyTorch, TensorFlow, FLASK REST API, FLASK webSockets

- **Overview:** Interface to exchange data with other components
- **Type:** REST/WebSockets
- **State:** Synchronous or asynchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Deployment Type	Either as a Docker container or K8S pod.
Authorisation	Authorisation will be implemented through SSL WebSocket's APIs
Definition	
Licence	Apache 2.0.

Table 78: AI Forecaster Component specification

5.8.1 Data Analysis module

Module Name	Data Analysis	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible for analysing and preprocess network data from the network environment.		
Interacts with	AI forecasting module		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ProcessData 		
Success Criteria	All module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria defined in unit tests.		

Table 79: Data Analysis module specification

ProcessData function

Function Name	ProcessData	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data from the external components namely: DRL, GNN, VTE and Graph Modeller and applies preprocessing based on the AI forecaster internal requirements.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GetData ProcessForecastInput ProcessAnomalyDetectionInput RunForecast RunAnomalyDetection 		
Success Criteria	Successfully process data and deliver them to the AI Forecasting & Anomaly Detection module of the AI Forecaster & Anomaly Detector component based on the defined unit tests.		

Table 80: ProcessData function specification

5.8.2 AI Forecasting & Anomaly detection module

Module Name	AI Forecasting & Anomaly detection	Priority	Must
Description	The module is the core engine of the component, aiming to provide the detected infrastructure anomalies and the forecasted network based on application demands, security concerns and network changes to the GNN and DRL to obtain the optimised forecasted schedule.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data analysis module Data exchange module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RunForecast ProcessForecastInput RunAnomalyDetection ProcessAnomalyDetectionInput 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 81: AI Forecaster module specification

RunForecast function

Function Name	RunForecast	Priority	Must
Description	This function is triggered to forecast the needs in telemetry data for a specific future time step.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process Data ProcessForecastInput SendData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 82: RunForecast function specification

ProcessForecastInput function

Function Name	ProcessInput	Priority	Should
Description	Obtain the data preprocessed by the processData function and deliver them to the runForecast function.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RunForecast ProcessData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 83: ProcessingInput function specification

RunAnomalyDetection function

Function Name	RunAnomalyDetection	Priority	Must
Description	This function is triggered to detect anomalies in the CCC infrastructure devices.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Process Data Process input SendData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 84: RunForecast function specification

ProcessAnomalyDetectionInput function

Function Name	ProcessInput	Priority	Should
Description	Obtain the data preprocessed by the processData function and deliver them to the runAnomalyDetection function.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> RunAnomalyDetection ProcessData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

5.8.3 Data Exchange module

Module Name	Data Exchange	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible for handling the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster component.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DRL Graph Modeller GNN VTE 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GetData 		

Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SendData All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.
-------------------------	---

Table 85: Data Exchange module specification

GetData function

Function Name	GetData	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data from the external components and moves them to the ProcessData function.		
Interacts with	ProcessData		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 86: GetData function specification

SendData function

Function Name	SendData	Priority	Must
Description	This function delivers the output of the RunForecast and RunAnomalyDetection function to the external components.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RunForecast • RunAnomalyDetection 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 87: SendData function specification

5.9 Deep Reinforced Learning (DRL) Agent component

Component Name	Deep Reinforcement Learning Agent
Intro / Overview	This component harnesses the power of AI Reinforcement learning to efficiently optimise the placement of application demands within the network infrastructure. The component is composed of 3 modules: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Data analysis module is responsible to analyse and preprocess network data from the network environment. • The AI scheduling module is the core engine of the component, aiming to explore/exploit the environment and trigger the GNN component to obtain the Q-value (best assignment of an application to a computing node). • The Data exchange module is responsible to handle the data throughput from/to the DRL agent component.
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Analysis module • AI Scheduling module • Data Exchange module
Component Workflow	The following diagram illustrates the internal workflow and the communication between the modules.

External Component Interaction

Prototypical Mock-ups

TRL

Potential Use-cases

Layer

Technologies

Interfaces

Deployment Type

Authorisation

Definition

Licence

The figure below describes the component interactions with its connected components of the ENACT platform.

This component is operating as a backend component. No UIs are going to be created.

Current: TRL-2
Expected: TRL-5

Applicable in all pilot scenarios
ENACT Cognitive Computing Orchestration Layer

Python Programming Language, PyTorch, TensorFlow, FLASK REST API, FLASK webSockets

- **Overview:** Interface to exchange data with other components
- **Type:** REST/WebSockets
- **State:** Synchronous or asynchronous
- **Data Format:** JSON

Either as a Docker container or K8S pod.

Authorisation will be implemented through SSL WebSocket's APIs.

Apache 2.0

Table 88: Deep Reinforced Learning Component specification

5.9.1 Data Analysis module

Module Name	Data Analysis	Priority	Must
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Description	The module is responsible to analyse and preprocess network data from the network environment.
Interacts with	AI Scheduler
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProcessData
Success Criteria	All module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria

Table 89: Data Analysis module specification

ProcessData function

Function Name	ProcessData	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data process them and forwards them to the AI scheduling module.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RunOptim • ProcessInput • GetData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 90: ProcessData function specification

5.9.2 AI Scheduler module

Module Name	AI Scheduler	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible to observe the environment states either with exploration or exploitation and based on a selected action, provide to GNN the state to obtain the Q-Value. The Q-value corresponds to the computation node in which an application shall be assigned.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Analysis module • Data Exchange module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RunOptim • ProcessInput 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 91: AI Scheduler module specification

RunOptim function

Function Name	RunOptim	Priority	Must
Description	This function executes the RL agent to calculate the optimal schedule		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProcessInput • SendData • ProcessData 		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 92: RunOptim function specification

ProcessInput function

Function Name	ProcessingInput	Priority	Should
Description	This function takes the preprocessed data and forwards them to the RunOptim function.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProcessData • RunOptim 		

Success Criteria	Describes the minimal criteria, which the implementation should fulfil, related to the requirements of D2.5.
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Table 93: ProcessInput function specification

5.9.3 Data Exchange module

Module Name	Data Exchange	Priority	Must
Description	The module is responsible to handle the data throughput from/to the AI Forecaster, Application Controller, Dynamic Graph Modeller, and Security Risk Modeller components.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • AI Forecaster • Application Controller • Dynamic Graph Modeller • Security Risk Modeller 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GetData • SendData 		
Success Criteria	All Module functions have been evaluated to be successful from their success criteria.		

Table 94: Data Exchange module specification

GetData function

Function Name	GetData.	Priority	Must
Description	This function obtains the data from the external components and moves them to the ProcessData function.		
Interacts with	ProcessData		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 95: GetData function specification

SendData function

Function Name	SendData	Priority	Must
Description	This function delivers the output of the RunForecast function to the external components.		
Interacts with	RunForecast		
Success Criteria	Pass the unit tests defined for this function.		

Table 96: SendData function specification

5.10 Orchestrator component

Component Name	Orchestrator
Intro / Overview	<p>The Orchestrator component is responsible for executing the deployment orders requested by the Application Controller, that will give direct instructions about which mapping should be enforced between applications and clusters resources (Deployment Plans). These deployment plans are provided by the AI Layer (DRL) to the Application Controller. A best-effort approach will be performed to satisfy the mapping with the nodes and resources available. If a mapping cannot be satisfied due to unavailability of resources, then new deployment plans will be requested from the Application Controller.</p> <p>The Orchestrator will be able to perform deployments over a heterogeneous range of nodes in the edge-cloud continuum, abstracting the technological details related to the deployment.</p> <p>The Orchestrator main functions are:</p>

Extracted Modules
Component
Workflow

- Receiving deployment plans from the Application Controller component and converting these instructions to be executed by the Orchestrator.
- Handle requests from the Application Controller including rescheduling plans or stopping/disabling pods.
- Request new deployment plans if needed.
- Request the ZTP to create new nodes and onboard them in the cluster.

N/A

Inside the Orchestrator component, the flow of information should be as follows:

<p>External Component Interaction</p>	
<p>Prototypical Mock-ups</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>TRL</p>	<p>Current: TRL-4 Expected: TRL-6</p>
<p>Potential Use-cases Layer</p>	<p>Applicable in all pilot scenarios</p>
<p>Technologies</p>	<p>ENACT Orchestration Layer</p> <p>The Orchestrator component is composed by the following technologies:</p> <p>Programming Languages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Go • JavaScript <p>Frameworks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kubernetes: Automation of deployment, auto scaling and management of containerised applications. • Docker: Build applications and run them in multiple containers, with a shared image. • KubeEdge: Extends orchestration and deployment capabilities to the edge.
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>ZTP Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Interface to exchange device information and configurations between Orchestrator and ZTP component • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Application Controller Interface:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Interface to receive optimisation requests/deployment feedback from the Application Controller • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type	Docker Containers (The Orchestrator in its own pod will run alongside the other containers).
Authorisation Definition	To send information and to request data from the Orchestrator, the other components must be authenticated prior to the operation and be authorised to handle these.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 97: Orchestrator component specification

Application Controller Handler function

Description	Application Controller Handler	Priority	Must
Interacts with	This function handles the requests/feedback that deployed Application Controllers send to the Orchestrator. Those requests may include moving application components to other cluster nodes (e.g., to reduce communication delays or due to node performance degradation), requesting more resources or asking the Orchestrator to activate/deactivate specific application components that are not being used (e.g., to optimise energy consumption). After the request from an Application Controller is analysed, an internal request is sent to the Deployment Plan Handler to ask for changes in the deployment to the Application Components.		
Success Criteria	The Application Controller Handler should be able to collect incoming requests from an Application Controller and redirect them to the Deployment Plan Handler for execution of the orders.		

```

graph TD
    AC[Application Controller] -- "Request/Response feedback on Application Actions" --> ACH[Application Controller Handler]
    ACH -- "Deployment / Redeployment Requests" --> DPH[Deployment Plan Handler]
    
```

Table 98: Application Controller Handler function specification

Deployment Plan Handler function

Function Name	Deployment Plan Handler	Priority	Must
Description	The Deployment Plan Handler (DPH) function will receive deployment information and change requests from the Application Controller Handler. When deployment plans are received from the Application Controller Handler, they are validated and transformed, generating deployment descriptions aligned with the technologies used/understood by the cluster. Those deployment descriptions may be autocompleted with deployment-specific information, required for a more precise deployment instruction. The processed data is then sent to the scheduler, ready for execution.		

Interacts with	<p>Requests to update Application deployments originated from the Application Controller Handler are also processed in this function. Based on the information received, the Orchestrator adjusts the implementation of the deployment plans.</p>
	<pre> graph TD ZTP[ZTP Handler] -- Resource Description --> DPH[Deployment Plan Handler] App[Application Controller Handler] -- Deployment / Redeployment Requests --> DPH Scheduler -- Scheduler Ready Information --> DPH Scheduler -- Scheduler Ready Information --> Scheduler style DPH stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>
Success Criteria	<p>The DPH is able to generate valid deployment descriptions based on the Optimal Deployment Plan received from the Application Controller.</p>

Table 99: Deployment Plan Handler function specification

ZTP Handler function

Function Name	ZTP Handler	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The ZTP Handler provides the interface between the ZTP and the Orchestrator and manages requests to the ZTP to create new nodes and join them in the cluster. When more resources are needed, the ZTP Handler will send a request to the ZTP, asking for a new node to be created or an existing node to be onboarded in the current cluster. The ZTP Handler will also provide the ZTP with the required configuration and credentials for nodes to join an existing cluster.</p>		
Interacts with	<pre> graph LR ZTP -- Resource descriptions / configurations --> ZTH[ZTP Handler] ZTH -- Resource Description --> DPH[Deployment Plan Handler] style ZTH stroke:#f00,stroke-width:2px </pre>		
Success Criteria	<p>The ZTP Handler function should be able to communicate with the ZTP Service to create new nodes and add them to the cluster.</p>		

Table 100: ZTP Handler function specification

Scheduler function

Function Name	Scheduler	Priority	Must
Description	<p>The Scheduler function provides the interface between the Orchestrator and the Cluster, with the role of executing the received deployment orders. As such, the Scheduler will handle the details of the used technology to support the deployment of applications in the Edge-Cloud Continuum and capable of deploying application on heterogeneous systems over multiple clusters.</p>		
Interacts with	<pre> graph TD Cluster([Cluster]) DS[Deployment Specification] Scheduler[Scheduler] SRIS[Scheduler Ready Information] DPH[Deployment Plan Handler] DS --> Cluster Scheduler --> DS DPH --> SRIS SRIS --> Scheduler </pre> <p>The diagram illustrates the Scheduler's interactions. At the top is an oval labeled 'Cluster'. Below it is a box labeled 'Deployment Specification' with an arrow pointing up to the Cluster. Below that is a box labeled 'Scheduler' with an arrow pointing up to the 'Deployment Specification' box. To the right of the Scheduler is a box labeled 'Scheduler Ready Information' with an arrow pointing left to the Scheduler. Below 'Scheduler Ready Information' is a box labeled 'Deployment Plan Handler' with an arrow pointing up to 'Scheduler Ready Information'. The Scheduler box is circled in red.</p>		
Success Criteria	<p>The Scheduler should be able to handle deployment descriptions, execute them and keep this type of deployment as close as possible to the desired state, considering resource availability, heterogeneity of nodes and application requirements.</p>		

Table 101: Scheduler function specification

5.11 AI Act Compliance Checker component

Component Name	AI Act Compliance Checker
Intro / Overview	<p>With the introduction of the AI Act, it is important for solution developers to ensure compliance with these acts to avoid potential legal problems and financial repercussions.</p> <p>The AI Act Compliance Checker component is responsible for executing automatic check of the developed application against the AI Act provisions (and potentially other relevant legislation/policies). It will use meta information provided by the application as well as user manuals, descriptions and other relevant documents to, for example, categorise the application (from the AI Act perspective), assess the completeness and the quality of the provided documentation, together with recommendations on the required changes.</p> <p>AI Act Compliance Checker component consists of two modules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Compliance Logic represents the main method, checking compliance of the solution with the AI Act, leveraging data submitted by the application and the Knowledge base. The module should receive information about the data planned

to be used by the application, together with the relevant meta data, and provide assessment from the compliance with the AI Act perspective.

- The AI Act Knowledge base in the form of AI model/LLM and supporting RAG features, trained for analysis of the AI Act. The module has to be able to provide/generate answers to questions about the AI act, to assess compliance of an application and, potentially, provide suggestions on how to fix potential issues.

Further, through the interaction with the Application Controller module, the AI Act Compliance Checker component will obtain access to the representative data used for training the AI model to assess it from the AI Act perspective as well as make it available in the AI training data sets data space.

Extracted Modules

- ComplianceLogic
- AIAct Knowledge Base

Component Workflow

External Component Interaction

Prototypical Mock-ups

N/A

TRL

TRL1 – TRL4

Potential Use-cases Layer

Applicable in all pilot scenarios and main platform developments.

ENACT Application Development Layer

Technologies	<p>Programming Languages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • C#/.NET • Python <p>Services:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Azure OpenAI: A cloud service that provides access to OpenAI's powerful language models for various applications, such as text generation, translation, and code completion. • Azure AI Search: A cloud search service that enables developers to easily add scalable search capabilities to their applications. • Azure Blob Storage: A cloud object storage solution for storing large amounts of unstructured data, such as text or binary data. • Azure Prompt Flow: A development tool for building, testing, and deploying large language model (LLM) applications with customizable workflows and prompt engineering. <p>Libraries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NumPy: A library for the Python programming language, adding support for large, multi-dimensional arrays and matrices, along with a large collection of high-level mathematical functions to operate on these arrays. • SciPy: A library for scientific and technical computing. • Pandas: An open-source data analysis and manipulation tool. • Scikit-learn: An opensource library for Machine Learning
Interfaces	<p>Score API Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This API accepts content information (metadata, content, additional details) as input and returns a determination of whether the content aligns with the AI Act requirements. • Update knowledge database - This API recreates a knowledge base based on newly uploaded documents. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON <p>Update knowledge database Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: This API recreates a knowledge database based on newly uploaded documents. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	Dockerised software modules with defined APIs for consumption of provided services. Expected to have two distinct docker containers, one for the logic and another for the knowledge base/AI/LLM model.
Authorisation Definition	TBD. Open-source being considered.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 102: AI Act Compliance Checker Component specification

5.11.1 ComplianceLogic module

Module Name	ComplianceLogic	Priority	Must
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Description	The main method, checking compliance of the solution with the AI Act, leveraging data submitted by the application and the Knowledge base.
Interacts with	Application Controller
Extracted Functions	TBD
Success Criteria	The module should receive information about the data planned to be used by the application, together with the relevant metadata, and provide an assessment of compliance with the AI Act perspective.

Table 103: ComplianceLogic module specification

ComplianceLogicScore function

Function Name	ComplianceLogicScore	Priority	Must
Description	This API will accept content information (metadata, content, additional details) as input and return a decision on whether and to what extent the content complies with the requirements of the AI Act.		
Interacts with	Application Controller		
Success Criteria	The ability to successfully determine the compliance of input data with the AI Act.		

Table 104: AI ComplianceLogicScore function specification

5.11.2 AIActKnowledgeBase module

Module Name	AIActKnowledgeBase	Priority	Must
Description	The AIActKnowledge base in the form of AI model/LLM and supporting RAG features, trained for analysis of the AI Act.		
Interacts with	ComplianceLogic		
Extracted Functions	AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate		
Success Criteria	The module should receive information about the data planned to be used by the application, together with the relevant metadata, and provide assessment from the compliance with the AI Act perspective.		

Table 105: AIActKnowledgeBase module specification

AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate function

Function Name	AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate	Priority	Must
Description	This REST API function will recreate a knowledge database based on newly uploaded documents. The database is initially created with an initial set of documents		
Interacts with	ComplianceLogic		
Success Criteria	The ability to successfully update local knowledge database		

Table 106: AIActKnowledgeBaseUpdate function specification

5.12 Application Programming Model (APM) component

Component Name	Application Programming Model
Intro / Overview	The APM is a framework comprising languages, libraries, and tools designed to build applications and services with characteristics such as dynamism, adaptation, elasticity, load balancing, replication, portability, identification, secure communication, self-registering, etc. APM abstracts these complexities, providing a set of APIs, high-level objects, and concepts for developers to create and manage distributed applications efficiently.

Extracted Modules

- APM Data Services
- APM Dynamic Querying Layer
- APM Abstraction Layer

Component Workflow

APM Data Services offers CRUD operations through APIs for communication with data sources.

APM Dynamic Querying Layer supports querying language functionalities for dynamic data interactions.

APM Abstraction Layer provides high-level objects and concepts to simplify application development.

External Component Interaction

Should provide / implement functions for all ENACT components to ensure any scenario. Example:

Prototypical Mock-ups

CRUD operation editor:

TRL Potential Use-cases Layer Technologies Interfaces Deployment Type Authorisation Definition Licence	<p>The diagram illustrates the APM component architecture. On the left, a vertical container labeled 'Assets' contains three entries: 'Asset 1', 'Asset 2', and 'Asset 3'. To the right, a larger rounded rectangle is divided into two sections. The top section is labeled 'Query Script' and contains the text 'Dynamic Querying operation'. The bottom section is labeled 'Output'.</p>
	<p>Data Services Interface: Interface to access CRUD operations and dynamic querying.</p> <p>Abstraction Layer Interface: High-level coding interface for developers.</p>
	<p>Expected: TRL-5</p>
	<p>Applicable to all Use Cases.</p>
	<p>App Development Layer</p>
	<p>Programming Languages: Python, Java</p> <p>Security: HTTPS/TLS, Oauth 2.0, JWT, mTLS, AWS KMS</p>
	<p>Code implementation of individual APM Component Java/Python objects, according to documentation/guidelines, following active conventions. Code is created directly by end user or by SDK.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software as a Service (SaaS) • Docker Containers
	<p>Authentication and authorisation are managed through the ENACT Security and User Management system (GUI part). Access control policies can be defined to restrict or allow access to specific models and data pipelines.</p> <p>APM Jars use HTTPS/TLS, Oauth 2.0, JWT, mTLS, AWS KMS to ensure secured, exclusive and authorised access.</p>
	<p>Apache 2.0</p>

Table 107: APM component specification

5.12.1 APM Data Service module

Module Name	APM Data Service	Priority	Must
Description	The APM Data Services module will provide the functions to interact with the Data Layer.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Layer • SDK 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-level APIs • List of available data sources 		

Success Criteria	Performance Indicators are registered, and Events are generated based on indicator violations.
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Table 108: APM Data Service module specification

High-level function

Function Name	High-Level APIs	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary abstraction for interacting with different types of data sources easily and intuitively.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Layer SDK 		
Success Criteria	The function success criteria are provided by the ability to interact with multiple data sources intuitively.		

Table 109: High-level function specification

List of Available Data Sources function

Function Name	List of Available Data Sources	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide a list of all available data sources that are connected at a given time as well as one for what types of data sources can be connected.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources 		
Success Criteria	The ability to provide the list of available connected data sources, as well as the one for available types of data sources, that can be connected.		

Table 110: List of Available Data Sources function specification

5.12.2 APM Dynamic Querying Layer module

Module Name	APM Dynamic Querying Layer	Priority	Must
Description	The APM Dynamic Querying Language module will provide the functions to query and interact with data sources.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CRUD Specification 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below.		

Table 111: APM Dynamic Querying Layer module specification

CRUD Specification function

Function Name	CRUD Specification	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary specification on what should be given to each of the four operations in CRUD so it can function as expected, and be able to interact with the data sources.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data Sources 		
Success Criteria	The ability to specify a complete and comprehensive specification of each of the four CRUD operations.		

Table 112: CRUD Specification function specification

5.12.3 APM Abstraction Layer module

Module Name	APM Abstraction Layer	Priority	Must
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Description	The APM Abstraction Layer will provide the capability to communicate with various data sources and display a common interface for interacting with all the available data sources and/or with the AI layer.
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Sources • SDK • AI Layer
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connector • Markup UI
Success Criteria	The ability to be able to connect and communicate with a specific data source.

Table 113: Abstraction Layer module specification

Connector function

Function Name	Connector	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the connection to a specific data source. For each data source, a connector will need to be specified.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Sources 		
Success Criteria	The ability to be able to connect and communicate with a specific data source.		

Table 114: Connector function specification

Markup UI function

Function Name	Markup UI	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide a UI that only contains the high-level components necessary for interacting with the connectors and the data sources.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Connector 		
Success Criteria	The ability to be easily interacted with and to communicate successfully with the connectors.		

Table 115: Markup UI function specification

5.13 Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME) component

Component Name	Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine
Intro / Overview	The TDCME component is a set of software agents and tools utilised to monitor multi-mode virtualised infrastructures. It aggregates real-time data from distributed nodes deployed at each site and monitors applications Quality indicators and Policies as specified by administrators and users.
Extracted Modules	<p>Policy Monitoring: Policy Module is responsible for monitoring distributed Applications and ensure Policies, as defined by the user/administrator, are not violated.</p> <p>Quality Monitoring: collects infrastructure and application metrics, preprocesses them and distributes them to other authorised entities.</p> <p>Log Exporter: offers infrastructure logs to other components</p> <p>Query Engine: performs intelligent queries on distributed data nodes.</p> <p>Alert module: produces alerts based on policy violations of infrastructure events.</p>

Component Workflow

External Component Interaction

Orchestration Layer: provides metrics, push events.
 Data Layer: forwards data and events for permanent storage or sharing with third-party applications or services.
 Modelling Layer: provides metrics and events to the Graph Modeller.

Prototypical Mock-ups

TRL

Current TRL: 2
 Expected TRL: 5

Potential Use-cases Layer

All ENACT UCs
 Orchestration Layer

Technologies Interfaces

Prometheus, Kubernetes, Cilium, Golang, Python

Quality Monitoring Interface:

- Overview: exposes methods to register/delete/retrieve quality indicators and their values
- Type: REST
- State: Synchronous
- Data Format: JSON

Deployment Type Authorisation Definition Licence	Policy Monitoring Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: exposes methods to register/delete/retrieve policies monitored • Type: REST • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON Alert Monitoring Interface: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: exposes methods to export alerts to other components • Type: REST • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Helm chart (software)
	None
	Apache 2.0

Table 116: Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine component specification

5.13.1 Quality Monitoring module

Module Name	Quality Monitoring	Priority	Must
Description	The Quality Monitoring module is responsible for monitoring infrastructure logs and produce events when certain Performance Indicators violate threshold values as defined by the user.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alert module • Query Engine 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register Quality Indicator • Calculate Quality Indicator • Retrieve Quality Indicator • Remove Quality Indicator 		
Success Criteria	Performance Indicators are registered, and Events are generated based on indicator violations.		

Table 117: Quality Monitoring module specification

Register Quality Indicator function

Function Name	Register Quality Indicator	Priority	Nice to have
Description	Provides an API to register a quality indicator for monitoring a distributed application.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	The quality indicator is registered, and alerts are produced successfully.		

Table 118: Register Quality Indicator function specification

Calculate Quality Indicator function

Function Name	Calculate Quality Indicator	Priority	Must
Description	Calculates a quality indicator based on infrastructure metrics.		
Interacts with	This is an internal function.		
Success Criteria	A valid computed value is calculated and temporarily stored.		

Table 119: Calculate Quality Indicator function specification

Retrieve Quality Indicator function

Function Name	Retrieve Quality Indicator	Priority	Must
Description	Returns a list of quality indicators registered or a specific quality indicator value.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	The value is retrieved and successfully pulled by the Alert module to produce an alert.		

Table 120: Retrieve Quality Indicator function specification

Remove Policy function

Function Name	Remove Policy Function	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Removes a policy and no longer monitors if violated.		
Interacts with	Alert Module		
Success Criteria	An enforced policy successfully removed and is no longer monitored.		

Table 121: Remove Policy function specification

5.13.2 Policy Monitoring module

Module Name	Policy Monitoring	Priority	Must
Description	The Policy Monitoring module is responsible for monitoring infrastructure logs and generating events when violation of system or user-defined policies are attempted.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alert module Query Engine 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Register Policy Retrieve Policy 		
Success Criteria	Policies to be monitored are registered and events are generated when a violation is attempted.		

Table 122: Policy Monitoring module specification

Register Policy function

Function Name	Register Policy	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Registers a policy to monitor		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	An enforced policy successfully registered and monitored.		

Table 123: Register Policy function specification

Retrieve Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Policy	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Retrieves a list of monitored policies for a given distributed application.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	Return a list of monitored polices and counters of violation attempts.		

Table 124: Retrieve Policy function specification

Remove Policy function

Function Name	Remove Policy	Priority	Nice to Have
Description	Removes a policy and no longer monitors if violated		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Success Criteria	An enforced policy successfully removed and is no longer monitored.		

Table 125: Remove Policy function specification

5.13.3 Log Exporter module

Module Name	Log Exporter	Priority	Nice to have
Description	The Log exporter offers raw infrastructure logs to other components.		
Interacts with	Alert module		
Extracted Functions	Forward Logs		
Success Criteria	Logs are delivered to registered applications.		

Table 126: Log Exporter module specification

Forward Logs function

Function Name	Forward Logs Function	Priority	Must
Description	Forwards infrastructure logs to registered services/components.		
Interacts with	Forwards an alert to registered components		
Success Criteria	Alerts are successfully delivered to registered services.		

Table 127: Forward Logs function specification

5.13.4 Query Engine module

Module Name	Query Engine	Priority	Must
Description	The Query Engine is responsible for forming queries related to infrastructure metrics and events and returning results efficiently, ensuring fast and accurate data access for other modules.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Monitoring module Policy Monitoring module Log Exporter 		
Extracted Functions	N/A		
Success Criteria	Queries are executed in a distributed manner.		

Table 128: Query Engine module specification

5.13.5 Alert module

Module Name	Alert	Priority	Must
Description	Exposes an API to other components for registering Policies, Quality Indicators and forwards alerts on these components.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Monitoring module Policy Monitoring module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Push alert 		
Success Criteria	Alerts are generated and delivered to registered Applications.		

Table 129: Alert module specification

Push Alert function

Function Name	Push alert	Priority	Must
Description	Forwards alerts to other components		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Quality Monitoring module 		

Success Criteria	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy Monitoring module <p>An alert is successfully delivered to registered components.</p>
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Table 130: Push alert function specification

5.14 Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) component

Component Name Intro / Overview	<p>The Zero-Touch Provisioning Service</p> <p>The ZTP Service automates the provisioning and configuration of edge devices, either bare metal or virtual machines, ensuring they are securely onboarded to the network and managed without manual intervention. The ZTP service is split in ZTP agents which will manage a particular remote network and the ZTP server which is the central point and will communicate with all the agents (clients).</p>
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZTP server: The central ZTP sever that aggregates the agents deployed remotely. ZTP agent: The agent that will be deployed on a remote network and will contain all the necessary things to be self-sustainable.

The following diagram presents the interaction between the central ZTP server and the ZTP agents and the connection with the Orchestrator component:

External Component Interaction

Prototypical Mock-ups

TRL

Potential Use-cases Layer

Technologies

Interfaces

- Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine: Provides data for monitoring device health and performance.
- Orchestrator: Coordinates provisioning tasks and schedules updates.

N/A

TRL-4

- ALL ENACT UCs.

ENACT Orchestration Layer

- Programming Languages:
- Python
 - Go
 - Java
- Frameworks
- Websockets
 - REST API
- Libraries:
- OpenSSL
 - websockets
 - net/http
- Tools:
- Ubuntu MAAS
 - K8s

- ZTP Agent Authentication Endpoint:
- Overview: Authenticates a ZTP agent through the ZTP server.
 - Type: WebSocket
 - State: Async
 - Data Format: JSON
- Machine Discovery Endpoint:
- Overview: Detects and lists new devices.
 - Type: REST API
 - State: Asynchronous
 - Data Format: JSON

	Machine Deployment Endpoint: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Deploys new devices. • Type: REST API • State: Asynchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Agent discovery Endpoint: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Detects and lists all available agents connected to the central ZTP server. • Type: REST API • State: Asynchronous • Data Format: JSON
Deployment Type	On-Premises
Authorisation	Requires authentication through the ENACT Security and User Management system.
Definition	Elevated user authorisation needed.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 131: Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP) Service specification

5.14.1 ZTP Central Server module

Module Name	ZTP Central Server	Priority	Must
Description	This is the central ZTP Server that will aggregate all the ZTP Agents that are connected to it and interact with them.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orchestrator • ZTP Agents 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authentication of a ZTP Agent • Agent Discovery • Devices Deployment and Configuration 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria is for each particular function to be executed correctly and produce the right response.		

Table 132: ZTP Central Server module specification

Authentication of a ZTP Agent function

Function Name	Authentication of a ZTP Agent	Priority	Must
Description	This function is a WebSocket that will be called by the installer script and needs to register the Agent in a database in order to be recognised when the Agent will connect to the central server.		
Interacts with	ZTP Agent		
Success Criteria	The success criteria for this function will be to successfully authenticated a ZTP agent and store it in the database.		

Table 133: Authentication of a ZTP Agent function specification

Agent Discovery function

Function Name	Agent Discovery	Priority	Must
Description	This will be a REST API endpoint that will retrieve all the Agents that are connected to the central ZTP server and show them to the Orchestrator.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ZTP Agents • Orchestrator 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria is to successfully retrieve all the Agents connected, and present that information to the Orchestrator when asked.		

Table 134: Agent Discovery function specification

Devices deployment and configuration function

Function Name	Devices deployment and configuration	Priority	Must
Description	This will be a REST API endpoint that will be called by the Orchestrator when wanting to deploy a Device connected to a ZTP Agent.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orchestrator ZTP Agent 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria is to successfully interact with a machine from a particular ZTP Agent in order to configure and deploy a machine from a remote network.		

Table 135: Devices deployment and configuration function specification

5.14.2 ZTP Agent

Module Name	ZTP Manager for K8 Clusters Module	Priority	Must
Description	This is the ZTP Agent that will be deployed through a script on a remote network and connect to the central ZTP server.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZTP server Ubuntu MAAS K8s 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Installer/Uninstaller scripts ZTP server K8s main cluster 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria is for each particular function to be executed correctly and produce the right response.		

Table 136: ZTP Agent module specification

Installer/Uninstaller scripts function

Function Name	Installer/Uninstaller scripts	Priority	Must
Description	This will be comprise of two scripts that deploys all the contents of the ZTP agent and authenticate with the main ZTP server.		
Interacts with	ZTP Server		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of this function is to successfully deploy the ZTP Agent and to authenticate against the central ZTP server.		

Table 137: Installer/Uninstaller scripts function specification

Ubuntu MAAS Shell function

Function Name	Ubuntu MAAS Shell	Priority	Must
Description	This will be a Shell like application that will connect to the ZTP server and lets the Orchestrator interact with remote machines and networks.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ZTP Server Orchestrator through ZTP server 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of this function will be to successfully connect to Ubuntu MAAS and to the central ZTP server, and deploy machines with a particular configuration on remote networks.		

Table 138: Ubuntu MAAS Shell function specification

K8s main cluster function

Function Name	K8s main cluster	Priority	Must
Description	This will be deployed through the Installer/Uninstaller scripts and will be a main K8s node that will connect to a principal K8s node inside the ENACT CCC. To this cluster, all the cluster nodes from a particular network will be connected.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Orchestrator Telemetry Data Collector and Monitoring Engine 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria is to successfully connect to the main K8s node, and to interact with the work nodes that will be connected to it when a machine will be deployed.		

Table 139: K8s main cluster function specification

5.15 Security Risk Modeller (SRM) component

Component Name	Security Risk Modeller (SRM)
Intro / Overview	<p>SRM performs security risk analysis on the system model which represents the structural and functional aspects of the applications and infrastructure of the ENACT. It also includes various processing components and their interconnections. Physical objects (such as data, databases, processes, servers, etc.) are represented as nodes in the system model which are termed as assets. The interaction between these assets is referred to as connections.</p> <p>SRM will provide control strategies to lower the security risk. The controls may include authentication mechanisms, encryption algorithms, access controls, intrusion detection/prevention systems, and secure coding practices. With respect to network-related actions, Kubernetes-compliant network policies will be generated that partially or fully mitigate these risks, offering developers an easy-to-use and automated procedure to secure their cloud-native applications.</p>
Extracted Modules	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Interface System Model (SM) Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) Network Security Policies (NetSecPol)
Component Workflow	<p>To illustrate the component workflow that takes place within the Security Risk Modeller, diagrams reflecting the interaction and workflow between components can be seen below.</p>
External Component Interaction	<p>Interaction with the external component is performed through the DRL+GNN, which provide optimal deployment configuration in graph data. This graph data is processed by SRM which auto-generates system models to perform risk analysis. The outcomes of risk</p>

assessment are visualised in the Graph Modeller and also used by DRL+GNN component to provide updated deployment schedules based on the risk and compliance standards. The outcomes of the SRM will be displayed in the Graph Modeller GUI.

Prototypical Mock-ups

Login Page: This is the first page which appears to the user to get access to the SRM tool. The sign-in credentials are managed via Keycloak.

Home Page: Home page provides the modelling environment where a user can create a system model by dragging and dropping of different asset. Users can also select the connection type between assets, as there can be more than one connection available. The controls are generated once the system model is completed and risk analysis is performed.

TRL	Current: TRL-3 Expected: TRL-6
Potential Use-cases	Applicable in all pilot scenarios
Layer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENACT Modelling Layer
Technologies	<p>Programming Languages:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Java Typescript SPARQL Python <p>Frameworks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Docker AngularJS Node.js Gradle <p>Libraries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nginx proxy server Tomcat Server MongoDB JenaDB Keycloak
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> iframe
Deployment Type	Software Docker container
Authorisation Definition	Keycloak Open-source Identity and Access Management
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 140: Security Risk Modeller (SRM) Component specification

5.15.1 Interface module

Module Name	Interface	Priority	Should
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Description	Interface provides the frontend modelling environment and access to the SRM interface via Keycloak.
Interacts with Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Web UI • KeyCloak • Mongo DB
Success Criteria	The interface should provide access to the modelling environment.

Table 141: Interface module specification

Web UI function

Function Name	Web UI	Priority	Must
Description	The Web UI provides the Graphical User Interface for the modelling environment.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	Web UI should provide a user-friendly access to the SRM.		

Table 142: Web UI function specification

Keycloak function

Function Name	Keycloak	Priority	Must
Description	Keycloak manages the user access to the SRM tool by allowing single sign-on with identity and access management.		
Interacts with			

Success Criteria Keycloak prevents unauthorised access to the SRM interface.

Table 143: Keycloak function specification

MongoDB function

Function Name	MongoDB	Priority	Must
Description	MongoDB stores authorisation data (access rights of the users) and model metadata (last edit data, last user logged in, etc.).		
Interacts with	<p>The diagram illustrates the Security Risk Modeller (SRM) architecture. It is divided into an Interface and a System Model. The Interface includes a Web UI, Keycloak Authentication data, and a MongoDB database (circled in red). The System Model is further divided into Data Transformation and System Model Development. Data Transformation involves DRL+GNN, Graph Data, Data Transformation, and Transformed Data. System Model Development includes Jena DB (Knowledgebase and System Model Details), Threat and Risk Modelling, and OWASP GDPR ISO27005. The System Model Development outputs a Risk Treatment Plan, which is then processed by an NSP Generator to produce Network Security Policies.</p>		
Success Criteria	MongoDB maintains data about model metadata.		

Table 144: MongoDB function specification

5.15.2 System Model module

Module Name	System Model (SM)	Priority	Must
Description	SM represented the assets and their relationships. This is developed from the optimal deployment configuration received from DRL+GNN. SM is analysed through SRM for possible attack paths.		
Interacts with	SM interacts with RTP		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Transformation • System Model Development 		
Success Criteria	SM correct mapping to the devices and processes of ENACT deployment configuration.		

Table 145: System Model module specification

Data Transformation function

Function Name	Data Transformation	Priority	Must
Description	This Data Transformation will be a wrapper which performs the conversion of nodes and edge information from the DRL+GNN into acceptable format for the SRM. The SRM stores and processes the system models in N-Quads (nq) format. System model details are taken from JenaDB which are needed for the correct transformation of nodes information to asset types in the SRM.		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	<p>The Data transformation should process graph data and generate nq file format for system model development module.</p>

Table 146: Data Transformation function specification

System Model Development function

Function Name	System Model Development	Priority	Must
Description	<p>System Model Development is performed based on the transformed data using JenaDB. This step is performed using system asset information from JenaDB.</p>		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	<p>The system model development function should auto-generate the system model for risk analysis in the SRM tool.</p>		

Table 147: System Model Development function specification

5.15.3 Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) module

Module Name	Risk Treatment Plan	Priority	Must
Description	<p>Threats and controls (i.e., security measures); may include authentication mechanisms, encryption algorithms, access controls, intrusion detection/prevention systems.</p>		
Interacts with	System Model		
Extracted Functions	Risk Mitigation Strategies		
Success Criteria	Overall risk to the system is reduced.		

Table 148: Risk Treatment Plan (RTP) module specification

Risk Mitigation Strategies function

Function Name	Risk Mitigation Strategies	Priority	Must
Description	Risk Mitigation Strategies are computed based on the risk of every security threat in the system. Threat and risk modelling is carried out on the system models and is checked for GDPR and OWASP based on ISO 27005 risk assessment procedure already defined in the knowledge base.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	Overall risk to the system is reduced.		

Table 149: Risk Mitigation Strategies function specification

5.15.4 Network Security Policies module

Module Name	Network Security Policies	Priority	Must
Description	Network Security Policies (NetSecPols) translates network-related SRM Action to Cilium Network Policies, thus mitigating these risks at application runtime. Additionally, NetSecPols offers an API for administrators to generate Cilium Network policies in a simple manner, without the need for advanced knowledge of computer networks.		
Interacts with	NetSecPols interacts with Risk Treatment Plan		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce Network Policy • Receive SRM Actions 		
Success Criteria	A list of Cilium Network Policies is returned		

Table 150: Network Security Policies module specification

Produce Network Policy function

Function Name	Produce Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	The administrator can use the API to generate Cilium Network Policies that performed pilot concerning the live streaming and automatic analysis of predefined functions. This aims to provide an easy-to-use mechanism of generating networks policies in Kubernetes environments..		

Interacts with	
Success Criteria	A valid Cilium Network Policy is returned.

Table 151: Produce Network Policy function specification

Receive SRM Actions function

Function Name	Receive SRM Actions	Priority	Must
Description	The NetSecPols receives the list of SRM Actions and generate one or more Cilium Network Policies.		
Interacts with			
Success Criteria	A list of Cilium Network Policies is returned.		

Table 152: Receive SRM Actions function specification

5.16 Software Development Kit (SDK) component

Component Name	Software Development Kit (SDK)
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<p>Intro / Overview</p>	<p>The SDK provides developers with tools, libraries, and documentation to develop and integrate applications within the ENACT ecosystem. It facilitates the development of portable apps capable of distributed management of data by mobile devices.</p>
<p>Extracted Modules</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SDK Libraries • Development tools • Documentation
<p>Component Workflow</p>	<p>SDK Libraries provide essential libraries for building ENACT-compatible applications. Development tools include tools for coding, debugging, and testing. Documentation offers comprehensive guides and API documentation. TBD. Sample Applications demonstrate best practices and common UCs.</p>
<p>External Component Interaction</p>	
<p>Prototypical Mock-ups</p>	<p>SDK Dashboard is the central hub for accessing tools, libraries, and documentation. Code editor provides an integrated development environment with syntax highlighting and debugging features. API Explorer is an interface for exploring and testing available APIs.</p>
<p>TRL Potential Use-cases</p>	<p>Expected: TRL-6</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Application development • Edge Computing Applications • Data analytics and visualisation
<p>Layer Technologies</p>	<p>ENACT App Development Layer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Programming Languages: Python, JavaScript, Java • Frameworks: Angular, React • Libraries: Axios, Lodash • Tools: Visual Studio Code, Git, Jenkins
<p>Interfaces</p>	<p>SDK Libraries API</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Provides essential functions and methods for application development. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Development Tools API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Offers tools for debugging and testing applications. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous • Data Format: JSON
	Documentation API <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: Access to guides and API documentation. • Type: REST API • State: Synchronous Data Format: HTML or DOCX or MD
	Software
Deployment Type	Software
Authorisation Definition	Access to the SDK requires authentication. Permissions are managed through the ENACT Security and user management system. Developers must have appropriate permissions to access certain modules and functions.
Licence	Apache 2.0

Table 153: Software Development Kit (SDK) Component specification

5.16.1 SDK Libraries

Module Name	SDK Libraries	Priority	Must
Description	The SDK Libraries module provides the necessary interactions with different platforms and components to create hyper-distributed applications.		
Interacts with	Other (Maybe All) ENACT Components		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries that interact with platforms (devices and clusters) • Libraries that interact with ENACT Components 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below.		

Table 154: SDK Libraries specification

Libraries that interact with platforms function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with platforms	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the different types of platforms that will be included in the ENACT project to asset types in the SRM.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the different types of platforms.		

Table 155: Libraries that interact with platforms function specification

Libraries that interact with ENACT function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with ENACT	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the components in the ENACT architecture.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM • Other ENACT Components 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the ENACT components (architecture).		

Table 156: Libraries that interact with ENACT function specification

5.16.2 Development Tools

Module Name	Development Tools	Priority	Must
Description	The Development Tools module will provide utilities to be able to interact with the ENACT platform.		
Interacts with Extracted Functions	Other (Maybe All) ENACT Components <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM Functions • Various functions which act like wrappers of exposed by the ENACT components 		
Success Criteria	The success criteria of each function are described individually below.		

Table 157: Development Tools specification

Libraries that interact with platforms function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with platforms	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the different types of platforms that will be included in the ENACT project.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the different types of platforms.		

Table 158: SDK Libraries function specification

Libraries that interact with ENACT function

Function Name	Libraries that interact with ENACT	Priority	Must
Description	This function will provide the necessary libraries to interact with the components in the ENACT architecture.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APM • Other ENACT Components 		
Success Criteria	The ability to correctly interact with the ENACT components (architecture).		

Table 159: Libraries that interact with platforms function

5.16.3 Documentation module

Module Name	Documentation	Priority	Must
Description	The Documentation module provides the documentation on the usage of each library and module development inside the ENACT SDK.		
Interacts with	N/A		
Extracted Functions	N/A		
Success Criteria	The success criteria are offered by the ease of understanding of the documentation of ENACT SDK.		

Table 160: Documentation module specification

5.17 Application Policy Model component

Component Name	Application Policy Model		
Intro / Overview	The Application Policy Model offers distributed application owners a mechanism to specify runtime policies that the underlying infrastructure should cover, ensuring that applications adhere to desired performance, security, and compliance requirements while dynamically adapting to changing conditions and resource availability.		

Extracted Modules

Distributed application owners can specify networking, storage, computational and locality policies.

- **Network Policies Module:** this module validates runtime policies related to networking such as packets per second, desired bandwidth, minimum delay, etc.
- **Storage Policies Module:** this to validates runtime policies related to storage such as desired I/O, underlying encryption technology, etc.
- **Computational Policies Module:** this module to validates runtime policies related to computational capabilities such as accelerators, number of cores, etc.
- **Locality Policies Module:** this module validates runtime policies related to placement of components across the Edge-to-cloud continuum.
- **Policies Datastore Module:** this module is responsible for efficiently storing policies.
- **Policy Manager Module:** this module acts as an interface between external components and internal modules. The Policy Manager forwards policies to their respected modules and provides a unified interface.

Component Workflow

External Component Interaction	<pre> graph TD Owner([Distributed Application owner]) -- Specify Policies --> Model[Application Policy Model] Model <--> Retrieve/Update runtime Policies Controller[Application Controller] </pre>	
Prototypical Mock-ups	N/A	
TRL	Current TRL: 2 End TRL: 5	
Potential Use-cases	all ENACT UCs	
Layer	App Development Layer	
Technologies	etcd, Go/Python	
Interfaces	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview: provides a user-friendly and secure way for application owners and administrators to manage runtime policies. It supports operations to create, read, update, and delete (CRUD) runtime policies. • Type: probably REST, though considering gRPC • State: synchronous • Data Format: JSON if REST, else protobuf if gRPC 	
Deployment Type	containerised application, helm chart	
Authorisation	probably basic authentication	
Definition		
Licence	Apache 2.0	

Table 161: Application Policy Model Component specification

5.17.1 Network Policies module

Module Name	Network Policies	Priority	Must
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Description	The Network Policies Module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to networking. These policies cover aspects such as packets per second, desired bandwidth, minimum delay, and other quality of service (QoS) parameters. This module ensures that distributed application owner network requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations.
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies Datastore module • Policy Manager
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate network Policy • Store network Policy • Retrieve network Policy • Delete network Policy
Success Criteria	Network Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and safely removed from the datastore.

Table 162: Network Policies module specification

Validate Network Policy function

Function Name	Validate Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored to the policy datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations.		

Table 163: Validate Network Policy function specification

Store Network Policy function

Function Name	Store Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of network policies related to a distributed application from the policies datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored efficiently in the Policy Datastore.		

Table 164: Store Network Policy Function specification

Retrieve Network Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of network policies related to a distributed application from the policies datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 165: Retrieve Network Policy function specification

Delete Network Policy function

Function Name	Delete Network Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Safely deletes a network policy.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 166: Delete Network Policy function specification
5.17.2 Storage Policies module

Module Name	Storage Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Storage Policies module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to storage resources. These policies specify the required storage type (such as SSDs, HDDs, or cloud storage), capacity, redundancy, and performance requirements. This module ensures that distributed application owner storage requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations, efficiently allocating storage resources to meet performance and reliability demands.		
Interacts with	Policies Datastore module: stores, retrieves and deletes Storage policies Policy Manager: interact with Policy Manager for any Storage Policy		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate Storage Policy • Store Storage Policy • Retrieve Storage Policy • Delete Storage Policy 		
Success Criteria	Storage Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and safely removed from the datastore.		

Table 167: Storage Policies module specification
Validate Storage Policy function

Function Name	Validate Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Validates a storage policy ensuring the policy is well structured.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations.		

Table 168: Validate Storage Policy function specification
Store Storage Policy function

Function Name	Store Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored to the policy datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored successfully.		

Table 169: Store Storage Policy function specification
Retrieve Storage Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of storage policies related to a distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 170: Retrieve Storage Policy function specification
Delete Storage Policy function

Function Name	Delete Storage Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Safely deletes a storage policy.		

Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.

Table 171: Delete Storage Policy function specification

5.17.3 Computational Policies module

Module Name	Computational Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Computational Policies module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to computational resources. These policies specify the required accelerators (such as GPUs, DPUs or SmartNICs), the number of CPU cores, memory allocation, and desired processing power. This module ensures that distributed application owner computational requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations, efficiently allocating resources to meet performance demands.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies Datastore module • Policy Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate Compute Policy • Store Compute policy • Retrieve Compute Policy • Delete Compute Policy 		
Success Criteria	Computational Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and removed in a safe manner from the datastore.		

Table 172: Computational Policies module specification

Validate Compute Policy function

Function Name	Validate Compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Validates a storage policy ensuring the policy is well structured.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations		

Table 173: Validate Compute Policy function specification

Store Compute Policy function

Function Name	Store compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored to the Policy datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored efficiently in the Policy Datastore.		

Table 174: Store Compute Policy function specification

Retrieve Compute Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a compute policy from the datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore.		

Table 175: Retrieve Compute Policy function specification
Delete Compute Policy function

Function Name	Delete Compute Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Deletes a compute policy from the Policies Datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	the policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 176: Delete Compute Policy function specification
5.17.4 Locality Policies module

Module Name	Locality Policies	Priority	Must
Description	The Locality Policies module is responsible for validating and storing runtime policies related to the geographical placement of components across the Edge-to-Cloud continuum. These policies determine where application components should be deployed to optimise latency, bandwidth, and resource utilisation. This module ensures that distributed application owner locality requirements are documented and can be utilised by other components to perform intelligent operations, optimising performance, compliance, and data sovereignty.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policies Datastore module • Policy Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Validate Locality Policy • Store Locality Policy • Retrieve Locality Policy • Delete Locality Policy 		
Success Criteria	Locality Policies are validated, inserted, retrieved and removed without causing any integrity issues from the datastore.		

Table 177: Locality Policies module specification
Validate Locality Policy function

Function Name	Validate Locality Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Validates a locality policy ensuring the policy is well structured		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	A network policy is checked for any violations		

Table 178: Validate Locality Policy function specification
Store Storage Policy function

Function Name	Store Storage Policies	Priority	Must
Description	If the policy is valid, it is stored in the Policy datastore		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is stored successfully		

Table 179: Store Storage Locality Policy function specification

Retrieve Locality Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Locality Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of locality policies related to a distributed application from the policies datastore		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is retrieved efficiently from the Policy Datastore		

Table 180: Retrieve Locality Policy function specification

Delete Locality Policy function

Function Name	Delete Locality Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Safely deletes a network policy		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Policy Datastore 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 181: Delete Locality Policy function specification

5.17.5 Policies Datastore module

Module Name	Policies Datastore	Priority	Must
Description	The Policies Datastore module is responsible for efficiently storing runtime policies related to various resources (i.e., compute, locality, network, storage).		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Store Policy • Retrieve Policy • Delete Policy 		
Success Criteria	Policies are stored in a failsafe manner to the database ensuring integrity, availability and consistency of information.		

Table 182: Policies Datastore module specification

Store Policy function

Function Name	Store Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Stores a policy to the underlying database.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		
Success Criteria	A policy is checked for any violations.		

Table 183: Store Policy function specification

Retrieve Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Policy	Priority	Must
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Description	Retrieves policies related to a given distributed application.
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager
Success Criteria	The policy is successfully retrieved.

Table 184: Retrieve Policy function specification

Delete Policy function

Function Name	Delete Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Deletes a policy.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module • Policy Manager 		
Success Criteria	The policy is safely removed from the Policies Datastore.		

Table 185: Delete Policy function specification

5.17.6 Policy Manager module

Module Name	Policy Manager	Priority	Must
Description	The Policy Manager module acts as an interface between external components and internal modules. It is responsible for receiving policies from external sources, forwarding them to the appropriate module for validation and storage, and providing a unified interface for policy management.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		
Extracted Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inset Policy • Retrieve Policy • List Policies • Delete Policy 		
Success Criteria	Policies are analysed and forwarded to the corresponding module to perform checks and store them in the datastore.		

Table 186: Policy Manager module specification

Insert Policy function

Function Name	Insert Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Receives a new policy and stores it in the datastore.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		

Success Criteria	Inserts a new policy and efficiently stores in the datastore. Communicates with other modules to performs validation checks on their respective parts.
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Table 187: Insert Policy function specification

Retrieve Policy function

Function Name	Retrieve Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Retrieves a list of policies related to a distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		
Success Criteria	Retrieves a policy successfully.		

Table 188: Retrieve Policy function specification

Delete Policy function

Function Name	Delete Policy	Priority	Must
Description	Deletes a policy related to a specified distributed application.		
Interacts with	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy Manager • Network Policies module • Storage Policies module • Computational Policies module • Locality Policies module 		
Success Criteria	Safely removes a policy from the datastore.		

Table 189: Delete Policy function specification

6. ENACT Use cases analysis and specifications

This Section presents the updated and extended analysis and specification of the use cases (UCs) within the ENACT project. While the previous version of the deliverable focused primarily on two of the three UCs (**UC1 - Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing by MOG Technologies**, and **UC3 - Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu’s Mobility Digital Twin Initiative**), this iteration completes the intended scope by including a detailed and comprehensive description of the third ENACT pilot use case (**UC2 - Production and distribution of media content for cultural heritage and tourism sectors**). This ensures that all pilots contributing to the project’s validation and implementation are equally represented and technically detailed.

The updated use case analysis maintains the structure established previously, outlining each pilot's objectives, scope, and expected impact within the ENACT platform. By incorporating the pilot 2, this deliverable now offers a complete overview of all relevant UCs. This addition also reinforces the project's commitment to iterative development, collaboration, and continuous refinement of technical documentation.

6.1 Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing by MOG Technologies

6.1.1 Overview

6.1.1.1 Introduction, Opportunities and Barriers

The streaming market for sports has experienced a seismic shift in recent years, transforming how fans consume their favourite games and events. Traditional cable and satellite TV subscriptions are no longer the sole gateway to live sports action; instead, viewers are increasingly turning to streaming platforms for their fix of athletic entertainment.

One of the key drivers behind this shift is the convenience and flexibility offered by streaming services. Unlike traditional TV packages, which often require long-term contracts and come with hefty subscription fees, streaming platforms typically offer more affordable and customizable options. This allows sports fans to pick and choose the specific events or leagues they want to follow, without being tied down by unnecessary channels or packages.

Moreover, streaming services have made it easier for fans to access sports content on a variety of devices, from smartphones and tablets to smart TVs and gaming consoles. This means that viewers can catch the action wherever they are, whether they are at home, on the go, or even abroad.

The rise of streaming has also led to increased competition in the sports broadcasting industry. Tech giants like Amazon, Google, and Facebook have entered the fray, bidding for rights to broadcast live sporting events alongside traditional broadcasters and cable networks. This competition has driven up the value of sports media rights, leading to lucrative deals for leagues and teams around the world.

Another key advantage of streaming platforms is their ability to offer a more interactive viewing experience. Many streaming services provide additional features such as live stats and real-time social media integration, allowing fans to engage more deeply with the action and with each other.

However, despite the many benefits of sports streaming, there are still some challenges and limitations to overcome. One major concern is the issue of automatically detecting in-game events or follow players to provide the user with a more engaging experience (e.g., heatmaps, player tracking overlays, search enhanced metadata).

This pilot focuses on adapting a video processing pipeline for automated analysis of live sports to take advantage of the opportunities available in the computing continuum, namely, the seamless interplay of edge and cloud resources to minimise the latency, the availability of heterogeneous devices to optimise the processing and storage capacities, automatic load-balancing and elasticity of applications to address varying demand patterns and dynamic adaptation to accommodate changes in the infrastructure or users behaviours.

6.1.1.2 Motivation

The market size of live sports streaming is huge and continuously growing²¹⁰. Figure 9 shows the amount of money companies are paying to secure the transmission of live sports. This means that the broadcasting companies expect to earn a lot more money from streaming the games themselves.

Companies are paying record amounts to stream live sports

Notable recent live sports rights streaming deals

League	Sport	Company	Geography	Total deal value (value per year)	Deal length
National Football League (<i>Thursday Night Football</i>)	American football	Amazon	United States	US\$13.2B (US\$1.2B/year)	11 years 2022–2033
Indian Premier League (Digital rights)	Cricket	Viacom18	India	US\$3B (US\$600M/year)	5 years 2023–2027
Premier League	Football (soccer)	Viaplay	9 European countries	US\$2.7B (US\$450M/year)	6 years 2022–2028
Serie A	Football (soccer)	DAZN	Italy	US\$2.5B (US\$840M/year)	3 years 2021–2024
Major League Soccer	Football (soccer)	Apple	Global	US\$2.5B (US\$250M/year)	10 years 2023–2032
LaLiga	Football (soccer)	DAZN	Spain	US\$2.4B (US\$470M/year)	5 years 2022–2027
Ligue 1	Football (soccer)	Amazon	France	US\$750M (US\$250M/year)	3 years 2021–2024
Major League Baseball (<i>Friday Night Baseball</i>)	Baseball	Apple	8 countries currently	US\$595M (US\$85M/year)	7 years 2022–2029

Notes: Some deal values were converted from euros to US dollars at the September 20, 2022 exchange rate of 1.00 euro = 1.00 US dollar. Value per year is the deal value averaged across the duration of the contract. Source: Multiple public sources.⁸

Deloitte Insights | deloitte.com/insights

Figure 9: Major sports streaming rights acquisitions

At the same time, the global sports analytics market size was valued at USD 3.19 billion in 2022. It is estimated to reach USD 16.45 billion by 2031, growing at a CAGR of 20.02% during the forecast period²¹¹.

²¹⁰ <https://www2.deloitte.com/xe/en/insights/industry/technology/technology-media-and-telecom-predictions/2023/live-sports-streaming-wars.html>

²¹¹ [https://straitresearch.com/report/sports-analytics-market#:~:text=The%20global%20sports%20analytics%20market,period%20\(2023%E2%80%932031\).](https://straitresearch.com/report/sports-analytics-market#:~:text=The%20global%20sports%20analytics%20market,period%20(2023%E2%80%932031).)

6.1.1.3 Target Objectives

In parallel, the cognitive computing continuum, proposed by ENACT, offers several motivations for utilising it in the context of live streaming, particularly for automatic analysis of sports content:

- (i) **Low Latency:** In live streaming, especially for sports events, minimising latency is crucial to providing viewers with a real-time experience. Edge computing brings processing power closer to the end-user, reducing the time it takes for data to travel between the source (e.g., sports venue) and the viewer's device. By processing and delivering content at the network edge, latency can be significantly reduced, enhancing the viewing experience.
- (ii) **Scalability:** Sports events, especially major tournaments or matches, can attract millions of viewers simultaneously and, therefore, are covered by several cameras. Cloud computing provides scalability, allowing streaming platforms with automatic computer vision analysis to dynamically allocate resources based on demand. Additionally, edge computing can offload processing tasks from centralised data centres to edge nodes, further enhancing scalability (e.g., adding one or more cameras to the analysis)
- (iii) **Enhanced Quality of Service (QoS):** The computing continuum allows for intelligent resource allocation and traffic management, leading to improved Quality of Service (QoS) for live streaming.
- (iv) **Reliability and Resilience:** Distributed computing architectures, such as edge and fog computing, enhance the reliability and resilience of live streaming systems. By decentralising processing and storage capabilities across multiple edge nodes, these architectures reduce single points of failure and improve fault tolerance. In the event of network disruptions or server failures, edge computing ensures continuity of service by seamlessly redirecting traffic to alternate nodes, thereby enhancing overall system reliability.

Overall, the computing continuum offers compelling motivations for leveraging its capabilities in live streaming, particularly for sports content where real-time delivery, scalability, and quality are paramount. By harnessing edge and cloud computing technologies, streaming platforms can deliver immersive, high-quality viewing experiences to sports fans worldwide.

6.1.1.4 Key Research Areas

This pilot concerning the live streaming and automatic analysis of sports content is highly relevant in the context of the following challenges faced in the media industry:

1. Distributed Media Processing.
2. Player Tracking and Recognition.
3. Broadcast Enhancement.

6.1.2 Use Case Scenario

6.1.2.1 Participants

EVS Broadcast is globally recognised as the leading provider of live video technology for broadcast and new media productions. Throughout its history, EVS has maintained its industry leadership by constantly innovating and evolving its portfolio to meet the increasing demand for flexibility, scalability, and performance across diverse production setups.

EVS solutions span the entire live production process, supporting broadcasters and media companies with advanced technologies like IP, artificial intelligence, HDR, and the cloud. These solutions allow customers to create, manage, and distribute live content efficiently and reliably. EVS's core objective is to enable its customers to produce smarter, faster, and more engaging stories, leveraging its expertise to support workflows that range from traditional on-premise setups to hybrid and fully cloud-based infrastructures.

This long-standing commitment to innovation and customer success directly connects to the ENACT project. Processing data across heterogeneous and distributed platforms is now a daily reality in live sports production. EVS, with its deep expertise, is an ideal participant for UC1, helping advance the integration of sports venues, edge devices, and cloud platforms into a single seamless content pipeline.

EVS's business case under the ENACT project focuses on the automatic annotation of live sports content. Leveraging the computing continuum and ENACT's adaptable architecture, EVS aims to optimise and scale real-time data annotation to enhance sports broadcasts. This includes using AI to enrich streams with metadata like player tracking, all with minimal human intervention and the highest reliability.

The solution developed within this UC will help overcome existing limitations in current fixed and rigid systems by making data pipelines more flexible and responsive to real-time demands. This will also enable EVS to demonstrate the benefits of an adaptive and distributed architecture for sports broadcasters allowing live content to be produced, enriched, and distributed more efficiently and intelligently.

By utilizing ENACT's innovations and architecture, EVS expects to tackle two core challenges in the media industry: first, reliably transporting high-speed live sports content across diverse platforms to the authorised broadcaster; and second, enriching content automatically with relevant metadata during the event itself. This pilot will highlight EVS's ongoing leadership in future-proof media solutions and demonstrate its role as a pioneer in enabling the next generation of live sports production.

6.1.2.2 Scenario Description

This UC focuses on addressing the viewers' engagement and experience in the live broadcast events, by automatically annotating large quantities of media data, from various sources. As a result, it is mainly focusing on the processing of high-frequency video and audio streams. In such streams, the data starts from the event venue and flows through the continuum to the broadcaster headquarters or end user. The input and output data of the pipeline is in standardised video and audio stream formats, complying with professional video streaming standards. The processing of the data within the pipeline results in structured and human-friendly text annotation. This annotated and augmented data is then delivered to the final client as metadata (as illustrated on Figure 10).

Highlighting relevant data assets, regarding camera acquisition data, which encompasses video acquisition at a rate of up to 3 Gbits/sec per camera. For a typical setup involving 4-5 cameras (HD cameras per event; the data will be collected from two different sources: video and audio. each one containing different frames). This results in a substantial amount of data, especially considering the duration of an event like a 90-minute football match. The calculation is as follows: 3 Gbits/sec x number of cameras (typically 4-5) x (90 minutes x 60 seconds). Despite the fluctuation, based on the

information that the component can extract, the metadata could represent 2.5 KB of data (JSON file) for every frame, and up to 300MB for a whole football match recording.

```

1  {
2  "prediction": {
3    "0": [
4      {
5        "bb": [
6          1378,
7          447,
8          1397,
9          488
10       ]
11      },
12     {
13       "bb": [
14         0,
15         836,
16         13,
17         902
18       ]
19     },
20     {
21       "bb": [
22         895,
23         324,
24         911,
25         357
26       ]
27     },
28     {
29       "bb": [
30         1357,
31         388,
32         1372,
33         414
34       ]
35     },
36     {
37       "bb": [
38         763,
39         908,
40         909,
41         912,
42         913,
43         914,
44         915,
45         916,
46         917,
47         918,
48         919,
49         920,
50         921,
51         922,
52         923,
53         924,
54         925,
55         926,
56         927,
57         928,
58         929,
59         930,
60         931,
61         932,
62         933,
63         934,
64         935,
65         936,
66         937,
67         938,
68         939,
69         940,
70         941,
71         942,
72         943,
73         944
74       ]
75     }
76   ],
77   "48": [
78     {
79       "bb": [
80         427,
81         1056
82       ]
83     },
84     {
85       "bb": [
86         562,
87         486,
88         583,
89         533
90       ]
91     },
92     {
93       "bb": [
94         751,
95         929,
96         779,
97         1007
98       ]
99     },
100    {
101      "bb": [
102        1691,
103        574,
104        1715,
105        620
106      ]
107    }
108  ],
109  "status": "processed",
110  "video_path": "uploads/2e576778-1c0e-4b92-t"
111 }

```

Figure 10: Example of metadata annotations

Additionally, it is expected to provide the right data to other stakeholders, generating specific outcomes, likely:

- **Business domain expert (media manager)** can expect a clear vision about costs and resources involved and tools to support decision making.
- **DataOps Operator** will be able to assist deployments over heterogeneous virtual environments and the deployments will not be attached to a specific public, private or hybrid cloud.
- For a **Data Scientist**, the expected outcomes include access to AI-based tools that support modularisation, enabling the development of experiments for generating new insights. Additionally, the automation of data access and the definition of datasets depending on the experiment are anticipated. There is also the need to highlight the easy reconfiguration of resource architecture to carry out data analytics experiments based on the properties of the datasets.

6.1.2.3 High-level architecture

Figure 11 illustrates the use-case data pipeline and its modular components. As depicted in the figure, the data follows through a structured path and is processed or treated by different components, ensuring that a rich and uninterrupted video stream provides a smooth experience to the final user during a sports event.

A key change was made to the previous architecture of our use case. Initially, all processing was done exclusively via streaming, requiring all resources to be available in real-time to process incoming data. This approach risked memory leaks and system instability due to resource overloading.

In the updated design, an intermediate stream-to-file processing step has been introduced. Instead of processing the data immediately as it arrives, the stream is first broken into multiple files, allowing parallel and asynchronous processing by the AI layer.

Integration with SDK/APM component has also been considered on this updated design. In this approach, SDK/APM is used as a library, receiving the chunks resulting from the stream-to-file process. Subsequently, SDK/APM invokes the AI event detection API to obtain the metadata files and the video file.

This new approach provides greater control over AI workflows and decouples processing from real-time constraints. It enables better resource management by allowing the system to defer intensive tasks to off-peak times, thus reducing memory usage and improving overall stability. Furthermore, this modular architecture simplifies integration with ENACT components and enhances system scalability.

Figure 11: High-level architecture of the use-case data pipelines

6.1.2.4 Flow Description

The use-case focuses on the processing of multimedia data in the sports event broadcasting domain. The time-critical scenario of live events broadcast requires a maximum time to process a new data sample. For the European market, the amount of time a frame is on the screen is typically 40 milliseconds (25 fps); that means, one frame stays on the screen 40 milliseconds, and it is replaced by the next frame. This brings the challenge of not only performing continuous and high-speed data processing in the compute continuum, but also respecting the data pace to ensure that a new video frame is readily available every 40 milliseconds.

Therefore, the multimedia data processing components are critical for the use-case as the drop of even a few seconds may compromise future services for the end client. To mitigate this risk, the data flow needs to split into various paths with different priorities: main broadcast, AI extraction and annotation, and others that focus on extra ingest/transcode features.

After being captured, media data first goes into the stream split component which distributes it into the various paths. The main broadcast path is critical so it requires reliable resources and prioritisation among the other data paths to ensure that the data will arrive properly at the end-client. Parallel to the broadcast path, another path processes the data by splitting the stream into multiple files. This stream-to-file approach enables parallel processing by the AI layer. Leveraging AI models, the system extracts valuable information from the video content, benefiting from a more flexible data processing timeline. Additionally, integration with the SDK/APM component has been considered. SDK/APM functions as a library, receiving chunks of data resulting from the stream-to-file process. Once the data is received, SDK/APM invokes the AI event detection API to fetch the metadata files and video. Other paths may exist if the workflow is arranged in other forms using an additional module to encode the video into different formats. Moreover, other modules to create extra visual content using the metadata extracted could be deployed within the architecture depicted in Section 6.1.2.3.

Considering the focus on providing enriched media broadcasts of live events, the use-case pipeline is ideally deployed just prior to the initiation of a specific live event. Subsequently, it may be deactivated upon completion of all video processing tasks, with offline processing available as a fallback option in instances of insufficient resources. The use-case, particularly its pipeline components are designed to guarantee that, despite parallel analysis and metadata extraction, the final user will receive an uninterrupted broadcast. Thus, all components along the main broadcast take into account this requirement. Ideally, all components should deploy simultaneously. However, priority components must consistently remain operational, maintaining low latency to swiftly convey the main video stream to its destination and maintain initial quality. This means that subsequent components may be sacrificed to safeguard the broadcast path's integrity.

Table 190 below describes the technologies and technological modules present in the data processing pipeline - to be used for testing and validation of ENACT solutions.

Module name	Description	Technologies/Format
Camera	Physical video camera, deployed in the sports arena and pointing to the sports field, where its position and field of view is controlled by MOG. The camera will be connected to the "Transcoding Encoding" module with an SDI connection or equivalent.	-
Transcoding Encoding	Physical equipment that receives the uncompressed media data from the professional camera via SDI connection and processes it to compress and wrap the data in standardised IP/UDP protocol to be delivered to the following components.	-
Stream Split	A virtualised module that receives a media-standardised data stream and splits it on each of its media essence streams (Video and Audio). The split essence streams still go through IP/UDP connections.	Nginx RTMP Dockerised Container
Stream Relay	A virtualised module that receives compressed essence streams and wraps them in a standardised data stream to the broadcaster or end user. Different output data streams (e.g., RTMP, HLS, DASH) require different modules.	ffmpeg Dockerised Container

Video Decoder	Virtualised module that handles a compressed video data stream and decodes the video to provide an uncompressed data stream.	ffmpeg Dockerised Container
Stream to file	Virtualised module that splits the stream into multiple files	Dockerised Python component
AI Event Detection	Virtualised module to identify relevant events and information available in the uncompressed video data stream. The ancillary data created by this module is associated with the respective video frame timecode.	Python and CV Libraries Dockerised component
Metadata Enrichment	Virtualised module that grabs all the identified data events and aggregates them in a structured and standardised form to be delivered to the end broadcaster	Dockerised Python container
Video Encoder	Virtualised module that creates a new compressed video data stream, from the uncompressed video stream. This compressed stream can be different from the original one. This module is optional.	ffmpeg Dockerised Container
Visual Enhancer	A virtualised module that uses the metadata extracted to create extra visual content. This module is optional.	Dockerised Python container

Table 190: Technologies and technological modules in the data processing pipeline

As mentioned before, these components will be containerised and deployed across the compute continuum in a distributed manner using the ENACT solutions, with the goal of achieving benefits such as enhanced performance efficiency and reduced latency.

Highlight to the AI Event Detection and Metadata Enhancement modules that represent macro components that are under continuous development, leading to evolving functionalities over the project's course. Despite this overarching description, they can be decomposed into smaller modules responsible for extracting information from the incoming video stream. Nevertheless, the core functionality of this pair remains consistent, ingesting unformatted video input and delivering annotated video output.

6.1.2.5 Datasets and Models

The data utilised within this use-case is primarily based on multimedia and timing information which needs to be processed promptly and according to the respective broadcast standards. High-quality and reliable multimedia streaming implies an assertive decision regarding the chosen video and audio codecs and the respective wrappers. Also, the configuration of the codecs has a huge impact on the amount of data to be processed, the video and audio delays, and the bandwidth needed to transfer the data. The multimedia data that flows through the pipeline exists in both uncompressed and compressed formats. For instance, for a 1080p video captured at 25 frames per second (fps), the uncompressed video stream (only one camera) would require a minimum of approximately 800 Mbps, while the compressed version typically ranges between 10-20 Mbps. This data is shared between the first components of the pipeline and is identified in the high-level architecture (Figure 11). This UC can involve several media streams, that with the appropriate video codecs and wrappers should generate data at a rate of approximately 1GB per second.

All the components described in Section 6.1.2.4 process multimedia data, however, AI Event Detection and Metadata Enhancement, also extract and handle information about the live event, such as player classification, player tracking, and team segmentation. This data, identifiable by a

video timestamp, is temporarily stored in JSON/XML format, following the structure presented in Figure 10. Subsequently, these components store this information temporarily before shipping it along with the video as metadata to the broadcaster. With further development, the data could start being stored and distributed via cache databases, like a local Redis deployment or through a local data streaming application like Kafka.

For validation purposes, the use case will initially rely on a private dataset provided by EVS, containing football match videos totalling several terabytes of data. This dataset will be used for preliminary testing. In a second stage, we will create a dataset of sports events videos captured in real-world scenarios that will help create testing simulations. This multi-media dataset will have various formats, codecs, and wrappers to validate the pipeline for different capture scenarios.

On the other hand, the use-case development does not encompass the training of AI models, it rather focuses on utilising models that are already integrated in the use-case. The new models that may increase the use-case performance and/or speed should be open-source. The current models employed are based on the YOLO architecture²¹² and are currently extracting information regarding player positioning (tracking).

6.1.2.6 ENACT Impact

ENACT presents a significant impact across various dimensions, including technological advancements, business enhancements, and environmental sustainability:

Technological Advancements:

- **Integration of Edge-Cloud Continuum:** ENACT introduces innovative aspects through the integration of an Edge-Cloud Continuum in media processing, enabling uninterrupted broadcasting, intelligent annotation, and peak performance across the end-to-end data processing pipeline.
- **Runtime Operation Monitoring:** ENACT monitors the runtime operation of the application - video production workflow - to understand performance drops and changes in QoS or QoE, and to react accordingly.
- **Lower Production Costs in Decentralised Sports Events:** ENACT reduces the cost of covering decentralised sports events by dynamically allocating edge resources when available. This also lowers the end-to-end latency between the acquisition of a frame and the annotated video.

Business Enhancements:

- **Optimising Resource Utilisation and Reducing Operational Costs:** ENACT enhances the value proposition for media streaming providers by optimising resource utilisation and reducing operational costs. This results in cost savings and improved performance for customers while maintaining smooth and uninterrupted service for broadcast consumers.
- **Navigating Increasing Data Complexity:** ENACT's outcomes are expected to have a significant impact on managing Edge-Cloud Computing Continuum infrastructures, making the integration of data pipelines into organisational business processes more accessible to a

²¹² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/You_Only_Look_Once

wider set of stakeholders, including start-ups and SMEs, regardless of hardware infrastructure.

Environmental Sustainability:

- **Reducing Resource Utilisation and Increasing Energy Efficiency:** The technological innovations introduced by ENACT lead to reduced resource utilisation and increased energy efficiency, fostering environmental sustainability in the media sector.

Overall, ENACT aims to enhance the efficiency, intelligence, and sustainability of distributed computing resources within the Cloud-Edge Continuum, benefiting media processing and business operations alike.

6.1.2.7 Current Status

The pipeline’s components are currently deployed locally. In ENACT, the data pipeline will be distributed across the compute continuum to test and verify the impact of distributed deployment and adaptive management of components on the key performance parameters. The use-case will evolve in terms of its scalability and AI-based media processing techniques. This will require research on the state-of-the-art distributed media processing and AI techniques, to ensure that the use-case performances meet the constantly updated market performances.

Due to recent architectural changes, several internal logic components are being refactored or updated to accommodate the new stream-to-file approach, develop the AI event detection API and enable more efficient processing workflows.

As a result, while the pipeline remains runnable in a virtualised environment, certain modules are still under adaptation.

For testing purposes, these physical modules can be simulated through a virtualised module that will simulate the functionality of the real-time video streaming source (camera), which will be developed in the ENACT project. The pipeline’s deployment will follow MOG’s standard strategy using a Helm Chart on a single Kubernetes cluster (on-prem or AKS) with GPU resources. This means that no edge devices are currently being used which, in a test case scenario, can augment the latency between the video stream and its processing components.

6.1.2.8 ENACT Benefits

ENACT benefits our media streaming application and process by integrating it into the Edge-Cloud Continuum, ensuring seamless transitions of computing tasks, dynamic resource optimisation, and improved communication reliability. Its innovations streamline operations, supports scalability, and offers potential cost savings. Essentially, these ENACT innovations should allow the application to reach the KPIs presented in Table 191 below.

KPI	Type	Current Scenario	Baseline	Metrics
Increase the application reliability and quality (system failure recovery) by 35%	Functional	The use case application is currently containerised (Docker) and is deployed on prem in a single server, A failure in one of the services propagates to the other services of the application. The solution is to manually restart all the services and	Failure recovery time	Downtime, video frame loss

		(possibly) the server. The end-to-end time between the failure happens, it is detected and the system is fully recovered can take at least a half an hour. At the same time, the pipeline has two subbranches with different priorities. In the current scenario there is no way to give more priority to one of the branches.		
Improve Resource utilisation efficiency by 15%.	Operational	Current deployment involved predefined resources with limited scalability. However, these resource configurations may over-provision and its management often rely on relatively static and less intelligent strategies.	Average CPU and memory allocation (100%). Current deployment does not allow for dynamic provisioning of resources so resources are permanently allocated to the workflow even without being processing the data.	Average CPU and memory allocation – The dynamic provisioning can enhance performance and reduce costs.
Reduce Operational Costs by 20%	Strategic	Current production with OBVans and satellite connections. ENACT will help migrate the on prem deployment to the Edge and Cloud Continuum.	A medium-sized coverage of sports will need 5/6 cameras + adaptors + switchers, servers, a OB Van and satellite distribution services which will cost approximately around 42.000 euros. The inclusion of the personnel will, easily, raise this value to 45.000 euros (10 people with a 300 euros average daily salary).	Cloud computing bill.
Increase data processing performance by 20%	Operational	The current application runs on a single machine independently and processes two cameras at the same time.	44 frames/second – 2x 22 fps.	Frames/Second

Table 191: Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing Use-case KPIs

For this innovations impact assessment, several parameters are designated for comparison between the status presented in Section 6.1.2.7 and the envisioned impact after the integration. These quantifiable characteristics serve as vital benchmarks to gauge the transformative effects of ENACT across various domains. Parameters such as resource utilisation, cloud costs, latency, environmental impact, and custom multimedia processing metrics can be utilised to delineate the existing operational landscape against the anticipated enhancements facilitated by ENACT. By systematically evaluating these metrics, stakeholders can ascertain the efficacy of ENACT in optimising resource allocation, enhancing performance, and reducing costs and environmental impact. Furthermore, these parameters also provide a comprehensive snapshot of the current operational dynamics. 6.1.2.10 presents the essential scenarios and metrics for validating these expected enhancements.

6.1.2.9 ENACT Technologies

ENACT presents a comprehensive array of layers and technologies aimed at enhancing the efficiency and intelligence of distributed computing resources within the Cloud-Edge Continuum (CCC). This use-case intends to extensively leverage ENACT across its various layers and components.

By incorporating ENACT's components into this pilot, we aim to improve infrastructure utilisation, scheduling, orchestration, and security measures. These enhancements will lead to better performance, lower operational effort, and smoother deployment of all parts of the data pipeline.

Scheduling & Resource Management

The following ENACT components will be directly leveraged to optimise scheduling and resource allocation:

- **Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP):** Presents a dynamic edge-cloud resources handling approach, minimising manual intervention and enhancing resource accessibility. In our use case, ZTP will be tested and deployed within the existing infrastructure to automate the provisioning of physical servers into the Kubernetes cluster, streamlining the infrastructure setup and deployment processes.
- **Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM) and Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME):** These components will be deployed within the existing infrastructure to monitor edge-cloud resources and support adaptive management. It will help reduce cloud costs while improving communication reliability and quality between edge and cloud nodes.
- **Orchestrator:** Ensures efficient deployment of the data processing pipeline by optimizing resource usage, improving energy efficiency, and enhancing the performance of different modules in the end-to-end data processing pipeline. Initially, this component will be used to deploy our use case on the UNP cluster. In a subsequent phase, we will extend deployment to our own cluster, integrating the Orchestrator and its dependencies.

Supporting Components

The following components make up the AI Layer, which we plan to deploy within the existing infrastructure to support intelligent decision-making, prediction capabilities, and runtime adaptation:

- **Graph Neural Network (GNN) & Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) Agent**
- **AI Forecaster**

Compliance, Policy, and Model Integration

- **Application Programming Model (APM):** This component will have direct integration in our use case. It provides an SDK interface that receives video chunks from the stream to file process. The APM then invokes our AI Event Detection API, generating both metadata files and enriched video. These outputs are stored in a MinIO instance managed by the APM. While we currently do not have a direct integration with the Data Layer, future interoperability may be established. The APM/SDK's current role places it as a key part of the data processing flow.

These components will guide deployment strategies and runtime compliance but are not directly integrated by the use case:

- **Data & Policy Models (Compliance & Governance):** While these models will not be directly integrated, they are essential to support the Application Controller in applying decisions.

- **CCC Data Models & Application Policy Model:** It is important to follow the CCC telemetry data model development to ensure compatibility and implement telemetry models as needed during Application Controller integration. Additionally, understanding and aligning with the format for Application Policy Model integration is also important.

To support the Compute Continuum, deploying these components and layers is fundamental to enabling intelligent, continuous, and coordinated operations across the distributed infrastructure.

6.1.2.10 Test and Validation

This use case can be validated through both local and live scenarios. During the initial testing stages (pre-pilot phase), we plan to use simulated professional camera streams based on a sports video dataset. EVS has provided a private dataset containing several terabytes of football match footage, which will be used to replace the physical video capture modules. This will allow us to validate the pipeline and deploy the remaining components as planned, using ENACT in a realistic environment.

Later, the use-case should be tested entirely in a real environment depending on available resources (pilot phase).

Various scenarios are proposed to rigorously test and validate the application's and ENACT's capabilities, including its elasticity, load balancing, and environmental impact. There must be a focus on the elasticity and load balancing, to test ENACT's ability to dynamically distribute application components across the edge-cloud continuum to ensure seamless scalability and performance optimisation. This includes stress testing scenarios where services are removed to assess resource prioritisation and verify sustained functionality even under fluctuating workloads. Furthermore, stress tests should also be conducted, using more computationally demanding videos (e.g. higher resolutions, bitrates), and performing additional encodings or AI analysis. Likewise, there should also be testing scenarios focused on the environmental impact scenario that should evaluate the ecological footprint and cost implications of resource distribution, aiming to minimise energy consumption and carbon emissions while maintaining economic efficiency. By aligning testing scenarios with environmental considerations, the application can optimise resource usage and demonstrate its commitment to sustainability and responsible resource management under lighter loads.

This validation should be done considering these scenarios and then compared with similar metrics, aligned with the benefits specified, from the current (before ENACT) deployment, as presented in Section 6.1.2.8.

Efficient resource utilisation and load distribution are pivotal for ENACT's impact assessment and are quantified through various metrics. These metrics and parameters are used to measure pilot's KPIs (see Table 191) and in general help to quantify ENACT's impact assessment, guide improvements, and enable superior market value and differentiation. Key parameters and metrics include:

- **Efficient Resource Utilisation and Load Distribution**
 - CPU utilisation
 - Memory usage
 - Workload distribution across the Edge-Cloud Continuum

- **Cloud Costs**
 - Monthly bills
 - Resource provisioning expenses
 - Infrastructure costs
- **Latency and Communication Performance**
 - Round-trip time
 - Data transfer rates
- **Environmental Impact Assessment**
 - Resources energy consumption
 - Metrics from resource utilisation and distribution
- **Custom Multimedia and AI Enhancement Metrics**
 - Media processing quality
 - AI model inference speed

6.1.2.11 Expected Computing Continuum Resources for Validation

The challenge for the business case adaptation is considerable. Typically, adaptation means a short period where the data pipeline is on halt, but for the live broadcast, this is not an option. To mitigate the risk that some of the components may accidentally stop, the required resources need to be oversized to reduce the risk of losing part of the stream for a short period. Table 192 below systematises the estimated resources needed for the use-case modular components. Every described component is deployed in 1 container, except for the Metadata Enrichment component, which may include several containers

Tasks	Stream Split (Edge)	Stream Relay (Broadcast module - Edge)	Video Decoder	AI Extractor	Metadata Enrichment	Video Encoder
Resource requirements						
vCPU	2	2	4	16	2	4
RAM	4GB	4GB	4GB	64GB	4GB	8GB
Storage	10GB	10GB	10GB	100GB	10GB	10GB
Network	40Mbps	40Mbps	100Mbps	1Gbps	40Mbps	1Gbps
out	100Mbps	100Mbps	1Gbps	100Mbps	40Mbps	100Mbps
GPU	-	-	-	Requiring CUDA		-

Table 192: Resources needed for the use-case components

The components that are part of the broadcast flow (stream split, stream relay) should be, in theory, deployed in the edge to ensure low latency resulting in an uninterrupted stream to the end user. The others should be deployed through the continuum available (edge or cloud), ensuring the best possible performance, but always prioritising the broadcast reaching the end-user with the necessary QoE.

The infrastructure for this UC should include servers distributed across both the cloud (with GPUs supporting CUDA) and edge devices. While there is no fixed number of servers required, their combined capacity must meet the specified requirements for each component.

6.2 Production and distribution of media content for cultural heritage and tourism sectors

6.2.1 Overview

6.2.1.1 Introduction, Opportunities and Barriers

The Bandera de la Concha is one of the most prestigious and culturally significant rowing regattas in Spain. Held annually in the city of San Sebastián, in the Basque Country, this traditional event takes place over two Sundays in September and brings together the best rowing teams from across the region to compete in the picturesque waters of La Concha Bay. With origins dating back to the late 19th century, the regatta has become a powerful symbol of Basque maritime heritage and competitive spirit.

Figure 12: Overview of the Bandera de la Concha Regatta in San Sebastián

More than just a sporting competition, the Concha Regatta marks the closing of the cultural summer season along the Basque coast. Its unique blend of tradition, sport, and collective celebration transforms the harbour and beachfront into a festive gathering space filled with spectators and team supporters. The event is especially popular among younger audiences, who follow it both in person and through digital platforms in an increasingly participatory manner.

In 2023, the regatta achieved an impressive 46.3% audience share and reached 25,227 unique viewers, demonstrating its broad appeal and relevance. From an economic perspective, it acts as a major tourism driver, attracting visitors from across Spain and abroad, filling hotels and restaurants, and reinforcing San Sebastián's position as a key destination for cultural and sports-related tourism.

The event's visibility is amplified through coverage by EITB (Euskal Irrati Telebista), the Basque public broadcaster, which provides access via television, radio, and online platforms. However, the current digital experience remains limited, largely following a conventional broadcast model that restricts interactivity, personalisation, and scalability.

Building on this context, the Regata de la Concha presents a valuable opportunity to demonstrate how advanced edge-to-cloud computing strategies can improve the technical quality, efficiency, and responsiveness of **digitally mediated cultural events**. Through ENACT, new capabilities can be introduced to optimise data processing and audience interaction across distributed infrastructures.

The main technical opportunities include:

- **Immersive spectator experiences:** The integration of Virtual Reality (VR) will allow users to experience the race from multiple perspectives, such as onboard or aerial views, simulating the atmosphere of being present at the event.
- **Interactive digital participation:** By leveraging platforms like Osoigo, remote users will be able to vote, select viewpoints, and engage with other spectators in real time, bringing a dynamic and interactive layer to the experience.
- **Smart tourism infrastructure:** Thanks to ENACT's advanced orchestration and edge computing capabilities, the regatta can serve as a pilot for low-latency, high-performance digital experiences within the cultural tourism domain, enabling better accessibility without altering the content itself.
- **Edge computing for real-time performance:** Processing GPS, video, and interaction data closer to the source significantly reduces latency, ensuring that race tracking, live video, and user actions remain synchronised.
- **Adaptive data orchestration:** AI-powered workload coordination across the continuum improves the system's responsiveness, helping manage variable user loads and network conditions efficiently.

Despite this potential, several technical challenges must be addressed to enable a successful transformation:

- **Latency and synchronisation:** Delays introduced by traditional CDN processing affect the alignment between GPS data, video feeds, and user interactions.
- **Limited familiarity with immersive tech:** Audiences are not yet widely accustomed to VR in live cultural contexts, requiring accessible, cross-platform implementations.
- **Scalability constraints:** The infrastructure must support thousands of concurrent users without degradation in performance or quality.
- **Hybrid engagement complexity:** Ensuring a seamless, integrated experience for both physical and digital participants requires a cohesive, low-latency architecture.

By addressing these challenges, ENACT will enable a more fluid, interactive, and resilient digital experience, making the Concha Regatta a reference for modernizing live heritage events through cognitive continuum technologies, without altering their content or narrative essence.

6.2.1.2 Motivation

Cultural heritage events face increasing pressure to modernise their visitor experience while preserving authenticity. While many initiatives focus on static digital archives or recorded media, **live cultural events have yet to fully embrace real-time, immersive, and interactive technologies.** The Regata de la Concha, as both a heritage celebration and a competitive event, represents an opportunity to showcase how advanced digital engagement strategies can elevate a historically rooted experience without losing its essence.

Despite its strong local and media presence, the regatta still follows a traditional event model, where spectators experience it either in person or through a standard broadcast. This limits its global accessibility, interactivity, and potential for deeper audience engagement. The challenge is not just to expand the reach of the event, but to redefine how digital audiences can connect with cultural traditions in a meaningful and technically robust way.

Broadcasting the event is already a key driver for tourism, attracting visitors who discover San Sebastián and its traditions through media exposure. However, its full potential is constrained by a

lack of technical flexibility and responsiveness. With the right infrastructure in place, the regatta could be positioned as a smart tourism reference, showcasing how real-time, digitally accessible and interactive cultural events can enhance visibility and engagement without altering their content. Moreover, expanding the digital experience allows remote spectators to feel the atmosphere of the event, potentially influencing their decision to attend future editions in person.

Most cultural heritage events, including the Regata de la Concha, still lack these capabilities. The event has the potential to become a reference for digital heritage tourism, but several limitations must be addressed:

- The absence of immersive and interactive elements makes it difficult to engage remote audiences beyond traditional spectatorship.
- Limited personalisation means that all viewers receive the same experience, with no way to tailor it to their preferences or interests.
- Lack of real-time orchestration limits synchronisation between components such as GPS tracking, live video, and user input.

What distinguishes this use case within the cultural heritage domain is its capacity to offer a hybrid model, where live participation, digital engagement, and technical coordination merge into a seamless, real-time experience. By leveraging **AI-driven device orchestration** for real-time synchronisation, **edge computing** for low-latency processing, and a distributed **cloud infrastructure**, the regatta can become a digitally enhanced cultural event, not by modifying its content, but by delivering it more efficiently and interactively.

Unlike static museum exhibitions or recorded heritage media, this model will allow:

- Live, AI-supported orchestration of video, GPS and interaction data, enabling a consistent, multi-perspective experience in real time.
- A virtual attendance option, allowing global spectators to follow the race as if they were present in San Sebastián.
- An interactive layer, where users can participate in live voting, choose viewpoints, and experience the event in a way that matches their context and connectivity.

With this approach, the Regata de la Concha will serve as a flagship use case for the future of digitally enabled cultural heritage events, demonstrating how intelligent infrastructure can expand reach, accessibility, and engagement without interfering in the content or narrative of the event itself.

6.2.1.3 Target Objectives

The Regata de la Concha Use Case aims to demonstrate how advanced digital infrastructure orchestration can enhance the technical delivery of a **live cultural heritage event**, enabling real-time, interactive and immersive user experiences. The pilot focuses on deploying and validating ENACT technologies to ensure scalable, low-latency and resilient data management across a cognitive cloud continuum, from edge to cloud.

To achieve this, the use case is structured around the following key objectives:

- **Improving the technical quality of digital experiences:** The event will integrate immersive and interactive features, such as virtual reality and real-time audience participation, into a single interface. ENACT will ensure these elements function reliably by managing

synchronisation between video, GPS data, and user interactions, without altering or enriching the original content.

- **Leveraging AI and edge-cloud orchestration for real-time performance:** The pilot will deploy edge computing nodes to process video feeds, telemetry, and user inputs closer to the data source, reducing latency and enabling real-time responsiveness. AI-based orchestration modules will dynamically adapt resource allocation across the infrastructure to optimise delivery based on load and context.

6.2.1.4 Key Research Areas

The Regata de la Concha Use Case integrates research across multiple technical domains to enhance the delivery of real-time immersive experiences while maintaining system responsiveness and scalability. The key research areas include:

- **Edge-to-Cloud Compute Continuum:** Dynamic distribution of computing workloads across edge and cloud nodes to minimise latency and optimise data flow between GPS telemetry, video streaming, and interaction services.
- **AI-driven Orchestration:** Implementation of machine learning-based modules for real-time resource allocation, fault tolerance, and autonomous deployment of services across the continuum.
- **Immersive Media Infrastructure:** Integration of virtual reality environments (developed by external partners) with real-time GPS data and multi-camera feeds, ensuring synchronisation and low-latency rendering managed by ENACT.

6.2.2 Use Case Scenario

6.2.2.1 Participants

EITB

Euskal Irrati Telebista (EITB) is the leading public broadcaster in the Basque Country, offering a comprehensive range of television and radio services. Established in 1982, the organisation was created to promote and preserve Basque language and culture. Over the years, EITB has expanded its reach, serving not only the Basque region but also the global Basque diaspora through its international channels and digital platforms.

The organisation has a workforce of over 1,000 employees, making it one of the largest media companies in the region. Its operations include several television channels, such as ETB1 and ETB2, as well as radio stations catering to diverse linguistic and cultural audiences. EITB has also embraced the digital era, offering on-demand streaming services and interactive content to engage modern viewers.

Figure 13: EITB Facilities – Newsroom Environment for Live and Recorded Broadcasting

EITB has been involved in numerous research and development initiatives, particularly in digital broadcasting technologies, content production, and audience analytics. These efforts reflect its commitment to innovation and adapting to evolving media consumption habits.

In ENACT, EITB contributes its real-time audiovisual data and acts as a key partner for public-facing content delivery. Through the project, EITB will explore innovative ways to reduce latency in CDN broadcasting and enhance user interaction through immersive media experiences.

Osoigo

Osoigo is a SaaS SME focused on promoting civic engagement through a platform that connects citizens with elected representatives, fostering transparency and participatory democracy. Founded in 2014, the company has grown into a prominent player in the field of digital democracy, primarily operating in Spain and other European countries. The platform enables users to pose questions to politicians and receive direct responses, bridging the gap between the electorate and decision-makers.

Figure 14: User Interaction and Content Access Environment from Osoigo

The company remains relatively small, with a dedicated team of professionals specializing in technology, communication, and political science. Despite its size, Osoigo has had a significant impact on civic participation, hosting thousands of discussions on issues ranging from local policies to global challenges. Its work has been recognised for enhancing public accountability and citizen empowerment.

Osoigo's R&D efforts focus on improving its platform's usability and expanding its reach. The company has invested in machine learning and natural language processing to facilitate effective communication between users and politicians. Economically, Osoigo operates under a sustainable model, supported by collaborations with public institutions and private organisations interested in fostering democratic engagement.

Through ENACT, Osoigo will explore how its participatory platform can be expanded to support real-time interactions in large-scale events, gaining valuable insights into low-latency user engagement and scalable civic interfaces.

Arctur

Arctur is a high-tech, research-driven SME based in Slovenia, with over 30 years of experience in digital transformation, innovation, and advanced computing services. The company operates its own supercomputing centre and employs more than 60 highly qualified professionals. It plays a strategic role in multiple EU-funded projects, offering expertise in high-performance computing (HPC), cloud and edge computing, artificial intelligence (AI), data analytics, and immersive media technologies. Arctur provides tailored computational infrastructure and services to research institutions, businesses, and public administrations across Europe.

Figure 15: High-Performance Infrastructure for Data Processing from Arctur

One of Arctur's flagship initiatives is Tourism 4.0, Slovenia's largest tourism development project, now an international partnership with over 240 members. Through it, Arctur applies Industry 4.0 technologies, such as Big Data, AI, IoT, Blockchain, and VR/AR, to develop innovative solutions for tourism, food, and culture. The company supports DMOs in adopting digital tools for governance, crisis management, and sustainable tourism strategies.

Arctur's leadership in this field is further reinforced by its participation in European projects such as D3HUB²¹³, DeployTour²¹⁴, 5D Culture²¹⁵, TEMS²¹⁶, EuroHPC²¹⁷, EuroCC²¹⁸, Fortissimo²¹⁹, and Inclusive Border Cycling²²⁰.

In ENACT, Arctur is responsible for the development of the immersive visualisation environment for the Regata de la Concha, leveraging its expertise in rendering, telemetry integration, and cross-platform user experiences. ENACT provides Arctur with a unique opportunity to extend its Tourism 4.0 capabilities into immersive real-time settings, validating its visualisation and edge computing solutions in a complex, data-intensive cultural event.

²¹³ <https://www.d3hub-competencecentre.eu/>

²¹⁴ <https://deploytour.eu/>

²¹⁵ <https://5dculture.eu/>

²¹⁶ <https://tems-dataspace.eu/>

²¹⁷ https://eurohpc-ju.europa.eu/index_en

²¹⁸ <https://www.eurocc-access.eu/>

²¹⁹ <https://www.fortissimo-project.eu/>

²²⁰ <https://interreg-danube.eu/projects/ibc>

Innovalia Association

Innovalia Association is a private research and innovation organisation based in Spain, founded in 2002 to foster collaboration among SMEs, universities, and research centres. Its core mission is to promote technological advancement in fields such as advanced manufacturing, quality control, and digital transformation. The association has participated in numerous European projects, contributing its expertise in integrating cloud computing, edge computing, IoT, and artificial intelligence (AI) into industrial environments.

Innovalia combines distributed systems, real-time analytics, and predictive algorithms to optimise production and inspection processes. It has played a key role in Horizon 2020 projects like BOOST 4.0²²¹, focused on big data and AI for smart manufacturing, and Z-Fact0r²²², which addressed zero-defect production through IoT and AI-based anomaly detection.

In ENACT, Innovalia brings its experience in orchestrating distributed digital infrastructures and contributes to the technical coordination and validation of the use case. The project allows the association to explore how its know-how in AI, edge-cloud architectures, and industrial data systems can be transferred to new domains such as smart tourism and interactive cultural experiences.

6.2.2.2 Scenario Description

The Regata de la Concha Use Case focuses on enhancing digital engagement around one of the most iconic cultural events in the Basque Country: a traditional rowing competition held annually in San Sebastián. While the regatta already enjoys widespread media coverage through EITB's television, radio, and online platforms, its digital experience remains largely passive. Spectators, whether on-site or remote, can follow the race, but they have limited control over what they see or how they interact with the event. There is currently no way to personalise the experience, access enriched data in real time, or actively participate beyond conventional viewing.

To address this gap, ENACT introduces a distributed infrastructure that enables real-time orchestration of audiovisual content, telemetry data, and user interactions. Rather than replacing the existing media systems, this approach complements them by offering new, layered experiences that can run in parallel with traditional broadcasting. The goal is to enrich, not replicate, cultural heritage events like the regatta by making them more dynamic, accessible, and interactive through cutting-edge digital technologies.

²²¹ <https://boost40.eu/>

²²² <http://www.z-fact0r.eu/>

Figure 16: Conceptual structure of the use case

As illustrated, the use case integrates three functional environments: 1) live audiovisual content and telemetry from EITB, 2) a user engagement platform developed by Osoigo, and 3) a virtual representation of the race environment generated by Arctur. ENACT coordinates these environments through an edge-to-cloud continuum that processes and synchronises data in real time, enabling adaptive responses to fluctuating network loads, user behaviour, and interaction demand. This ensures low-latency delivery of content and seamless integration between platforms.

Figure 17: Desktop mock-ups showing quiz, voting, and image survey components

Mock-ups of the upcoming participatory platform illustrate how spectators will be able to interact with the event using formats such as quizzes, image-based surveys, or voting panels. These tools are designed to complement the live streaming interface and are displayed alongside VR or 2D video views of the race. The interaction design reflects EITB’s branding guidelines and adapts to different types of devices and screens.

Figure 18: Mobile interface mock-ups with stream, chat, and camera selector

In mobile environments, users will be able to switch camera views, explore rankings, or interact with live comments. The integration of participatory features into the main event stream is expected to enhance engagement and create a hybrid space where spectators are no longer passive viewers, but active participants in a digital extension of a heritage event.

The pilot is structured in three key phases:

- **Pre-event setup:** Edge nodes and orchestration modules are deployed and configured. GPS devices are installed on the boats, the VR environment is initialised with updated geospatial models, and Osoigo’s participatory platform is linked to EITB’s content layer.
- **Live event execution:** During the race, telemetry and video streams are processed at the edge and synchronised with interactive dashboards. The audience can switch viewpoints, participate in polls or predictions, and follow the race from multiple perspectives, including a real-time 3D visualisation based on live GPS data. ENACT manages flow synchronisation and quality adaptation in real time.
- **Post-event analysis:** After the race, the system compiles telemetry, user interaction logs, and platform performance metrics. These data are used to evaluate latency, QoS/QoE metrics, and the effectiveness of adaptive mechanisms, and to refine the orchestration logic for future iterations.

This use case does not introduce a new broadcast model, but rather extends the cultural value of the regatta through participatory, immersive and multi-modal access. In doing so, it showcases how heritage events can evolve in the digital age without losing their authenticity, bridging traditional formats with real-time, user-driven experiences enabled by ENACT.

6.2.2.3 High-level architecture

Figure 19: High-level Architecture of Use Case 2

The architecture of the Regata de la Concha Use Case is based on a modular and distributed design that integrates three functional environments:

- **Media Production and Telemetry Capture**, led by EITB, which collects GPS data and live video/audio feeds during the regatta.
- **User Interaction and Participatory Engagement**, supported by Osoigo, which enables real-time voting, surveys, and second-screen features.
- **Immersive Visualisation**, developed by Arctur, which reconstructs the event in a 3D environment for screen-based access.

These environments are coordinated by ENACT components across a cloud-edge continuum that includes a centralised cloud node (Node A) for signal ingestion and a set of edge nodes (Nodes B) for content distribution. Orchestration modules ensure synchronised data delivery and optimise performance under variable loads. The architecture supports two main delivery pathways:

- A media and interaction layer, integrating traditional broadcast with participatory elements.
- An immersive layer, built upon real-time telemetry rendered into a 3D experience.

This configuration ensures that each component remains loosely coupled but interoperable, enabling modular integration and progressive validation without interfering with editorial or broadcasting workflows. The system architecture has been updated to avoid unnecessary replication of GPS or media signals, acknowledging technical limitations in upstream bandwidth. All incoming data is managed via a single Node A instance, which then feeds downstream services.

This architecture represents a provisional configuration that remains open to adaptation as the development of the use case progresses. Its evolution will depend on the specific needs identified at each stage of implementation.

6.2.2.4 Flow Description

The Regata de la Concha Use Case is built upon a distributed edge-cloud architecture designed to enable seamless integration of live audiovisual content, geolocation data, and user interactions. This configuration ensures synchronisation across multiple platforms and supports a rich combination of traditional broadcasting, participatory features, and immersive experiences.

The system begins with two core data sources:

- **GPS production system:** Collects live telemetry from boats, including positional coordinates and race dynamics.
- **Media production system:** Captures live video and audio using UHD cameras, drones, and other fixed or mobile sources.

These sources are ingested through a single centralised Node A instance deployed in the cloud. This node represents the point of entry for GPS and media signals and manages signal routing to a corresponding set of Node B instances. These edge nodes are responsible for distribution, user-facing delivery, and partial processing when required.

Two primary delivery pathways operate in parallel:

- **The Media and Interaction Layer:** GPS and media data are processed and sent to the Broadcasting and Interaction Platform (Osoigo + EITB). This layer supports second-screen experiences, such as selecting camera angles, participating in quizzes or polls, and accessing race analytics.
- **The Immersive Layer:** GPS data is forwarded to the VR Platform (Arctur), where a real-time 3D visualisation of the regatta is rendered, offering an onboard or bird's-eye view of the race.

Both layers are accessible to the user via the EITB portal, which acts as the main access point for traditional, participatory, and immersive experiences. These layers are loosely coupled but partially synchronised, allowing users to switch between perspectives while maintaining a coherent race timeline.

Beyond the delivery of data, the use case integrates a monitoring and feedback loop. As media and interaction platforms operate during the event, they capture and transmit Quality of Service (QoS) and Quality of Experience (QoE) metrics. These include latency, jitter, buffering events, and user behaviour data such as interaction rates, dwell times, and satisfaction indicators. These metrics are gathered in real time and sent back through the system's observability layer.

In response to these metrics, the system is expected to support adaptive behaviour. For example:

- If a spike in latency is detected in one node, traffic can be dynamically rerouted through alternate pathways to maintain responsiveness.
- If rebuffering or user drop-off increases in a region, media quality settings can be adjusted, or edge processing can be scaled up.
- If one experience (e.g., VR) becomes more popular, resources may be reallocated to sustain quality.

This adaptive orchestration loop is central to ENACT's vision, even though individual components responsible for telemetry collection, decision-making, and orchestration are not detailed in this Section.

As the pilot evolves, the system will progressively test more sophisticated interaction patterns, including:

- Real-time voting and feedback that alter what is shown in the interface
- Synchronised overlays of GPS data on the video feed
- Hybrid visualisations combining 2D video with 3D boat positioning

It is important to note that this flow description reflects the current system vision and is subject to ongoing adjustments. As development proceeds and the capabilities of each platform mature, the ordering, role, and interconnection of components may evolve. These changes will depend on functional requirements, validation feedback, and insights obtained during deployment and testing.

6.2.2.5 Datasets and Models

The Regata de la Concha Use Case processes multiple heterogeneous data streams, which need to be synchronised in real time to ensure a seamless, immersive, and interactive viewing experience. These datasets originate from EITB (GPS and multimedia), Osoigo (user interaction), and Arctur (VR visualisation) and are handled through an Edge-to-Cloud Compute Continuum to optimise latency and performance.

This Section describes the types of data used, their formats and storage strategies.

The main datasets used in this use case include:

1. GPS Data (Boat Geolocation)

- **Source:** GPS devices on each boat.
- **Format:** JSON (latitude, longitude, timestamp, speed).
- **Update Frequency:** Every 1s.
- **Processing:**
 - GPS data is transmitted to the CDN, where ENACT optimises latency using edge computing.
 - Synchronised with live video and VR environments.
- **Regulatory Constraints:** Not stored outside the EU, restricted project access.
- **EITB GPS Data Structure:**

The following fields correspond to the JSON structure used by EITB's GPS tracking system, which is applied across all races in the regatta season. This structure is generated by the devices installed on each boat and transmitted at one-second intervals. It includes standardised metadata used for live visualisation and synchronisation in both television and interactive formats.

Figure 20: Example of JSON Structure for Regatta GPS Telemetry Data

To ensure correct interpretation and integration of GPS telemetry data from the Regata de la Concha, the following table provides a translation and explanation of each field name used in the JSON structure. These data points are essential for real-time tracking, synchronisation, and visualisation of the regatta in both standard and immersive formats.

Field Name (in JSON)	English Term	Description
txapelketa	Competition	The name of the championship or overall event
proba	Race Event	The name or identifier of the specific heat or race within the championship
iturri	Source	The origin or provider of the data
kalek	Lanes	Collection of lanes assigned to competing teams
kale	Lane	Individual lane number in which a team competes
trainera	Team Name / Boat	Name of the team or rowing boat (trainera)
ibilbide	Track / Race Path	The set of GPS points representing the race path of a boat
UMT	UTC Time	Timestamp of the data point (in Coordinated Universal Time)
abiadura	Speed	Speed of the boat at the recorded moment
norabide	Heading / Direction	Movement direction of the boat (typically in radians or degrees)
long	Longitude	Geographical longitude coordinate of the boat
lat	Latitude	Geographical latitude coordinate of the boat

Table 193: Translation and explanation table

- Key Data Characteristics**

The GPS data is generated by boat-mounted devices and transmitted every second in JSON format. It includes key fields such as team name, boat lane, geolocation (latitude, longitude), speed, and heading, with UTC timestamps. This standardised structure, used across the entire

regatta season, enables real-time synchronisation and visualisation on both broadcast and interactive platforms. The data is private, not stored outside the EU, and is reused throughout the project in real time to enable synchronised VR rendering, broadcast overlay and analytics. The positioning format follows the NMEA standard, with additional metadata for race visualisation. Total data volume per race is approximately 483 KB.

2. Live Video and Audio Streams

- **Source:** EITB production cameras (shore, aerial, onboard).
- **Format:** SRT multimedia streams (H.264/H.265 video, AAC audio).
- **Update Frequency:** 10ms to 1s, depending on bitrate adaptation and streaming optimisation.
- **Processing:**
 - Distributed via Secure Reliable Transport (SRT).
 - Optimised for low-latency streaming using AI-driven network resource optimisation to ensure stable transmission.
- **Key Data Characteristics**

Live video and audio content is streamed via SRT using H.264/H.265 video and AAC audio. Streams originate from production cameras (onboard, aerial, shore) and are processed in real time through edge and cloud components. Although not stored persistently, the data is reused in ENACT for adaptive bitrate delivery, synchronised overlay, and validation. These private streams are encrypted, not shared outside the project, and managed under EU data protection regulations.

3. User Interaction Data

- **Source:** Osoigo participatory platform.
- **Format:** JSON/WebSockets (user actions, votes, chat messages).
- **Processing:**
 - Data is captured, analysed, and used to enhance user engagement.
 - Audience interactions influence live race experiences and VR content updates.
- **Osoigo User Interaction Data Structure:**

The fields below are defined by Osoigo's internal data schema for tracking user interactions during live events. These JSON objects are generated by the platform in real time and include user actions such as voting or chat messages. The structure is consistent across participatory sessions, regardless of the specific regatta or event being broadcast.

```
{
  "user_id": int,
  "interaction_type":
str,
  "timestamp": int,
  "event_type": str,
  "event_id": int,
  "extra_data": {
    "survey_id": int,
    ...
  }
}
```

Figure 21: Example of Structured Interaction

- **Key Data Characteristics**

Interaction data from the participatory platform is captured in real time using JSON and WebSocket formats. It includes anonymised user actions such as voting, chat messages, and perspective switching. The data is stored on OVH servers operated by Osoigo and processed via HTTPS APIs. It is open-code, project-private, and complies with GDPR by ensuring anonymisation and EU data residency. The dataset is reused for engagement tracking and interface optimisation, with a volume estimate of 500 GB.

4. VR Content and 3D Visualisation

- **Source:** Arctur's VR rendering system.
- **Format:** 3D model data (e.g., .obj, .fbx), synchronised with GPS and video
- **Update Frequency:** Real-time updates driven by GPS telemetry (min. 30Hz rendering rate)
- **Processing:**
 - VR generated dynamically, offering multiple viewing perspectives.
 - Synchronises VR visualisation with live race events.
- **Key Data Characteristics**

Arctur's VR platform processes geospatial and event-specific data, such as official race routes and boat positions, to generate 3D assets used in the immersive visualisation of the regatta. These assets include 3D models (.obj, .fbx) and textures (.jpg, .png), which are embedded in the application and rendered dynamically using live GPS telemetry. The data is not shared or streamed externally; it remains fully embedded within the local VR application. No personal information is included, and no storage is required outside the app runtime. Only the streamed GPS and multimedia data (from EITB and Osoigo) enters or exits the application, ensuring data protection. The VR system also reuses open geodata (e.g., GIS from Gipuzkoa) to build the race environment. In-app data is verified prior to each release to ensure rendering consistency, while streamed data is not stored. A UUID is assigned to each object for internal referencing, but no standardised ontologies or external metadata systems are applied.

6.2.2.6 ENACT Impact

The Regata de la Concha is not only a major sporting event but also a living expression of Basque maritime heritage. However, cultural heritage events often face challenges in adapting to the digital era, limiting their accessibility, global reach, and interactivity. The ENACT project contributes to addressing this gap by enabling immersive, interactive, and widely accessible digital experiences that preserve the authenticity of traditional events while embracing technological innovation.

The Regata de la Concha Use Case illustrates how an AI-driven Edge-to-Cloud infrastructure can enhance cultural participation through real-time media synchronisation, immersive visualisation, and user interactivity.

The expected impact of ENACT can be categorised into four key areas:

Technological Impact – Expanding Access to Cultural Heritage Through Digital Innovation

ENACT introduces a range of digital tools that significantly broaden the reach and inclusivity of the event. By combining real-time GPS telemetry, live video streaming, and immersive VR content into a unified and synchronised experience, the regatta becomes accessible to a much wider audience beyond those physically present in San Sebastián.

The project enables spectators from around the world to follow the race through interactive interfaces and immersive media, enhancing engagement and removing geographical barriers. The integration of edge computing ensures that all this content is processed with minimal delay, preserving the immediacy and emotional intensity of the event. As a result, ENACT lays the groundwork for a hybrid event model, where traditional in-person experiences are complemented and enriched by real-time digital participation.

This transformation turns the regatta into a digital heritage showcase, demonstrating how cultural events can leverage innovation to preserve tradition while expanding their relevance in the 21st century. Additionally, the Regata de la Concha pilot serves as a real-world testing ground for adaptive orchestration strategies, making it a valuable reference for future deployments of immersive and interactive services within ENACT.

Security and Data Protection Impact – Preserving Cultural Integrity in the Digital Space

As the regatta transitions into a digitally mediated experience, the protection of cultural and personal data becomes a central concern. ENACT incorporates strict data protection protocols to ensure GDPR compliance, respecting both user privacy and the integrity of cultural content.

All sensitive information, such as personal interaction data, is anonymised and stored securely within the European Union. The multimedia content (including video, GPS signals, and interaction logs) is transmitted using encrypted channels, protecting it from tampering or unauthorised access.

Moreover, ENACT safeguards the cultural authenticity of the event by ensuring that digital representations, such as VR visualisations and race data, remain faithful to the real experience. This creates a trusted environment in which audiences can engage confidently, knowing that both their personal data and the cultural content they consume are secure and ethically managed.

Decision-Making Impact – Enabling Adaptive and Engaging Experiences

Traditional cultural events often present a passive experience for remote audiences, with limited interactivity and personalisation. ENACT changes this paradigm by offering tools that empower spectators to take an active role in shaping their own experience.

Through the integration of user interaction data, captured via the Osoigo participatory platform, viewers can influence aspects of the broadcast, select preferred viewpoints, and engage with live race statistics. Although the system does not include AI-generated narratives, it does support adaptive user experiences based on preferences and behaviours, such as switching between camera feeds or visual layers in the VR interface.

Additionally, real-time data analytics can support decision-making by organisers, helping them better understand audience behaviour, optimise resource allocation, and continuously improve the digital offering. Thanks to the monitoring of QoE and QoS indicators, future versions of the platform may incorporate feedback loops where configuration adjustments at infrastructure level (e.g., node switching, resource scaling) are triggered in response to performance degradation.

Environmental and Sustainability Impact – A Model for Sustainable Heritage Tourism

In line with the growing need for sustainable tourism models, ENACT demonstrates how digital transformation can also contribute to environmental responsibility. By enabling immersive and interactive remote access, the regatta offers a compelling alternative to physical attendance, reducing the environmental footprint associated with travel, accommodation, and on-site logistics.

The use of edge computing nodes further supports sustainability goals by decreasing the energy consumption linked to centralised cloud processing. By processing and distributing data closer to the source, the system reduces bandwidth usage and improves overall energy efficiency.

Furthermore, the availability of high-quality virtual content, such as race replays, historical data, and interactive maps, encourages ongoing digital engagement beyond the event itself. This supports a low-impact, year-round cultural tourism strategy that values preservation, accessibility, and environmental stewardship.

6.2.2.7 Current Status

The current implementation of the Regata de la Concha Use Case relies on the coordinated contribution of three key partners: EITB, Osoigo, and Arctur. Each of them brings pre-existing platforms and infrastructures that are being progressively integrated and adapted to the ENACT ecosystem.

EITB – Media Production and GPS Tracking

EITB is responsible for the audiovisual production and GPS tracking of the regatta. The media system includes an UHD mobile production unit equipped with high-resolution cameras and professional encoding equipment. Video and audio streams are encoded using H.265 and AAC respectively and transmitted via SRT (Secure Reliable Transport) to a cloud-based processing environment. From there, they are transcoded into adaptive formats (HLS, DASH) and distributed through CDN channels to reach television, web, and mobile audiences.

Figure 22: Initial setup of Regata de la Bandera de la Concha

While the current setup is robust for traditional broadcasting, it presents limitations in latency and synchronisation. The cumulative delay introduced by encoding, SRT transport, transcoding, and CDN processing can exceed 30–60 seconds. This affects real-time alignment with GPS data and user interactions. As a result, the current system is not suitable for immersive or interactive scenarios without additional orchestration and real-time optimisation, gaps that the ENACT architecture is designed to address.

EITB also collects live GPS telemetry from each boat, which is overlaid on broadcast video streams. However, the GPS data is not currently synchronised with alternative platforms or distributed outside EITB’s environment. In ENACT, this telemetry is now being decoupled and made available as an independent, high-frequency data stream for integration into external systems like Arctur and Osoigo.

This initial setup, illustrated in the baseline architecture, served as the starting point for the use case. The system originally captured UHD video and audio streams, encoded them with minimal delay, and routed them via SRT to a central cloud matrix for transcoding and distribution. Although efficient for conventional broadcast, this setup lacked the flexibility and responsiveness required for real-time interaction and orchestration.

Currently, EITB is transitioning to a node-based infrastructure aligned with the high-level architecture of the pilot. Data acquisition and distribution are now managed through Node A and Node B instances that separate processing responsibilities. In this context, EITB is conducting early-stage performance testing with the streaming provider, focusing on how these nodes behave under constrained resource conditions (e.g., reduced CPU, network throughput, and cache availability). These tests aim to assess the feasibility of maintaining synchronisation and low latency in high-demand scenarios, and to identify infrastructure thresholds for scalable deployment.

Osoigo – Participatory Interaction Platform

Osoigo’s contribution to the pilot is a web-based interface for real-time user engagement, including interactive elements such as polls, camera selection, and race data exploration. As of now,

development is focused primarily on the front-end design, aligning the visual identity of the platform with EITB's branding (colors, style, layout) to ensure a coherent user experience.

Figure 23: Initial backend structure for main platform

The system architecture shown in the current design, including Django²²³, PostgreSQL²²⁴, Redis²²⁵, RabbitMQ²²⁶ and Celery²²⁷, has been prepared as the initial backend structure, but many features remain to be implemented. The role of this platform may evolve depending on functional needs such as data storage or integration with ENACT components (e.g., the Application Controller), and modifications to the backend architecture are expected as the use case progresses.

Arctur – Immersive Visualisation Platform

Arctur is leading the development of the immersive visualisation platform for the Regata de la Concha, with the aim of reconstructing the event in a real-time 3D environment. Unlike traditional broadcast formats that rely on fixed camera views, this platform will offer users an enriched, spatially dynamic perspective of the race. The experience is designed for screen-based access (e.g., web browsers), rather than VR headsets, to ensure broader accessibility.

At this stage, the platform is in a conceptual and early development phase, with no functional prototype available. The planned system will rely on live GPS telemetry to update boat positioning and movement within a virtual rendering of the race environment. Arctur is currently evaluating the

²²³ <https://www.djangoproject.com/>
²²⁴ <https://www.postgresql.org/>
²²⁵ <https://redis.io/>
²²⁶ <https://www.rabbitmq.com/>
²²⁷ <https://docs.celeryq.dev/en/stable/>

feasibility of features such as camera-switching, simulated onboard views, and real-time overlay of race metrics, although these remain exploratory and subject to performance testing.

As development progresses, the visualisation platform is expected to serve both as a standalone experience and as a complementary view linked to other user-facing components of the pilot.

6.2.2.8 ENACT Benefits

ENACT’s core innovations aim to improve race visualisation accuracy, enhance the stability of real-time interactions, and increase the efficiency of content distribution. These advancements ensure that both on-site and remote audiences can enjoy a seamless and engaging experience of the Regata de la Concha. Furthermore, the integration of immersive technologies such as Virtual Reality (VR) contributes to modernising the way cultural heritage events are experienced and shared.

The benefits outlined below are directly linked to the technical validation scenarios described in Section 6.2.2.10. Each indicator allows for measurable assessment of ENACT’s impact on system performance, responsiveness, and user satisfaction during the pilot deployment.

KPI	Type	Current Scenario	Baseline	Metrics
User Satisfaction	Strategic	The regatta is widely broadcasted on TV, radio, and streaming platforms. The goal is to enhance the immersive experience through VR and interactive participation.	0	Average rating > 4/5
Latency Optimisation	Technical	Achieve an optimal latency for delivering close to real-time regatta audiovisual content, tracking updates, ensuring a seamless and responsive user experience.	Variable (up to ~30s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Edge Latency 10–100ms • Cloud Latency < 1s (excluding encoding/decoding delays)
High-Quality VR Experience	Technical	VR is optimised and smooth	0	Delivered 360° VR experience runs smoothly on modern mobile devices, with texture resolutions 1K or higher and rendering time ≤ 15ms.
System Uptime	Technical	Maintain a system uptime of at least 96%, ensuring continuous availability of augmented content and real-time regatta data during live events.	96%	96% uptime during events

Scalability	Operational	The current system handles the audience with delay, but it requires load testing to ensure a higher volume of users on a close to real-time viewing.	10.000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 users per Node Type B (1Gbps) • 300 users per Node Type A (15Gbps) • Based on a 50Mbps MPTS (multi-program Transport Stream)
-------------	-------------	--	--------	---

Table 194: UC2 KPIs

The deployment of ENACT is expected to reduce latency, improve scalability, and ensure system stability during high-demand moments of the regatta. With the introduction of real-time edge processing, optimised VR performance, and enhanced audience interaction, the platform is designed to offer a robust and immersive experience. These improvements will contribute to raising user satisfaction and setting a technological precedent for future digital heritage events.

6.2.2.9 ENACT Technologies

ENACT introduces a comprehensive suite of advanced technologies designed to optimise the performance, security, and adaptability of distributed digital services within the Edge-Cloud Continuum. These technologies collectively address the challenges of low-latency processing, orchestration of computing tasks, secure data handling, and seamless application integration, all of which are essential for delivering real-time, immersive, and interactive experiences during the Regata de la Concha Use Case.

Smart Resource Management

To ensure efficient utilisation of computing resources across the Edge and Cloud layers, ENACT employs a multi-layered orchestration strategy:

- **Reinforcement Learning (RL)** algorithms and **Graph Neural Networks (GNNs)** are used to generate dynamic scheduling plans for GPS tracking, Virtual Reality rendering, and audience interaction features. These AI techniques allow the system to adaptively prioritise workloads based on performance demands, system health, and user behaviour.
- The **ENACT Orchestrator** coordinates the execution of these plans by dynamically allocating computing tasks, minimizing latency and avoiding resource bottlenecks. This ensures consistent performance even under fluctuating system load, such as during peak user activity or high-frequency telemetry updates.
- The **Dynamic Graph Modeller (DGM)** provides a continuously updated model of system topologies and resource states, enabling predictive orchestration and optimised workload allocation across distributed nodes.

Real-Time Data Processing

ENACT is designed to support real-time responsiveness across multiple streams of heterogeneous data:

- Data from GPS systems, video feeds, and user interactions is ingested and processed through a distributed architecture composed of Node A (capture and ingestion) and Node B (processing and distribution).

- The **Telemetry Data Collector & Monitoring Engine (TDCME)** captures key QoS and QoE metrics, such as latency, throughput, rebuffering, and participation, which inform the Orchestrator about system status and help guide performance optimisation.
- These capabilities enable the synchronisation of media and data across platforms (broadcast and VR) while supporting user-driven interactions and feedback loops.

Security and Compliance

Given the sensitive nature of both user data and cultural content, ENACT integrates strong security and compliance mechanisms:

- The **Security Risk Modeler (SRM)** identifies vulnerabilities and recommends configurations to secure data flows and platform connections.
- The **AI Act Compliance Checker** evaluates the use of AI functionalities to ensure alignment with applicable EU regulations.
- **Zero-Touch Provisioning (ZTP)** allows for automated, secure deployment of edge-cloud infrastructure with minimal manual configuration.
- A **Data Space Framework** supports sovereign and compliant data exchange, ensuring that all information remains within regulated boundaries.

Application Integration and Compatibility

To facilitate integration within external applications:

- The **Application Programming Model (APM)** offers a Software Development Kit (SDK) and abstraction tools for embedding ENACT functionalities, such as orchestration signals, metrics reporting, or synchronisation commands, into third-party platforms.
- This ensures that platforms can interact with ENACT without requiring deep architectural changes.
- Although not yet deployed, the **Application Controller** is expected to translate user-driven events at the application level into orchestration intents, enabling adaptive system behaviour.

This Section reflects the current integration prospects of ENACT within the Regata de la Concha Use Case. The specific components to be deployed are still under evaluation, and final configurations will depend on technical feasibility, partner needs, and pilot objectives.

6.2.2.10 Test and Validation

The validation of the Regata de la Concha Use Case follows a structured methodology that combines preliminary simulations with in-situ trials during the live event. The aim is to demonstrate how ENACT technologies improve synchronisation, elasticity, user interactivity, and real-time data responsiveness across a distributed infrastructure.

ENACT's validation strategy includes three progressive stages:

- **Phase 1 (Lab Testing):** Simulated video, GPS, and user interaction data are used to validate the orchestration logic, real-time processing capabilities, and adaptive workload scheduling mechanisms in a controlled environment.

- **Preliminary Field Testing:** During July and August, functional components will be tested under real conditions but with limited scale, using regatta-related events and partial deployments.
- **Phase 2 (Live Event Validation):** Final validation will take place during the Regata de la Concha in September. It will assess orchestration performance, synchronisation accuracy, system responsiveness, and user satisfaction under realistic, high-demand conditions.

Validation Scenarios and Testing Methodology

Based on an analysis of the literature and the specific characteristics of the pilot, seven critical validation scenarios have been identified. These reflect the main technical and experiential risks that may affect the Regata de la Concha broadcast. Out of these, a reduced selection (two, or a maximum of three) will be implemented in the final validation phase, ensuring feasibility while maximizing representativeness.

Each scenario links directly to QoS/QoE metrics and KPIs, ensuring traceable, metric-driven testing:

- **Elastic Resource Allocation:** Tests the orchestrator's ability to detect overload conditions (e.g., CPU saturation, packet loss) and reallocate sessions or processes dynamically between nodes A and B.
- **Scalability under Peak Load:** Simulated user peaks test the ability to replicate services or balance sessions across nodes, ensuring video continuity and low latency.
- **Partial Node Failure:** Validates ENACT's reconfiguration logic when a node loses capacity, ensuring service continuity via migration and fallback routes.
- **Synchronisation Issues:** Assesses how ENACT detects and resolves inconsistencies across GPS, video, and interaction channels, maintaining coherent experience alignment.
- **Quality Degradation on Mobile Devices:** Tests bitrate drops and increased rebuffering in low-performance user environments, verifying adaptive behaviour and responsiveness.
- **User Interaction Latency:** Measures end-to-end delay between user actions (polls, camera switching) and system updates in the VR and streaming interfaces.
- **Geographically Distributed Latency:** Validates ENACT's ability to infer and correct misalignments when traffic routes between remote viewers and core nodes introduce cross-region lag.

Each scenario includes measurable thresholds (e.g., latency <700ms, rebuffering <1/5min, throughput >5 Mbps) and is designed to test a specific ENACT function or metric.

Operational, Business, and Regulatory Constraints

- **Operational:** The regatta is a time-constrained public event. All components must be pre-tested and stable prior to deployment. Environmental factors (weather, sea conditions) may affect GPS and video signal quality and are considered in fallback and validation procedures.
- **Business:** Validation will assess the modularity and scalability of the ENACT solution, including its capacity to reduce infrastructure costs via edge processing, and its ability to support reuse in similar heritage or media events.
- **Regulatory:** All tests are designed to comply with GDPR and to anticipate AI Act obligations. While ENACT provides supporting tools, such as data flow audits, anonymisation checks, and

transparency mechanisms, it is the responsibility of each pilot and participating entity to ensure that ethical and legal requirements are fully met during deployment and validation.

Validation Metrics and Expected Impact

Impact will be evaluated through the following dimensions, directly aligned with the KPIs of Section 2.8:

- **Synchronisation and Latency:** Timestamp comparisons between GPS, video, and VR outputs.
- **System Scalability:** Performance stability under simulated user peaks and live session loads.
- **QoS/QoE Metrics:** Jitter, packet loss, throughput, startup delay, rebuffering, and user engagement duration.
- **Resource Optimisation:** CPU/GPU usage, edge offloading efficiency, and energy consumption.
- **User Satisfaction:** Feedback surveys and interaction logs (polls, votes, perspective switching) targeting a satisfaction score of 4/5 or higher.

The deployment of ENACT is expected to reduce latency, improve scalability, and ensure operational resilience during peak moments of the regatta. By leveraging real-time edge processing, VR optimisation, and enhanced user interaction capabilities, the platform aims to deliver a robust and immersive experience. These improvements will help demonstrate the value of ENACT technologies and support future adoption in similar digital heritage scenarios.

6.2.2.11 Expected Computing Continuum Resources for Validation

The validation of the Regata de la Concha Use Case requires a distributed computing infrastructure capable of supporting real-time data synchronisation, user interactivity, and immersive VR experiences. To achieve this, the ENACT Computing Continuum will be designed to allocate processing tasks intelligently across Edge and Cloud resources. This structure ensures that latency-sensitive operations, such as GPS processing, audience interaction, and VR rendering, are handled close to the data source, while centralised cloud services provide orchestration, scalability, and persistent storage. The overall architecture aims to maximise system responsiveness, optimise resource utilisation, and ensure a smooth user experience during both testing and live deployment phases.

This infrastructure is currently under review to determine the optimal mapping between ENACT components and the specific technical needs of the pilot. The definition of deployment models is being refined based on evolving system requirements and the potential of the ENACT architecture to support fault tolerance, elasticity, and service orchestration across distributed environments.

Resource Distribution Across the Computing Continuum

The computational workload for validation will be distributed across Edge and Cloud infrastructures, each playing a complementary role to ensure responsiveness, scalability, and system resilience.

- **Edge Computing Layer:** Responsible for real-time processing of GPS data, audience interaction inputs, and telemetry collection. Edge nodes will execute low-latency decision-making tasks, manage interaction logic, and support VR rendering components required close to the user. By

processing data locally, the edge layer minimises dependence on centralised resources and ensures fast, synchronised delivery of immersive and interactive content.

- **Cloud Computing Layer:** The cloud layer handles centralised orchestration, persistent data storage, and the execution of AI-based models for system-wide optimisation. It supports high-performance processing tasks, such as cross-platform synchronisation and advanced analytics, and complements the edge layer for scalable content distribution. The cloud infrastructure may also assist in rendering tasks where additional GPU resources are required, ensuring continuity and adaptability under varying load conditions.

Below, we present the expected computing resources per partner.

EITB – ENACT CDN Optimisation

EITB will integrate with ENACT to optimise real-time GPS data processing and ensure precise synchronisation with live video and audio feeds. To support this, a flexible CDN architecture will be deployed, allowing different node configurations depending on the role they play in the system. The resources to be used will depend on the scope of the pilot and the infrastructure available within the project, although a maximum reference configuration has been defined and is included in the corresponding table.

The technical setup may include:

- Edge computing instances dedicated to the preprocessing, filtering, and transmission of GPS telemetry near the point of capture.
- CDN nodes supporting both production media (video/audio) and geolocation data, ensuring scalable and low-latency distribution.
- Cloud-based AI components for predictive analytics and performance monitoring, contributing to enhanced race tracking accuracy.
- Secure data storage solutions for archiving GPS signals and associated metadata to support post-event analysis and performance evaluation.

This adaptable multi-node architecture will improve real-time responsiveness, reduce latency, and ensure consistent alignment between GPS telemetry and broadcast content throughout the event.

Component	CPU	Memory	Storage	Network
Node A1 (cloud)	16 vCPU	16 GB RAM	No data storage (only gateway)	1 Gbps
Node A2 (cloud)	16 vCPU	16 GB RAM	500 GB for 20 hours (~50 Mbps)	1 Gbps
Node B1 (edge)	16 vCPU	16 GB RAM	No data storage (only gateway)	1 Gbps
Node B2 (edge)	16 vCPU	16 GB RAM	500 GB for 20 hours (~50 Mbps)	1 Gbps

Table 195: Potential resource needs for EITB

Osoigo – Interactive Audience Platform

Osoigo’s platform will serve as the main interface for audience participation, providing real-time access to live content, polls, and interaction features. To support a high number of concurrent users while maintaining responsiveness and reliability, ENACT’s distributed computing infrastructure will be leveraged. The expected requirements for this integration include:

- **Edge computing nodes** positioned near the user base to process real-time interactions—such as voting, commenting, or switching perspectives—with minimal latency and reduced network overhead.
- **Cloud-based services** for scalable storage, indexing, and retrieval of audience data, including interaction logs and analytics required for post-event evaluation.
- **Orchestration mechanisms** to dynamically balance workloads between edge and cloud environments, ensuring optimal resource usage and service continuity under varying user loads.
- **Security and compliance components** to ensure that all audience interaction data is anonymised, securely processed, and handled in full accordance with GDPR and other relevant data protection regulations.
- This configuration ensures that Osoigo can deliver a seamless and secure participatory experience, while enabling ENACT to manage technical complexity in a transparent and automated manner.

Component	CPU	Memory	Storage	Network
Storage	8 virtual CPU cores	16 GB	500GB	10 Gbps connectivity between nodes

Table 196: Potential resource needs for Osoigo

Arctur – VR Processing and Rendering

Arctur’s VR platform is responsible for rendering the immersive 3D environment of the regatta, allowing users to experience the race from multiple virtual perspectives. The 3D application is rendered locally on the user’s device—whether through a browser or a VR headset—and therefore does not require centralised or high-performance computing infrastructure for visual processing.

However, to ensure that the virtual environment remains synchronised with real-time race data (e.g., GPS positions and media feeds), the supporting infrastructure must provide low-latency network connectivity. This enables the timely delivery of telemetry and interaction data from ENACT’s backend systems to the end-user application. While the local system only requires sufficient memory and CPU to support the VR application, the quality of the experience depends heavily on minimizing transmission delays and ensuring consistent data flow throughout the race.

The suitability and allocation of ENACT components across the infrastructure are still under evaluation, with the goal of selecting the optimal deployment model for each task. This ensures that the system can achieve both high performance and functional robustness throughout the pilot validation.

6.3 Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

6.3.1 Overview

6.3.1.1 Introduction, Opportunities and Barriers

The goal of this pilot is to develop distributed deployment configurations for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform to enable its execution in a cloud-to-edge continuum.

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform, also known as Dracena (Dynamically Reconfigurable Asynchronous Consistent Event Processing Architecture), is an innovative real-time digital twin platform designed to address the growing needs of the mobility sector. As the automotive industry undergoes a significant transformation towards connected and autonomous vehicles, there is an increasing demand for platforms that can process and analyse vast amounts of real-time data from multiple sources.

Dracena serves as a cloud-based digital twin platform capable of creating virtual representations of people, things, and contexts from the real world. It is specifically engineered to handle large-scale concurrent stream processing, allowing for the real-time analysis and prediction of events in the mobility domain. The platform's architecture is built to process high-frequency data transmitted from millions of devices such as connected cars, smartphones, and various sensors distributed across the transportation infrastructure.

Key features of the Mobility Digital Twin platform include:

- Real-time data processing: Dracena can handle large volumes of stream data at high speeds, enabling timely decision-making and service delivery.
- Flexible digital twins: The platform abstracts real-world data in real time, providing flexible representations of mobility-related entities that can be easily adapted for various services.
- Seamless upgrading: Dracena allows for dynamic additions or changes to data processing programs without service interruption, ensuring continuous operation of critical mobility services.
- Scalability: The platform is designed to scale efficiently, accommodating the growing number of connected vehicles and devices in the mobility ecosystem.
- Service object architecture: Dracena uses a unique object-oriented approach, separating generic "real-world objects" from service-specific "service objects," allowing for efficient development and event processing.

The Mobility Digital Twin platform has numerous potential applications in the automotive and transportation sectors, including real-time traffic information services, predictive maintenance, autonomous driving support, and enhanced safety features. By collecting and analysing sensor data from large numbers of network-connected vehicles, Dracena can provide valuable insights into traffic patterns, road conditions, and potential hazards, contributing to smarter and safer mobility solutions.

As the mobility sector continues to evolve, platforms like Dracena play a crucial role in enabling the next generation of intelligent transportation systems and services. The integration of such platforms

with edge-cloud computing paradigms, as proposed in the ENACT project, represents a significant step towards more efficient, responsive, and scalable mobility solutions.

In the ENACT project, the Mobility Digital Twin platform will be deployed in the edge-cloud continuum and its functional and non-functional aspects will be validated and compared with current deployment model. Distributed management of data, coming into the Mobility Digital Twin platform from various sources, will be achieved in the edge-cloud continuum by adopting the ENACT innovations represented by the AI Orchestrator and APM paradigms. With UNP we will develop an innovative way to deploy and manage distributed data coverage control function to significantly decrease data duplications in the edge-cloud continuum.

Digital Twin technology has the potential to significantly showcase the ENACT platform capabilities by enabling real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimisation of complex systems like cities.

Fujitsu Technology Solutions Sp. z o.o. has obtained a license to utilise the Digital Twin Platform (DTP), an advanced software solution developed and owned by FUJITSU LIMITED, Japan. The DTP enables the efficient orchestration of user access across multiple cloud environments, supporting complex and dynamic project requirements.

This licensing agreement permits Fujitsu Poland to leverage the DTP solution specifically for the ENACT project, ensuring seamless integration and execution of project objectives. The use of this cutting-edge platform reinforces Fujitsu's commitment to delivering innovative and reliable solutions within the scope of Horizon Europe initiatives.

6.3.1.2 Motivation

In this pilot, we are aiming to leverage Digital Twin technology, the Dracena platform, and the Integra visualisation tool to create a powerful solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimisation of urban environments.

Key motivation includes:

- Create a virtual replica of the urban environment using Digital Twin technology, which will serve as a dynamic, data-driven model of the city.
- Integrate various data sources and API endpoints to gather real-time data from IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and other relevant city data streams.
- Utilise the Dracena platform to ingest, process, and analyse the massive volumes of streaming data in real-time, enabling the Digital Twin to stay up to date with the current state of the city.
- Leverage advanced analytics and ML models within the Digital Twin to derive insights, predict future states, and optimise city operations.
- Present the insights and predictions generated by the Digital Twin on an interactive, user-friendly dashboard using the Integra visualisation platform.
- Enable city planners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders to explore the city data in a visually intuitive way, drilling down into specific areas of interest and simulating the impact of potential interventions.

By combining the power of Digital Twins, real-time data processing with Dracena, and interactive visualisation with Integra, we aim to provide a visibility, understanding, and control over complex urban systems.

This solution will support data-driven decision making, enable proactive management of city resources and services, and ultimately lead to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators.

6.3.1.3 Target Objectives

This pilot aims to estimate and validate distributed management of high-frequency, high-volume data, coming from various sources in the mobility domain, such as GPS, mobile phones, roadside sensors, traffic controls systems, etc., using Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform.

The ENACT edge-cloud infrastructure and application programming model would enable the real-time ingestion, processing, and analysis of the massive volumes of streaming sensor data powering the city Digital Twin.

- **Real-time Data Processing:** The mobility sector generates massive amounts of data that need to be processed in real-time to provide valuable insights and services. Dracena's ability to handle large-scale concurrent stream processing makes it ideal for this pilot.
- **Scalability:** As the number of connected vehicles and smart infrastructure elements grows, the system needs to scale seamlessly. Dracena's architecture allows for efficient handling of data from millions of devices without compromising performance which is also backed up by cloud computing.
- **Flexibility and Agility:** The rapidly evolving nature of mobility services requires a platform that can adapt quickly. Dracena's feature of seamless upgrading without service interruption enables agile development and deployment of new services.
- **Distributed Computing Optimisation:** By leveraging the cloud-to-edge continuum, we can optimise data processing by performing certain tasks closer to the data source, reducing latency and bandwidth usage. This is crucial for time-sensitive applications like traffic management or autonomous driving support.
- **Energy Efficiency:** With growing concerns about the environmental impact of digital technologies, it is crucial to optimise energy usage. Testing different deployment configurations will help identify the most energy-efficient setups.
- **Cost Optimisation:** By distributing processing across edge and cloud resources, we can potentially reduce the overall cost of data management and processing, utilizing resources more efficiently.
- **Enhanced Service Quality:** The ability to process data closer to its source can lead to faster response times and improved service quality, which is critical in mobility applications where milliseconds can make a difference.
- **Data Sovereignty and Privacy:** Distributed data management allows for better control over where data is processed and stored, which is increasingly important due to data protection regulations.
- **Resilience and Fault Tolerance:** Testing the platform's resilience and fault tolerance in a distributed environment is crucial for ensuring uninterrupted service in the face of network issues or hardware failures.
- **Futureproofing:** As mobility services evolve towards more autonomous and connected systems, having a flexible, scalable, and efficient data processing platform becomes crucial

for future innovations. Overall, a city Digital Twin powered by ENACT would provide a real-time operational view of the urban environment to enable data-driven decision making and smart, proactive management to improve quality of life for citizens. The air pollution monitoring example illustrates how the Digital Twin could be applied to optimise a city sustainability KPI.

6.3.1.4 Key Research Areas

Distributed deployment configurations: This area focuses on optimizing how the Mobility Digital Twin platform is deployed across the cloud-to-edge continuum. Key aspects:

- Identifying optimal placement of components across cloud, fog, and edge resources.
- Developing algorithms for dynamic resource allocation based on workload and network conditions.
- Investigating trade-offs between centralised and decentralised architectures.
- Exploring containerisation and serverless computing for flexible deployments.
- Designing strategies for seamless migration of services between edge and cloud.

Research questions include:

- How can we automatically determine the best deployment configuration for a given set of resources and requirements?
- What are the performance impacts of different distributed configurations on latency, throughput, and resource utilisation?

Distributed data coverage: This area examines how to efficiently manage and process data across distributed locations while maintaining comprehensive coverage. Key aspects:

- Developing techniques for distributed data storage and replication.
- Creating mechanisms for ensuring data consistency across distributed nodes.
- Designing strategies for efficient data routing and aggregation.
- Investigating methods for distributed query processing.
- Exploring techniques for handling data heterogeneity from various mobility data sources.

Research questions:

- How can we ensure complete data coverage while minimizing redundancy and storage costs?
- What are effective strategies for maintaining data freshness and consistency in a distributed environment?

Hyper-distributed data processing: This area focuses on processing large volumes of data across highly distributed environments. Key aspects:

- Developing algorithms for distributed stream processing.
- Creating techniques for distributed ML and AI.
- Designing methods for real-time analytics in distributed settings.
- Investigating approaches for distributed event detection and pattern recognition.
- Exploring techniques for distributed data fusion from multiple mobility data sources.

Research questions include:

- How can we optimise data processing algorithms for highly distributed environments?

- What are effective strategies for load balancing and task allocation in hyper-distributed systems?

Testing and validation of Digital Twin: This area involves creating comprehensive methodologies for testing and validating the distributed Mobility Digital Twin platform. Key aspects include:

- Developing benchmarks and metrics for evaluating distributed system performance.
- Creating simulation environments for testing various deployment scenarios.
- Designing methodologies for stress testing and fault injection.
- Investigating approaches for validating data integrity and consistency in distributed settings.
- Exploring techniques for end-to-end testing of distributed mobility services.

Research questions include:

- How can we effectively simulate real-world conditions to test the platform's performance and reliability?
- What metrics are most relevant for evaluating the success of distributed deployment configurations in the mobility domain?

6.3.2 Use Case Scenario

6.3.2.1 Participants

Fujitsu is a leading global information and communication technology (ICT) company that offers a wide range of technology products, solutions, and services. The Fujitsu Poland Global Delivery Center (GDC) plays a crucial role in driving research and development (R&D) efforts, particularly in the areas of Cloud Computing, Hybrid Cloud, Professional IT Services and Artificial Intelligence (AI). As an R&D hub, the Poland GDC focuses on developing innovative solutions. By leveraging the expertise of the Horizon Europe (HEU) Innovation Hub Poland and the HEU operations core team, the GDC aims to strengthen its IP generation capabilities, foster a customer-centric and entrepreneurial mindset, upskill talent, and enhance its brand positioning. Looking ahead, the Poland GDC seeks to align its R&D efforts with the key research areas outlined in Section 6.2.1.4, while building strategic partnerships with industry players, startups, and academia to extend its capabilities and drive innovation in the ICT domain.

6.3.2.2 Scenario Description

The UC scenario involves leveraging Digital Twin technology, the Dracena platform, and the Integra visualisation tool to create a comprehensive solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimisation of urban environments. The goal is to develop a virtual replica of the city that integrates data from various IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and other relevant city data streams.

The Dracena platform will play a crucial role in ingesting, processing, and analysing the vast amounts of real-time streaming data generated by the city's IoT infrastructure. This data will be used to create a dynamic and accurate representation of the city's current state within the Digital Twin. Advanced analytics and ML models will be applied to the data to derive insights, predict future scenarios, and optimise city operations.

For example, the Digital Twin could focus on monitoring and mitigating air pollution within the city. Real-time air quality data from sensors across the city would be ingested and analysed to identify pollution hotspots, predict pollution levels, and evaluate the impact of potential policy changes or

interventions. The Dracena platform's real-time processing capabilities would ensure that the Digital Twin always reflects the most current environmental conditions.

The insights and predictions generated by the Digital Twin will be visualised using the Integra platform, providing an interactive and user-friendly interface for city planners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders. This will enable them to explore the city's data, drill down into specific areas of interest, and simulate the effects of different interventions or policies.

By combining Digital Twin technology, real-time data processing with Dracena, and interactive visualisation with Integra, this UC aims to provide unprecedented visibility, understanding, and control over the complex systems that make up a city. This will support data-driven decision making, enable proactive management of city resources and services, and ultimately lead to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators.

The air pollution monitoring example demonstrates how this approach can be applied to a specific urban challenge, but the same principles could be extended to optimise energy consumption, traffic management, public safety, and other critical aspects of city operations. The Digital Twin platform's ability to process real-time data and provide actionable insights makes it a valuable tool for various fields, contributing to the overall capabilities and sustainability of the ENACT project.

6.3.2.3 High-level architecture

The Mobility Digital Twin platform leverages containerisation technology and cloud infrastructure for its deployment. The platform consists of various microservices, and components packaged as container images, enabling a modular and scalable architecture.

Figure 24: Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin setup

Figure 24 above illustrates the Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin setup, delineating the configurations for both development and production environments. Figure 25 below presents an example of a standalone customer deployment.

Figure 25: A standalone customer deployment

Technology stack

The components of the Mobility Digital Twin platform are developed using the following technologies:

Data Ingestion and Messaging:

- Apache Kafka²²⁸: Distributed streaming platform for high-throughput, fault-tolerant data ingestion.
- Zookeeper²²⁹: Coordinates Kafka brokers and manages configuration.

Stream Processing:

- Apache Flink²³⁰: Distributed stream processing engine for real-time data analytics.
- Java (OpenJDK)²³¹: Programming language for implementing Flink jobs and custom logic.

Storage:

- Elasticsearch²³²/OpenSearch²³³: Distributed search and analytics engine for fast data querying.
- Hadoop²³⁴ HDFS (optional): Distributed file system for large-scale data storage.

²²⁸ Apache Kafka: <https://kafka.apache.org/>

²²⁹ Apache ZooKeeper: <https://zookeeper.apache.org/>

²³⁰ Apache Flink: <https://flink.apache.org/>

²³¹ Java: <https://www.java.com/>

²³² Elasticsearch: <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

²³³ OpenSearch: <https://opensearch.org/>

²³⁴ Hadoop HDFS: <https://hadoop.apache.org>

- AWS S3²³⁵ (alternative to HDFS): Scalable object storage for resilient file storage.

Deployment and Orchestration:

- Kubernetes²³⁶: Container orchestration platform for managing deployments.
- AWS EKS²³⁷: Managed Kubernetes service for easier deployment and scaling.
- AWS EC2²³⁸: Virtual servers in the cloud for hosting components.

Serverless Computing:

- AWS Lambda²³⁹: Serverless compute service for running code without provisioning servers.

Content Delivery and API Management:

- AWS CloudFront²⁴⁰: Content delivery network for fast and secure content distribution.
- AWS API Gateway²⁴¹: Fully managed service for creating, publishing, and securing APIs.

Monitoring and Observability:

- Prometheus²⁴²: Monitoring system and time series database for metrics collection.
- Grafana²⁴³: Analytics and visualisation platform for collected metrics.

Infrastructure as Code (IaC):

- Terraform²⁴⁴: Infrastructure as code tool for building and versioning infrastructure.
- GitOps²⁴⁵ using Flux Integration.

6.3.2.4 Flow Description

As presented in Figure 26, the system utilises edge devices and gateways to collect and pre-process sensor data, which is securely transmitted to AWS IoT Core. Real-time analysis is performed using Kafka and Flink, updating the digital twin core. Processed data is stored in Amazon Timestream for historical analysis and cached in Redis for low-latency access. Spark handles data analytics, providing insights visualised through Grafana. The API layer facilitates interaction with the digital twin, while Prometheus and ELK monitor and log system metrics for operational insights.

Data Flow

- **Edge Devices** → **Edge Gateways**: Raw data from sensors and IoT devices is collected and pre-processed at edge gateways.

²³⁵ Amazon S3: <https://aws.amazon.com/s3/>

²³⁶ Kubernetes: <https://kubernetes.io/>

²³⁷ Amazon EKS: <https://aws.amazon.com/eks/>

²³⁸ Amazon EC2: <https://aws.amazon.com/ec2/>

²³⁹ AWS Lambda: <https://aws.amazon.com/lambda/>

²⁴⁰ Amazon CloudFront: <https://aws.amazon.com/cloudfront/>

²⁴¹ Amazon API Gateway: <https://aws.amazon.com/api-gateway/>

²⁴² Prometheus: <https://prometheus.io/>

²⁴³ Grafana: <https://grafana.com/>

²⁴⁴ Terraform: <https://www.terraform.io/>

²⁴⁵ GitOps: <https://www.gitops.tech/>

- **Edge Gateways** → **IoT Hub**: Aggregated and filtered data is securely transmitted to the cloud IoT hub.
- **IoT Hub** → **Stream Processing**: Data is ingested into a stream processing system for real-time analysis.
- **Stream Processing** → **Digital Twin Core**: Processed data updates the state of digital twin objects in real-time.
- **Digital Twin Core** → **Time Series Database**: Historical data is stored for long-term analysis and trend detection.
- **Digital Twin Core** → **In-Memory Cache**: Frequently accessed data is cached for low-latency access.
- **Digital Twin Core** → **Analytics Engine**: Data is analysed for insights, predictions, and anomaly detection.
- **Analytics Engine** → **Visualisation Layer**: Insights and predictions are visualised for end-users.
- **API Layer** ↔ **All Components**: Provides interfaces for external systems to interact with the Digital Twin.
- **All Components** → **Monitoring & Logging**: System metrics and logs are collected for operational insights.

Figure 26: Following diagram between components

Figure 27: Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin high level design

Figure 28: Data Ingestion

Deployment details

The deployment process will involve the following steps:

- **Containerisation:** Each microservice and component of the Mobility Digital Twin platform will be packaged into a container image using tools like Docker. These images will encapsulate the application code, dependencies, and runtime environment.
- **Container Registry:** The container images will be pushed to a container registry, such as Amazon Elastic Container Registry (ECR), which serves as a secure and scalable repository for storing and managing container images.

- **Kubernetes Manifest Files:** Kubernetes manifest files (typically in YAML format) will be created to define the desired state of the Mobility Digital Twin platform components. These manifest files will specify the Stateful Set configurations, including the number of replicas, container images, volumes, and network settings.
- **Deployment to AWS EKS:** Using the Kubernetes manifest files, the Mobility Digital Twin platform components will be deployed to the AWS EKS cluster. The Kubernetes control plane will ensure that the desired state specified in the manifest files is achieved and maintained.
- **Scaling and Monitoring:** AWS EKS provides built-in mechanisms for scaling based on resource utilisation or custom metrics. Monitoring and logging solutions, such as Amazon CloudWatch or Elasticsearch, can be integrated to collect and analyse performance metrics and logs from the deployed containers.

The ENACT project's focus on testing and validation will benefit from this deployment approach, as it provides a reliable and reproducible environment for evaluating the platform's functionality, performance, and integration with other ENACT components. The use of AWS EKS aligns with industry best practices and enables seamless integration with other AWS services, such as storage, networking, and security solutions.

Development Environment consists of:

- Locally containerised services (e.g., Local K8s) which serve the purpose of simulating the production environment on a smaller scale, enabling developers to work in isolation.
- Single-node instances of Kafka, Flink, and Elasticsearch which provide the core functionalities for data streaming, processing, and storage in a simplified setup.
- Local IDEs with Scala/Java support which facilitate efficient coding and debugging of the Digital Twin application.
- Git for version control which enables collaborative development and code history tracking.
- CI/CD pipeline with Jenkins or GitLab CI which automates testing and integration processes, ensuring code quality.

Production Environment consists of:

- Cloud-based infrastructure (e.g., AWS) with multi-region setup which ensures high availability and global scalability of the Digital Twin platform.
- Distributed, scalable services including:
 - Kafka cluster for data ingestion which handles high-volume, real-time data streams.
 - Flink cluster on Kubernetes for stream processing which enables scalable, fault-tolerant data processing.
 - Elasticsearch cluster for short-term storage which provides fast data querying capabilities.
 - S3/HDFS for long-term storage which offers cost-effective storage for historical data.
 - API Gateway which provide secure and flexible interfaces for data access and manipulation.
 - Comprehensive security measures (IAM, VPC, encryption) which protect the Digital Twin platform and its data from unauthorised access and breaches.

- Robust monitoring and logging (ELK stack, CloudWatch) which offer deep insights into system performance and aid in troubleshooting.
- CI/CD for automated deployments which ensures consistent and reliable updates to the production environment.
- Edge computing integration which enables local processing of data, reducing latency and bandwidth usage.

Deployment constraints

There are several potential constraints that need to be considered to ensure a successful implementation. Here are some key deployment constraints to keep in mind:

- *Infrastructure Limitations:* Digital Twin require significant computational power to process and analyse large amounts of data in real-time. Ensuring sufficient computational resources, such as servers or cloud instances with adequate CPU, memory, and storage capacity, is crucial.
- *Data Integration and Interoperability:* System often involves integrating data from various sources, such as sensors, devices, and enterprise systems. Ensuring compatibility and interoperability among these diverse data sources can be challenging, requiring data standardisation and integration.
- *Scalability and Performance:* As the number of connected devices and the volume of data grow, the Digital Twin system should be able to scale horizontally and vertically to accommodate increased workload. The architecture should be designed to handle scalability requirements, leveraging technologies like containerisation (e.g. EKS) and distributed computing (like autoscaling groups in AWS)

Execution pattern

The platform is designed for real-time processing of large volumes of data from various sources in a distributed environment.

The execution pattern of a Digital Twin involves the continuous synchronisation and interaction between the physical entity and its digital counterpart. Here is a detailed explanation of the execution pattern:

- **Data Acquisition:** Sensors, devices, and other data sources collect real-time data from the physical entity. The data can include various parameters such as temperature, pressure, position, velocity, etc., depending on the nature of the physical entity.
- **Data Ingestion and Storage:** The digital twin receives the data from the physical entity which is ingested into the platform and stored in a structured format, typically in a database or a data store.
- **Data Processing and Analysis:** The platform processes and analyses the ingested data using various techniques, such as data transformation, filtering, and aggregation. Advanced analytics, ML algorithms, and rules engines can be applied to extract meaningful insights and detect patterns or anomalies in the data. The processed data is used to update the state of the digital twin, reflecting the current conditions and behaviour of the physical entity.
- **State Synchronisation:** The Digital Twin synchronises state with the physical entity based on the processed data. The state includes the current values of relevant parameters, historical data, and derived insights. The digital twin platform ensures that the state is consistently

updated in real-time or near-real-time, depending on the data acquisition frequency and processing latency.

- **Simulation and Prediction:** The platform can simulate the behaviour of the physical entity under different conditions or scenarios. Predictive models and simulation engines can be employed to forecast future states, performance, or potential issues based on the current state and historical data. Simulations help in understanding the impact of different control strategies, optimising processes, and making informed decisions.
- **Visualisation and Interaction:** The Digital Twin provides a user interface or API for visualising the state and behaviour of the physical entity. Users can interact with the digital twin, such as querying data, setting parameters, or triggering actions.
- Visualisation techniques, such as 3D models, dashboards, or augmented reality, can be used to represent the digital twin objects in an intuitive and meaningful way (**using optional 'Integra' component**)
- **Action and Control:** Based on the insights derived from the digital twin, actions can be taken to control or optimise the behaviour of the physical entity. Control commands or settings can be sent from the digital twin platform to the physical entity to modify its operation or performance. It can also trigger automated actions or alerts based on predefined rules or thresholds.
- **Continuous Learning and Improvement:** The digital twin continuously learns and improves over time as more data is collected and analysed. ML models can be retrained or updated based on new data to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of predictions and decision-making.

Figure 29: High Level Overview of Dracena

The execution pattern of a digital twin is a continuous loop of data acquisition, processing, analysis, state synchronisation, simulation, visualisation, action, and learning. This pattern enables real-time monitoring, optimisation, and control of the physical entity through its digital representation.

The specific implementation of the execution pattern may vary depending on the UC, the complexity of the physical entity, and the technologies used. However, the core principles of data-driven synchronisation, real-time processing, and continuous learning remain fundamental to the execution of digital twins.

Data Ingestion:

- IoT devices and other data sources send data to Kafka topics.
- Zookeeper manages Kafka cluster coordination.

Stream Processing:

- Flink jobs, written in Java, consume data from Kafka topics.
- Flink processes the streams in real-time, updating digital twin states.

State Management:

- Processed data and digital twin states are stored in Elasticsearch/OpenSearch for fast querying.
- Long-term storage or large datasets can be stored in HDFS or S3.

Deployment:

- The entire platform is containerised and orchestrated using Kubernetes.
- AWS EKS manages the Kubernetes cluster.
- EC2 instances serve as the underlying compute resources.

Serverless Extensions:

- AWS Lambda functions can be used for event-driven processing or extending platform capabilities.

API and Data Access:

- AWS API Gateway exposes APIs for external service integration.
- CloudFront can be used to distribute data or content to end-users efficiently.

Monitoring:

- Prometheus collects metrics from all components.
- Grafana provides dashboards and visualisations of the collected metrics.

Infrastructure Management:

- AWS CDK or terraform is used to define and manage the cloud infrastructure.
- Configuration management tools ensure consistent configuration across the platform.

Figure 30: Example of Internals workflow of Digital Twin

Monitoring resource utilisation

The solution bundles Grafana with Prometheus for monitoring. We can also use deployment-based solutions, e.g., AWS Cloudwatch.

Current Monitoring Setup:

Prometheus:

- Used for collecting and storing time-series data from various components.
- Scrapes metrics from HTTP endpoints exposed by services.

Grafana:

- Provides visualisation of metrics collected by Prometheus.
- Allows creation of customised dashboards for different aspects of the system.

AWS CloudWatch:

- Monitors AWS resources and applications running on AWS.
- Collects logs, metrics, and events for analysis.

Table 197 below presents the list of available metrics per category.

Category	Metric
Resource Utilisation	CPU usage Memory usage Disk I/O Network I/O
Data Storage	Storage capacity usage

	Read/Write operations per second
	Latency of read/write operations
Network	Network throughput
	Connection count
Kafka	Message throughput
	Consumer lag

Table 197: List of metrics per category

6.3.2.5 Datasets and Models

In the context of a Digital Twin system, datasets and models play a crucial role in enabling the accurate representation, simulation, and prediction of the physical entity's behaviour.

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin platform introduces a data management approach that treats each piece of data from real-world devices as individual objects. These objects can be grouped together to define and manage data processing programs called Plugins. Objects can belong to multiple groups simultaneously. The platform allows the creation of new objects from real-world data or the results of Plugin processing. For example, road information can be extracted from vehicle data to create new road objects.

Plugins can be added or modified without disrupting the constant data upload, enabling quick modifications and logic verification without affecting other Plugins. The platform also supports external system linkage, allowing stream data and Plugin processing results to be connected to external systems. Data can be temporarily stored in the digital space for analysis in combination with external system processing results.

Datasets

Historical Data:

- Description: Historical data represents the past state and behaviour of the physical entity over time. It includes sensor readings, operational data, performance metrics, and other relevant information captured from the physical entity.
- Purpose: Historical data is used to train and validate models, identify patterns and trends, and gain insights into the past performance of the physical entity.

Real-time Data:

- Description: Real-time data refers to the current state and behaviour of the physical entity, collected in real-time or near-real-time from sensors, devices, and other data sources.
- Purpose: Real-time data is used to update the Digital Twin's state, monitor the physical entity's current condition, and enable real-time decision-making and control.

Regarding data that will be used in this pilot, the platform mainly uses data produced by distributed probes and vehicles. This data is pre-processed on edge devices and cloud resources, while taking into account the GDPR and other data protection protocols.

Sources of real data to be used are:

- AWS Location Service (Maps and traffic).
- Polish General Inspectorate of Environmental Protection (aggregated data).

In cases that generation of workload fluctuations is needed, further generation of data that will mock vehicles is considered. Each virtual machine will be treated as the edge device that aggregates all the data from the set of vehicles. In addition to this, further open datasets may be considered during the project for these purposes. The use of open-data will not have an impact on the project related activities, since the focus of this pilot is on how the digital twin platform handles the changes in the volume of data (spikes) or constraints or dynamic changes in the (compute and storage) resources.

Depending on source data format and particular UC, we have identified the following data patterns.

Traffic and Road Condition Data:

- Data: Traffic flow, congestion levels, road closures, accidents, weather conditions, etc.
- Format: JSON, XML, or CSV
- Frequency: Real-time or near-real-time updates
- Volume: Moderate to high, depending on the coverage area and the number of data sources

Sensor Data:

- Data: Environmental sensors (temperature, humidity), occupancy sensors, etc.
- Format: JSON, CSV, or binary formats
- Frequency: Real-time or periodic updates
- Volume: Low to moderate, depending on the number and type of sensors

Geospatial Data:

- Data: Maps, POIs, geofences, etc.
- Format: GeoJSON, Shapefile, or other geospatial data formats
- Frequency: Relatively static, with occasional updates
- Volume: Moderate, depending on the level of detail and coverage area

Data Models

The following example shows the data structure used by Fujitsu Digital Twin:

```
{
  "mversion": "2.0",
  "oid": "car001",
  "stage": 0,
  "eventTime": 1562658762151,
  "body": {
    "speed": 45.32,
    "position_lat": 35.679603,
    "position_lng": 139.757313
  }
}
```

Figure 31: Example of Fujitsu Digital Twin data structure

Table 198 below presents the Dracena data structures. “Body” has a flexible schema, dependent on the type of object.

Name	Type	Default Value	Summary
mversion	string	"2.0"	Message format version Only "2.0" available
oid	string	(required)	Destination Object ID
stage	number	0	Destination Object Stage
eventTime	number	0	Event occurrence time (UNIX milliseconds) of the corresponding sensor data
body	Map	(required)	Key-value data to store in the state of the object

Table 198: Dracena data structures

Data Structures types:

- Entity Structure: Hierarchical decomposition of physical entities and their relationships
- Attribute Structure: Static and dynamic properties associated with each entity
- Time-series Data Structure: Historical and real-time sensor data over time
- Metadata Structure: Descriptive information about entities, attributes, relationships

Data Storage:

- Short-term: In-memory storage in Apache Flink
- Medium-term: Elasticsearch/OpenSearch clusters
- Long-term: Centralised HDFS or AWS S3 with potential for multi-datacentre distribution

Data Processing Patterns:

- Real-time data ingestion using Apache Kafka
- Stateful stream processing with Apache Flink
- Complex event processing for pattern detection
- In-memory state management with checkpointing
- Continuous real-time analytics and aggregation
- Publish-subscribe data distribution
- Write-behind caching for data persistence
- Periodic batch processing for heavy computations
- Time-based data lifecycle management
- Feedback loop for closed-loop control
- Multi-tenancy via logical data/processing separation
- Edge processing for distributed computing

Access to Data:

- Self-managed service with full data access
- Real-world challenges: data localisation, ownership, sharing, access control

6.3.2.6 ENACT Impact

In the scope of the use-case, ENACT introduces technological advancements, particularly through the integration of an Edge-Cloud Continuum in data processing.

It also promotes business enhancements, considering that by optimising resource utilisation and reducing operational costs, ENACT enhances not only the value proposition for data streaming providers but also the customer experience, offering cost savings and improved performance to their customers while maintaining a smooth service.

Naturally, the discussed technological innovation aspects and their potential impact on the media business (across all stakeholders involved) also results in reduced resource utilisation and increase energy efficiency, which fosters environmental sustainability in the sector.

Technological Advancements:

1. Enabling real-time processing and analysis of massive volumes of vehicle sensor data across the edge-cloud continuum.
2. Implementing data reduction and replication strategies to optimise storage and bandwidth utilisation.
3. Leveraging AI and ML for intelligent workload placement and adaptive performance optimisation.

Business Enhancements:

1. Improved scalability to support a rapidly growing fleet of connected vehicles and increasing data volumes.
2. Faster time-to-market for new mobility services and features by leveraging a flexible and adaptive platform.
3. Increased competitiveness in the market by offering advanced capabilities like predictive maintenance, real-time traffic insights, and intelligent route optimisation.
4. Unlocking new revenue streams and business models based on data-driven services and partnerships.
5. Contributing to sustainability goals by optimising resource consumption and minimising environmental impact of data processing.

6.3.2.7 Current Status

Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin solution and framework is currently operational in at least two deployments within the European region. As part of the ENACT project, we aim to significantly enhance and expand this technology through several key initiatives:

- Infrastructure Modernisation: Developing a new, state-of-the-art infrastructure to support advanced functionalities.
- Plugin Development: Creating new plugins to extend the platform's capabilities and adaptability.
- Containerisation: Implementing container-based architecture to improve scalability and deployment flexibility.
- EU Ecosystem Alignment: Adapting the system to align with European digital infrastructure standards and requirements.
- Distribution Optimisation: Enhancing the distributed nature of the platform to improve performance and resilience.
- Data Integration:
 - Expanding data ingestion capabilities to incorporate diverse sources, including urban environments and IoT devices.

- Implementing robust data sanitisation and standardisation processes to ensure data quality and consistency.
- Unification: Integrating the platform with the INTEGRA component to enhance overall system cohesion.
- Visualisation Enhancements: Developing advanced visualisation tools to improve data interpretation and user experience.

These initiatives aim to elevate the Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin platform, ensuring its continued relevance and effectiveness in the rapidly evolving digital landscape of Europe's mobility sector.

Digital Twin Platform currently has two instances running on Azure and AWS clouds. These instances are being used by FUJ for further development and testing purposes.

6.3.2.8 ENACT Benefits

The Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin platform aims to provide distributed data access, analysis, and decision support functionalities to enable the creation of high-precision maps, development of autonomous vehicles, and better understanding of driving conditions. However, the increasing number of connected vehicles and the associated data volume poses significant challenges in efficiently handling, orchestrating, and managing the underlying distributed compute and storage infrastructure.

ENACT aims to deliver improvements to the following key performance indicators in the UC:

KPI	Type	Current Scenario	Baseline	Metrics
Reliability: Increase to 90%	Strategic	Both the cluster size and the number of pod replicas are constant. The deployment configuration cannot be updated at runtime. In case of a node disaster, some components might not have enough suitable resources to be provisioned.	Node recovery is time-consuming. As a result, in node disasters, availability is about 80%.	Availability checked every 5s. The system is containerised. Kubernetes should keep all the pods up and running, but also nodes should be provisioned dynamically.
Infrastructure costs: Lowered by 50% in cloud computing costs due to distribution of data and processing over edge clusters.	Strategic	Currently, we have a fixed number of nodes and clusters. Most data are pushed to the cloud increasing the cost.	Cost of infrastructure is about 1200 euro per month.	Monthly costs reduced by decreasing the data send and stored in the cloud, while the cost of virtual machines is adjusted according to the needs. By choosing the proper node type with specific CPU and memory and keeping utilisation on a high level we can minimise the number of nodes and as a result lower the cost. When the node has low utilisation then scaling vertically down should be considered. In this use case, all

virtual machines should run with high memory and CPU utilisation. All containers are running on a minimal number of VMs.

Data replicated to the cloud: Reduced by 70% while maintaining the same quality of service.	Operational	Currently, the vast majority of data is sent without any processing nor filtering to the cloud.	90% of data processed in the cloud.	Amount of data processed in the cloud will be decreased by 70%.
Use of edge devices: Increased by 60% for enhanced scalability of the platform and reduced cost of data collection.	Operational	In the current scenario, only a small portion of data is preprocessed on edge devices. The majority of data is collected in the cloud.	Only a few edge devices are used for pre-processing.	Number of edge devices being used for data processing.

Table 199: Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative Use-case KPIs

These benefits will be achieved through the application of ENACT technologies such as:

- Techniques for seamless networking and dynamic discovery of edge-cloud resources to ensure reliable communication.
- Distributed data processing capabilities to parallelise compute-intensive tasks like video analysis across available resources.

6.3.2.9 ENACT Technologies

ENACT's innovative technologies can significantly benefit the Fujitsu Mobility Digital Twin in the following ways:

- Scalable and Efficient Data Processing: ENACT's APM and Cognitive Orchestrator can enable the Mobility Digital Twin to efficiently process and manage the massive volumes of streaming vehicle data across the edge-cloud continuum. This will lead to improved scalability, reduced latency, and optimised resource utilisation.
- Enhanced Situational Awareness: The ENACT DGM can provide a real-time, unified view of the entire mobility ecosystem, integrating data from vehicles, infrastructure, and external systems. This will enable the Mobility Digital Twin to maintain a highly accurate and up-to-date digital representation of the real-world driving environment.
- Intelligent Workload Distribution: ENACT's AI-driven orchestration capabilities can dynamically distribute the Mobility Digital Twin's workloads across the edge-cloud continuum based on factors like data locality, resource availability, and application requirements. This will result in optimised performance, reduced data transfer costs, and improved energy efficiency.
- Seamless Scalability and Evolution: ENACT's ZTP and dynamic discovery mechanisms will allow the Mobility Digital Twin to seamlessly incorporate new vehicles, devices, and data sources as

the ecosystem grows and evolves over time. This will provide the necessary flexibility and scalability to support the platform's long-term growth and expansion.

Computing Continuum

In the Digital Twin platform, the computing continuum, which spans from edge to cloud, plays a crucial role in enabling real-time data processing, scalability, and efficient resource utilisation. Here's how the edge and cloud continuum are currently being used and how it can be further leveraged to provide more benefits:

Edge Computing:

- *Data Preprocessing:* Edge devices, such as gateways or smart sensors, perform initial data preprocessing tasks, such as filtering, aggregation, and compression. This reduces the volume of data transmitted to the cloud and minimises network bandwidth consumption.
- *Real-time Analytics:* Edge nodes can execute real-time analytics and ML models to provide immediate insights and enable low-latency decision-making. This is particularly important for time-critical applications that require fast response times.
- *Local Data Storage:* Edge devices can store data locally for short-term persistence and offline access. This ensures data availability even in scenarios with intermittent network connectivity.

Cloud Computing:

- *Centralised Data Storage:* The cloud provides scalable and reliable storage infrastructure to store and manage large volumes of data generated by the Digital Twin platform. It offers high availability, data replication, and backup capabilities.
- *Batch Processing and Analytics:* The cloud enables the execution of complex batch processing and analytics workloads on the collected data. It provides powerful computing resources and parallel processing capabilities to handle computationally intensive tasks.
- *Model Training and Deployment:* The cloud is used for training advanced ML models using aggregated data from multiple sources. These models can then be deployed to edge devices for real-time inference and decision making.

6.3.2.10 Test and Validation

The Intelligent City Digital Twin Platform will be validated through a combination of simulated and real-world scenarios. In the early testing stages, the platform will be tested using both real-world and generated data from various sources, such as IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and city data streams as explained before. This data will be used to test the platform's capabilities in a controlled setting. The results of testing and validation process will enable the measurement of the aforementioned KPIs for the pilot.

6.3.2.11 Expected Computing Continuum Resources for Validation

effectively validate the Fujitsu Intelligent City Digital Twin Platform, a diverse range of computing resources spanning the edge-cloud continuum will be required. These resources will be used to test the platform's ability to process and analyse large volumes of real-time data from various city data sources and IoT sensors.

Edge Devices and Gateways:

- IoT sensors and devices deployed across the city, such as environmental sensors, traffic cameras, and smart meters.
- Edge gateways and micro data centres that aggregate and preprocess data from IoT devices before sending it to the cloud.
- Edge computing resources, such as Raspberry Pi or Intel NUC, to run local data processing and analytics.

Table 200 below presents the estimated resources needed for the use-case components.

Component	CPU	Memory	Storage	Network
Lambda Functions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Varies based on workload • Burstable CPU performance 	512 MB – 4GB of RAM	Ephemeral storage up to 1 GB	High-speed, low-latency connectivity to event sources and services
Apache Flink	2 - 4 cores per task manager	1GB - 32GB of RAM per task manager	30GB	High-bandwidth, low-latency connectivity between Flink nodes
Containers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Varies based on application requirements. • 1 – 4 vCPU per container 	1-4 GB of RAM per container	Ephemeral and persistence storage	Fast, reliable networking between containers
Edge Devices	1 vCPU	1GB – 4GB	10GB	100MBps
Document Database – OpenSearch/ElasticSearch	2-4 vCPU	32 GB of RAM	100GB - 500GB (depending on data)	High-bandwidth, low-latency connectivity between cloud services

Table 200: Resources needed for the use-case components

The infrastructure for this UC should include servers distributed across both the cloud and edge devices. While there is no fixed number of servers required, their combined capacity must meet the specified requirements for each component.

7. ENACT Vision

This Section presents the goals and aspirations for the ENACT platform and the vision for each of the Pilots in their industries and domains of focus.

7.1 ENACT platform goals and aspirations

The ENACT platform’s overall objective is to provide a cognitive, highly adaptable and distributed solution tailored to meet the special needs of the Cloud-Edge Continuum such as dynamic environment changes, node heterogeneity, and resource and application constraints.

To this end, ENACT aims to create a holistic platform that brings together cutting-edge concepts and technological solutions to enable continuous network and infrastructure monitoring, resource modelling, risk assessment, automated resource provisioning, cognitive scheduling, orchestration, adaptive application deployment, distributed learning and sovereign data storage.

Figure 32: ENACT Project phases

The above aim of the ENACT project is realised through in the following phases (as also illustrated in Figure 32 above):

1. In the first phase, different types of edge and cloud resources are interlinked through innovative networking and remote configuration techniques to establish the connectivity underpinning the compute continuum. This phase concerns with realising the connected infrastructure that allows for orchestration and deployment of applications and services on suitable resources, from edge to the cloud.
2. The connected resources are modelled using innovative dynamic graph modelling techniques, allowing for greater visibility and understanding of available resources and the (application deployment and orchestration) opportunities available in the distributed edge-cloud continuum. In this respect, this phase is concerned with the development of dynamic graph models that provider greater awareness and insight into the opportunities available for distributed deployment of applications.
3. The dynamic graph model, representing the connected or interlinked edge-cloud resources are analysed through graph neural network and deep reinforcement learning techniques to determine the best deployment configurations for distributed applications.
4. AI optimisation techniques are also by the ENACT orchestrator to optimise the performance (in terms of resource utilisation, energy efficiency, cost, etc.) of the underlying edge-cloud resources through the management and adaptation of application deployment configurations. AI optimisation techniques are also used at the application level, where the application can make their own decisions about the optimal deployment and execution behaviour based on the analysis of monitoring data coming from the underlying resources and the application performance or execution behaviour.

5. The adaptation actions suggested by the AI-based optimisation techniques (within the ENACT orchestrator) are implemented through the use of state-of-the-art container orchestration and management solutions operating at the edge and cloud levels.
6. To take full advantage of the edge-cloud continuum and the dynamism in such distributed environment, ENACT develops an innovative application programming model. This programming model provides the libraries and constructs that enable the development of adaptive applications, capable of monitoring their performance or execution behaviour and suggesting possible adaptation actions that can help improve the performance related aspects.

To realise the various phases associated with the ENACT vision, the project will leverage recent technological advancements such as zero-touch provisioning, AI scheduling optimisation algorithms, Graphic Neural Networks, virtual training capabilities, application-level adaptation and Data Spaces.

The developed concepts and technological solutions will be tested and validated in 3 different domains, where distributed applications are expected to make significant economic and ecologic impacts. The ENACT Vision for the three (3) Pilot domains and use-case scenarios are described in the next Section.

7.2 Hyper-distributed Media Content Processing by MOG Technologies

ENACT aims to elevate the media streaming use-case across technological, security, and environmental efficiency domains. The integration of an Edge-Cloud Continuum in the media processing domain marks a significant technological advancement, enabling uninterrupted broadcasting and intelligent annotation, facilitating seamless transitions of computing tasks between edge devices and cloud servers. This integration ensures dynamic resource optimisation, enhancing efficiency and performance while improving communication reliability between cloud and edge nodes. Such innovation not only streamlines operations but also fosters further scalability and innovation with potential cost savings.

In terms of secure communications, integrating with ENACT, underscores the imperative of robust security measures. With proprietary data flowing through the pipeline, access controls and authentication mechanisms become pivotal to safeguard against unauthorised access and data breaches. This proactive security approach protects intellectual property and cultivates stakeholder trust. From a business perspective, introducing an application within a dynamic and intelligent Edge-Cloud Continuum presents a compelling opportunity. By optimising resource utilisation and reducing operational costs, ENACT enhances the value proposition for MOG's customers. Leveraging the continuum effectively translates into tangible cost savings, minimising infrastructure overheads while maximising performance, thus bolstering competitiveness and market positioning.

Last, but certainly not least, the environmental impact is vital. ENACT's efficient distribution of infrastructure resources minimises energy consumption and reduces carbon footprint. This optimisation ensures that computing resources are utilised carefully, minimising unused resources and, therefore, the environmental impact. Furthermore, by prioritising environmental sustainability, the application can capitalise on the growing market demand for sustainable solutions, thereby enhancing MOG's brand reputation and market positioning.

7.3 Production and distribution of media content for cultural heritage and tourism sectors

The Regata de la Concha pilot illustrates how ENACT enables the transformation of live cultural events into dynamic, immersive digital experiences. By leveraging a cognitive Edge-to-Cloud continuum, the pilot introduces advanced orchestration and adaptive service deployment that ensure the timely and synchronised delivery of media content and interaction channels to end users. The system dynamically adapts to fluctuating network and processing conditions, guaranteeing low latency and high responsiveness throughout the event.

The ENACT-enabled infrastructure facilitates a flexible separation between data acquisition, processing, and media distribution. This architectural shift allows computing tasks to be executed at the most appropriate level of the Continuum (whether close to the data source or in cloud environments) according to real-time requirements, resource availability, and audience distribution. This approach not only ensures optimal performance but also enhances scalability and operational efficiency, opening the door to new models of real-time media engagement in tourism and cultural heritage contexts.

Security and data integrity are equally critical, given the live nature of the content and the need to manage proprietary media streams, location data and user interactions. ENACT's integration into the pilot supports a robust and intelligent approach to service coordination and data protection, ensuring reliable and trusted delivery across the continuum.

From a broader perspective, the pilot validates the potential of ENACT to reduce environmental impact by promoting efficient use of distributed computing resources. By avoiding redundant data transmissions and offloading tasks to strategically positioned nodes, the system lowers energy consumption and infrastructure strain. This contributes to both sustainability goals and operational cost reduction.

The concepts and functionalities explored in this pilot can be extended to similar domains such as concerts, public events, and live festivals, reinforcing the replicability of the approach. Overall, the use case confirms ENACT's vision for future-proof, intelligent media delivery ecosystems aligned with digital transformation and green transition objectives in the tourism and culture sectors.

7.4 Hyper-distributed Data Processing for Fujitsu's Mobility Digital Twin Initiative

Digital Twin technology has the potential to significantly impact the ENACT project by enabling real-time monitoring, simulation, and optimisation of complex systems like cities.

Cities can leverage **Digital Twins** to create a virtual replica of the urban environment that integrates real-time data from various IoT sensors and systems. This allows city planners and managers to visualise, analyse and run simulations on city operations. For example, a city Digital Twin could ingest real-time air pollution data from sensors across the city and use advanced data analytics and ML models to identify pollution hotspots, predict pollution levels, evaluate the impact of policy changes, and optimise traffic flows to minimise emissions.

The **Integra** visualisation platform could be used to create interactive visualisations and dashboards of the city Digital Twin. This would allow stakeholders to intuitively explore the air pollution, traffic data in the context of the virtual city model, drilling down to street level to see hyper-local variations.

The ENACT edge-cloud infrastructure and application programming model would enable the real-time ingestion, processing, and analysis of the massive volumes of streaming sensor data powering the city Digital Twin. The cognitive orchestrator could dynamically allocate computing resources to ensure the Digital Twin simulations and visualisations always have sufficient performance.

Overall, a city Digital Twin powered by ENACT would provide a real-time operational view of the urban environment to enable data-driven decision making and smart, proactive management to improve quality of life for citizens. The air pollution monitoring example illustrates how the Digital Twin could be applied to optimise a city sustainability KPI.

In this UC, Digital Twin technology, the Dracena platform, and the Integra visualisation tool will be leveraged to create a powerful solution for real-time monitoring, analysis, and optimisation of urban environments, which enable the development of a comprehensive virtual replica of the urban environment, integrating a variety of data sources and endpoints that collect real-time data from IoT sensors, environmental monitoring systems, and other pertinent city data streams. The created model will serve as a dynamic, data-driven representation of the city.

The Dracena platform will be employed to ingest, process, and analyse the vast amounts of streaming data in real-time, ensuring the Digital Twin reflects the current state of the city accurately. Advanced analytics and ML models will be utilised within the Digital Twin to derive insights, predict future states, and optimise city operations.

The insights and predictions generated by the Digital Twin will be presented on an interactive, user-friendly manner using the Integra visualisation platform. This will enable city planners, decision-makers, and other stakeholders to explore city data in a visually intuitive manner, allowing them to drill down into specific areas of interest and simulate the impact of potential interventions.

By combining the power of Digital Twins, real-time data processing with Dracena, and interactive visualisation with Integra, the aim is to provide an visibility, understanding, and control over complex urban systems.

This solution will support data-driven decision making, enable proactive management of city resources and services, and ultimately lead to improvements in key urban sustainability, resilience, and quality of life indicators.

The air pollution monitoring example showcases how this approach could be applied to track and mitigate a critical environmental challenge, but the same principles could be extended to optimise energy consumption, traffic management, public safety, and other vital aspects of city operations.

Additionally, the Digital Twin technology is providing real-time data processing which can be used for usage scenarios in various fields that will utilise the ENACT project results, hence contributing to the ENACT platform capabilities and sustainability.

Reduced data duplications and optimised data distribution: The Digital Twin platform in ENACT can address the challenge of data duplications and enable optimised data distribution across the system. By employing intelligent data deduplication techniques, such as data hashing and content-based addressing, the platform can identify and eliminate redundant data storage across different nodes and devices. This reduces storage costs, improves data consistency, and streamlines data management. Additionally, the Digital Twin platform optimises data distribution by leveraging edge computing and distributed storage mechanisms. Data can be strategically placed closer to the points of consumption, minimising latency and network congestion. Intelligent data replication and

synchronisation techniques ensure that critical data is available where and when needed, while minimising unnecessary data transfers and duplications.

Advanced hyper-distributed data processing: ENACT can leverage the Digital Twin platform to enable advanced hyper-distributed data processing capabilities. The platform supports the seamless distribution and parallel processing of data across multiple nodes, edge devices, and cloud resources. By employing distributed computing frameworks, such as Apache Spark or Flink, the Digital Twin platform can efficiently process large volumes of data in real-time, enabling complex analytics, ML, and AI applications. The hyper-distributed architecture allows for the optimal utilisation of computing resources, load balancing, and scalability. Data processing tasks can be intelligently partitioned and assigned to different nodes based on their capabilities, locality, and workload characteristics. This enables the Digital Twin platform to handle the growing volume, velocity, and variety of data generated in the ENACT ecosystem, providing real-time insights and actionable intelligence.

8. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the second and final iteration (for WP2) of the SotA analysis, the specification of the ENACT platform components, the definitions and specifications of the ENACT UCs, and the Impact and Vision for the ENACT platform and the ENACT Pilots.

In the first iteration of this deliverable, a comprehensive SotA analysis was presented in fourteen (14) distinct innovation topics and subtopics that are highly relevant to ENACT scopes and developments, including an in-depth analysis of the current research directions and related work, and a presentation of the most relevant and commonly used market-ready, commercial and industrial solutions and standards. The advancements that are foreseen within the frame of ENACT project were also detailed, accompanied with information about the relevant ENACT platform components. Finally, the relevant projects and technologies (along with their TRL) were identified.

In the second iteration, one (1) new SotA subtopic was introduced and populated, bringing the total to fifteen (15). Six (6) topics and subtopics underwent major revisions, while three (3) received minor updates. Nine (9) additional relevant projects were identified and analysed in terms of their relevance to ENACT.

The first iteration of the ENACT platform components specification included the detailed definition of seventeen (17) components, forty-three (43) modules, one hundred and eighteen (118) functions and three (3) data models to be developed within the frame of the ENACT project. For each of these components, the internal modules, workflow, interactions with other components, prototypical GUI mock-ups, TRLs, relevance and applicability in the ENACT Pilots, relevance with the different layers of the ENACT architecture, and implementation details, such as technologies, frameworks, libraries and tools envisioned to be used, high-level interfaces, deployment type, authorisation details and licensing information were provided. Additionally, the functional specifications of each component's modules and functions were defined, including, a comprehensive description, implementation priority, interactions and success criteria.

In the second iteration, most components underwent major revisions, in alignment with developments in WP3, WP4, and WP5, as well as the updated ENACT architecture. Specifically, sixteen (16) out of seventeen (17) components were updated, including the three (3) data models; twelve (12) received major updates, while four (4) were subject to minor changes. Eighteen (18) modules were

revised and three (3) new ones were introduced, bringing the total number of modules to forty-seven (47). Additionally, forty-four (44) functions were updated and nine (9) new ones were added, resulting in a total of one hundred and thirteen (113) functions.

In the first iteration, only two (2) ENACT Pilots were defined in detail, as the partners associated with the third pilot outlined in the ENACT proposal withdrew during the early stages of the project. Subsequently, a new third Pilot was successfully introduced. Accordingly, in this second iteration, all three (3) ENACT Pilots were described in detail. This includes the description of each Pilot, opportunities and barriers, motivation, target objectives and key research areas. The UC scenarios were also specified, covering their description and participants, high-level architecture, involved components, information flows, datasets and models, as well as the anticipated ENACT impact and benefits. Additional details were provided regarding the current status, along with testing and validation information. In addition to the introduction of the third Pilot (UC2) in this document, the contributions of the other two Pilots were revised, with particularly substantial updates made to UC1.

The content of this deliverable has already served internally as valuable input for the second iteration of user and system requirements analysis (provided in deliverable D2.5 at Month 18 of the project) and the specification of the revised ENACT platform architecture (provided in D2.6 at Month 18 also). This work will further inform the updating and integration of ENACT components within WP7, the final specifications of which will be presented deliverable **D7.1 (ENACT Final Requirements and Specifications)** at Month 30.

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